

Novembro 2022

Herpetologia Brasileira

SBH
SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE
HERPETOLOGIA

Suplemento 1
ISSN: 2316-4670

Herpetologia Brasileira

Uma publicação da Sociedade
Brasileira de Herpetologia

Sociedade Brasileira de Herpetologia
www.sbherpetologia.org.br

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ISSN: 2316-4670
Suplemento 1
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Atelopus hoogmoedi
Laranjal do Jari, AP
@ André Teles

Nota dos Editores

Neste ano em que comemoramos os 10 anos da Herpetologia Brasileira trazemos como presente um volume especial da Herpetologia Brasileira onde são apresentadas as etimologias dos nomes genéricos e epítetos específicos de 1206 espécies de anfíbios Brasileiros. Agradecemos imensamente a Esteban Lavilla e demais autores que cordialmente aceitaram incluir esta contribuição em um volume especial em comemoração aos 10 anos da Herpetologia Brasileira.

Esperamos que apreciem este volume especial.

Boana geographica
Manaus, AM
@ Franciele C. Souza

Melanophryniscus macrogranulosus
Dom Pedro de Alcântara, RS
@ Mariana Pontes

Pithecopus nordestinus
Ilhéus, BA
@ Daniela Pareja-Mejia

Nyctimantis bokermanni
Florianópolis, SC
@ Larisa Zanette

Proceratophrys velhochico
Boqueirão da Onça, BA
@ Diego G. Cavalheri

Etymologies of Brazilian Amphibians

Esteban O. Lavilla¹, Ulisses Caramaschi², José Antonio Langone³, Délio Baêta²

1 UEL - Conicet + Fundación Miguel Lillo, Miguel Lillo 251, 4000 San Miguel de Tucumán, Argentina. E-mail: eolavilla@gmail.com

2 Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Museu Nacional, Departamento de Vertebrados, Quinta da Boa Vista, São Cristóvão, 20940-040 Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brasil. E-mail: ulisses@acd.ufrj.br; deliobaeta@gmail.com

3 Departamento de Herpetología, Museo Nacional de Historia Natural, Casilla de Correos 399, 11000 Montevideo, Uruguay. E-mail: pp.langone@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6787198

ABSTRACT

The etymologies of the generic names and specific epithets of 1,206 Brazilian amphibian species and their synonyms, are presented. The compilation ranges from *Rana pipa*, the first Brazilian species described in the 10th edition of the *Systema Naturae* by Linnaeus (1758), to *Osteocephalus melanops*, published by Melo-Sampaio et al. on December 20, 2021. Within this range are 18 species named in the XVIII century, followed by 204 in the XIX, 527 in the XX, and 457 in the first 21 years of the XXIth century. A total of 1,706 primary quotations are listed, representing a much larger number if the referred desinenses and variations of a same name were considered.

Key words: Amphibia, Scientific names, Generic names, Specific epithets.

INTRODUCTION

Below are the etymologies of the generic names and specific epithets of 1206 Brazilian amphibian species and their synonyms, totaling the explanation of more than 1600 words. The compilation ranges from *Rana pipa*, the first Brazilian species described in the 10th edition of the *Systema Naturae* (Linnaeus, 1758), to *Osteocephalus melanops*, published by Melo-Sampaio et al. on December 20, 2021. Within this range are included 18 species named in the XVIII century, followed by 204 in the XIX, 527 in the XX, and 457 in the first 21 years of the XXIth century. Many of them are due to a single author, or a couple of them, perhaps a trio ... but taxonomists working alone in the XXIth century are increasingly being replaced by true international “consortia” that, reviewing this or that clade, generate unusual, almost grotesque situations, such as the fact that there are names due to 16 authors.

This contribution is almost a lexicographic analysis and does not claim to be a systematic or synonymic list (although it was necessarily based on them), nor it is intended to be a nomenclatorial work in the sense of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN 1999). The primary source of taxa was an updated version of Segalla et al. (2021), and their synonyms came from the contents of the American Museum of Natural History’s *Amphibian Species of the World* site (Frost 2022), as well as the analysis of each and every one of the original descriptions (see the aforementioned page for the corresponding bibliographic references).

As far as possible, each analyzed term is accompanied by the word or words that make it up, its language of origin (**A.** = Abyssinian; **Ar.** = Arawak; **Ap.** = Apurina; **B.** = Borun; **C.** = Caribe; **D.** = Dutch; **E.** = English; **F.** = French; **G.** = Greek; **Ge.** = German; **Gê** = Gê; **Gu.** = Guaraní; **H.** = Hebrew; **HC.** = Haitian creole; **It.** = Italian; **Iq.** = Iquitos; **J.** = Jê; **K.** = Karajás; **Ka.** = Kakano; **Ki.** = Kimbundú; **L.** = Latin; **M.** = Machiguanga or Matsigenka; **Ma.** = Malagasy; **Mu.** = Munduruku; **N.** = Nheengatu; **P.** = Portuguese; **Pe.** = Pemón; **Pl.** = Polysynthetic language; **Pu.** = Puri; **Q.** = Quechua; **Qi.** = Quimbundu; **S.** = Spanish; **Sh.** = Shiwilo (= Jebero); **T.** = Tupi; **Ta.** = Taíno; **Tu.** = Turkish; **Y.** = Yanomami], a fragment of the original description with which the interpretation of the name is validated (in case the etymology was not explicit), the original combination in which it was used, later combinations (not exhaustive), and present synonymy. Question marks (?) previous to the name indicates that the original language is unknown (to us); at the end of the etymologies reflect that there are no further data associated to the root or meaning

of of the name in the original description. It was also tried to refer the dates of birth and death of each patronym, that is, the person honoured by a scientific name when it is known that the person passed away. If there is no information about the dates of birth and death, a question mark (?) was added after the name, while when the honored person is currently alive, no date or mark was added.

Brown's lexicon (1954) has been a classic tool in zoological nomenclature since the middle of the 20th century. Paradoxically, it is the most consulted book, at the time of practically never being cited in the works in which new names are proposed (the exact transcriptions or translations of its definitions in various articles indicate this). Although it is an indispensable instrument, it is occasionally insufficient, so we rely on some other sources. For Greek, Bailly (1895), Beekes & Van Beek (2010), Borror (1960), Diggle et al. (2021), and Lidell & Scott (1996); Latin includes the dictionaries by Borror (1960), De Vaan (2008), and Glare (2012). Portuguese followed the famous Aurélio, of Ferreira et al., 2010, and VV. AA., 2021, and the native Tupí terms were defined with the help of Barbosa (1951), Dias (1858), Navarro (2008), Carvalho (1987), and Sampaio (1987). Additionally, some names were identified based on Beolens et al. (2013). Although all the specific epithets were elucidated, there is one name (*Hyla robersimoni* Donoso-Barros, 1965) that was not yet explained, since we couldn't identify the people to whom it was dedicated. We hope that the readers of this article can fill in this gap.

ACKNOWLEDGES

We were able to gather and consult the original descriptions of all Brazilian amphibians, thanks to the generosity of Jessica Fratani, Sonia Z. Kretzschmar, César Barrio-Amorós, Aaron Bauer, Carlos E. Carabajal, Santiago Castroviejo-Fisher, Juan Diego Daza, Taran Grant, Enrique Lamarca, Nicolás Pelegrín, José P. Pombal Jr., Gustavo J. Scrocchi, and Juan Carlos Stazonelli-Sadir, who generously shared their libraries and knowledge.

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For original descriptions and mentioned combinations, see Frost (2022).

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la langue grecque classique; les indications grammaticales usuelles; la quantité; le sens, justifié par d'abondantes références, avec renvois au texte, et par de nombreux exemples traduits; l'étymologie; les noms propres placés à leur ordre alphabétique; suivi d'une liste des racines mentionnée dans l'ouvrage, de tableaux sur le calendrier, les monnaies, les poids, et mesures la numération des Grecs, et précédé d'une liste des auteurs et des ouvrages cités. Par M. A. Bailly (...). Librairie Hachette, Paris.

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ETYMOLOGIES

abbreviata, abbreviatus: L. *abbreviata*, -us, shortened, cut off. *Hyla abbreviata* Spix, 1824. (“... corpore abbreviato ...”). Also *Enydrobius abbreviatus* — Wagler, 1830. *Ololygon abbreviatus* — Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. *Hylodes abbreviatus* — Hensel, 1867. *Platymantes abbreviata* — Luederwaldt, 1929. *Eleutherodactylus abbreviatus* — Hoogmoed & Gruber. In the synonymy of *Haddadus binotatus* (Spix, 1824).

abdita: L. *abdita*, hidden, secret. *Ischnocnema abdita* Canedo & Pimenta, 2010. (“... It refers to the male habit of calling hidden in the basis of bushes, between leaves and or branches ...”).

abei: Abe + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Augusto Shinya Abe, Brazilian herpetologist. *Bufo abei* Baldissera et al., 2004. Also *Chaunus abei* — Frost et al., 2006. *Rhinella abei* — Chaparro et al., 2007. In the synonymy of *Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824).

academicus: L. *academicus*, academic; of the Academy. *Pristimantis academicus* Lehr et al., 2010. (“... The name refers to the collecting sites of the new species, which are within the Arboretum of the Universidad Nacional de la Amazonía Peruana ...”).

acangatan: T. *acanga*, head + T. *atan*, strong. *Cycloramphus acangatan* Verdade & Rodrigues, 2003. (“... in reference to the strong and massive jaw adductor muscles of these frogs ...”).

achavali: Achaval + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Federico Achaval Elena (1941-2010), Uruguayan herpetologist. *Bufo achavali* Maneyro et al., 2004. Also *Chaunus achavali* — Frost et al. 2006. Today *Rhinella achavali* (Maneyro et al., 2004).

achuar: Sh. *Achuar*, native Ecuadorian nation, from Sh. *achu*, vernacular name of the palm *Mauritia flexuosa* + Sh. *shuar*, people, human being. *Pristimantis achuar* Elmer & Cannatella, 2008. (“... This species is named for the Achuar indigenous nation of the upper Amazon basin, who are ardent

protectors of their biodiversity ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis luscombei* (Duellman & Mendelson, 1995).

acreana, acreanus: P. Acre, Brazilian state (from T. *a'quiri* or *a'kiru*, green river) + L. *-ana, -anus*, belonging to. *Hyla acreana* Bokermann, 1964. Also *Hyla senicula acreana* — B. Lutz, 1973. Today *Dendropsophus acreanus* (Bokermann, 1964).

Acrodytes: Gr. *akron* (ἄκρον), extreme or topmost part, peak, summit, top (of a hill or mountain) + G. *dýtis* (δύτης), diver. *Acrodytes* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus* Tschudi, 1838.

actaeus: G. *aktaios* (ακταῖος), on the coast or shore, coastal. *Brachycephalus actaeus* Monteiro et al., 2018. (“... The name is used in allusion to the typical habitat of the new species, the coastal lowlands of the Atlantic Forest ...”)

acuminata, acuminatus: L. *acuminatus*, sharp, pointed, tapering. (1) *Phyllodytes acuminatus* Bokermann, 1966 (“... Espécie pequena, de focinho acuminado ...”). (2) *Eleutherodactylus acuminatus* Shreve, 1935. (“... with a very differently sharpened snout ...”). Today *Pristimantis acuminatus* (Shreve, 1935). (3) *Hyla acuminata* Cope, 1862. (“... Head longer than wide, muzzle rather pointed, depressed ...”). Also *Scytopsis acuminatus* — Cope, 1874. *Oloolygon acuminata* — Fouquette and Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax acuminata* — Duellman and Wiens, 1992). Today *Scinax acuminatus* (Cope, 1862).

acutirostris: L. *acutus*, sharp, pointed + L. *rostris*, beak, snout. *Bufo* (*Oxyrhychus*) *acutirostris* Spix, 1824. (“... *Subexiguus, brunnescens, acutirostris* ...”). Also *Bufo* (*Rhinella*) *acutirostris* — Cuvier, 1829. Today *Rhinella acutirostris* (Spix, 1824).

Adelastes: G. *a-dilos* (α-δῆλος), inconspicuous, unseen + G. *ásteios* (ἄστειώς) cleverly—ref. to speaking, *Adelastes* Zweifel, 1986. (“... The generic name derives from the Greek words *adelos*, meaning concealed, and *astes*, a singer, and is of masculine gender ...”). The same root in *Adelastinae* Peloso et al., 2016.

- Adelophryne:** *G. a-dilos* (ἀ-δηλος), unseen, unknown, obscure+ *G. phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Adelophryne* Hoogmoed & Lescure, 1984. (“... in reference to the fact that these small froglets hardly have been collected for science until recently ...”).
- Adelphobates:** *G. adelphos* (αδελφος), brother + *G. bates* (βατές), a walker. *Adelphobates* Grant et al., 2006. (“... We take great pleasure in proposing this name in honor of Charles W. Myers and John W. Daly, ... scientific “brothers” ...”).
- adenocheira:** *G. adenos* (αδενος), gland + *G. cheiros* (χειρός), hand. *Cochranella adenocheira* Harvey & Noonan, 2005. (“... The name calls attention to the distinctive white glands above the webbing and along the fingers of this species ...”). Today *Teratohyla adenocheira* (Harvey & Noonan, 2005).
- adenoderma:** *G. adenos* (αδενος), gland + *G. dermos* (δερμος), skin. *Hyla adenoderma* B. Lutz, 1968. (“... Skin extremely coriaceous, entirely glandular and mammillate on the dorsal surface and sides of the body ...”). Also *Phrynohyas adenoderma* — Vanzolini (1986). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).
- Adenomera:** *G. adenos* (αδενος), gland + *G. meros* (μερος), thigh. *Adenomera* Steindachner, 1867. (“...eine grosse, flache Drüse an den Lenden...”).
- adiastola:** *G. a-diaستي* (α-διαστολη), not separated, confused. *Adelophryne adiaстola* Hoogmoed & Lescure, 1984. (“... in reference to the fact that originally these specimens were referred to *Phyzelaphryne miriamae* ...”).
- admirabilis:** *L. admirabilis*, admirable, wonderful; strange, astonishing, remarkable. *Melanophryniscus admirabilis* Di Bernardo et al., 2006. (“... refers to the adjective “admirable,” because of the beautiful coloration of this toad ...”).
- adspersa:** *L. adspersa*, sprinkle, splash. *Corythomantis adspersa* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Le fond du dos est châtain clair, à petites taches noires dans les régions latérale et lombaire ...”). Also *Aparasphenodon adspersus* — Goin, 1961. In the synonymy of *Nyctimantis bruno*i (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

aeneus: L. *aeneus* (also *aheneus*), copper, of copper; bronze, made of bronze. *Crossodactylus aeneus* Müller, 1924. (“... Die ganze Rückenzone — von der Schnauze bis zum After —, sowie die Oberarme sind lichtbronzefarbig mit starkem Metallglanz ...”). In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus gaudichaudii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

affinis: L. *affinis*, related, akin, connected. (1) *Hyla affinis* Spix, 1824. (“... *Corpus mediocre*, *Hylae nebulosae affine* ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax x-signatus* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Rana affinis* Peters, 1859. (“... Dieser Frosch unterscheidet sich von unserer *Rana temporaria*, mit welcher er durch die Form des Körpers, der Extremitäten ...”). Also *Ranula affinis* — Cope, 1866. *Rana (Ranula) affinis* — Sumichrast, 1880. In the synonymy of *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824).

agilis: L. *agilis*, agile, nimble, quick, active; energetic. *Hyla agilis* Cruz & Peixoto, 1983 “1982”. (“... O nome “*agilis*” foi atribuído em função da extraordinária agilidade apresentada pelos indivíduos dessa espécie, o que dificulta, em muito a sua captura ...”). Also *Ololygon agilis* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Scinax agilis* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1983).

agrestis: L. *agrestis*, rustic, inhabiting countryside; rude, wild, savage. *Hyla agrestis* Bell, 1843. (“... Mr. Darwin observes that this species was found in numbers in the open grass plains, and likewise in swamps, about Maldonado, and that they can never ascend trees, as these are entirely wanting at the places frequented by the *Hylae* ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana pulchella* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

agua: (?) *agua*, apocope of (?) *aguaquaquan*, vernacular name of unknown origin, according to Seba (1734). (1) *Bufo agua* Latreille in Sonnini de Manoncourt & Latreille, 1801 “An. X.” (“... Séba l’a figuré sous plusieurs noms, mais ses figures sont à peine reconnaissables ...”). Also *Docidophryne agua* — Fitzinger, 1843. In the synonymy of *Rhinella icterica* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Phrynoidis agua* — Cope, 1862. Simultaneously in the synonymy of *Rhinella poeppigii* (Tschudi, 1845) and *Rhinella icterica* (Spix, 1824), *vide* Frost (2021).

aguirrei: Aguirre + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Álvaro Coutinho Aguirre (1899-1987), Brazilian zoologist. *Physalaemus aguirrei* Bokermann, 1966.

ahenea: L. *ahenea* (also *aenea*), copper, of copper; bronze, made of bronze. *Hyla ahenea* Napoli & Caramaschi, 2004. (“... in preservative, dorsal surfaces bearing copper or bronze ...”). Also *Boana ahenea* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla ahenea* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 2004).

ajurauna: T. *ajura*, throat + T. *una*, black. *Leptodactylus ajurauna* Berneck et al., 2008. [“... throat overall dark (densely speckled with numerous brown spots) ...”]. Today *Adenomera ajurauna* (Berneck et al., 2008).

ajuricaba: P. *Ajuricaba*, angry wasp, a leader of the Manaus native Brazilian nation; from corr. T. *kã-go-aiba*, angry, wrathful, exalted, fierce + T. *kaba*, bee or wasp. *Synapturanus ajuricaba* Fouquet et al., 2021. (“... The specific name *ajuricaba* ... is given as a reference to the legendary indigenous figure, Ajuricaba, a prominent leader of the Manaus indigenous people ...”).

alagoana, alagoanus: P. Alagoas, Brazilian state (in turn, a flooded field or marsh) + L. *-ana*, *-anus*, pertaining to. (1) *Chiasmocleis alagoana* Cruz et al., 1999. (“... The specific name refers to the occurrence of the species as an inhabitant of the State of Alagoas, Brazil ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis alagoanus* Cruz et al., 1999. *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) alagoana* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. (2) *Phyllobates alagoanus* Bokermann, 1967. (“... coleccionado em Mangabeiras, Alagoas, Brasil ...”). Also *Colostethus alagoanus* — Edwards, 1971. *Allobates alagoanus* — Grant et al., 2006. In the synonymy of *Allobates olfersioides* (A. Lutz, 1925).

Alainia: F. Alain + L. *-ia*, suffix commemorative and dedicative. Honouring Alain Dubois, French batrachologist. *Alainia* Duellman & Cannatella, 2018.

albicans: L. *albicans*, be white; have a whitish tinge, verge on white. (1) *Bufo albicans* Spix, 1824. (“... *Corpus submediocre, supra brunnescenti-albicans* ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Hyla albicans* Bokermann, 1967. (“... Todo el diseño dorsal es blanquecino y marginado de blanco puro ...”). Also *Ololygon albicans* — Peixoto & Weygoldt, 1987. Today *Scinax albicans* (Bokermann, 1967).

albida: L. *albida*, white, whitish, pale. *Hyla albida* Melin, 1941. (“... Above whitish with sparse, small, dark spots ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus rhodopeplus* (Günther, 1858).

albifrons: L. *albus*, white, pale + L. *frons*, fore part of anything. *Bufo albifrons* Spix, 1824. (“...*fronte albicante* ...”). Also *Bombinator albifrons* — Schlegel, 1826. *Paludicola albifrons* — Wagler, 1830. Today *Physalaemus albifrons* (Spix, 1824)

albiventris: L. *albus*, white, pale + L. *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly. *Physodes albiventris* Jan, 1857 (*nomen nudum*). (?). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema brachyops* (Cope, 1869).

albofrenata, albofrenatus: L. *albus*, white, pale + L. *frenum*, bridle, rein + L. *-ata, -atus*, state or condition of. *Hyla albofrenata* A. Lutz, 1924. (“... elle a aussi, des deux côtés, une ligne blanche sur le canthus rostralis qui est aigu ...”). Also *Aplastodiscus albofrenatus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. *Boana albofrenata* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Aplastodiscus albofrenatus* (A. Lutz, 1924).

albolineata, albolineatus: L. *albus*, white, pale + L. *lineata*, lined. (1) *Hyla albolineata* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939. (“... None of the green frogs found in the same region have the narrow white lines that characterise it ...”). Also *Gastrotheca albolineata* — Sachsse et al., 1999. *Gastrotheca (Australotheca) albolineata* — Duellman, 2015. *Gastrotheca (Alainia) albolineata* — Duellman & Cannatella, 2018. Today *Alainia albolineata* (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939). (2) *Brachycephalus albolineatus* Bornschein et al., 2016. (“... in reference to the characteristic white stripe across the dorsum of the new species, present in most specimens ...”).

albomarginata, albomarginatus: L. *albus*, white, pale + L. *marginata, -us*, provided with borders. *Hyla albomarginata* Spix, 1824. (“... *inter oculos, tympanum, nec non pone tarsum & anum albo-marginata* ...”). Also *Hypsiboas albomarginatus* — Wagler, 1830. *Hypsiboas (Phyllobius) albomarginatus* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Phyllobius albomarginatus* — Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. *Hypsiboas albomarginatus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana albomarginata* (Spix, 1824).

albonotatus: *L. albus*, white, pale + *L. notatus*, marked, signed. (1) *Leiuperus albonotatus* Steindachner, 1864. (“... Der Rücken ist in der Regel hellgrau, selten graulich violett. Dunkelbraune Flecken mit hellgesäumtem Rande liegen unregelmässig zerstreut auf der Rückenfläche, fliessen in den meisten Fällen an ihren Enden mehr oder minder zusammen und schliessen so hellere, grössere oder kleinere Flecken von der Grundfarbe des Körpers vollständig oder nur zum Theile ein (...). Hierauf bezieht sich der von Fitzinger gewählte Artnamen *Ph. Albonotatus* ...”). Also *Physalaemus albonotatus* Jan, 1857. *Gomphobates albonotatus* — Günther, 1865. Today *Physalaemus albonotatus* (Steindachner, 1864). (2) *Bufo albonotatus* Daudin, 1803 “An. XI”. (“... Le crapaud a taches blanches ...”). Also *Bufo albonatus* — Merrem, 1820 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Lithodytes lineatus* (Schneider, 1799).

albopunctata, albopunctatus: *L. albus*, white, pale + *L. punctata*, -us, punctuated; pointed. (1) *Hyla albopunctata* Spix, 1824. (“... femoribus postice punctatis ...”). Also *Hypsiboas albipunctatus* — Cope, 1867 (error for *Hypsiboas albopunctatus*). *Hyla albopunctata albopunctata* — Rivero, 1961. *Hypsiboas albopunctatus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana albopunctata* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Engystoma albopunctatum* Boettger, 1885. (“... corpore undique laete albopunctato ...”). Also *Gastrophryne albopunctata* — Stejneger, 1910. *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) albopunctata* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. *Chiasmocleis (Relictus) albopunctata* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. Today *Chiasmocleis albopunctata* (Boettger, 1885).

albosignata, albosignatus: *L. albus*, white, pale + *L. signata* -us, mark, stamp. *Hyla albosignata* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938. (“... The species name is derived from the other principal character, an agglomeration of glandular dots that form part of the anal pattern ...”). Also *Boana albosignata* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Aplastodiscus albosignatus* (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938).

albotunica: *L. albus*, white, pale + *L. tunica*, undergarment, shirt, tunic. *Cochranella albotunica* Taylor & Cochran, 1953. [“... eyeball surrounded largely by a white tunic (seen easily on inside of mouth) ...”]. Also *Centrolenella albotunica* — Lynch & Duellman, 1973. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana uranoscopa* (Müller, 1924).

- albovittata:** L. *albus*, white, pale + L. *vittata*, wearing or carrying a ritual vitta. *Hyla albovittata* Lichtenstein & Martens, 1856. (“... *labio superiore et vitta a naribus in supercilia indeque per latera corporis ad flexuram inguinalem producta, alteraque latus externum crurum occupante albis ...*”). In the synonymy of *Boana pulchella* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).
- alcatraz:** P. Alcatraz[es], island in the state of São Paulo. *Hyla catharinae alcatraz* B. Lutz, 1973. (“... Three specimens of *Hyla* belonging to the group of *Hyla catharinae*, from the island of Alcatrazes, on the coast of the state of São Paulo, are described here as a new race ...”). Also *Ololygon alcatraz* — Peixoto, 1988. Today *Scinax alcatraz* (B. Lutz, 1973).
- alfaroi:** Alfaro + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Eloy Alfaro Delgado (1842-1912), former Ecuadorian president (1895-1901 and 1906-1911). *Hypsiboas alfaroi* Caminer & Ron, 2014. Today *Boana alfaroi* (Caminer & Ron, 2014).
- alios:** L. *alae*, wing + L. *os*, mouth. *Altigius alios* Wild, 1995. (“... in reference to the uniquely large scalloped oral flaps pendant over the mouth of the tadpole ...”). Today *Hamptophryne alios* (Wild, 1995).
- alipioi:** Alipio + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alípio de Miranda Ribeiro (1874-1939), Brazilian zoologist. (1) *Brachycephalus alipioi* Pombal & Gasparini, 2006. (2) *Melanophryniscus alipioi* Langone et al., 2008. (3) *Macrogenioglottus alipioi* Carvalho, 1946; also *Odontophrynus alipioi* — Lynch, 1971.
- alium:** L. *alius*, other, another; different, changed. *Pleurodema alium* Maciel & Nunes, 2010. [“... The specific epithet is derived from the Latin “*alius*” (English “other”) in allusion to the unexpected finding of this new species ...”].
- alleni:** Allen + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Harrison Allen (1841-1897), US American physician and anatomist. *Scytopsis alleni* Cope, 1870 “1869”. Also *Ololygon alleni* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax alleni* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. In the synonymy of *Scinax ruber* (Laurenti, 1768).

allenorum: Allen + L. *-orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. Honouring Arly, Constance, and Harold Allen (?), US American printers. *Hyla allenorum* Duellman & Trueb, 1989. Also *Dendropsophus allenorum* — Faivovich et al., 2005. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus timbeba* (Martins & Cardoso, 1987).

Allobates: G. *allos* (ἄλλος), other, different + G. *bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (in turn, from βαίνω, move by taking step). *Allobates* Zimmermann & Zimmermann, 1988. [“... Der Name weist darauf hin, daß die Angehörigen dieser Gattung (unter *femoralis* sind bisher zwei bioakustisch unterschiedliche Formen bekannt) im Habitus und Verhalten, besonders aber in der Toxizität und in den Werbefernrufen ganz verschieden zu allen anderen Arten der Dendrobatidae (außer *Colostethus*) sind ...”]. The same root in *Allobatinae* Grant et al. (2006).

Allophryne: G. *allos* (ἄλλος), other, different + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Allophryne* Gaige, 1926. (“... A collection received by the Museum of Zoology from British Guiana some time ago includes a single specimen of a new species of frog which apparently belongs to the family Bufonide ..., but differs sufficiently from the known genera to warrant the erection of a new genus ...”). The same root in *Allophrynidae* Savage, 1973.

Alsodidae: G. *alsodis* (ἄσώδης), belonging to the forest / which grows in the forest; from *alsos* (ἄσος), sacred grove. Also, from G. *Alsêides* (Ἀλσηιδες), nymph of flowers, glens and groves + L. *-idae*, suffix indicating the category of family in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). *Alsodidae* Mivart, 1869.

altamazonica, altamazonicus: L. *alta*, high, elevate, upper + S., P. Amazonas, a South American river and a Brazilian state [in turn, from G. *Amazón* (Ἀμαζών), women warriors of the classic world] + L. *-ica, -icus*, suffix indicating belonging to, pertaining to. (1) *Argenteohyla altamazonica* Henle, 1981. (“... *Argenteohyla altamazonica* erhielt ihren Namen nach ihrem Vorkommen im oberen Amazonasbecken ...”); in the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Oedipus altamazonicus* Cope, 1874. (“... From Nauta ...” [a city near the confluence of the Marañón and Ucayali rivers, whose confluence originates the Amazon ...]). Also *Geotri-*

ton altamazonicus — Smith, 1877. *Spelerpes altamazonicus* — Boulenger, 1882. *Bolitoglossa (Eladinea) altamazonica* — Parra-Olea et al., 2004. Today *Bolitoglossa altamazonica* (Cope, 1874). (3) *Eleutherodactylus altamazonicus* Barbour & Dunn, 1921. (“... from the upper Amazon, probably collected ... at Nauta ...”). Today *Pristimantis altamazonicus* (Barbour & Dunn, 1921).

alter, altera: L. *alter*, *altera*, one (of two); second/another. *Hyla rubra altera* B. Lutz, 1973 (replacement name for *Hyla rubra orientalis* B. Lutz, 1968). (“... *nomen novum* for *Hyla rubra orientalis* B. Lutz, 1968 ...”). Also *Ololygon altera* — Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 1991. *Scinax altera* — Pombal et al., 1995. *Scinax alterus* — Silvano & Pimenta, 2001. Today *Scinax alter* (B. Lutz, 1973).

Altigius: Altig + L. *-ius*, suffix commemorative/dedicative. Honouring Ronald Altig, US American herpetologist. *Altigius* Wild, 1995. In the synonymy of *Hamptophryne* Carvalho, 1954.

altomontana: L. *alta*, high, elevated + L. *montana*, mountainous. *Chiasmocleis altomontana* Forlani et al., 2017. (“... The specific name is a combination derived from the Latin words *altus* meaning high and *montani* meaning mountain that characterizes the high altitudinal mountain distribution up to 1,000 m of the new species ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) altomontana*— de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

aluminiata: L. *aluminiata*, provided with aluminium. *Hyla aluminiata* Anderson, 1906. (“... The front part of the head is either uniform silvery white, or there are ... a few scattered spots ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus rhodopeplus* (Günther, 1858).

alvarengai: Alvarenga + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Colonel Moacyr Alvarenga (1915-2010), Brazilian Air Force officer and zoologist. *Hyla alvarengai* Bokermann, 1956. Today *Bokermannohyla alvarengai* (Bokermann, 1956).

amadoi: Amado + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jorge Amado [Jorge Leal Amado de Faria] (1912-2001), Brazilian modernist writer. *Phyllodytes amadoi* Vörös et al., 2017.

amapaensis: P. Amapá, a Brazilian state, in turn from N. *amapá*, ending land + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Adelophryne amapaensis* Taucce et al., 2020. (“... The species is named after the Brazilian state of Amapá, from which all known specimens come ...”).

Amazonella: S., P. Amazonas, a South American river and a Brazilian state [in turn, from G. *Amazṓn* (Ἀμαζών), women warriors of the classic world] + L. *-ella*, suffix diminutive. *Amazonella* Fouquet et al. (2012). (“... It means “small Amazonian”, alluding to the small body size of the species and their Amazonian distribution ...”). Preoccupied by *Amazonella* Lundblad, 1921 (Acari). In the synonymy of *Amazophrynella* Fouquet et al., 2012.

amazonica, amazonicus: S., P. Amazonas, a South American river and a Brazilian state [in turn, from G. *Amazṓn* (Ἀμαζών), women warriors of the classic world] + L. *-ica, -icus*, pertaining/belonging to; connected with. (1) *Leptodactylus amazonicus* Heyer, 1978 (“... Distribution. — Throughout the greater Amazon Basin, Guianas, northern Atlantic forest, and cerrados bordering the Amazon Basin ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus mystaceus* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Dendrobates amazonicus* Schulte, 1999 (“... Die Bezeichnung *amazonicus* bezieht sich auf die weite Verbreitung der Art entlang des Amazonas/Solimoes und seiner Nebenflüsse bis nach Surinam und den Guayanas und welche sich wahrscheinlich nach bisherigen Fundortangaben genau mit der Verbreitung von *Epipedobates trivittatus* deckt ...”). Today *Ranitomeya amazonica* (Schulte, 1999).

Amazophrynella: S., P. Amazonas, a South American river and a Brazilian state [in turn, from G. *Amazṓn* (Ἀμαζών), women warriors of the classic world] + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + L. *-ella*, suffix diminutive. *Amazophrynella* Fouquet et al., 2012. (“... alluding to the small body size of the species and their Amazonian distribution ...”).

Amblyphrynus: G. *amblys* (αμβλύς), blunt, obtuse + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Amblyphrynus* Cochran & Goin, 1961. (“... Head broad and flattened. Snout prominent, rounded when viewed from above, sloping in profile, the upper jaw extending but little beyond the lower ...”). In the synonymy of *Strabomantis* Peters, 1863.

Ameerega: Meere + Tu. *aga*, chief, master, lord (divided in a- as a prefix and -ga, as suffix); honouring Jan Meere, Dutch herpetoculturist. *Ameerega* Bauer, 1986. (“... *A-meere-ga* is a combination of his name with “*aga*”. *Aga* means in middle-eastern history something as the first, the foremost; in Greek it is a prefix referring to good or very ...”).

ameghini: Ameghino + L. -i, suffix that indicates the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Florentino Ameghino (1853-1911), Argentinian paleontologist. *Paludicola ameghini* Cope, 1887. Today *Pseudopaludicola ameghini* (Cope, 1887).

americana, americanus: L. *americana*, demonym (f.) of the inhabitants of América. (1) *Pyxicephalus americanus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Ce Pyxicéphale, ainsi que l’indique son nom, est originaire du nouveau monde ...”). Also *Tomopterna americana* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Ceratophrys americana* — Boulenger, 1882. Today *Odontophrynus americanus* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841). (2) *Pipa americana* Laurenti, 1768. (“... *Habitat Surinam. Caro nigris Americanis in deliciis est ...*”). In the synonymy of *Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

ametarsia: G. *a-* (ἀ-), privative prefix + G. *metarsios* (μετάρσιος), which stands in high areas. *Centrolenella ametarsia* Flores, 1987. (“... The species name is from Ancient Greek and combines a-, “not,” and metarsia, “of the highlands. ...”). Also *Cochranella ametarsia* — Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana ritae* (B. Lutz in B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952).

amicorum: L. *amicus*, friendly, dear, fond of + L. -*orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. Honouring the members of the ‘*Allobates femoralis* project’ led by Albertina P. Lima throughout Brazilian Amazonia. *Adenomera amicornum* Carvalho et al., 2020.

amnicola: L. *amnicola*, growing beside a river. *Hylodes amnicola* Pombal et al., 2002. (“... The name of the new species, *amnicola*, ... means rivulet inhabitant, in allusion to the habitat of this species ...”).

Amphiumophis: G. *amphi* (ἀμφί), on both or all sides + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. *Amphiumophis* Werner, 1901. (?). In the synonymy of *Caecilia* Linnaeus, 1758.

Amphodus: *G. amphodous* (ἀμφόδους), dentate above and below (etymology by the author). *Amphodus* Peters, 1873 “1872”. (“... Zähne im Zwischen-, Ober- und Unterkiefer, an den Gaumenknochen und am Keilbeine ...”). In the synonymy of *Phyllodytes* Wagler, 1830.

anataliasiasi: *Anatalias* + unclear suffix¹. Honouring Mr. *Anatalias* J. Rodrigues (?), collector of the type. *Hyla anataliasiasi* Bokermann, 1972 (“... A espécie pertence ao grupo rubicundula e é aqui descrita como nova e dedicada a seu descobridor ...”). Today *Dendropsophus anataliasiasi* (Bokermann, 1972).

anceps: *L. anceps*, double; with two meanings; ambiguous. (1) *Hyla anceps* A. Lutz, 1929. (“... Nous décrivons ici une nouvelle *Hyla*, pour laquelle nous proposons le nom de *anceps*, parce qu’elle offre un mimétisme double ...”). Today *Dendropsophus anceps* (A. Lutz, 1929). (2) *Leptodactylus anceps* Gallardo, 1964. (“... Esta especie fue confundida por varios autores con *L. prognathus*, es en realidad netamente chaqueña, y respecto de ésta es en cierto modo su vicariante en la región ...”). Also *Leptodactylus latinasus anceps* — Ceñal, 1980. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latinasus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875.

Anchylorana: *G. ankylo[sis]* (ἀγκύλωσις), decrease or inability of movement in a joint + *L. rana*, frog. *Anchylorana* Taylor, 1942. [“... A genus of Pliocene frogs characterized by the fusion of the last two (the eighth and ninth sacral) vertebrae ...”]. In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

anderssoni: *Andersson* + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Lars Gabriel Andersson (1868-1951), Swedish herpetologist. (1) *Bufo anderssoni* Melin, 1941. Also *Rhaebo anderssoni* — Frost et al. 2006. In the synonymy of *Rhaebo guttatus* (Schneider, 1799). (2) *Eleutherodactylus anderssoni* Lynch, 1968 (replacement name for *Syrhophus calcaratus* Andersson, 1945, preoccupied by *Hylodes calcaratus* Boulenger, 1908). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis ockendeni* (Boulenger, 1912).

¹ Apparently the specific epithet *anataliasiasi* was a typographic error for *Anatalias* + *L. -i*, but there are evidences that Bokermann by one’s free will proposed the name.

- andianus:** S. Andes, South American mountain range [in turn, from ? *Andes*, a pre-Hispanic people in the Jauja region (Junín, Peru) that gave the mountain range its name] + L. *-anus*, belonging to. *Bufo andianus* Cope, 1868. (“... From the valley of Quito ...”). The same root in *Bufo marinus andinensis* Melin, 1941. In the synonymy of *Rhinella poeppigii* (Tschudi, 1845).
- andicola:** S. Andes, South American mountain range [in turn, from ? *Andes*, a pre-Hispanic people in the Jauja region (Junín, Peru) that gave the mountain range its name] + L. *-cola*, dwelling in, inhabiting, living among. *Amphiumophis andicola* Werner, 1901. [“... Ein Exemplar ... vom Chanchamayo ...” (a province in Junin Department, Peru)]. In the synonymy of *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758.
- Andinophryne:** S. *andino*, demonym (m.) of the inhabitants of the Cordillera de los Andes [in turn, from ? *Andes*, a pre-Hispanic people in the Jauja region (Junín, Peru) that gave the mountain range its name] + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Andinophryne* Hoogmoed, 1985. (“... Named for the Andes, the mountain range that has such a profound influence on the distribution of animals and plants in western South America, and from the Greek *phryne*, toad, in reference to the fact that these toads only are known from the western slopes of the Andes ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhaebo* Cope, 1862.
- andreae:** André + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating belonging to. Honouring André Goeldi (?), Brazilian botanist and photographer. *Leptodactylus andreae* Müller, 1923. Also *Leptodactylus (Lithodytes) andreae* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Adenomera andreae* (Müller, 1923).
- angrensis:** P. Angra [dos Reis], from P. *angra*, small and open bay + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Physalaemus angrensis* Weber et al., 2005. (“... The specific name is a Latinized adjective derived from the geographical name Angra dos Reis, referring to the type locality of the new species ...”). (2) *Hyla catharinae angrensis* B. Lutz, 1973. (“... Two specimens from Angra dos Reis, in the southern part of the state of Rio de Janeiro, are described as a new subspecies of *Hyla catharinae* ...”). Also *Hyla angrensis* — Pomal & Gordo, 1991. *Ololygon angrensis* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Scinax angrensis* (B. Lutz, 1973).

anguillaformis: L. *anguillaformis*, eel-shaped. *Typhlonectes anguillaformis* Taylor, 1968. (“... Low dermal “fin” visible from the greater part of body length ...”). In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

angustifrons: L. *angustus*, narrow, steep + L. *frons*, fore part of anything. *Hyla* (*Trachycephalus*) *angustifrons* Werner, 1893. [“... Unterscheidet sich von allen *Hyla*-Arten mit rauher und dem Knochen verwachsener Frontoparietalhaut durch die schmale Interorbitalregion (kaum breiter als ein oberes Augenlid) ...”]. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus nigromaculatus* Tschudi, 1838.

anisitsi: Anisits + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring János Dániel Anisits (1856-1911), Hungarian professor, active in Asunción (Paraguay). *Hylella anisitsi* Méhely, 1904. Also *Hyla anisitzi* – Nieden, 1923. *Hyla anisitzi* – Duellman, 1977 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Scinax nasicus* (Cope, 1862).

annulata, annulatus: L. *anulata*, *-atus*, provided with a ring, ringed; fitted with a fetter, fettered. *Caecilia annulata* Mikan, 1822. (“... corpore crasso, nigra, annulis albo-marginatis ...”). Also *Coecilia annulata* – Fitzinger, 1826. *Caecilia* (*Siphonops*) *annulata* – Van der Hoeven, 1833. *Siphonops annulata* – Duméril & Bibron, 1841. Today *Siphonops annulatus* (Mikan, 1820).

Anomaloglossus: G. *anomalous* (ανωμαλοσ), uneven, irregular, inconsistent, abnormal, unusual, deviating from the regular rule + G. *glossa* (γλώσσα), tongue. (“... in reference to the unusual tongue bearing the median lingual process ...”). *Anomaloglossus* Grant et al., 2006. The same root in *Anomaloglossinae* Grant et al., 2006.

antenori: Antenor + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Antenor Leitão de Carvalho (1910-1985), Brazilian herpetologist and ichthyologist. *Syncope antenori* Walker, 1973. Also *Chiasmocleis* (*Syncope*) *antenori* – de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. Today *Chiasmocleis antenori* (Walker, 1973).

antrum: L. *antrum*, cave; cavern; hollow; cavity. *Oreobates antrum* Vaz-Silva et al., 2018. (“... This name refers to the habitats where this species is found, caves of the calcareous rocky outcrops of the Cerrado associated to dry forests ...”).

Anura: G. *an-* (αν-), without, absent + *oura* (οὐρά), tail. (“... Batraciens ... a corps ramassé, sans queue ...”). Anura Duméril, 1805.

Aparasphenodon: G. *aparasalefstos* (ἄπαρασάλευτος), firm, unshankable + G. *odons* (ὀδονς), teeth. *Aparasphenodon* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... Dentes vomerinos e palatinos como em *Diaglena*, estes porém firmes e não apenas cutâneos ...”). In the synonymy of *Nyctimantis* Boulenger, 1882.

apiau: P. [Serra do] Apiaú, (probably from Y *apía'u*, the river of apia trees), locality in Roraima (2. 430168 N, 61. 411715 W). *Anomaloglossus apiau* Fouquet et al., 2015. [“... The specific epithet ... refers to the name of the region where the type locality lies (Serra do Apiaú, Roraima State, Brazil) ...”].

apicalis: L. *apicalis*, pertaining to the point, top, summit; cap, crown; conical priest cap. *Corythomantis apicalis* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (?). Also *Aparasphenodon apicalis* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Nyctimantis bruno* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

Aplastodiscus: Lutz, 1950. G. *aplastos* (ἀπλαστός), not shaped by moulding; unshapen, rough + G. *diskos* (δίσκος), circular plate. [“...Caracteres estruturais de *Hyla*, salvo quanto aos discos e dedos. Discos em forma de laminae, i e. unhas; estreitos, não ultrapassando a largura dos dedos...”].

appendiculata: L. *appendicula*, small addition; appendage + L. *-ata*, having, having a, provided with. (1) *Hyla appendiculata* Boulenger, 1882. (“... heel with a short, triangular dermal appendage ...”). Also *Hyla punctatissima appendiculata* — Parker, 1933. Today *Boana appendiculata* (Boulenger, 1882). (2) *Phyllomedusa appendiculata* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Le talon présente un appendice conique ...”). Today *Phrynomedusa appendiculata* (A. Lutz, 1925). (3) *Ceratophrys appendiculata* Günther, 1873. (“... Allied to *C. Boiei*; but the upper parts are covered with skinny appendages instead of with tubercles ...”). Also *Stombus appendiculatus* — Miranda-Ribeiro,

1920. *Ceratophrys appendiculata* — Nieden, 1923. *Stombus appendiculatus appendiculatus* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. Today *Proceratophrys appendiculata* (Günther, 1873).

apuana: T. *apuana*, to walk very fast (stepping high), running. *Megaelosia apuana* Pombal et al., 2003. (“... ‘*Apuana*’ is a Tupi indigenous word, here used as a noun in apposition, meaning agile ...”). Also *Hylodes apuanus* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Phantasmarana apuana* (Pombal et al., 2003).

Aquarana: L. *aqua*, water + L. *Rana*, genus of anurans due to Linnaeus (1758), in turn from *L. rana*, frog, derived from the onomatopoeia *rā*. (“... ce nom évoque le mode de vie très aquatique de ces Grenouilles ...”). *Aquarana* Dubois, 1992.

araguaius: T. *Araguaia*, large river in Central Brazil; [Municipality of Pontal do] Araguaia, state of Mato Grosso, Brazil; in turn, from T. *ará-guaya*, the tame parrots + L. *-ius*, pertaining to. *Pithecopus araguaius* Haga et al., 2017. (“... a reference to the Araguaia River, which cross the type-locality of the new species ...”).

araguaya: T. *Araguaia*, large river in Central Brazil; [Municipality of Pontal do] Araguaia, state of Mato Grosso, Brazil; in turn, from T. *ará-guaya*, the tame parrots. *Hyla araguaya* Napoli & Caramaschi, 1998. (“... O nome específico ... refere-se à área de ocorrência da espécie, às margens do rio Araguaia ...”). Today *Dendropsophus araguaya* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1998).

araguari: P. [River] Araguari, Municipality of Uberlândia, Minas Gerais, Brazil (in turn from T. *aráguá-r-y*, the water or river of the parrots’ lowland). *Phyllomedusa araguari* Giaretta et al., 2007. [“... The specific epithet “*araguari*” is an indigenous Tupi word for the white-eyed parakeet (*Aratinga leucophthalmus*), it is also the name of the dammed river bordering the type locality of the new species and the name of a municipality at its margins ...]. In the synonymy of *Pithecopus oreades* (Brandão, 2002).

aramunha: T. *aramunha*, giant. *Strabomantis aramunha* Cassimiro et al., 2008. (“... in allusion to the large size of the species ...”). Today *Haddadus aramunha* (Cassimiro et al., 2008).

arapapa: T. *arapapá*, vernacular name of *Cochlearius cochlearius* (Ciconiiformes, Ardeidae), the Boat-billed Heron. *Aparasphenodon arapapa* Pimenta et al., 2009. (“... Its wide and flattened beak resembles the snout of the new *Aparasphenodon* described here ...”). Today *Nyctimantis arapapa* (Pimenta et al., 2009).

ararype: T. *ararype*, macaw’s river; from T. *arara*, macaw + T. *y*, river + T. *pe*, on the. *Proceratophrys ararype* Mângia et al., 2018. (“...Because the new species is known only from the Araripe region, we name it after this area...”).

araucaria: L. *Araucaria*, genus of the order Pinales of Gondwanic origin. *Adenomera araucaria* Kwet & Angulo, 2003. (“... The new species is named after the Paraná pine, *Araucaria angustifolia*, in allusion to the preferred microhabitat at CPCN Pro-Mata ...”). Also *Leptodactylus (Lithodytes) araucaria* — Frost et al., 2006.

araxa: T. *araxa*, from *ara*, world + *eça*, to see (the first place where the sun can be seen). Etymology by the authors. *Physalaemus araxa* Leal et al., 2021. (“... Also used to indicate the highest mountain in a landscape. That is the specific case of the type locality of *Physalaemus araxa* sp. nov., found on the mountaintop of the highest hill of the Atlantic forest ...”).

Arcovomer: L. *arcus*, bow, arc, coil, arch + L. *vomer*, a bone. *Arcovomer* Carvalho, 1954. [“... The generic name *Arcovomer* (arched vomer) is Latin and is descriptive of the peculiar prevomer of this genus ...”].

arduous: L. *arduus*, arduous, difficult. *Scinax arduous* Peixoto, 2002. (“... O epíteto específico faz referência à dificuldade de colecionamento de adultos desta espécie ...”). Also *Ololygon arduoa* — Duellman et al., 2016.

arenarum: L *arena*, sand + L. *-arum*, having the nature of. *Bufo arenarum* Hensel, 1867. (“... Sieben Individuen, deren grösstes 75 mm. lang ist, wurden bei der Stadt Rio-Grande do Sul gefangen, wo sie bei Nacht auf den trockenen Sanddünen umherlaufen, bei Tage sich unter den Wurzeln der Sträucher gesellschaftlich verbergen ...”). Also *Bufo arenarius* — A. Lutz, 1934 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Chaunus arenarum* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella arenarum* (Hensel, 1867).

Argenteohyla: *L. argenteus*, latinization of Argentina (from *L. argentum*, silver) + *L. Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Argenteohyla* Trueb, 1970. (“... With reference to Argentina, the country in which this genus is most widely distributed, this new genus is here given a name derived from the Latin *argenteus* ...”). In the synonymy of *Nyctimantis* Boulenger, 1882.

argentina: S. Argentina, South American country (in turn, from *L. argentus*, silver). *Ceratophrys argentina* Philippi, 1902. (“... la especie pequeña podría llamarse acaso: *Ceratophrys argentina* Ph. ...”). In the synonymy of *Odonotophrynus americanus* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

argyreornata, argyreornatus: *G. argyros* (αργυρός), silver + *L. ornata*, -us, richly adorned, ornate. *Hylodes argyreornatus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... Côr em cima negra e sepia com quatro máculas prateadas ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus argyreornatus* — Myers, 1962. *Hyla argyreornata* — Bokermann, 1966. *Oloolygon argyreornata* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax argyreornata* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax argyreornatus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

ariadne: *G. Ariadne* (Ἀριάδνη), the daughter of King Minos of Crete. *Hyla ariadne* Bokermann, 1967. (?). Also *Oloolygon ariadnae* — Peixoto & Weygoldt, 1987. Today *Scinax ariadne* (Bokermann, 1967).

ariana: Ariane + *L. -ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Ariane Luna Peixoto, wife of the second author. *Hyla arianae* Cruz & Peixoto, 1987 “1985”. In the synonymy of *Aplastodiscus ehrhardti* (Müller, 1924).

aridus: *L. aridus*, dry, arid, parched. *Proceratophrys aridus* Cruz et al., 2012. (“... The specific epithet, “*aridus*”, is a Latin adjective meaning dry, in allusion to the climate of the Caatinga Domain, where the type-locality is placed ...”). In the synonymy of *Proceratophrys cristiceps* (Müller, 1883).

arii: Ari + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ari Santiago Lima-Verde, Brazilian physician. *Chthonerpeton arii* Cascon & Lima-Verde, 1994.

- arildae:** Arilda + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Arilda M. Gonçalves da Cruz, wife of the first author. *Hyla arildae* Cruz & Peixoto, 1987 “1985”. Also *Boana arildae* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Aplastodiscus arildae* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1987).
- armata:** L. *armata*, defensively armed, armor clad. *Caecilia armata* Dunn, 1942. (“... This remarkable form has the hind half of the body with bony scales ...”).
- Aromobatidae:** G. *aroma* (άρωμα), smell, fragrant spice + G. *bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (from βαίνω, move by taking step) + L. *-idae*, suffix indicating the category of family in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). Aromobatidae Grant et al., 2006.
- aromothyella:** G. *aroma* (άρωμα), smell, fragrant spice + G. *thyella* (θύελλα), storm-wind, gale, squall; blast. *Scinax aromothyella* Faivovich, 2005. (“... The name is intended to mean “smell of the storm”, alluding to the propensity of these frogs to appear during or after heavy rains ...”). Also *Ololygon aromothyella* — Duellman et al., 2016.
- arrabali:** Arrabal + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jailton Aguiar Arrabal (?), collector of the type material. *Pipa arrabali* Izecksohn, 1976.
- Aruncus:** M. *arauco*, water toad. *Aruncus* Philippi, 1902. [“... Forma general del cuerpo i de sus miembros como en el jénero *Bufo* ...”]. In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.
- asper, aspera:** L. *asper*, rough/uneven/shaggy, coarse, harsh. (1) *Cycloramphus asper* Werner, 1899. (“... Oberseite mit kleinen spitzigen Warzen dicht besetzt ...”). Also *Telmatobius asper* Boulenger, 1907. *Cyclorhamphus asper* — Barbour & Noble, 1920. *Iliodiscus asper* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. *Grypiscus asper* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1935. (2) *Elosia aspera* Müller, 1924. Today *Hylodes asper* (Müller, 1924). (3) *Hylomantis aspera* Peters, 1873. (?). Also *Phyllomedusa aspera* — Boulenger, 1882. *Phyllomedusa (Hylomantis) aspera* — B. Lutz, 1950. *Hylomantis aspera* — B. Lutz, 1968. *Agalychnis aspera* — Faivovich et al., 2010. *Hylomantis asperus* — Duellman et al., 2016. (4) *Hyperoodon asper* Philippi, 1902. Also *Hiperoodon asper*

— Philippi, 1902 (incorrect spelling of generic name); in the synonymy of *Odontophrynus americanus* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841). (5) *Lepidobatrachus asper* Budgett, 1899. (“... Skin of dorsal surface a dull leaden colour, much tuberculated and tough ...”). Also *Ceratophrys aspera* — Boulenger, 1919.

astarteia: G. *Astarte*, Phoenician goddess of love and fertility. *Hyla astartea* Bokermann, 1967. (?). Today *Bokermannohyla astartea* (Bokermann, 1977).

Asterodactylus: G. *asteros* (ἀστέρος), star + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. (1) *Asterodactylus* Wagler, 1827. (“... Der zahn- und zungenlosen Sternfingerunke (*Asterodactylus* m. *Pipa* Auctor) steht sie am nächsten ...”). Same root in *Astroedactylus* — Hogg, 1839 (presumably an incorrect subsequent spelling of *Asterodactylus* Wagler, 1827). In the synonymy of *Pipa* Laurenti, 1768. (2) *Leptopus asterodactylus* Mayer, 1835. (“... *palmae apicibus digitorum quadrifidae* ...”). In the synonymy of *Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Atelophryniscus: G. *ateles* (ἀ-τελής), imperfect + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + L. *-icus*, pertaining to. *Atelophryniscus* McCranie et al., 1989. [“... The name is a reference to the resemblance of the tadpole to that of species of *Atelopus* and the resemblance of the adult to species of *Bufo*, as well as to the small size of the adults ...”]. In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

ateloide, ateloides: L. *Atelopus*, genus of anurans due to Duméril & Bibron (1841) (see) + G. *-oeides* (-οειδής), similar to. (1) *Brachycephalus ateloide* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... desaparecimento completo dos escudos dorsaes e do revestimento cephalico, com uma substituição concomittante de verrugas salientes sobre a pelle, numa variedade perfeitamente *ateloide* ...”). (2) *Phyllomedusa ateloides* Duellman et al., 1988. (“... The name is used in allusion to the *Atelopus*-like morph and gait of *P. ateloides* ...”). Today *Callimedusa ateloides* (Duellman et al., 1988).

Atelopus: G. *ateles* (ατελες), imperfect + G. *podos* (ποδος), foot. *Atelopus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Cinq orteils, dont un non distinct extérieurement; les quatre autres aplatis, réunis à leur base par une membrane ...”). Same root in *Ateleopus* Agassiz, 1846 (unjustified emendation); *Antelopus* — Orton, 1876 (incorrect subsequent spelling).

atim: T. *atim*, from T. *tî*, front (in general), beak, muzzle, nose, bow. *Physalaemus atim* Brasileiro & Haddad, 2015. (“... *Atim* is a Tupi indigenous word that means “big nose”. It is used here ... in allusion to the long snout of the new species ...”).

atlantica, atlanticus: L. *atlantica*, -us, belonging to Atlantic. (1) *Hyla atlantica* Caramaschi & Velosa, 1996. (“... O nome da espécie faz alusão a sua ocorrência no leste brasileiro, na região da Floresta Atlântica, que se contrapõe à ocorrência de sua espécie afim, *Hyla punctata*, na Amazônia ...”). Also *Hypsiboas atlanticus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana atlantica* (Caramaschi & Velosa, 1996). (2) *Chiasmocleis atlantica* Cruz et al., 1997 (“... The specific name, a Latin adjective, refers to the Atlantic Rain Forest of eastern Brazil ...”). (3) *Physalaemus atlanticus* Haddad & Sazima, 2004. (“... refers to the habitat of the new species, the Atlantic rain forest in southeastern Brazil, where the new species may be found at the seashore ...”).

atlas: G. *Atlas* (Ἀτλας), Titan forced by Zeus to support the heavens on his shoulders. *Trachycephalus atlas* Bokermann, 1966. (?).

atragula: L. *atra*, black, dark; dark-colored + L. *gula*, throat, neck, gullet, maw. *Pseudopaludicola atragula* Pansonato et al., 2014 [“... It is used in reference to the dark gular region of most males (in life) – unusual within the genus *Pseudopaludicola* – with white areolations interspersed among dark reticulation ...].

atrata, atratus: L. *atrata*, -us, darkened, blackened, dingy; clothed in black, in/wearing mourning. *Hyla atrata* Peixoto, 1989 “1988”. (“... O epíteto específico faz referência à coloração escurecida dos exemplares ...”). Also *Ololygon atrata* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Scinax atratus* (Peixoto, 1989).

Atretochoana: G. *a-tretos* (α-τρητος), imperforate + G. *choane* (χοάνη), funnel or tube, choana. *Atretochoana* Nussbaum & Wilkinson, 1995. (“... typhlonectid caecilians with sealed choanae, no lungs, no pulmonary blood vessels ...”).

atroluteus: L. *ater*, black, dark; dark-colored + L. *luteus*, yellow; saffron; of mud or clay. *Atelopus atro-luteus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. [“... Cor (no alcool)

negro retinto de pez, os espinhos albicantes ...”]. Also *Melanophryniscus stelzneri atroluteus* — Gallardo, 1961. Today *Melanophryniscus atroluteus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

attenuata: *L. attenuata*, weakened, diminished, shrunked, reduced in size. *Hyla senicula attenuata* B. Lutz, 1973 (*nomen nudum*). (?). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus melanargyreus* (Cope, 1887).

Auletris: *G. auletris* (αὐλητρίς), female aulos-player, being *aulos* (αὐλός) a double flute. *Auletris* Wagler, 1830. (“... Αὐλητρίς tibicina ...”). In turn, *Tibicina* is the latin name of the female performer on the tibia. In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

aurantiaca, aurantiacus: *L. aurantiaca*, orange-colored. (1) *Adenomera aurantiaca* Carvalho et al., 2020. (“... referring to the brightly orange-coloured limbs of this species ...”). (2) *Ephippipher aurantiacus* Cocteau, 1835. (“... *Supra subtusque aurantiacus immaculatus* ...”). Also *Brachycephalus aurantiacus* — Girard, 1858. In the synonymy of *Brachycephalus ephippium* (Spix, 1824). (3) *Hyla aurantiaca* Daudin, 1802 “An. XI”. (“... Couleur d’un jaune orangé, plus pâle sous le corps, avec une teinte rougeâtre rare sur le dos ...”). Also *Calamita aurantiacus* — Merrem, 1820. *Auletris aurantiaca* — Wagler, 1830. *Dryomelictes aurantiacus* — Cope, 1865. *Dendropsophus (Dryomelictes) aurantiacus* — Cope, 1871 “1870”. *Scytopis aurantiacus* — Cope, 1874. *Hyla (Sphaenohyla) aurantiaca* — A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938. *Sphaenohyla aurantiaca* — Goin, 1957. *Sphaenorhynchus aurantiacus* — Myers & Leviton, 1961. The same root in *Rana aurantia* Shaw, 1802 (possibly an incorrect spelling of *Hyla aurantiaca* Daudin, 1802). In the synonymy of *Sphaenorhynchus lacteus* (Daudin, 1800).

aurata, auratus: *L. aurata*, -us, gilded, overlaid/adorned with gold, golden. *Hyla aurata* Wied-Neuwied, 1821. (“... der Rücken ist daher mit drey gelben Längsstreifen bezeichnet, auch bemerkt man auf den Oberarmen und Schenkeln einige gelbe oder goldfarbene Fleckchen ...”). Also *Ololygon aurata* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax auratus* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).

aureolineatus: L. *aureus*, of gold, golden; gilded; gold bearing; gleaming like gold + L. *lineatus*, lined. *Eleutherodactylus aureolineatus* Guayasamin et al., 2006. (“... The name is used in reference to the dorso-lateral golden stripe characteristic of the new species ...”). Today *Pristimantis aureolineatus* (Guayasamin et al., 2006).

aurita: L. *aurita*, with/having ears. *Bufo auritus* Raddi, 1823. (“... Egli supera in grandezza il precedente, e ne differisce essenzialmente per le sue prominente piano-triangolari Δ situate sopra le palpebre superiori, da dove sporgono in fuori, quasi rappresentando due orecchie ...”). Today *Ceratophrys aurita* (Raddi, 1823).

auroguttatus: L. *aurum*, gold + L. *guttatum*, provided with drops, spots or specks. *Brachycephalus auroguttatus* Ribeiro et al., 2015. (“... remaining regions of body with a mixture of brown and yellow ...”).

Australotheca: L. *australis*, southern; of/brought by the south wind + G. *theke* (θήκη), storage-container, chest. *Australotheca* Duellman, 2015. (“... The name refers to the southern distribution of the subgenus ...”). Preoccupied by *Australotheca* Malinky, 2009, a fossil sponge. In the synonymy of *Alainia* Duellman & Cannatella, 2018.

avelinoi: Avelino + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Avelino Barrio (1920-1979), Argentinian herpetologist. *Proceratophrys avelinoi* Mercadal de Barrio & Barrio, 1993.

avilapiresae: Ávila Pires + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Teresa Cristina Sauer de Ávila Pires, Brazilian herpetologist. *Chiasmocleis avilapiresae* Peloso & Sturaro, 2008. Also *Chiasmocleis* (*Chiasmocleis*) *avilapiresae* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

avivoca: L. *avis*, bird + L. *voca*, call, summon; name; call upon. *Leptodactylus avivoca* Carvalho et al., 2021. [... *avivoca* (= bird-voiced), a noun in apposition, is an allusion to the trill calls of the new species ...].

ayarzagüenai: Ayarzagüena + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Ayarzagüena Sanz (1952-2011), Span-

ish herpetologist active in Venezuela. *Osteocephalus ayarzaguenai* Gorzula & Señaris, 1997 “1996”. In the synonymy of *Osteocephalus leprieurii* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

ayeaye: F., from Ma. *aye-aye*², *Daubentonia madagascariensis* Gray, 1863. *Pithecopus ayeaye* B. Lutz, 1966. (“... In 1868, Cope chose the appropriate trivial name *tarsius* for a large *Pithecopus* ... Later, Boulenger named two other ... *Phyllomedusa lemur* and *P. loris* ... The author thus adds one of the names not yet used, *ayeaye* ...”). Also *Phyllomedusa ayeaye* — Duellman, 1968.

azarai: Azara + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Félix Francisco José Pedro de Azara y Perera (1742-1821), Spanish military officer, engineer, and naturalist. *Bufo granulatus azarai* Gallardo, 1965. Today *Rhinella azarai* (Gallardo, 1965).

azurea, azureus: L. *azurea*, *-us*, azure; blue; of lapis lazuli. (1) *Dendrobates azureus* Hoogmoed, 1969. (“... Above and below bright blue with black spots ...”). Also *Dendrobates tinctorius azureus* — Ouboter & Jairam, 2012. In the synonymy of *Dendrobates tinctorius* (Cuvier, 1797). (2) *Phyllomedusa azurea* Cope, 1862. (“... Color of the upper surfaces of the body and extremities, except that of the brachium, milky purplish blue ...”). Also *Phyllomedusa hypochondrialis azurea* — Mertens, 1926. *Pithecopus hypochondrialis azureus* — B. Lutz, 1966. Today *Pithecopus azureus* (Cope, 1862).

babax: G. *babac* (βᾶβαξ), chatterer, a vain talker. *Hylodes babax* Heyer, 1982. [“... The name *babax* is Greek for chatterer, in allusion both to the insistent diurnal calling of this species (as in many other *Hylodes* species) and to the fact that of the two species of the *H. lateristrigatus* group from Caparaó, this is the only one known to call ...”].

bacurau: P. *bacurau*, common name for several nocturnal birds in tropical Amer-

² Name coined by Sonnerat (1782), referring to a strepsirrhine primate: “... Le nom de Aye-aye que je lui ai conservé est un cri d'exclamation & d'étonnement des habitans de Madagascar; nous ne le connoissons que depuis peu d'années, parce que nous fréquentons peu la côte de l'Ouest, partie de cette île qu'il habite; les habitans de la côte de l'Est m'assurèrent que c'étoit le premier qu'ils avoient vu ...”

ica, including caboré and corujão (Caprimulgidae). *Allobates bacurau* Simões, 2016. [... The specific epithet is in reference to the Portuguese word “bacurau” (modified from the original native Tupi word “wakura’wa”), which designates several species of nighthawks (Family Caprimulgidae). Inhabitants of Manicoré have historically entitled themselves “Povo Bacurau”. (“The Nighthawk People”) ...].

baeobatrachus: G. *baios* (βάιος), little, small + G. *batrachos* (βάτραχος), frog. *Colostethus baeobatrachus* Boistel & De Massary, 1999. [... cette espèce (16 à 17 mm) est plus grande que *C. beebei* ...” (in turn, of 13-15 mm) ...]. Today *Anomaloglossus baeobatrachus* (Boistel & De Massari, 1999).

bagnoi: Bagno + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Marcelo Araújo Bagno (1969-2002), Brazilian ornithologist. *Proceratophrys bagnoi* Brandão et al., 2013.

bahiana: P. Bahia, Brazilian state + L. -ana, pertaining to. *Phyllomedusa bahiana* A. Lutz, 1925 (“... Trouvé à Bahía ...”). Also *Pithecopus burmeisteri bahiana* — B. Lutz, 1966. *Pithecopus bahiana* — Laurent, 1967. *Phyllomedusa burmeisteri bahiana* — Pombal and Haddad, 1992.

Bahius: P. Bahia, Brazilian state. *Bahius* Dubois et al., 2021. (“... This nomen refers to the name “Bahia” of the state of Brazil where these frogs occur ...”).

baileyi: Bailey + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Joseph R. Bailey (1913-1998), US American zoologist. *Hyla goughi baileyi* Cochran, 1953. Also *Hyla baileyi* — Bokermann, 1966. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus wernerii* (Cochran, 1952).

baliomma: G. *balios* (βαλιός), dappled + G. *omma* (ομμα), eye (in various ways, but not in the anatomical sense). *Vitreorana baliomma* Pontes et al., 2014. (“... The name of this new species refers to the distinctive punctuated pattern on the iris, unique among the *Vitreorana* species described from the Atlantic Forest ...”).

bandeirantes: P. *bandeirantes*, participants in a *bandeira* or expedition aimed at exploring mines or apprehending Indians. *Hypsiboas bandeirantes* Cara-

maschi & Cruz, 2013. [“...The specific epithet refers to the “*bandeirantes*”, men that, in the XVI to XVIII centuries, departed from São Paulo to explore the interior of Brazil searching for gold, silver, precious stones, and slaves, increasing the country territory to the current borders...”]. In the synonymy of *Boana polytaenia* (Cope, 1870).

bandeirensis: P. [Pico da] Bandeira, a 2,450 m a.s.l. mountain in the state of Espírito Santo, Brazil + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Cycloramphus bandeirensis* Heyer, 1983. (“... named after the type locality ...”).

barbudensis: Barbuda, a Caribbean island + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Hyla barbudensis* Auffenberg, 1958. (“... Type Locality and Horizon: — Cave I, Two Foot Bay, Barbuda, British Leeward Islands; Late Pleistocene or Recent ...”). In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus johnstonei* Barbour, 1914 (an introduced species in Brazil).

barrioi: Barrio + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Avelino Barrio (1920-1979), Argentinian herpetologist. (1) *Lepidodactylus barrioi* Silva et al., 2020. (2) *Physalaemus barrioi* Bokermann, 1967.

Barycholos: *G. barycholos* (βαρύχολος), savage. *Barycholos* Heyer, 1969. (“... The new genus is named in honor of Dr. Jay M. Savage ...”).

Basanitia: Unclear. *G. basis* (βάσις), lower limb or foot, or *G. basa* (βασά, from βαίνω), walk, step + *G. itis* (ίτης), who walks forward. *Basanitia* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. (“... Dedos e artelhos providos de pelota terminal evidente, dividida, como em *Elosia* ...”). In the synonymy of *Ischnocnema* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862.

bassleri: Bassler + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Harvey Bassler (1883-1950), US American geologist. *Chiasmocleis bassleri* Dunn, 1949. Also *Chiasmocleis bassleri* Dunn, 1949. *Syncope bassleri* — de Sá et al., 2012. *Chiasmocleis (Syncope) bassleri* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

Batrachychthis: *G. batrachos* (βάτραχος), frog + *G. ichthys* (ἰχθύς), fish. *Batrachychthis* Pizarro, 1876. [“... A primeira vista parece ser este animal um gyri-no (têtard) em periodo de evolução anterior ao seu completo desenvolvimento, que depois de experimentar as ultimas metamorphoses próprias á esta classe de animaes deve originar um batrachio de proporções relativamente collossaes ...”]. Also *Batrachichthys* — Boulenger, 1882 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Pseudis* Wagler, 1830.

baturitensis: *P. Baturité* (corr. of *T. ybytyra-etê*, from *ybytyra*, high ground, hill), true mountain, mountain range par excellence + *L. -ensis*, belonging to a place. *Adelophryne baturitensis* Hoogmoed et al., 1994. (“... Named after the type locality, the Maciço de Baturité, an isolated mountain range close to the litoral of Ceará ...”).

baumgardneri: Baumgartner (*sic*) + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hans Baumgartner (?), Venezuelan physician and naturalist. *Hyla baumgardneri* Rivero, 1961. Also *Ololygon baumgardneri* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Originally spelled *baumgardneri* instead of *baumgartneri*, possibly in error. Today *Scinax baumgardneri* (Rivero, 1961).

beckeri: *Becker* + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Johann Becker (1932-2004), Brazilian entomologist. *Hyla beckeri* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2004. Also *Hypsiboas beckeri* — Faivovich, et al., 2005. In the synonymy of *Boana polytaenia* (Cope, 1870).

belloni: *Bellon* + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Bellon (collector of the holotype of the new species). *Scinax belloni* Faivovich et al., 2010. Also *Ololygon belloni* — Duellman et al., 2016.

belzebul: *L. belzebul*, from *H. Baal Zebub* (בּוּבּוּ לְעַב), the prince of demons, Semitic deity. *Proceratophrys belzebul* Dias et al., 2013. (“... makes allusion to horn-like palpebral appendages and the dark color of the specimens ...”).

benitezi: *Benítez* + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jaime Benítez Rexach (1908-2001), Porto-Rican law-

yer. *Boana benitezi* (Rivero, 1961). Also *Hyla benitezi* Rivero, 1961. Today *Hypsiboas benitezi* — Faivovich et al., 2005.

bergi: Berg + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Friedrich Wilhelm Karl Berg (1843-1902), Latvian-Argentinian naturalist. *Bufo bergi* Céspedes, 2000 "1999". Also *Chaunus bergi* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella bergi* (Céspedes, 2000).

berohoka: K. *berohokã*, big river. *Ameerega berohoka* Vaz-Silva & Maciel, 2011. (“... *Ameerega berohoka* occurs in sub-basins related to the Araguaia River. So, the specific name is in recognition of this important Brazilian river ...”).

berthae: Bertha + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Bertha Maria Julia Lutz (1894-1976), Brazilian herpetologist. *Hyla berthae* Barrio, 1962. Also *Ololygon berthae* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax berthae* (Barrio, 1962).

berthalutzae: Bertha Lutz + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Bertha Maria Julia Lutz (1894-1976), Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Dendrophryniscus berthalutzae* Izecksohn, 1994. (2) *Hyla berthalutzae* Bokermann, 1962. Today *Dendropsophus berthalutzae* (Bokermann, 1962).

biancae: Bianca + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Bianca Luiza Reinert, Brazilian ornithologist. *Melanophryniscus biancae* Bornschein et al., 2015.

bibroni: Bibron + L. *-i*, suffix that indicates the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Gabriel Bibron (1805-1848), French herpetologist. *Pleurodema bibroni* Tschudi, 1838. Also *Paludicola bibronii* — Boulenger, 1882.

bicegoi: Bicego + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Beniamino Bicego (1849-?), technician in the Museu Paulista under Ihering’s direction. *Chiasmocleis bicegoi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) bicegoi* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

bicolor: L. *bicolor*, of two colors. (1) *Oxyrhynchus bicolor* Guérin-Méneville, 1838. (?). Also *Oxyrhincus bicolor* — Duméril & Bibron, 1841 (incorrect subsequent spelling of the generic name). *Engystoma ovale* var. *bicolor* — Boulenger, 1885. *Elachistocleis ovale bicolor* — Parker, 1927. *Elachistocleis ovalis bicolor* — Müller & Hellmich, 1936. *Engystoma bicolor* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Elachistocleis bicolor* (Valenciennes in Guérin-Ménéville, 1838). (2) *Rana bicolor* Boddaert, 1772. (“... *Rana pedibus fissis, palmis tetradactylis, plantis pentadactylis omnibus orbiculato dilatatis, superne cyanea, inferne fulva. Adjecto nomine breviari bicoloris ...*”). Also *Calamita bicolor* — Schneider, 1799. *Hyla bicolor* — Daudin, 1800. *Rana (Phyllomedusa) bicolor* — Guérin-Méneville, 1838. *Phyllomedusa (Phyllomedusa) bicolor* — B. Lutz, 1950. Today *Phyllomedusa bicolor* (Boddaert, 1772).

bifurca, bifurcus: L. *bifurca*, -us, two-forked, two pronged, bifurcated. *Hyla (Hylella) bifurca* Andersson, 1945. [“... Upper surface of forehead to a curved line between the front corners of the orbits bright white (in life possibly red). This white area is prolonged backwards by two very distinct white (red?) streaks, running along the outer margins of the upper eyelids above tympanum and shoulders on the sides of back to sacrum, where they end ...”]. Today *Dendropsophus bifurcus* (Andersson, 1945).

bigibbosa: L. *bi*, two + L. *gibba*, bulge, protuberance. *Ceratophrys bigibbosa* Peters, 1872. (“... sondern ist eine eigenthümliche Art mit Augenschildern fast wie *A. turpicola*, welche ich wegen der grossen runden Höcker hinter den Augen *C. bigibbosa* benenne ...”). Today *Proceratophrys bigibbosa* (Peters, 1872).

biligonigerus: L. *bilis*, anger, ill temper, madness + G. *goao* (γοάω), wailing, moaning. *Liuperus biligonigerus* Cope, 1861 “1860”. (?). Also *Pleurodema biligonigera* — Cope, 1862. *Gomphobates biligonigerus* — Cope, 1870 “1869”. *Paludicola (Gomphobates) biligonigerus* — Peters, 1873. *Paludicola biligonigera* — Boulenger, 1882. Today *Physalaemus biligonigerus* (Cope, 1861).

bilineata, bilineatus: L. *bi*, two + L. *lineatus*, lined. (1) *Eleutherodactylus bilineatus* Bokermann, 1975 “1974”. (“... Dorso negro, apresentando de cada lado, uma faixa longitudinal esbranquiçada ...”). Also *Ischnocnema bilin-*

eata — Heinicke et al., 2007. *Heyerus bilineatus* — Motta et al., 2021. Today *Bahius bilineatus* (Bokermann, 1975). (2) *Rana pachypus bilineata* Mayer, 1835. (“... Die Rückenstreifen fehlen und es sind nur zwei seitliche Streifen zugegen. Ich habe ihn daher mit dem Namen *Rana Pachypus bilineata* benannt ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768).

bilinguis: L. *bilinguis*, two-tongued, speaking two languages. *Amazophrynella bilinguis* Kaefer et al., 2019. (“... The epithet “bilinguis” is Latin and means “bilingual”. It refers to the two distinct advertisement calls emitted by the male individuals ...”).

bilobatus: L. *bi-*, two + L. *lobus*, a rounded projection or protuberance, lobe + L. *-atus*, having the nature of. *Dendropsophus bilobatus* Ferrão et al., 2020. (“... The name refers to the characteristic bilobate shape of the vocal sac of males of the new species ...”).

bimaculatus: L. *bi*, two + L. *maculatus*, spotted. *Bufo bimaculatus* Wied-Neuwied, 1821 (*nomen oblitum*). [“... fand ich hier eine Menge grosser, breiter Kröten, ... unter denen ich eine wahrscheinlich noch unbeschriebene Art (*Bufo bimaculatus*) mit zwey grossen dunkeln Feldern auf dem Rücken, bemerkte ...”]. In the synonymy of *Rhinella icterica* (Spix, 1824).

binotata*, *binotatus: L. *bi*, two + L. *notata*, *-us*, marked, signed. *Rana binotata* Spix, 1824. (“... *maculis in medio dorso geminis, ocellatis, nigris* ...”). Also *Hylodes binotatus* — Peters, 1872. *Eleutherodactylus binotatus* — Stejneger, 1904. *Eleutherodactylus cinotatus* — Luederwaldt, 1929 (typographic error). Today *Haddadus binotatus* (Spix, 1824).

biobeba: T. *biobeba*, corr. *mbi-opeba*, flat foot or spread foot, name given by the Guaraníes of Paraguay to the Tupi people of São Paulo³. *Hyla biobeba* Bokermann & Sazima, 1973. (“... O nome *biobeba* é de origem indígena, e significa mão grande ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana lundii* (Burmeister, 1856).

3 Alfredo de Taunay, 1925. História Geral das Bandeiras Paulistas. Typ. Ideal - Heitor L. Canton. São Paulo. T. 2, p. 67.

biolat: E. BIOLAT, acronym for the Biological Diversity in Tropical Latin America project. *Dendrobates biolat* Morales, 1992. [“... El nombre *biolat* honra la labor desempeñada por el programa de Diversidad Biologica para America Latina (BIOLAT) del Smithsonian Institution de Washington D. C., U. S. A. Este programa realiza investigaciones cientificas en los Parques Nacionales de Sudamerica y brinda apoyo a los investigadores nacionales ...”]. Also *Ranitomeya biolat* — Grant et al., 2006. In the synonymy of *Ranitomeya sirensis* (Aichinger, 1991).

bipunctata, bipunctatus: L. *bi-*, two + L. *punctata*, -us, punctuated; pointed. *Hyla bipunctata* Spix, 1824. (“... dorso medio nigro-bipunctato ...”). Also *Scinax bipunctatus* — Wagler, 1830. *Scinax bipunctata* — Peters, 1872. *Hyla bipunctata bipunctata* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. Today *Dendropsophus bipunctatus* (Spix, 1824).

bischoffi: Bischoff + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Theodor Bischoff (1807-1882), Brazilian schoolmaster and amateur naturalist, active in Rio Grande do Sul. (1) *Hyla bischoffi* Boulenger, 1887. Also *Hyla bischoffi bischoffi* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. *Hypsiboas bischoffi* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana bischoffi* (Boulenger, 1887). (2) *Paludicola bischoffi* Boulenger, 1887. Also *Physalaemus bischoffi* — Parker, 1927. In the synonymy of *Physalaemus cuvieri* Fitzinger, 1826.

bivittata, bivittatum: L. *bi*, two + L. *vittata*, wearing or carrying a ritual vitta. (1) *Hyla bivittata* Boulenger, 1888. (“... Greyish above, with two parallel darker bands along the back, more distinct in the young than in the adult ...”). Also *Hyla minuta bivittata* — Barrio, 1967. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus minutus* (Peters, 1872). (2) *Caecilia bivittata* Guérin-Méneville, 1838. (?). Also *Coecilia bivittatum* Cuvier, 1829. Today *Rhinatrema bivittatum* (Guérin-Méneville, 1838).

blombergi: Blomberg + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Rolf Blomberg (1912-1996), Swedish explorer and photographer active in Ecuador. *Phyllomedusa blombergi* Funkhouser, 1957. In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa vaillantii* Boulenger, 1882.

Boana: *G. boama* (βοαμα), scream, howl. *Boana* Gray, 1825. (?).

boans: *G. boao* (βοάω), make a noise, cry out, shout. (1) *Rana boans* Linnaeus, 1758. (?). Also *Calamita boans* — Schneider, 1799. *Hyla boans* — Daudin, 1800. *Hypsiboas boans* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana boans* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Hyla boans* Latreille in Sonnini de Manoncourt & Latreille, 1801 “An. X”. (“...La raine beuglante...”). Also *Auletris boans* — Wagler, 1830. *Hypsiboas boans* — Tschudi, 1838. *Hyla (Hyla) boans* — Burmeister, 1856. In the synonymy of *Boana albopunctata* (Spix, 1824).

bocaina, bocainensis: [Serra da] Bocaina, mountain range in the states of Rio de Janeiro and São Paulo (from *P. bocaina*, deep valley between two nearby foothills; narrow passage between two hills; if T., from *mbo-caia*, fire made for the preparation of gardens) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Ischnocnema bocaina* Taucce et al., 2019. [“... The specific epithet refers to the Bocaina Mountain Range (Serra da Bocaina, in Portuguese), where the type locality of the species is located, in recognition of the great biodiversity importance of this mountain range ...]. (2) *Megaelosia bocainensis* Giaretta et al., 1993. (“... As the holotype of the new species was collected at the Serra da Bocaina, we propose the name *Megaelosia bocainensis* sp. nov. ...”). Also *Hylodes bocainensis* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Phantasmarana bocainensis* (Giaretta et al., 1993). (3) *Hyla catharinae bocainensis* B. Lutz, 1968. (“... This form was first seen by A. Lutz in 1925 at his brother’s Fazenda do Bonito in the Serra da Bocaina, at approximately 1,100 meters altitude ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax ariadne* (Bokermann, 1967).

boesemani: Boeseman + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Marinus Boeseman (1916-2006), Dutch ichthyologist. *Hyla boesemani* Goin, 1966. Also *Ololygon boesemani* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax boesemani* (Goin, 1966).

boiei: Boie + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Friedrich Boie (1789-1870) or his brother Heinrich Boie (1794-1827), German naturalists. (1) *Phyllomedusa boiei* Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa bicolor* (Boddaert, 1772). (2) *Ceratophrys boiei* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. Also *Stombus bojei* — Gravenhorst, 1829. *Ceratophrys bojei* — Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. *Ceratophrys*

dorsata boiei — Gadow, 1901. *Stombus boiei* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. Today *Proceratophrys boiei* (Wied-Neuwied, 1824).

bokermanni: Bokermann + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Werner Carlos Augusto Bokermann (1929-1995), Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Leptodactylus bokermanni* Heyer, 1973. Also *Leptodactylus (Lithodytes) bokermanni* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Adenomera bokermanni* (Heyer, 1973). (2) *Dendrophryniscus bokermanni* Izecksohn, 1994 “1993”. Also *Amazonella bokermanni* — Fouquet et al., 2012. Today *Amazophrynella bokermanni* (Izecksohn, 1994). (3) *Cochranella bokermanni* Taylor & Cochran, 1953. Also *Centrolenella bokermanni* — Duellman, 1977. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana eurygnatha* (A. Lutz, 1925). (4) *Crossodactylodes bokermanni* Peixoto, 1983. (5) *Crossodactylus bokermanni* Caramaschi and Sazima, 1985. In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus trachystomus* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862). (6) *Hyla bokermanni* Goin, 1960. Today *Dendropsophus bokermanni* (Goin, 1960). (7) *Aparasphenodon bokermanni* Pombal, 1993. Today *Nyctimantis bokermanni* (Pombal, 1993). (8) *Phrynomedusa bokermanni* Cruz, 1991. (9) *Physalaemus bokermanni* Cardoso & Haddad, 1985.

Bokermannohyla: Bokermann (see *bokermanni*) + connecting o + L. *Hyla* (see), noun widely used in relation to tree-frogs. *Bokermannohyla* Faivovich et al., 2005. (“... This genus is honouring Werner Carlos Augusto Bokermann (1929-1995), as homage to his contribution to the knowledge of Brazilian anurans ...”).

bolbodactyla, bolbodactylus: G. *bolbos* (βολβός), a swelling, bulb + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. (1) *Eupemphix bolbodactyla* A. Lutz, 1925. *Ischnocnema bolbodactyla* (A. Lutz, 1925). (“... Les doigts & les orteils présentent une dilatation terminale ...”). Also *Basanitia bolbodactyla* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. *Eleutherodactylus bolbodactylus* — Lynch, 1968. Today *Eupemphix bolbodactyla* A. Lutz, 1925. (2) *Pseudis bolbodactyla* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... doigts & orteils à pointes renflées ...”). Also *Pseudis paradoxus bolbodactylus* — Gallardo, 1961. *Pseudis paradoxa bolbodactyla* — Bokermann, 1966.

Bolitoglossa, bolitoglossus: *G. bolitis* (βωλίτης), mushroom + *G. glossa* (γλῶσσα), tongue. (1) *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854. (“... Langue formant un disque arrondi, libre dans son pourtour, supportée en dessous & au centre par un pédicule grêle, musculoux & protractile, simulant ainsi une sorte de champignon ...”). (2) *Borborocoetes bolitoglossus* Werner, 1897. [“... Diese merkwürdige Art ist durch die auffallende Form der Zunge ausgezeichnet, welche rundherum frei ist und im ausgestreckten Zustande einen niedrigen Cylinder vorstellt, dessen obere Fläche eine dünne Scheibe von wenig größerem Durchmesser bildet, welche einen sehr schmalen hornigen Rand und vier, zusammen einen Rhombus bildende Furchen (nebst einer weiteren, einer Seite parallelen Furche in der Mitte) besitzt ...”]. Also *Craspedoglossa bolitoglossa* — A. Lutz, 1929. *Eupsophus bolitoglossus* — Gorham, 1966. *Zachaenus bolitoglossus* — Harding, 1983 (unexplained combination). Today *Cycloramphus bolitoglossus* (Werner, 1897).

boliviana, bolivianus: S. Bolivia, from [Simón] Bolívar (1783-1830), Venezuelan military and political leader⁴ + L. *-ana, -anus*, pertaining to. (1) *Chiasmocleis boliviana* Parker, 1927. (“... in the British Museum from Buena Vista, Santa Cruz, Bolivia ...”). Today *Hamptophryne boliviana* (Parker, 1927). (2) *Leptodactylus bolivianus* Boulenger, 1898. (“... The large collection formed by the late Prof. Balzan for the Genoa Civic Museum, which adds much to our knowledge of the herpetological fauna of Bolivia ...”). Also *Leptodactylus (Pachypus) bolivianus* — A. Lutz, 1930. (3) *Lysapsus bolivianus* Gallardo, 1961. (“... The specimens studied come from the NW of Bolivia, Beni Department, Amazonian drainage through the Beni River and the Madeira ...”). Also *Lysapsus limellus bolivianus* Gallardo, 1961. *Pseudis boliviana* — Aguiar et al., 2007. (4) *Phyllomedusa boliviana* Boulenger, 1902. (“... Two specimens, male and female, from Chulumani, Bolivia, 2000 metres ...”). Also *Phyllomedusa (Pithecopus) boliviana* — B. Lutz, 1950. *Pithecopus boliviana* — B. Lutz, 1966. (5) *Pseudopaludicola boliviana* Parker, 1927. (“... in the British Museum, from Sta. Cruz, Bolivia ...”).

4 On October 3, 1825, Manuel Martín Cruz, from Potosí, proposed to the General Assembly of Deputies of the Provinces of the Alto Perú: “... si de Rómulo viene Roma, de Bolívar Bolivia ...”, thereby establishing the name of the country (today Estado Plurinacional de Bolivia).

bonairensis: *S. bonaerense*, demonym of the inhabitants of the Buenos Aires province in Argentina. *Leptodactylus ocellatus* var. *bonairensis* Cei, 1949. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus luctator* (Hudson, 1892).

boraceienseis: P. Boracéia (from T. *boracea*, corr. of *poracé*, feast, revelry, wild dance) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Cycloramphus boraceienseis* Heyer, 1983. (“... Named for the University of São Paulo field station, where I was first introduced to the Atlantic Forest fauna and have since spent many enjoyable weeks learning about the environment ...”).

Boreorana: G. *Boreas* (Βορέας), Greek god of the north wind + L. *rana*, frog. *Boreorana* Dubois et al., 2021. Alludes to the range of its type species, *Rana sylvatica* LeConte, 1825. In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

boticariana, boticario: P. [Fundação Grupo] Boticário [de Proteção à Natureza] + L. *-ana*, pertaining to. (1) *Brachycephalus boticario* Pie et al., 2015. (“... The specific epithet is a homage to the Fundação Grupo Boticário de Proteção à Natureza, which not only partially funded the fieldwork of this study, but also is a major contributor to conservation research in Brazil ...”). (2) *Megaelosia boticariana* Giaretta & Aguiar, 1998. (“... The specific epithetum honours the Fundação Boticário de Proteção à Natureza, that supports projects in nature conservation in Brazil, including the herpetological studies in the type locality of the new species ...”). Also *Hylodes boticarianus* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Phantasmarana boticariana* (Giaretta & Aguiar, 1998).

botocudo: P. *botocudo*, those who use *botoque*, a disk or plug worn in their lower lip and ears. *Sphaenorhynchus botocudo* Caramaschi et al., 2009. (“... The “botocudos” were great warriors and were never dominated by the Portuguese invaders ...”).

botoque: P. *botoque*, ornamental knob made of a circular piece, usually of wood, inserted in the ears, nostrils or lower lip; from P. *batoque*, plug with which the hole of the barrels and casks is sealed. *Corythomantis botoque* Marques et al., 2021. (“...The specific epithet botoque refers to the Aimore native ethnic group that inhabited the states of Bahía, Minas Gerais, and

Espírito Santo. Botoque is a wooden round disc they used as an ornament to enlarge their ears and lips and resembles the prominent rostrum of the species.... ”).

botumirim: P. [Veredas de] Botumirim, locality at 17°07'S, 43°02'W (659 m altitude), Municipality of Botumirim. State of Minas Gerais. Brazil (from T. *botu*, corr. *mbitú*, breath, evaporation, inner heat + T. *mirim*, little, small). *Hypsiboas botumirim* Caramaschi et al., 2009. (“... The specific epithet is a noun in apposition and refers to the type locality of the new species ...). Today *Boana botumirim* (Caramaschi et al., 2009).

boulengeri: Boulenger + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring George Albert Boulenger (1858-1937), Belgian-British herpetologist. (1) *Cyclorhamphus boulengeri* A. Lutz, 1929. In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus asper* Werner, 1899. (2) *Calamobates Boulengeri* De Witte, 1930. Today *Crossodactylus boulengeri* (De Witte, 1930). (3) *Hemiphractus boulengeri* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Hemiphractus scutatus* (Spix, 1824). (4) *Rhinella boulengeri* Chaparro et al., 2007. In the synonymy of *Dendrophryniscus proboscideus* (Boulenger, 1882).

braccata, braccatus: L. *bracata*, *-us*, who wears pants. *Dendrobates braccatus* Steindachner, 1864. (“... An dem kleinsten nur 15” langen Individuum des kais. Museums fließen die beiden Schenkelflecken in einen einzigen zusammen ...”). Also *Dendrobates pictus braccatus* — B. Lutz, 1952. *Epipedobates braccatus* — Martins & Sazima, 1989. Today *Ameerega braccata* (Steindachner, 1864).

Brachycephalus: G. *brachys* (βραχύς), short + G. *kéfali* (κεφάλη), head. *Brachycephalus* Fitzinger, 1826. (“... *Rictus angustus* ...”). The same root in *Brachycephalidae* Günther, 1858.

brachyops: G. *brachys* (βραχύς), short + G. *ops* (οψ), eye. *Lystris brachyops* Cope, 1869 “1868”. (“... diameter of bony orbit equal length of muzzle ...”). Also *Paludicola brachyops* — Boulenger, 1882. Today *Pleurodema brachyops* (Cope, 1869).

brachypodius: G. *brachys* (βραχὺς), short + G. *podos* (ποδος), foot. *Eleutherodactylus brachypodius* Rivero, 1961. (“... very short hind limbs, the heel of which does not reach the nostril ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis vilarsi* (Melin, 1941).

bracteator: L. *bracteator*, gold-beater, worker in gold-leaf. *Hyla bracteator* Hensel, 1867. (“... besitzen eine metallische Stimme, welche genau dem Tone gleicht, der durch Schlagen mit einem Hammer auf Blech hervorgebracht wird, daher sie auch von den Colonisten als Blechschmiede bezeichnet werden ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana pulchella* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

bradei: Brade + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alexandre Curt Brade (1881-1971), German architect and botanist. *Holoaden bradei* B. Lutz, 1958.

Bradymedusa: G. *bradys* (βραδύς), slow + G. *medusa*, apocope of *Phyllomedusa* (see). *Bradymedusa* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... Forma próxima de *Phyllomedusa* ...”). In the synonymy of *Pithecopus* Cope, 1866.

braestrupi: Bræstrup + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Frits Wimpffen Bræstrup (1906-1999), Danish zoologist. *Chthonerpeton braestrupi* Taylor, 1968.

branneri: Branner + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring John Casper Branner (1850-1922), US American geologist. *Hyla bipunctata branneri* Cochran, 1948. Also *Hyla branneri* — Borkermann, 1966. *Hyla decipiens branneri* — B. Lutz, 1973. Today *Dendropsophus branneri* (Cochran, 1948).

branti: Brant + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Sérgio Brant Rocha, Brazilian Engineer Agronomist. *Procera-tophrys branti* Brandão et al., 2013.

brasiliensis: P. Brasil, South American country; from P. *pau de brasa* or *pau brasil*⁵ + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Telmatobius brasiliensis* Stein-

5 *Paubrasilia echinata* (Lam.) E. Gagnon, H.C. Lima & G.P. Lewis, wood from which a red dye is obtained, similar to the color of coal embers.

dachner, 1864. [“... Fundort: Brasilien (wahrscheinlich die Umgebung von Rio Janeiro) ...”]. Also *Cycloramphus brasiliensis* — Barbour & Noble, 1920. *Iliodiscus brasiliensis* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. *Grypiscus brasiliensis* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1935. Today *Cycloramphus brasiliensis* (Steindachner, 1864). (2) *Sminthillus brasiliensis* Parker, 1926. (“... from the Organ Mountains, Brazil ...”). Also *Noblella brasiliensis* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. Today *Euparkerella brasiliensis* (Parker, 1926). (3) *Siphonops brasiliensis* Lütken, 1851. (“... Det beskrevne Exemplar hidrører fra Brasilien og er sendt til Europa af Dr. Langgaard. / Da denne nye Art synes i det sydlige Brasilien at repræsentere den samme Grundform indenfor Slægten *Siphonops* som *S. mexicanus* i Central-Amerika, er Artsnavnet valgt i Overeensstemmelse dermed ...”). Also *Dermophis brasiliensis* — Peters, 1880 “1879”. Today *Luetkenotyphlus brasiliensis* (Lütken, 1852). (4) *Pseudis brasiliensis* Peters, 1863. (“... drei Exemplaren ... aus Brasilien ...”). In the synonymy of *Pseudis minuta* Günther, 1858. (5) *Phyllobates brasiliensis* De Witte, 1930. [“... Deux exemplaires males, provenant de Cachoeiras (Etat de Rio de Janeiro) ...”]. In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus gaudichaudii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

Brasilotyphlus: P. Brasil, South American country; from P. *pau de brasa* or *pau brasil* + G. *tyflos* (τυφλος), blind. *Brasilotyphlus* Taylor, 1968. (“... Type of genus: *Gymnophis braziliensis* Dunn ...”).

brauni: Braun + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Pedro Canisio Braun (1938-1992), Brazilian herpetologist. *Proceratophrys brauni* Kwet & Faivovich, 2001.

braziliensis: Brasil + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place (see *brasiliensis*). *Gymnopsis braziliensis* Dunn, 1945. (“... Four caecilians from Brazil, recently sent me for identification by Mr. C. M. Bogert, represent an undescribed species of the genus *Gymnopsis* and add that genus to the fauna of Brazil ...”). Today *Brasilotyphlus braziliensis* (Dunn, 1945).

bressloui: Bresslau + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ernst Bresslau (1877-1935), German zoologist. (1) *Crossodactylus bressloui* Müller, 1924. In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus trachystomus* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862). (2) *Paludicola bressloui* Müller,

1924. Also *Physalaemus bresslaui* — Parker, 1927. In the synonymy of *Physalaemus signifer* (Girard, 1853).

brevifrons: L. *brevis*, short, little, small, stunted + L. *frons*, fore part of anything. *Hyla brevifrons* Duellman & Crump, 1974. (“... The name is used in allusion to the short head of the species ...”). Today *Dendropsophus brevifrons* (Duellman & Crump, 1974).

brevipalmata: L. *brevis*, short, little, small, stunted + L. *palmata*, webbed. *Ranula brevipalmata* Cope, 1874. (“... with the web of the posterior digits only reaching the bases of the ultimate, or in the fourth toe, the penultimate phalange ...”). Also *Hylarana brevipalmata* — Brocchi, 1877. *Rana brevipalmata* — Fowler, 1913. In the synonymy of *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824).

brevipes: L. *brevis*, short, little, small, stunted + L. *pes*, foot. (1) *Leptodactylus brevipes* Cope, 1887. (“... Form rather stout, legs short ...”). (2) *Pleurodema bibroni* var. *brevipes* Philippi in Cei, 1958 (*nomen nudum*). (?). Also *Pleurodema brevipes* — Cei, 1958. In the synonymy of *Pleurodema bibroni* Tschudi, 1838.

brevipollicatus: L. *brevis*, short, little, small + L. *pollex, pollicis*, thumb + L. *-atus*, suffix indicating quality of. *Dendrophryniscus brevipollicatus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. (“... pollice brevissimo, ejus disco adherente parvo, rotundo ...”).

brevirostris: L. *brevis*, short, little, small + L. *rostris*, beak, snout. *Phyllodytes brevirostris* Peixoto & Cruz, 1988. (“... focinho curto e arredondado nas vistas dorsal e lateral ...”).

brieni: Brien + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paul Brien (1894-1975), Belgian zoologist. (1) *Hylodes ? Brieni* De Witte, 1930. In the synonymy of *Thoropa miliaris* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Hyla Brieni* De Witte, 1930. Also *Hyla strigilata brieni* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. *Hyla catharinae brieni* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Ololygon catharinae brieni* — Heyer, 1980. *Hyla brieni* — Haddad & Pombal, 1987. *Ololygon brieni* — Peixoto & Weygoldt, 1987 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Ololygon brieni* — Heyer et al., 1990. Today *Scinax brieni* (De Witte, 1930).

britti: Britto + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Father L. de Britto (?), director of the Salesian Mission at S. Gabriel (Rio Negro) [currently São Gabriel da Cachoeira, state of Amazonas, Brazil, in the Rio Negro basin]. *Hyla leprieurii britti* Melin, 1941. Also *Osteocephalus britti* — Goin, 1961. In the synonymy of *Osteocephalus leprieurii* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

bromeliaceus: L. *bromelia*, in this context, a colloquial name for diverse plants of the family Bromeliaceae (not the Linnaean genus) + L. *-aceus*, suffix signifying belonging to, pertaining to. *Dendropsophus bromeliaceus* Ferreira et al., 2015. (“... refers to the reproductive habit of the new species, which deposits eggs in bromeliads and spends the larval phase in the rainwater accumulated in these plants ...”).

bromelicola: L. *bromelia*, in this context, a colloquial name for diverse plants of the family Bromeliaceae (not the Linnaean genus) + L. *-cola*, dwelling in, inhabiting, living among. *Sphaenorhynchus bromelicola* Bokermann, 1966. (“... A maioria dos exemplares foi obtida em bromélias terrestres juntamente com numerosos jovens não incluídos na série de parátipos ...”).

brunneus: L. *brunneus*, brown. (1) *Prostherapis brunneus* Cope, 1887. (“... Color of superior and lateral surfaces brown ...”). Also *Phyllobates brunneus* — Barbour & Noble, 1920, *Colostethus brunneus* — Edwards, 1971. Today *Allobates brunneus* (Cope, 1887). (2) *Brachycephalus brunneus* Ribeiro et al., 2005. (“... The name is used in allusion to its general brown colour ...”).

brunoi: Bruno + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Bruno Álvares da Silva Lobo (1884-1945), Brazilian zoologist. *Aparasphenodon brunoi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. Also *Corythomantis brunoi* — Mertens, 1926. *Corthomantis (Aparasphenodon) brunoi* — B. Lutz, 1954. Today *Nyctimantis brunoi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

bryomantis: *G. bryos* (βρύον), seaweed, moss + *G. mantis* (μάντης), tree-frog⁶. *Thoropa bryomantis* Assis et al., 2021. [“... The epithet *bryomantis* is Greek for moss frog (*bryos* = moss; *mantis* = anuran/frog), in reference to the substrate it occupies and by which it is camouflaged (rocks covered by moss) ...”].

Bubonias: *G. boubon* (βουβών), groin. *Bubonias* Cope, 1874. (“... A large gland in the inguinal region ...”). In the synonymy of *Edalorhina* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

buccinator: *L. buccinator*, trumpeter; proclaimer. *Eleutherodactylus buccinator* Rodríguez, 1994. (“... The name is given to the new species in allusion to the similarity of its call to the sound produced by a honk ...”). Today *Pristimantis buccinator* (Rodríguez, 1994).

buckleyi: Buckley + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Clarence Buckley (?), British collector active in Ecuador, Bolivia, and possibly Colombia. (1) *Hyla buckleyi* Boulenger, 1882. Today *Osteocephalus buckleyi* (Boulenger, 1882). (2) *Edalorhina buckleyi* Boulenger, 1882. Also *Pleurodema buckleyi* — Nieden, 1923. In the synonymy of *Edalorhina perezi* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

bufo: *L. bufo*, toad. *Leptodactylus bufo* Andersson, 1911. (“... Habit very stout ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus labyrinthicus* (Spix, 1824). Same root in Bufonidae.

bufoides: *L. bufo*, toad + *L. -oides*, suffix indicating likeness. In the index that follows p. 380, Meuschen (1781) identifies as “*Bufoides*” the animal described under number 67 (p. 15) as *Rana corpore angustato laevi; palmis fissis; plantis semipalmatis: unguibus orbiculato-dilatatis*. *Hyla bufoides* Meuschen, 1781 (invalid name). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus leucophyllatus* (Beireis, 1783).

6 The concept of *mantis* (μάντης) as tree frog, in the sense of a weather forecaster, is due to Theocritus X: 18, according to the interpretation of the Lexicon of Hesichius of Alexandria. (“μάντης ὁ ἐν τοῖς χυποῖς βάρραχος”; i.a., Hesichius, 1867: 1012). [Hesichius. 1867. Hesychii Alexandrini Lexicon. Αἰλίου Διογενείου Περὶ Ἑργολογίας. Editionem minorem curavit Mauricius Schmidt. Editio altera, indice glossarum ethnicarum aucta. Jenae. Sumptibus Hermanni Dufftii (Libraria Maukiana). vi + 1612 cols.

bufonia, bufonium, bufonius: L. *bufo*, toad + L. *-ia, -ium, -ius*, quality of. (?).

(1) *Eleutherodactylus bufonius* Andersson, 1945. (“... Habit stout, *Bufo*-like ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis diadematus* (Jiménez de la Espada, 1875). (2) *Elosia bufonium* Girard, 1853. (The name is, perhaps, an oxymoron, since the original description says “... Skin quite smooth, without any pustules at all ...”). *Elosia bufonia* — Boulenger, 1882. *Megaelosia bufonia* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. *Hylodes (Megaelosia) bufonia* — Noble, 1927. In the synonymy of *Hylodes nasus* (Lichtenstein, 1823). (3) *Hyla bufonia* Spix, 1824. (“... *Grandis, nigro vel chalybeo-fusca, subtus fulva, granulosa* ...”). *Hypsiboas bufonia* — Wagler, 1830. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758). (4) *Leptodactylus bufonius* Boulenger, 1894 (?). (5) *Rana bufonia* Merrem, 1820 (substitute name for *Bufo surinamensis* Daudin, 1802). (?). In the synonymy of *Elachistocleis surinamensis* (Daudin, 1802).

bufonoides: L. *Bufo*, genus of anurans due to Guersault (1764) (in turn, from L. *bufo*, toad) + G. *-oeides* (-οειδής), similar to. *Brachycephalus bufonoides* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... não tem os escudos dorsaes, sendo todo o corpo coberto sómente de verrugas prózas da pelle. A esta ultima variedade será reservado o nome de *bufonoides* ...”). Also *Brachycephalus ephippium* var. *bufonoides* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920.

bumbameuboi: P. *bumba-meu-boi*, hit my ox, a social criticism in the form of a popular celebration. *Elachistocleis bumbameuboi* Caramaschi, 2010. (“... The name of the species, a noun in apposition, is allusive to the most popular feasts occurring in June at São Luís, Maranhão ...”). Also *Engystoma bumbameuboi* — Dubois et al., 2021.

buriti: P. [Município de] Buritis (15°37’S, 46°25’W), Minas Gerais, Brasil (from T. *mburi’ti*, vernacular name of several arecaceous palms, of the genera *Astrocaryum*, *Mauritia*, *Mauritiella*, and *Trithrinax*). *Hyla buriti* Caramaschi & Cruz, 1999. (“... O nome da espécie ... faz alusão à localidade tipo e, por extensão, à “palmeira-buriti”, *Mauritia vinifera*, típica das veredas do Brasil Central ...”). Also *Hypsiboas buriti* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana buriti* (Caramaschi & Cruz, 1999).

burmeisteri: Burmeister + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Karl Hermann Konrad Burmeister (1807-1892), German-Argentinian naturalist. (1) *Hyla burmeisteri* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861” (replacement name for *Hyla marmorata* Burmeister, 1856; *nomen oblitum*). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus seniculus* (Cope, 1868). (2) *Phyllomedusa burmeisteri* Boulenger, 1882. Also *Phyllomedusa (Pithecopus) burmeisteri* — B. Lutz, 1950. *Pithecopus burmeisteri burmeisteri* — B. Lutz, 1966.

butantan: P. Butantan, from T. *butantã*, corr. *yby-tantã*, hard, firm ground. *Microcaecilia butantan* Wilkinson et al., 2015. (“... The specific epithet is in honour of the Instituto Butantan, which enabled the discovery of the species through the Butantan na Amazônia (Butantan in Amazon) project ...”).

caatingae: P. *caatinga*, Northeastern Brazilian forest, where the vegetation has little foliage and is almost exclusively composed of hawthorns, cacti, and bromelids; from T. *caa*, vegetation, forest + T. *tinga*, white, clear + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating belonging to. *Leptodactylus caatingae* Heyer & Juncá, 2003. (“... The name, Latinized from the Portuguese word *caatinga*, refers to the characteristic distribution of this species within the Caatinga Morphoclimatic Domain ...”).

cabralensis: [Serra do] Cabral, mountain range in Minas Gerais + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Scinax cabralensis* Drummond et al., 2007. (“... The specific name of the new species refers to the Serra do Cabral, complex of mountains where the species was found ...”).

cabrerai: Cabrera + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Isadore Cabrera (*sic*); actually, Isidoro Cabrera-Rodríguez (1922-?), Colombian botanist. *Hyla cabrerai* Cochran & Goin, 1970. Today *Osteocephalus cabrerai* (Cochran & Goin, 1970).

cachimbo: P. Cachimbo, place at about 09°21'S, 54°57'W, Pará, Brazil, between 200 and 400 m; in turn, vernacular name of *Couratari guianensis* (Lecythidaceae). *Hyla cachimbo* Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999. (“... The specific name, a noun in apposition, refers to the type-locality, Cachimbo ...”). Today *Dendropsophus cachimbo* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999).

Caecilia, Coecilia: *L. caecilia*, blind-worm, in turn from *L. caecus*, blind. *Caecilia* Linnaeus, 1758. (?). Also *Coecilia* — Latreille in Sonnini de Manoncourt and Latreille, 1802 “An. X”. The generic name *Coecilia* is due to Linnaeus (1758), not an incorrect subsequent spelling of Latreille (An X), as mentioned by Frost (2021). In fact, Linnaeus used two alternative original spellings for the limbless amphibians included in SN 10, *Coecilia* on page 196 (corrected to *Caecilia* in the *Emendanda* after p. 823), and *Caecilia* on page 229. The following year (Linnaeus, 1759: 70; 81), consistently employed the spelling *Caecilia*, but again in SN 12 (Linnaeus, 1766), used both. The spelling *Caecilia* took precedence by the action of Linnaeus (1759) (art. 24. 2. 2, ICZN, 1999) although this work is not consistently binominal (see art. 12. 2. 1 for the criteria of availability). Same root in *Caeciliidae* Rafinesque, 1814.

Caecilita: *L. Caecilia*, genus of gymnophiones due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see) *L. -ita*, suffix diminutive. *Caecilita* Wake & Donnelly, 2010 (“... The generic epithet refers to the small size of the new caeciliid taxon ...”). In the synonymy of *Microcaecilia* Taylor, 1968.

caeruleodactylus: *L. caeruleus*, blue, cerulean, dark; greenish-blue, azure + *G. dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Colostethus caeruleodactylus* Lima & Caldwell, 2001. (“... The name is in allusion to the sky blue digits of the male frog during the breeding season ...”). Today *Allobates caeruleodactylus* (Lima & Caldwell, 2001).

caete: *P. caetê*, virgin forest, from *T. caá-etê*. true, virgin, or primitive forest. (1) *Hylodes caete* Malagoli et al., 2017. (“... Here, *caete* refers to the high preserved forests that harbor the fast streams with clear water in which the new species is known to breed ...”). (2) *Physalaemus caete* Pombal & Madureira, 1997. (“... The specific name is an allusion for the forest habitat, ... where *P. caete* and most of the species of *the P. signifer* group are collected ...”).

cafferi: Caffer + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Antonio Caffer (?), Italian assistant to the Royal Zoological Museum of Torino on board of the Frigate Regina (1839-1840). *Ceratophrys cafferi* Camerano, 1879. In the synonymy of *Proceratophrys appendiculata* (Günther, 1873).

caiaipo: T. *kayapo*, those who look like monkeys; native Brazilian self denominated *mebêngôkre*; from there to Caiapó, a river, and Caiapônia, a city. *Boana caiaipo* Pinheiro et al., 2018 (“... The holotype and topotypic paratypes were collected in lakes and backwaters of small rivulets in the Caiapó River Basin ...”).

caingua: Gu. *caingúá*, variant spelling of Gu. *kaiowá*, one of the three sub-groups of the Guaraní culture. *Hyla caingua* Carrizo, 1991 “1990”. (“... El nombre específico hace referencia a los caingúá, tribu indígena de Misiones y zonas próximas de Paraguay ...”). Also *Hypsiboas caingua* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana caingua* (Carrizo, 1991).

caipora: T. *kaa*, forest + T. *póra*, inhabitant. Also a character from Tupi mythology, inhabitant of forests, usually represented as a native smoking a pipe, known for being the protector of the forests, animals, for bringing bad luck or causing death. *Hypsiboas caipora* Antunes et al., 2008. (“... It refers to the habitat where the new species is found: the Atlantic Forest at Serra do Mar in Southeastern Brazil. Also, it refers to a personage of Brazilian folklore related to the life in the forest ...”). Today *Boana caipora* (Antunes et al., 2008).

caissara: P. *caiçara*; as masculine noun, fisherman who lives on the beach; trickster, bum. If feminine, dead grove, of which trunks remain; fence of sticks around a plantation; branches that are thrown into the water to attract fish; corral. *Scinax caissara* Lourenço et al., 2016. (“... This word is a Brazilian popular designation for the native people living in southeastern and southern coasts of Brazil. This name is quite appropriate considering the distribution of the new species, occurring in places where the caiçara people live ...”).

Calamobates: G. *kalamos*, reed + G. *bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (from βαίω, move by taking step). *Calamobates* De Witte, 1930. (?). In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

calcarata, calcaratus: L. *calcarata*, -atus, which has a spur. (1) *Hyla calcarata* Troschel, 1848. (“... leicht an der Färbung, so wie an dem häutigen Sporn zu erkennen. Letzterer ist eine reichlich eine Linie lange spitze Hautaus-

dehnung am Fersengelenk ...”). Also *Hypsiboas calcaratus* — Cope, 1867. Today *Boana calcarata* (Troschel in Schomburgk, 1848). (2) *Liuperus calcaratus* Philippi, 1902. (“... El tubérculo en el borde interior del tarso es mui largo i angosto, parecido a una espuela, i mui blanco ...”). Also *Paludicola calcarata* — Nieden, 1923. In the synonymy of *Physalaemus gracilis* (Boulenger, 1883). (3) *Syrrhophus calcaratus* Andersson, 1945. (“... Heel with a very short conical tubercle ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus calcaratus* — Myers, 1962. In the synonymy of *Pristimantis ockendeni* (Boulenger, 1912).

caldarum: P. [Poços de] Caldas, municipality in Minas Gerais, from L. *calda*, hot water; warm water + L. *-arum*, having the nature of. *Hyla duartei caldarum* B. Lutz, 1968. (“... I have called it *Hyla duartei caldarum* after the type locality, whose name is derived from the thermal springs found there ...”). Also *Hyla caldarum* — Cardoso et al., 1989. Today *Scinax caldarum* (B. Lutz, 1968).

caldwellae: Caldwell + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Janalee Paige Caldwell, US American herpetologist. (1) *Allobates caldwellae* Lima et al., 2020. (2) *Bolitoglossa caldwellae* Breko et al., 2013. Also in the combination *Bolitoglossa (Eladinea) caldwellae* — Raffaëlli, 2013.

caliginosus: L. *caliginosus*, foggy, misty; covered with mist; obscure, dark, gloomy. *Leptodactylus caliginosus* Girard, 1853. (“... Reddish brown, with indistinct blackish maculae on the back ...”). Also *Cystignathus caliginosus* — Günther, 1859 “1858”. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815).

Callimedusa: G. *kállos* (κάλλος), physical beauty, beauty + G. *Medousa* (Μέδουσα), a Gorgon; also, ending of some genera of Phyllomedusidae⁷. *Callimedusa* Duellman et al., 2016. (“... The generic name is derived from the Greek *kalos* meaning beautiful and the Greek *Medousa*. The name alludes to the beautiful coloration of the flanks of members of this genus ...”).

⁷ See comments under *Phyllomedusa*.

callipygia: G. *kállos* (κάλλος), physical beauty, beauty + G. *pygis* (πύγῆς), buttocks, rump, arse. *Hyla callipygia* Cruz & Peixoto, 1985 “1984”. (“... O nome atribuído é de origem grega e faz alusão à ornamentação cloacal ...”). Also *Aplastodiscus callipygius* — Faivovich et al., 2005. *Boana callipygia* — Wiens et al., 2005. In the synonymy of *Aplastodiscus albosignatus* (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938).

camacan: T. *Camacan*, members of a linguistic family of native-Brazilians (from T. *cama*, hill + T. *quaá*, hole). *Physalaemus camacan* Pimenta et al., 2005. (“... It is composed of the words “*cama*” and “*quá*”, meaning “a narrow valley between rounded hills ... The specific name honours the Camacan indians, which inhabited the same region where this new frog was found, between the rivers Pardo and Contas ...”).

camaquara: T. *camaquara*, well-digger. *Leptodactylus camaquara* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978. (“... O nome *camaquara* é de origem indígena e significa poceiro e é dado em alusão ao hábito dessa espécie de fazer escavações ...”).

camba: Gu. *kamba*, a demonym for black persons; by extension, used to refer to the aboriginal populations of the eastern plains of Bolivia. *Phyllomedusa camba* De la Riva, 2000. [“... from the Bolivian word “*camba*”, which designates the indigenous people from the lowlands (or the “*oriente*”, mostly in Santa Cruz, Beni, and Pando), as opposite to the people from the Andean highlands and valleys, which are called “*collas*” ...”].

cambaraensis: P. *Cambará* [do Sul], municipality in the state of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil (from T. *camará*, a shrub, probably of the genus *Lantana*) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Melanophryniscus cambaraensis* P. Braun & C. Braun, 1979. (“... O nome *cambaraensis* refere-se ao município onde foi coletada a nova espécie, Cambará do Sul, ao qual está restrita sua distribuição geográfica até o momento ...”).

cambui: P. *Cambuí*, from T. *kambuí*, diverse trees of the family Myrtaceae. *Hypsiboas cambui* Pinheiro et al., 2016. (“... derived from the tupi “*Kābu’i*,” attributed to many species of small o medium-size twisted trees of Myrtaceae that occur close to streams and wet soils, like those of the locality where we found the species. Also, the local people know the area where the

animals were collected with the name Cambu'í ...”). Today *Boana cambui* (Pinheiro et al., 2016).

cammaeus: French (F) *camaïeu* or *camaheu*, a carved precious stone, or mollusk shell, with two color layers. *Sphaenorhynchus cammaeus* Roberto et al., 2017. [“... It is given in reference to the name of the type locality (Pedra Talhada, i. e., carved stone) and also to the beauty of the species ...”].

camposseabrai: Campos Seabra + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carlos Alberto Campos Seabra (1916-2001), Brazilian businessman and entomologist. *Hyla camposseabrai* Bokermann, 1968. Also *Hyla x-signata camposseabrai* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Ololygon x-signata camposseabrai* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax camposseabrai* (Bokermann, 1968).

camufatus: It. *camuffato*, disguised. *Osteocephalus camufatus* Jungfer et al., 2016. (“... The species name *camufatus* is the Latinized past participle of Italian *camuffare*, to disguise or mask, from which the word camouflaged is derived, in allusion to the shape-dissolving pattern of greens and browns of the new species ...”); however, the correct latinization of the past participle of the verb *camuffare* should have preserved the double f.

canastrensis: P. [Serra de] Canastra, mountain range and national park in the state of Minas Gerais, Brazil; in turn, from P. *canastra*, wide, low basket made of wooden slats or lintel, sometimes with a lid. + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Hyla canastrensis* Cardoso & Haddad, 1982. (“... O epíteto específico é dado em alusão à descoberta desta espécie na Serra da Canastra ...”). Also *Ololygon canastrensis* — Duellman, 1985. Today *Scinax canastrensis* (Cardoso & Haddad, 1982).

canga: T. *acanga*, head, lode of ore (veeiro) outcrop. (1) *Pseudopaludicola canga* Giaretta & Kokubum, 2003. (“... The specific epithet *canga*, is a Tupi indigenous word to the exposed iron ore deposits where the new species was found ...”). (2) *Sphaenorhynchus canga* Araujo-Vieira et al., 2015. (“... The specific epithet is an allusion to the occurrence of this species in natural ponds located over ironstone outcrops, known as *canga* ...”).

caparu: S. *Caparú*, Ranch located at 14°48.795'S, 61°09.602'W; 158 m), Provincia Velasco, Department of Santa Cruz, Bolivia; from T. *ka'a pau*, isolated forest. *Hydrolaetare caparu* Jansen et al., 2007. (“... The name *caparu* is a noun used in reference to the type locality where the type series of the species was collected ...”).

capistrata: L. *capistratus*, provided with a halter, put a halter on a horse; fasten with a headstall; bind. *Hyla capistrata* Reuss, 1833. (“... *capistro lato, caeruleo marmorato, utrinque ad capitis latera usque ad mediam corporis partem producto* ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus bipunctatus* (Spix, 1824).

capixaba: P. *capixaba*, demonym of the inhabitants of the state of Espírito Santo, Brazil, from T. *kaá/caá* + *pixaba*, swiddens, clean land for planting. (1) *Chiasmocleis capixaba* Cruz et al., 1997. (“... The name of the species, a native Brazilian word here utilized as a noun in apposition, refers to the occurrence of the species as an inhabitant of the state of Espírito Santo ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) capixaba* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. (2) *Phyllobates capixaba* Bokermann, 1967. (“... coleccionado próximo à Lagoa do Macuco, Refúgio Sooretama, Linhares, Espírito Santo, Brasil ...”). Also *Colostethus capixaba* — Edwards, 1971. *Allobates capixaba* — Grant et al., 2006. In the synonymy of *Allobates olfersioides* (A. Lutz, 1925).

cappellei: Cappelle + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Herman van Cappelle Jr. (1857-1932), Dutch geologist. *Hylella Cappellei* Van Lidth de Jeude, 1904. Also *Hyla cappellei* — Nieden, 1923. *Centrolenella cappellei* — Noble, 1926. *Hyalinobatrachium cappellei* — Cisneros-Heredia & McDiarmid, 2007. Today *Hyalinobatrachium cappellei* (van Lidth de Jeude, 1904).

capra: L. *capra*, she-goat, nanny-goat; L. *caper*, he-goat, billy-goat. *Bokermannohyla capra* Napoli & Pimenta, 2009. (“... The specific name, a Latin substantive (*caper*= goat), is an allusion to the advertisement call of the new species, which sounds like a bleating of a goat ...”).

carajas: P. [Floresta Nacional de] Carajás (06°23'34.7"S, 50°19'09.8"W), municipality of Parauapebas, Pará, Brazil. From T. *karaiá*, lord of the jungle, (in turn, from T. *karai*, person to which great magical powers were supposed + T. *kaá* or *caá*, forest, leaf, herb). Additionally, *Carajas* alludes to the Carajás ethnic group, or *iny mahãdu* (see *caraya*). *Allobates carajas* Simões et al., et al., 2019. (“... The specific epithet ... refers to the species type locality at Floresta Nacional de Carajás ...”).

caramaschii: Caramaschi + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ulisses Caramaschi, Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Hyla caramaschii* Napoli, 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla caramaschii* (Napoli, 2005). (2) *Crossodactylus caramaschii* Bastos & Pombal, 1995. (3) *Sphaenorhynchus caramaschii* Toledo et al., 2007. (3) *Proceratophrys caramaschii* Cruz et al., 2012. In the synonymy of *Proceratophrys cristiceps* (Müller, 1883).

caraya: T. *carajás*, great people; group of native Brazilians from Araguaia region, a.k.a. *iny mahãdu* (see also *carajas*). *Lysapsus caraya* Gallardo, 1964. (“... En el presente trabajo describo una nueva subespecie de *Lysapsus limellus*, proveniente de la Ilha do Bananal, en el río Araguaia, Mato Grosso, Brasil, a la que denomino *Lysapsus limellus caraya* ...”). Also *Lysapsus limellus caraya* Gallardo, 1964. *Pseudis caraya* — Aguiaret al., 2007.

cardosoi: Cardoso + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Adão José Cardoso (1951-1997), Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Hylodes cardosoi* Lingnau et al., 2008. (2) *Paratelmatobius cardosoi* Pombal & Haddad, 1999. (3) *Pseudis cardosoi* Kwet, 2000. Also *Podonectes cardosoi* — Garda & Cannatella, 2007. (4) *Rupirana cardosoi* Heyer, 1999. (5) *Oloolygon cardosoi* S. Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 1991. Today *Scinax cardosoi* (S. Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 1991).

caribensis: S. Caribe, from Ta. *caribe*, word used to designate strength and bravery + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Pseudis paradoxus caribensis* Gallardo, 1961. (“... Nearly all the material that has been studied by me comes from the same locality, Mayaro, S. E. Trinidad Island ...”). Also *Pseudis paradoxa caribensis* — Murphy, 1997. In the synonymy of *Pseudis paradoxa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

carioca: *P. carioca*, demonym of the inhabitants of the city of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, from *T. cari-oca*, residence of white men. *Phyllobates carioca* Bokermann, 1967 (“... coleccionado na Represa Rio Grande, Rio de Janeiro, Guanabara, Brasil ...”). Also *Colostethus carioca* — Edwards, 1971. *Allobates carioca* — Grant et al., 2006. In the synonymy of *Allobates olfersioides* (A. Lutz, 1925).

carlesvilai: Carles Vilà + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carles Vilà, Spanish zoologist. *Hyalinobatrachium carlesvilai* Castroviejo-Fisher et al., 2009.

carneus: L. *carneus*, of the flesh, carnal; not spiritual. *Hylella carnea* Cope, 1868. (“... The pigment is light rose yellow ...”). Today *Sphaenorhynchus carneus* (Cope, 1868).

carnevallii: Carnevalli + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ney Eni Demas Carnevalli (1938-2002), Brazilian ornithologist. *Ololygon carnevallii* Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989. Also *Hyla carnevallii* — Pombal & Gordo, 1991. Today *Scinax carnevallii* (Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989).

carranca: *P. carranca*, sculpture that imitates a human or animal head, carved in wood and coarsely colored, used by boatmen on the São Francisco River, who placed them in the bow, to ward off evil spirits. *Proceratophrys carranca* Godinho et al., 2013. (“... is a historical symbol for safe navigation on the São Francisco River and also serves as a symbol of the artisan and commercial culture of many riverine human populations, including those in the municipality in which the new species was discovered ...”).

carrizorum: Carrizo + L. *-orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. Honouring Gustavo R. Carrizo, Argentinian herpetologist, and his sons, Rodrigo and Ramiro Carrizo. *Physalaemus carrizorum* Cardozo & Pereyra, 2018.

carvalhoi: Carvalho + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Antenor Leitão de Carvalho (1910-1985), Brazilian herpetologist and ichthyologist. (1) *Hyla carvalhoi* Peixoto, 1981. Also *Boana*

carvalhoi — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla carvalhoi* (Peixoto, 1981). (2) *Chiasmocleis carvalhoi* Cruz et al., 1997 (secondary homonym of *Syncope carvalhoi* Nelson, 1975). In the synonymy of *Chiasmocleis lacrimae* Peloso et al., 2014. (3) *Zachaenus carvalhoi* Izecksohn, 1983 “1982”. Today *Cycloramphus carvalhoi* (Izecksohn, 1983). (4) *Dendrophryniscus carvalhoi* Izecksohn, 1994. (5) *Elachistocleis carvalhoi* Caramaschi, 2010. Also *Engystoma carvalhoi* — Dubois et al., 2021. (6) *Odontophrynus carvalhoi* Savage & Cei, 1965. (7) *Protopipa carvalhoi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. Also *Hemipipa carvalhoi* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. Today *Pipa carvalhoi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937). (8) *Eleutherodactylus carvalhoi* B. Lutz in B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952. Today *Pristimantis carvalhoi* (B. Lutz in B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952).

casconi: Cascon + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paulo Cascon, Brazilian herpetologist. *Rhinella casconi* Roberto et al., 2014.

castanea: L. *castanea*, chestnut-tree, chestnut. *Rana castanea* Shaw, 1802. (“... Chestnut-coloured granulated Frog ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithodytes lineatus* (Schneider, 1799).

castaneicola: L. *castanea*, chestnut-tree, chestnut + L. *-cola*, dwelling in, inhabiting, living among. *Osteocephalus castaneicola* Moravec et al., 2009. (“... The name ... refers to the life history of the new species ...”).

castaneotica, castaneoticus: L. *castanea*, chestnut-tree, chestnut + L. *oti(i)*, leisure; spare time + L. *-ica, -icus*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to, pertaining to, having the nature of, made of, quality of, state or condition of. (1) *Dendrobates castaneoticus* Caldwell & Myers, 1990. (“... Fallen waterfilled fruit capsules of the Castanha do Pará appear to be an important habitat for the larvae of *Dendrobates castaneoticus* of Pará ...”). Today *Adelphobates castaneoticus* (Caldwell & Myers, 1990). (2) *Bufo castaneoticus* Caldwell, 1991. (“... The allusion is not to the European chestnut tree (*Castanea*) but rather to the tropical South American Brazil nut tree (*Bertholletia excelsa*, family Lecythidaceae), whose Brazilian common name is “Castanha do Pará” and whose fallen fruit capsules are the breeding site of this small *Bufo* ...”). Today *Rhinella castaneotica* (Caldwell, 1991).

catarinensis: P. [Santa] Catarina, a Brazilian state + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Cycloramphus catarinensis* Heyer, 1983. (“... Named for the State of Santa Catarina, where the specimens originated ...”).

catesbeiana, catesbeianus: Catesby + L. *-ana, anus*, suffix indicating belonging to, pertaining to. Honouring Mark Catesby (1683-1749), English naturalist, artist, and traveller. *Rana catesbeiana* Shaw, 1802. Also *Rana catesbyana* — Cope, 1889 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Rana (Rana) catesbeiana* — Boulenger, 1920. *Rana (Aquarana) catesbeiana* — Dubois, 1992. *Rana (Novirana, Aquarana) catesbeiana* — Hillis & Wilcox, 2005. *Lithobates catesbeianus* — Frost et al., 2006. *Lithobates (Aquarana) catesbeianus* — Dubois, 2006. *Rana (Lithobates) catesbeiana* — Fouquette & Dubois, 2014. *Aquarana catesbeiana* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802). Today *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802), although Segalla et al. (2021) included it in *Aquarana*.

catharinae: P. [Serra do] Catharina + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. *Hyla catharinae* Boulenger, 1888. Refers to the type locality, Serra do [da] Catharina, a mountainous region in the state of Santa Catarina, Brazil. Also *Hyla strigilata catharinae* — Gallardo, 1961. *Oloolygon catharinae* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax catharinae* (Boulenger, 1888).

Caudata: L. *cauda*, tail (animal); extreme part/tail of anything + L. *-ata*, provided with. Self-defined meaning. Caudata Scopoli, 1777. (“...provided with a tail...”), as opposed to *Ecaudata* (*e-* = privative particle).

cavernibardus: L. *caverna*, hollow, grotto, cavern, cave, crevice, hole + L. *bardus*, bard, poet-singer, minstrel. *Eleutherodactylus cavernibardus* Myers & Donnelly, 1997. (“... in reference to the diurnal sites commonly utilized by calling males ...”). Also *Pristimantis cavernibardus* — Heinicke et al., 2007. Today *Ceuthomantis cavernibardus* (Myers & Donnelly, 1997).

cavicola: L. *cavicola*, one who inhabits in hole, cavity, depression, pit, cave. (1) *Cavicola* A. Lutz, 1930. (?). [Preoccupied by *Cavicola* Ancey, 1887 (Mollusca)]. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826. (2) *Hyla cavicola* Cruz & Peixoto, 1985 “1984”. [“... O nome atribuído é de origem latina e se refere ao fato de a espécie construir ninhos subterrâneos (panelas),”]

onde vocaliza ...]. Also *Boana cavicola* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Aplastodiscus cavicola* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1985).

cedrensis: P. [Rio dos] Cedros + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Cycloramphus cedrensis* Heyer, 1983. (“... Named for the type locality: Brazil; Santa Catarina. 12 km E of Rio dos Cedros on road to rio São Bernardo, approximately 26°44’S, 49°20’ W ...”).

centralis: L. *centralis*, central; centrally located; in middle/center. (1) *Chiasmocleis centralis* Bokermann, 1952. (“... Localidade tipo: Aruanã, Estado de Goiaz [Goiás], Brasil ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) centralis* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. (2) *Physalaemus centralis* Bokermann, 1962. [referring both to its origin (“... Em novembro de 1961, tivemos a oportunidade de ... empreender uma curta excursão ao Xingu, campo de pousos da Força Aérea Brasileira ... Este local também é conhecido como Posto Jacaré ... está situado na margem direita do rio Coluene ... As suas coordenadas geográficas são: 53° 22’ Long. Oeste e 12° 00’ Lat. Sul ...”), or to a morphological character (“... Glândulas sacrais com mancha preta central ...”).] (3) *Phyllomedusa centralis* Bokermann, 1965. (?) No clues in the description. Reference to the type locality, Chapada dos Guimarães, in Central Brazil. Today *Pithecopus centralis* (Bokermann, 1965). (4) *Scinax centralis* Pombal & Bastos, 1996. (“... o nome específico faz alusão à sua ocorrência na região central do Brasil ...”). Also *Ololygon centralis* — Duellman et al., 2016.

Centrolenidae: L. *Centrolene*, genus of anurans due to Jiménez de la Espada, 1872 [in turn, from G. *kentron* (κέντρον), thorn, spur, any sharp point + G. *oleni* (ωλένη), forearm] + L. *-idae*, suffix indicating the category of family in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). The same root in *Centroleninae* Taylor, 1951.

Centrotelma: G. *kentron* (κέντρον), thorn, spur, any sharp point + G. *telmatos* (τέλματος), stagnant water, pond, marsh, lagoon. (“... scharfer leistenförmiger Randfalte am Vorderarm wie am äusseren Fussrande, welche sich *Centrotelma* Burmeister, 1856. am Hacken zu einer frei abstehenden spitzen Warze ausbildet ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

Cerathyla: *G. kerato* (κέρατο), horn + *L. Hyla*, noun widely used in relation to tree-frogs (see). *Cerathyla* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. The same root in *Ceratohyla* — Boulenger, 1882 (unjustified emendation). In the synonymy of *Hemiphractus* Wagler (1828).

Ceratophryne: *G. kerato* (κέρατο), horn + *G. phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Ceratophryne* Schlegel, 1858 (part.). (“... De gehoornde Kikvorschen ...”). In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys* Wied-Neuwied, 1824.

ceratophyes, ceratophrys: *G. kerato* (κέρατο), horn + *G. ofrys* (οφρύς), eyebrow, supercilium. (1) *Ceratophrys* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. (“... Augenlieder in kegel-förmige Spitzen verlängert ...”). (2) *Pseudopaludicola ceratophyes* Rivero & Serna, 1985. (“... *Ceratophyes*, del *G. keratophyes*, con cuernos, en referencia a las lengüetas cutaneas o “cuernitos” que tiene esta especie en los parpados ...”). (3) *Bufo ceratophrys* Boulenger, 1882. (“... upper eyelid produced in a horn-like appendage, the length of which is greater than the orbital diameter ...”). Also *Rhinella ceratophrys* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhaebo ceratophrys* (Boulenger, 1882). (4) The same root in *Ceratophryidae* Tschudi, 1838.

cerradensis: *P. cerrado*, South American natural formation + *L. -ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Hyla cerradensis* Napoli & Caramaschi, 1998. (“... O nome da espécie faz alusão à sua ocorrência, restrita ao Domínio Morfoclimático do Cerrado ...”). Today *Dendropsophus cerradensis* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1998). (2) *Rhinella cerradensis* Maciel et al., 2007. (“... The new species occupies Cerrado habitats in the Brazilian states of Piauí, Bahia, Goiás, Minas Gerais, and Distrito Federal ...”).

cesarii: Cesár[io] + *L. -ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Cesário Nazianzeno de Azevedo Motta Magalhães Júnior (1847-1897), Brazilian physician, politician, and writer. *Engystoma ovale cesarii* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. Also *Elachistocleis cesarii* — Toledo et al., 2010. *Engystoma cesarii*— Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Elachistocleis cesarii* (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920).⁸

8 The species author is Ihering; Miranda-Ribeiro (1920: 283) wrote: “... Poderá ser chamado do *E. -o-cesarii* Iher. The footnote of pp. 283-284 indicates: “... Em um dos frascos da série da sala de exposição ao publico, havia um exemplar com o seguinte rotulo á machina: *Engystoma cesarii* Iher.; em baixo do frasco, collado ao fundo, em manuscrito desconhecido: *Engystoma cesarii mottae*, Iher. S. Paulo.

cesarii-mottae: Cesári[o] Motta + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating belonging to. Honouring Cesário Nazianzeno de Azevedo Motta Magalhães Júnior (1847-1897). Brazilian physician, politician, and writer. *Engystoma cesarii mottae* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920 (*nomen nudum*). In the synonymy of *Elachistocleis cesarii* (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920).⁹

Ceuthomantis: G. *keutho* (κεῦθω), keep concealed or hidden + G. *mantis* (μαντις), tree-frog. *Ceuthomantis* Heinicke et al., 2009. [“... alludes to its hidden existence in the tepuis of the Guiana Shield, which became known as the Lost World through the writings of Arthur Conan Doyle (1912) ...”]. The same root in *Ceuthomantidae* Heinicke et al., 2009.

Chaguar: W. *chaguar*, vernacular name of quechua origin of several terrestrial bromeliads of textile use and chacoan distribution (mostly *Bromelia hyeronimi*, “caraguata” in guarani). *Bufo arenarum chaguar* Gallardo, 1965. (“... la nueva subespecie *B. a. chaguar* es chaqueña ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella arenarum* (Hensel, 1867).

chaquensis: S. Chaco, South American plain (in turn from Q. *chacu*, hunting ground) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Leptodactylus chaquensis* Ceï, 1950. (“... *Leptodactylus chaquensis* n. sp. Cuya área geográfica es fundamentalmente la del Gran Chaco ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus macrosternum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926.

charadranaetes: G. *charadros* (χάραδρος), ravine + G. *naétás* (ναέτας), inhabitant. *Hylodes charadranaetes* Heyer & Cocroft, 1986. [“... From the Greek *charadra* (bed of mountain stream) and *naetes* (inhabitant), referring to the habitat of the species ...].

Chaunus: G. *chaûnoo* (χαυνόω), puffed-up. *Chaunus* Wagler, 1828. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

cherrei: Cherrie + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring George Kruck Cherrie (1865-1948), US American naturalist and explorer. *Hyla cherrei* Cope, 1894. Also *Hyla cherrii* — Günther,

⁹ See previous note.

1901. *Hyla microcephala cherrei* — Duellman, 2001. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus microcephalus* (Cope, 1886).

Chianopelas: Unclear. G. *chiazō* (χιαζω), mark with a cross like the letter chi (X), or G. *chiano* (ξηιανο), dry + G. *pilas* (πηλός), clay, mud. *Chianopelas* Tschudi, 1845. (?). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838.

Chiasmocleis: G. *chiasma* (χιασμα), arranged diagonally, crosswise + G. *kleio* (κλείω), shut, closed by barring or locking. *Chiasmocleis* Méhelÿ, 1904. (Refers to the structure of the pectoral girdle, “... Precoracoids present, cartilaginous, arising from the inner edge of the coracoid and curving hook-like to the middle of the latter ...”).

chiastonotus: G. *chiastos* (χιαστος), crucified, arranged diagonally, crosswise; chi (X), twenty-second letter of the Greek alphabet + G. *notos* (νοτος), back, dorsum. *Eleutherodactylus chiastonotus* Lynch & Hoogmoed, 1977. [“... in reference to the X-shaped mark (chi-like) on the dorsum ...”]. Today *Pristimantis chiastonotus* (Lynch & Hoogmoed, 1977).

chicomendesi: Chico Mendes + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Chico Mendes [Francisco Alves Mendes Filho] (1944-1988), Brazilian environmental activist. *Adenomera chicomendesi* Carvalho et al., 2019.

Chilixalus: G. *chili*, from G. *cheilos* (χείλος), lip, rim + G. *ixalos* (ιξαλος), jumper, agile. *Chilixalus* Werner, 1899. (“... Nächstverwandt *Phyllodromus* Espada, aber Schnauze wie bei der Cyprinoidengattung *Chondrostoma* ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

Chilophryne: G. *cheilos* (χείλος), lip + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Chilophryne* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

chlorocraspedus: G. *chloros* (χλωρός), green + G. *kraspedon* (κρασπέδων), edge, border, curb. *Cryptophyllobates chlorocraspedus* Caldwell, 2005. (“... in allusion to the bright lime green dorsalolateral border that is continuous from the snout to the posterior dorsum ...”). Today *Hyloxalus chlorocraspedus* (Caldwell, 2005).

Chorophilus: L. *chorus*, choir; singing + G. *philos* (φίλος), friend. *Chorophilus* Baird, 1854, (?). See *Chorophilus cuzcanus* Cope, 1878 “1877”. Suggested as synonym of *Aplastodiscus perviridis* by B. Lutz, 1968; in the synonymy of *Gastrotheca marsupiata* (Duméril and Bibron, 1841).

Chthonerpeton: G. *chthon* (χθόν), earth, soil + G. *erpeton* (ερπετον), reptil. *Chthonerpeton* Peters, 1880. (?).

cicada: L. *cicada*, cicada, tree-cricket. *Physalaemus cicada* Bokermann, 1966. (“... O canto desta espécie tem certa semelhança com o de *Pseudopaludicola falcipes* ou de certas cigarras ...”).

Cinclidium: G. *kinklidos* (κιγκλίδος), latticed gate. *Cinclidium* Cope, 1867. (“... The generic name is from κιγκλῖς, a lattice ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

Cincloscopus: G. *kinklidos* (κιγκλίδος), latticed gate + G. *scopos* (σκοπός), watcher. *Cincloscopus* Cope, 1871 “1870”. (Replacement name for *Cinclidium*). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

cinctus: L. *cinctus*, surrounded/encircled. *Bufo cinctus* Schinz, 1822. (“... Am Auge beginnt ein breiter, schwarzbrauner Streif, welcher das ganze Thier längs den Seiten einfaßt ...”). Also *Otoloophus cinctus* — Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. In the synonymy of *Rhinella crucifer* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).

cinerascens: L. *cineris*, ashes + L. *-ens*, made of. *Hyla cinerascens* Spix, 1824. (“... *tota coeruleo-cinerea, immaculate* ...). Also *Hypsiboas cinerascens* — Wagler, 1830. Today *Boana cinerascens* (Spix, 1824).

cinereus: L. *cinereus*, resembling ashes, similar to ashes, ash-colored. *Lithodytes cinereus* Cope, 1885. (“... Color above gray, with pale brown markings ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis fenestratus* (Steindachner, 1864).

cipoensis: P. [Serra do] Cipó (from T. *ysypó*, vernacular name for vines and woody, long and flexible plants, which wrap themselves around the trunks of trees like ropes; a. k. a. *icipo*, *liana*). + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Hyla polytaenia cipoensis* B. Lutz, 1968. (“... All were taken near Alto do Palacio, in the Serra do Cipó, municipality of Jaboticatubas, between Lagoa Santa and Ferros, Minas

Gerais ...”). Also *Hyla cipoensis* — Cruz & Caramaschi, 1998. *Hypsiboas cipoensis* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana cipoensis* (B. Lutz, 1968).

circumdata: L. *circumdata*, surrounded; enveloped, enclosed. *Hypsiboas circumdatus* Cope, 1867 (*nomen nudum*); *Hypsiboas circumdatus* Cope, 1871 “1870”. (“... Femoral bands ten, blackish, very narrow and nearly surrounding the leg ...”). Also *Hyla circumdata* — Boulenger, 1882. *Hyla circumdata* — Bokermann, 1966 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Boana circumdata* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla circumdata* (Cope, 1871).

clamata: L. *clamata*, cry/shout out; accompany with shouts. *Rana clamata* — Daudin, 1802 “An. XI” (incorrect subsequent spelling of *Rana clamitans* Latreille, 1801); here in relation to *Rana clamata* var. *guianensis* Peters, 1863. In the synonymy of *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824).

claptoni: Clapton + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Eric Clapton, English rock and blues guitarist, singer, and songwriter. *Physalaemus claptoni* Leal et al., 2020.

claresignata: L. *clarus*, clear, bright, gleaming+ L *signatus*, mark, stamp. *Hyla claresignata* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939. (“... It is characterised by unusual dark markings, outlined in white, contrasting with the yellow, upper surfaces ...”). Also *Bokermannohyla claresignata* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana claresignata* (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939).

clepsydra: L. *clepsydra*, from G. *klepsydra* (κλεψύδρα), water-clock, hour-glass. *Hyla clepsydra* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Le museau présente une tache angulaire brune, une seconde très grande, figurant une clepsydre ...”). Also *Bokermannohyla clepsydra* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana clepsydra* (A. Lutz, 1925).

clipeata: L. *clipeata*, armed/furnished with a shield (*clipeus*). *Ceratophrys clipeata* Cuvier, 1829 (*nomen nudum*). (?). Same root in *Ceratophrys clypeata* — Cocteau, 1835. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys aurita* (Raddi, 1823).

cochranae: Cochran + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Doris Mable Cochran (1898-1968), US American

herpetologist. (1) *Hyla cochranae* Mertens, 1952. Today *Aplastodiscus cochranae* (Mertens, 1952). (2) *Euparkerella cochranae* Izecksohn, 1988. (3) *Phyllomedusa cochranae* Bokermann, 1966. Today *Phasmahyla cochranae* (Bokermann, 1966).

Cochranella: Cochran + L. -ella, diminutive suffix. Honouring Doris Mable Cochran (1898-1968), US American herpetologist. *Cochranella* Taylor, 1951.

Coelonotus: L. *coelum*, sky, heaven, heavens + L. *notus*, observe; record; become cognizant of/acquainted/familiar with. *Coelonotus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920 [preoccupied by *Coelonotus* Peters, 1855 (a marine fish)]. (?). In the synonymy of *Fritziana* Mello-Leitão, 1937.

coerulea: L. *caerulea*, blue, cerulean, dark; greenish-blue, azure. (“... *Submediocris, supra violacea* ...”). *Hyla coerulea* Spix, 1824. Also *Auletris coerulea* – Wagler, 1830. In the synonymy of *Scinax x-signatus* (Spix, 1824).

colibri: P. *colibrí*, in turn from the A. *colibrí*, hummingbird. *Ischnocnema colibri* Taucce et al., 2018. [“... Refers to the type locality, the municipality of Santa Teresa, which is known as “*doce terra dos colibris*” (sweet land of the hummingbirds) ...”].

coloratus: L. *coloratus*, colored; tanned; not pallid. *Brachycephalus coloratus* Ribeiro et al., 2017. (“... in reference to the unique combination of colors found in the species ...”).

Colostethinae: L. *Colostethus*, genus of anurans due to Cope (1866) (see) + L. -inae, suffix indicating the category of subfamily in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). Colostethinae Cope, 1867.

Colostethus: G. *kolos* (κόλος), (of cattle, goats) hornless + G. *stethos* (στήθος), breast, chest. *Colostethus* Cope, 1866. (“... The sternum is Raniform without manubrium ...”). In the synonymy of *Allobates* Zimmermann & Zimmermann, 1988 (*part.*).

compressicauda: L. *compressa*, constricted/narrow/pressed together + L. *cauda*. tail. *Coecilia compressicauda* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Extrémité postérieure du tronc assez fortement comprimée à sa partie supérieure ou tectiforme ...”). Also *Typhlonectes compressicaudus* — Peters, 1880 “1879”, *Thyphlonectes compressicauda compressicauda* Fuhrmann, 1914. Today *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

concavitympanum: L. *concavus*, hollow/hollowed out; concave/curving inward + L. *tympanum*, from G. *tympano* (τύμπανο), eardrum, tympanum, although originally it referred to a small drum that was played in religious ceremonies. *Proceratophrys concavitympanum* Giaretta et al., 2000. (“... The name refers to the depression on each side of the head at the location of the tympanum ...”).

concolor: L. *concolor*, of the same color; of uniform color throughout. (1) *Engystoma ovale concolor* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... de coloração parda no lado dorsal e apenas mais clara no lado ventral. Esta variedade pôde ser chamada *concolor* ...”). In the synonymy of *Elachistocleis bicolor* (Valenciennes in Guérin-Ménéville, 1838). (2) *Ischnocnema concolor* Targino et al., 2009. (“... refers to the uniform coloration of the body, without any strong pattern, after preservation ...”).

confusionis: L. *confusionis*, mingling/mixture/union; confusion/confounding/disorder. *Siphonops confusionis* Taylor, 1968. (Refers to the confusion of this species with *Siphonops*, *Luetkenotyphlus*, and *Chthonerpeton*). In the synonymy of *Luetkenotyphlus brasiliensis* (Lütken, 1852).

conirostris: L. *coni*, cone, conical figure/shape + L. *rostris*, beak, snout. *Hyla conirostris* Peters, 1863. (“... die stumpfe kegelförmige Schnauzenspitze über das Maul vorragt ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax ruber* (Laurenti, 1768).

connectens: L. *connectens*, join/fasten/link together. *Phryniscus connectens* Philippi, 1902. [“... *cute posterius laxa plica sat magna alba femux* (sic) *cum regione lumbari connectantes* ...”]. In the synonymy of *Rhinella arenarum* (Hensel, 1867).

conspersa: L. *conspersa*, sprinkle/strew/spatter, cover with small drops/particles. *Rana conspersa* LeConte, 1855. (“... Top of the back with an infinity of small dots of paler, and marked with numerous small, round, irregularly scattered spots of dusky, which are however sometimes nearly evanescent ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802).

conspicillatus: L. *conspicillatus*, provided with lens or spectacles. *Hylodes conspicillatus* Günther, 1858. (“... ein schwärzlicher Streif zwischen den Augen, ein zweiter vom Auge zum Tympanum und ein dritter unter dem Auge ...”). Also *Lithodytes conspicillatus* — Cope, 1868. *Eleutherodactylus conspicillatus* — Stejneger, 1904. Today *Pristimantis conspicillatus* (Günther, 1858).

conspicuus: L. *conspicuus*, visible, clearly seen, in sight/full view. *Colostethus conspicuus* Morales, 2002 “2000”. (“... *Conspicuus*, palabra latina que significa visible, notable. El nombre se refiere a que en vivo es bien distinguible de *C. trilineatus*, ya que en la localidad tipo habitan en simpatria ...”). Today *Allobates conspicuus* (Morales, 2002).

constrictus: L. *constrictus*, compressed/contracted. *Scinax constrictus* Lima et al., 2004. (“... it is used here in reference to the presence of a dorsolateral dermal constriction on the shoulders of the new species ...”).

Cophomantinae: *Cophomantis*, genus of anurans due to Peters (1870) (see); today in the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825) + L. *-inae*, suffix indicating the category of subfamily in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). *Cophomantinae* Hoffmann, 1878.

Cophomantis: G. *kophos* (κωφός), deaf + G. *mantis* (μαντις), tree-frog. *Cophomantis* Peters, 1870. (“... Kein Trommelfell und keine Tubae Eustachii ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

copii: Cope + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Edward Drinker Cope (1840-1897), US American herpetologist. *Rana copii* Boulenger, 1882. In the synonymy of *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824).

coracoralinae: P. Cora Coralina + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Cora Coralina (pseudonym of Anna Lins dos Guimarães Peixoto Bretas) (1889-1985), Brazilian candy maker, writer, and poetress. *Pseudopaludicola coracoralinae* Andrade et al., 2020.

cordeiroi: Cordeiro + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paulo Henrique Chaves Cordeiro, Brazilian biologist. *Chiasmocleis cordeiroi* Caramaschi & Pimenta, 2003. Also *Chiasmocleis* (*Chiasmocleis*) *cordeiroi* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

coriacea, coriaceus: L. *coriacea*, of leather, made of leather. (1) *Rana coriacea* Spix, 1824. (“... *hypochondria versus femur crassiora, coriacea* ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768). (2) *Hyla coriacea* Peters, 1867. (“... Oberseite des Körpers lederartig gerunzelt ...”). Also *Phrynohyas coriacea* — Duellman, 1968. Today *Trachycephalus coriaceus* (Peters, 1867).

cornuta, cornutus: L. *cornuta*, *-us*, horned; having horns. *Rana cornuta* Linnaeus, 1758. (“... *R. palpebris conicis* ...”). Also *Bufo cornutus* — Laurenti, 1768. *Bufo cornuta* — Lacépède, 1788. *Pipa cornata* — Oken, 1816. *Stombus cornutus* — Gravenhorst, 1825. *Ceratophrys* (*Stombus*) *cornuta* — Lynch, 1982. *Stombus cornutus* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Ceratophrys cornuta* (Linnaeus, 1758).

corrugatum: L. *corrugatum*, make wrinkled; corrugate. *Chthonerpeton corrugatum* Taylor, 1968. (“... Skin transversely wrinkled, somewhat more in adults than in young ...”). In the synonymy of *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

corticalis: L. *corticalis*, in a condition of bark. *Hyla* (*Lophopus*) *corticalis* Burmeister, 1856. (“... Ein ungemein flaches, niedriges, breithköpfiges Thier, das in der Ruhe mit untergeschlagenen Beinen einer Flechte ähnelt, wenn man es an den Baumen, gewöhnlich oben im Schalten des Laubes, unter der Krone, an einem Ast oder am Stamme selbst sitzen sieht ...”). Also *Hyla corticalis* — Günther, 1859 “1858”. In the synonymy of *Boana pardalis* (Spix, 1824).

corumbaensis: P. Corumbá, a city in the state of Mato Grosso do Sul, Brazil; from T. *curú-mbá*, the gravel bank + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Elachistocleis corumbaensis* Piva et al., 2017. (“... The specific name ... refers to the city of Corumbá, the westernmost and northernmost city in the state of Mato Grosso do Sul ...”). Also *Engystoma corumbaensis* – Dubois et al., 2021.

Corythomantis: G. *corysthos* (κόρυς + θος), helmet + G. *mantis* (μαντις) treefrog. *Corythomantis* Boulenger, 1896. (“... Head a bony casque, with projecting labial borders, formed as in *Triprion* and *Diaglena* ...”).

cosenzai: Cosenza + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Braz Antônio Pereira Cosenza, Brazilian biologist. *Scinax cosenzai* Lacerda et al., 2012. Also *Ololygon cosenzi* – Duellman et al., 2016.

cotuba: T. *cotuba*, robust, fleshy, or well-nourished. *Adenomera cotuba* Carvalho & Giaretta, 2013. (“... related to the very robust body shape of the species ...”).

counani: F. [État libre de] Counani (in turn, T. *counani*; name given by natives to the fish called “tucunaré”, *Cichla ocellaris*), a.k.a. République indépendante de Guyane, founded in 1886 by Jules Gross (1829-1891); today its territory corresponds, broadly speaking, to the Brazilian state of Amapá. *Dendropsophus counani* Fouquet et al., 2015. (“... The specific epithet refers to the utopic and short-lived “independent state of Counani” which was founded by French settlers and existed from 1886 to 1891 at the border of what is now French Guiana and the Brazilian Amapá State. It was governed by the self-proclaimed “Gros 1er” ...”).

courtoisae: Courtois L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Elodie Courtois, herpetologist in French Guiana. *Boana courtoisae* Fouquet et al., 2021.

cranwelli: Cranwell + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jorge Andrés Noel Cranwell (1916-2002), Argentinian herpetologist. *Ceratophrys cranwelli* Barrio, 1980.

Craspedoglossa: *G. kraspeda* (κράσπεδα), fringes + *G. glossa* (γλώσσα), tongue. *Craspedoglossa* Müller, 1922. (“... Die hell blaugrau (beim Formolpräparat) gefärbten Seitenpartien greifen noch etwas über die Ränder der hellgelben Zungenoberfläche über, von der sie durch einen schmalen, leicht wulstartig vortretenden, gewellten, schwarz-grau gefärbten Saum getrennt sind ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus* Tschudi, 1838.

craspedopus: *G. kraspeda* (κράσπεδα), fringes + *G. pous* (πούς), foot. *Phyllomedusa craspedopus* Funkhouser, 1957. (“... Dermal folds along both fore and hind border of tibia ...”). Also *Agalychnis craspedopus* — Duellman, 1968. Today *Cruziohyla craspedopus* (Funkhouser, 1957).

crassa, crassus: *L. crassa*, -us, thick/deep; fat/stout. (1) *Dermophis crassus* Cope, 1885 “1884”. (“... The most robust species of the genus ...”). In the synonymy of *Siphonops annulatus* (Mikan, 1820). (2) *Ischnocnema crassa* Silva-Soares et al., 2021. (“... The specific epithet “*crassa*” (*crassa* = fat) is a Latin name here used as an adjective in allusion to its rounded body shape in general view. Typically, *Ischnocnema parva* series are usually more elongated ...”).

Craugastoridae: *L. Craugastor*, genus of anurans due to Cope, 1862 [in turn, from *G. kreas* (κρέας), fleshy + *G. gastir* (γαστήρ), belly, stomach] + *L. -idae*, suffix that indicates the family category in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). *Craugastoridae* Hedges et al., 2008.

crepitans: *L. crepitare*, rattle/clatter; rustle/crackle; produce rapid succession of sharp/shrill noises. (1) *Hyla crepitans* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. (“... Der knackende Laubklebet ...”). Also *Hypsiboas crepitans* — Wagler, 1830. *Auletris crepitans* — Leunis, 1844. *Hyla (Hylomedusa) crepitans* — Burmeister, 1856. Today *Boana crepitans* (Wied-Neuwied, 1824). (2) *Eleutherodactylus crepitans* Bokermann, 1965. (“... O canto consiste de duas notas seguidas semelhante a um estalido curto e áspero que são repetidas com frequência, porém a espaço de tempo pouco regular ...”). Also *Pristimantis crepitans* — Heinicke et al., 2007. *Oreobates crepitans* — Padial et al., 2012. In the synonymy of *Oreobates heterodactylus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

cretatus: L. *cretatus*, chalked, marked with chalk; in white; powdered (woman). *Scinax cretatus* Nunes & Pombal, 2011. (“... in allusion to the dorsal color pattern of this new species ...”).

crispus: L. *crispus*, uneven, wrinkled, twisted. *Brachycephalus crispus* Condez et al., 2014. (“... The name is used in allusion to the roughness of the dorsum of this species ...”).

cristiceps: L. *crista*, ridge, crest + L. *-ceps*, -headed. *Ceratophrys cristiceps* Müller, 1883. (“... Zwischenaugenspatium concav. Von einem Augenlid zum andern eine kräftige Querleiste. Von der Vorderdecke des Auges läuft je ein flacher undeutlicher Kamm bis zur innern vordem Seite des Nasenlochs ...”). Also *Stombus cristiceps* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. *Ceratophrys cristiceps* — Nieden, 1923. Today *Proceratophrys cristiceps* (Müller, 1883).

cristinae: *Proceratophrys cristinae* P. Braun, 1973. Cristina + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Cristina Assunção Sirangelo Braun (1940-2017), Brazilian herpetologist. In the synonymy of *Proceratophrys bigibbosa* (Peters, 1872).

crombiei: Crombie + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ronald Ian Crombie, US American herpetologist. (1) *Colostethus crombiei* Morales, 2002 “2000”. Today *Allobates crombiei* (Morales, 2002). (2) *Physalaemus crombiei* Heyer & Wolf, 1989. Also *Eupemphix crombiei* — Dubois et al., 2021.

crospedospila, crospedospilus: G. *kraspedo* (κρασπεδο), fringe + G. *spilos* (σπίλος), spot, speck, stain. *Hyla crospedospila* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Le dos est à fond beige, avec des taches brunes disseminées sur le corps & formant des barres assez larges sur les extrémités ...”). Also *Hyla crospedospila* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Ololygon crospedospila* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax crospedospilus* — Köhler & Böhme, 1996. Today *Scinax crospedospilus* (A. Lutz, 1925).

Crossodactylodes: L. *Crossodactylus*, genus of anurans due to Duméril & Bibron, 1841 (see) + L. *-odes*, suffix indicating likeness. *Crossodactylodes* Cochran, 1938. (?).

Crossodactylus: *G. krossos* (κρόσος), fringe + *G. dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Crossodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Orteils légèrement aplatis, élargis au bout de la même manière que les doigts & garnis de chaque côté dans toute leur longueur, ainsi que le bord externe du tarse, d’une membrane flottante ...”).

crucifer: L. *crucifer*, cross-bearer. *Bufo crucifer* Wied-Neuwied, 1821. (“... Auch zeigte sich öfters eine röthliche Kröte mit einem dreyfachen schwarzen Kreuze auf dem Rücken ...”). Also *Bufo* (*Palaeobufo*) *crucifer* — Bolkay, 1919. *Chaunus crucifer* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella crucifer* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).

crucis: Cruz + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carlos Alberto Gonçalves da Cruz, Brazilian herpetologist. *Chiasmocleis crucis* Caramaschi & Pimenta, 2003. Also *Chiasmocleis* (*Chiasmocleis*) *crucis* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

cruentomma: L. *cruentus*, stained or mixed with blood, blood + *G. omma* (ομμα), eye (in its function of seeing). *Hyla cruentomma* Duellman, 1972. (“... I propose that the specific name be derived from the Greek—*cruentos*, meaning bloody, and *omma*, meaning eye ...”). Also *Ololygon cruentoma* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax cruentommus* — Lescure & Marty, 2000. Today *Scinax cruentomma* (Duellman, 1972).

crurifasciatum: L. *cruris*, leg; shank; shin + L. *fasciatum*, having a band/strip; ribbon. *Hyalinobatrachium crurifasciatum* Myers & Donnelly, 1997. [“... in allusion to the limbs, which are green crossbanded in life (markings disappear in preservative) ...”]. In the synonymy of *Hyalinobatrachium cappellei* (van Lidth de Jeude, 1904).

cruzi: Cruz + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carlos Alberto Gonçalves da Cruz, Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Hyla cruzi* Pombal & Bastos, 1998. Today *Dendropsophus cruzi* (Pombal & Bastos, 1998). (2) *Phasmahyla cruzi* A. Carvalho-e-Silva et al., 2009.

Cruziophyla: L. *Cruzius*, latinization of [Carlos Alberto Gonçalves da] Cruz + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Cruz-*

iohyla Faivovich & al., 2005. (“... We dedicate this new genus to our colleague and friend Carlos Alberto Gonçalves da Cruz, in recognition of his various contributions to our knowledge of Phyllomedusinae ...”).

cryptanthus: G. *kryptos* (κρυπτός), hidden from sight + G. *anthus* (άνθος), blossom, blooms, flowers. *Scytopis cryptanthus* Cope, 1874. (“... Groin and concealed surfaces of hind limbs black, with brilliant yellow spots ...”). Also *Phyllomedusa (Scytopsis) cryptanthus* — Knauer, 1878. In the synonymy of *Scinax ruber* (Laurenti, 1768).

cryptica: L. *cryptica*, covered, concealed. *Euparkerella cryptica* Hepp et al., 2015. (“... The Latin word *crypticus* means “covered” or “concealed,” and it is used in reference to the morphological similarity of some individuals of this species to *Euparkerella brasiliensis* or *E. cochranæ* ...”).

cryptomelan: L. *cryptico*, covered, concealed + G. *melan* (μέλαν), black. *Centrotelma cryptomelan* Cope, 1867. (“... anterior and posterior faces of femur, tibia below, and band from mouth to groin, black ...”). Also *Hyla cryptomelan* — Barbour & Loveridge, 1929. Same root in *Hyla cryptomelas* — Boulenger, 1882. In the synonymy of *Boana geographica* (Spix, 1824).

Cryptophyllobates: G. *kryptos* (κρυπτός), hidden from sight + L. *Phyllobates*, genus of anurans due to Bibron (1840) (see). *Cryptophyllobates* Lötters et al., 2000. (“... in reference to (a) its secretive way of life in the forest leaf litter ... and (b) its relative resemblance to the genus *Phyllobates* ...”). In the synonymy of *Hyloxalus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

Ctenocranius: G. *chtenos* (κτενος), comb + G. *kranion* (κράνιον), upper part of the head, cranium, skull. *Ctenocranius* Melin, 1941. [“... In this new genus I unite Hylodids of the type *H. cornutus* (Espada), which by their very large depressed head, subcircular snout, crestlike edges of the fronto-parietals, small or rudimentary disks of the fingers. etc., very much differ from other Hylodids ...”]. In the synonymy of *Strabomantis* Peters, 1863.

Ctenophryne: G. *chtenos* (κτενος), comb + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Ctenophryne* Mocquard, 1904. (“... Deux replis transversaux de la muqueuse sur la voûte pharyngienne, le postérieur pectiniforme, situé à l’entrée de l’œsophage, un peu en arrière des orifices des trompes d’Eustache ...”).

cultripes: L. *cultri*, knife; pruner edge; spear point; plowshare + L. *pes*, foot. *Odonotophrynus cultripes* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862. (“... ovenfor Udspringet af Indertaaen er der anbragt en lang, skarp, hornagtig Knude af samme Størrelse og af lignende Form som hos Pelobaterne. Fra denne Hornknude og op imod den egenlige Hæl lader en svag, bugtet, afrundet Hudlisle sig med Lethed forfølge ...”). Also *Pyxicephalus cultripes* — Cope, 1863. *Cerato-phrys cultripes* — Boulenger, 1882.

cunauaru: Pl. *cunhã*, wife + Pl. *aru*, toad. *Trachycephalus cunauaru* Gordo et al., 2013. (“... This is the name given by local Amazonian natives to the populations of *Trachycephalus cunauaru* and *T. resinifictrix* ...”).

cunhai: Cunha + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Osvaldo Rodrigues da Cunha (1928-2011), Brazilian herpetologist. *Typhlonectes cunhai* Cascon et al., 1991. In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

cunicularius: L. *cuniculus*, rabbit; underground tunnel/burrow/hole + L. *-arius*, pertaining to. *Leptodactylus cunicularius* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978. (“... O nome desta espécie é dado em alusão ao seu hábito de escavar no chão à maneira dos coelhos ...”).

cupreus: L. *cupreus*, copper, of copper. *Leptodactylus cupreus* Caramaschi et al., 2008. (“... The specific epithet, “*cupreus*”, is a Latin adjective referred to the copper general color pattern of the new species ...”).

curicica: P. *Curicica*, from T. *yacuri-ycyca*, the drooling tree. *Scinax curicica* Pugliesse et al., 2004. (“... The name is here used as a noun in apposition and is the nickname of our friend and artist from Museu Nacional, Paulo Roberto Nascimento ...”).

curupi, curupira: G. *Curupí*, T. *Curupira*, fantastic being, a character from Tupi mythology, who, according to popular belief, inhabits the Brazilian forests. He is usually presented as a red-haired, dwarf native whose feet have the heel facing forward and the toes facing backward. Spirit of the forests, he would be responsible for the mysterious noises, inexplicable fears and dis-

appearance of hunters, deceived by his lying tracks, which lead him away from the paths. (1) *Hypsiboas curupi* Garcia et al., 2007. (“... is a short, anthropomorphic mythological creature that, among other things, lives in the forest and protects its organisms ...”). Today *Boana curupi* (Garcia et al., 2007). (2) *Brachycephalus curupira* Ribeiro et al., 2017. (“... The specific epithet ... refers to the homonymous mythical character in Brazilian folklore whose aim is to protect the forests ...”).

cururu: T. *cururu*, toad. (1) *Pipa cururu* Spix, 1824. (?). Also *Pipa curururu* — Spix, 1824 (variant spelling.). *Bufo (Pipa) curururu* — Cuvier, 1829. In the synonymy of *Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Proceratophrys cururu* Eterovick & Sazima, 1998. (“... The name *cururu* means grunting toad in the Tupi native language and seems most appropriate for this warted, toadlike species with a moaning call ...”).

cuspidata, cuspidatus: L. *cuspidata*, -us, tip, provide with a point; make pointed. *Hyla cuspidata* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Voisine de *crospedospila*, mais plus petite & le museau encore plus pointu ...”). Also *Ololygon cuspidata* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax cuspidata* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax cuspidatus* (A. Lutz, 1925).

cuvieri: Cuvier + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jean Léopold Nicolas Frédéric, Baron of Cuvier (1769-1832), French zoologist. *Physalaemus cuvieri* Fitzinger, 1826. Also *Physalaemus cuvieri* — Jan, 1857.

cuzcanus: Cuzco, a Peruvian city and department + L. -anus, belonging to. *Chorophilus cuzcanus* Cope, 1878 “1877” (“... from the Chimbote Valley, Cuzco, Peru ...”). Also *Pseudacris (Chorophilus) cuzcanus* — B. Lutz, 1950. Suggested as an older name for *Aplastodiscus perviridis*, *fide* B. Lutz, 1968. In the synonymy of *Gastrotheca marsupiata* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

Cyclocephalus: G. *kyklos* (κύκλος), circle, ring + G. *kéfali* (κεφάλη), head. *Cyclocephalus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (?). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

Cycloramphus: G. *kyklos* (κύκλος), circle, ring + G. *rhamphos* (ραμφος), curving beak or snout. *Cycloramphus* Tschudi, 1838. (“... *Caput latum, rotundum, rictum oris latissimus* ...”). Same root in *Cycloramphidae* Bonaparte, 1850. Same root in *Cycloramphos* — Tschudi, 1838; *Cyclorhamphos* — Tschudi, 1838 and *Cyclorhamphus* — Tschudi, 1838 (alternative spellings).

cyclospinus: G. *kyklos* (κύκλος), circle, ring + L. *spina*, thorn/spine/prickle. *Crosodactylus cyclospinus* Nascimento et al., 2005. (“... The specific name refers to the circular distribution of keratinized spines on the thumb ...”).

cymbalum: L. *cymbalum*, from G. *kymbalo* (κύμβαλο), a kind of chordophone. Also *Hyla cymbalum* Bokermann, 1963. (“... El singular canto de esta especie, que nunca habíamos oído antes, nos llamó poderosamente la atención, ya que podía ser oído a más de 200 metros de distancia ...”). *Hypsiboas cymbalum* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana cymbalum* (Bokermann, 1963).

cynocephala: G. *kynos* (κυνός, from κύων), dog + G. *kephali* (κεφάλι), head. *Hyla cynocephala* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Le museau est large, coupé presque carrément au bout et relevé en deux petites éminences subhémisphériques, sur les cotés externes desquelles s’ouvrent les narines ...”). Also *Hyla cyanocephala* — Duellman, 1977 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Ololygon cynocephala* — Duellman, 1985. *Scinax cynocephalus* — Köhler & Böhme, 1996. In the synonymy of *Scinax nebulosus* (Spix, 1824).

Cystignathus: G. *cystis* (κύστις), bladder + G. *gnathos* (γνάθος), jaw. *Cystignathus* Wagler, 1830. [“... *Vesica aerea (maris) utrinque prope oris angulum nascente* ...]. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826.

dactylocinus: G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe + G. *kinisi* (κίνηση), movement. *Hylodes dactylocinus* Pavan et al., 2001. (“... in allusion to the conspicuous behavior of this frog, which characteristically moves its toes in an alternating and oscillatory way during intraspecific displays ...”).

dantasi: Dantas + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Edison de Souza Dantas (?), Bokermann assistant in Tarauacá, State of Acre, Brazil. *Leptodactylus dantasi* Bokermann, 1959. Today *Hydrolaetare dantasi* (Bokermann, 1959).

dantei: Dante + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Dante Luiz Martins Teixeira, Brazilian ornithologist. *Crossodactylus dantei* Carcerelli & Caramaschi, 1993.

dapsilis: L. *dapsilis*, sumptuous, plentiful, abundant; richly provided with everything. *Bufo dapsilis* Myers & Carvalho, 1945. (“... It is almost impossible to imagine the distinctiveness of this remarkable toad without having the specimen in hand and actually passing the fingers over the strange, soft, head structures ...”). Today *Rhinella dapsilis* (Myers & Carvalho, 1945).

darkside: E. dark + E. side, used as a noun in apposition. *Brachycephalus darkside* Guimarães et al., 2017. [“... It refers to the dark side of the body (...) which corresponds to the dark tissue surrounding the dorsal musculature, creating a dark background to the bright yellow-orange dorsum (...). It is also a reference to the album “The Dark Side of the Moon” by the British rock band Pink Floyd ...”].

darwinii: Darwin + L. *-ii*, suffix that indicates the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Charles Robert Darwin (1809-1882), British naturalist. *Pleurodema darwinii* Bell, 1843. Also *Paludicola darwinii* — Boulenger, 1882. In the synonymy of *Pleurodema bibroni* Tschudi, 1838.

dasynotus: G. *dasys* (δασύς), covered with a rough growth + G. *notos* (νοτός), back, dorsum. *Hyla dasynotus* Günther, 1869 "1868". (“... The skin from the occiput along the spine to the sacral vertebra is immovable and covered with warty excrescences ...”). Also *Güntheria dasynota* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus seniculus* (Cope, 1868).

Dasypops: G. *dasys* (δασύς), hoarse, rough; with a shaggy surface + G. *pous* (πούς), foot. *Dasypops* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1924. (“... *manibus fossoriis, digitis fossoriis, sub-fimbriatis, coriaceis, brevibus, pedibus bufoninis* ...”).

daudini: Daudin + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring François Marie Daudin (1776-1803), French zoologist. (1) *Ceratophrys daudini* Cuvier, 1829 (*nomen nudum*). In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys cornuta* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Dendrobates tinctorius* var.

daudini Steindachner, 1864. In the synonymy of *Dendrobates tinctorius* (Cuvier, 1797). (3) *Hyla daudini* B. Lutz, 1973. In the synonymy of *Boana boans* (Linnaeus, 1758).

davori: Davor + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Davor Vrcibradic, Brazilian herpetologist. *Dendrophryniscus davori* Cruz et al., 2019.

decipiens: L. *decipio*, cheat, deceive, mislead. *Hyla decipiens* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Cette espèce ressemble un peu à de jeunes exemplaires de *Hyla leucophyllata*, mais se distingue par les caractères de *Hylella* ...”). Today *Dendrosophus decipiens* (A. Lutz, 1925).

defleri: Defler + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Thomas Richard Defler, US American primatologist. *Ranitomeya defleri* Twomey & Brown, 2009. Also *Dendrobates defleri* — Santos et al., 2009.

deimaticus: G. *deimatóō* (δειματόω), frighten, terrify + L. *-icus*, suffix indicating having the nature of, quality of, state or condition of. *Physalaemus deimaticus* Sazima & Caramaschi, 1988. (“... O nome da nova espécie é derivado da palavra grega *deimos*, que significa medo, sendo dado em alusão à exibição, presumivelmente assustadora, adotada pelo animal quando perturbado por um predador potencial ...”).

delattini: de Lattin + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Gustaf de Lattin (1913-1968), German zoologist. *Leptodactylus gracilis delattini* Müller, 1968. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus gracilis* (Duméril & Bibron, 1840).

delicatissima: L. *delicatissimus*, delicate/dainty/pretty/fine. *Cochranella delicatissima* Taylor & Cochran, 1953. (?). Also *Centrolenella delicatissima* — Duellman, 1977. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana eurygnatha* (A. Lutz, 1925).

delius: (?). Delius, noun in apposition. Honouring Carlos Enrique Delius Evers, Bolivian petroleum engineer. *Eleutherodactylus delius* Duellman & Mendelson, 1995. (“... his name is associated with this distinctive species in

grateful appreciation for the extensive logistic support provided by his company ...”). Today *Pristimantis delius* (Duellman & Mendelson, 1995).

Dendrobates: *G. dendros* (δένδρος), a tree + *G. bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (in turn, from βαίνω, move by taking step). *Dendrobates* Wagler, 1830 (“... Δένδρος arbor, et βαίνω incedo ...”). The same root in *Dendrobatidae* Cope, 1865 and *Dendrobatinae* Cope, 1865 (1850).

Dendromedusa: *G. dendros* (δένδρος), a tree + *G. medeon* (μεδέων), *medeou-sa* (μεδέουσα), ruling, holding. *Dendromedusa* Gistel, 1848 [replacement name for *Hylaplesia* Boie, 1827 (= *Hysaplesia* Boie, 1826)]. (?). In the synonymy of *Dendrobates* Wagler, 1830.

Dendrophryniscus: *G. dendros* (δένδρος), a tree + *G. phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. + *G. -ikos* (-ίκος), looking like, belonging to. *Dendrophryniscus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. (?).

Dendropsophus: *G. dendros* (δένδρος), a tree + *G. psophos* (ψοφος), sound. *Dendropsophus* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). The same root in *Dendropsophinae* Fitzinger, 1843.

dengleri: Dengler + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hermann Dengler (1890-1945), German draftman and ethnographer. *Leptodactylus pentadactylus dengleri* Melin, 1941. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768).

dentei: Dente + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Emílio Dente (1919-1995), Brazilian collector and taxidermist. *Hyla dentei* Bokermann, 1967. Also *Hypsiboas dentei* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana dentei* (Bokermann, 1967).

depressa: L. *depressa*, flattened. (1) *Hyla depressa* Andersson, 1945. (“... Head and body very depressed ...”). In the synonymy of *Osteocephalus taurinus* Steindachner, 1862. (2) *Hyla depressa* Izecksohn, 1959 (error for *Hyla truncata* in the summary). (“... Corpo alongado, deprimido ...”). In the synonymy of *Xenohyla truncata* (Izecksohn, 1959).

depressiceps: L. *depressa*, flattened + L. *-ceps*, -headed. *Hyla depressiceps* Boulenger, 1882. (“... Head much depressed, as long as broad ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax funereus* (Cope, 1874).

deridens: L. *deridens*, mock/deride/laugh at/make fun of. *Osteocephalus deridens* Jungfer et al., 2000. [“... The specific name is the present participle of the Latin *deridere* (make fun of someone) in allusion to the males’ calls from the treetops that sound as if they are laughing at the collectors’ vain attempts to reach them ...”].

Dermatonotus: G. *dermatos* (δέρματος), skin + G. *notos* (νοτος), back, dorsum. *Dermatonotus* Méhely, 1904. (No clues in the generic description, but in that of *D. muelleri*, the type – and only species of the genus, “... Skin smooth, on the back strongly thickened, leatherlike, porous ...”).

devincenzii: Devincenzi + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Garibaldi José Devincenzi (1882-1943), Uruguayan zoologist. *Melanophryniscus devincenzii* Klappenbach, 1968.

diabolica, diabolicus: L. *diabolica*, *-us*, devilish/diabolic; characteristic of/proceeding/derived from the devil. *Hypsiboas diabolicus* Fouquet et al., 2016. (“... The specific name ... refers to the “Diables Rouges” (Red Devils), traditional characters of the carnival in French Guiana who dress in red and black, reminiscent of the black flanks and the carmine/crimson legs and webbing of the new species ...”). Today *Boana diabolica* (Fouquet et al., 2016).

diadematus: L. *diadematus*, crowned; wearing a diadem; adorned w/diadem. *Hylodes diadematus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (?). Also *Eleutherodactylus diadematus* — Stejneger, 1904. Today *Pristimantis diadematus* (Jiménez de la Espada, 1875).

diamantina: P. [Chapada] Diamantina, a plateau in central state of Bahia, Brazil. *Bokermannohyla diamantina* Napoli & Juncá, 2006. (“... The specific name ... refers to the Chapada Diamantina, the region in the State of Bahia in which is located the type locality of the new species ...”).

dibernardoii: Di-Bernardo + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Marcos Di-Bernardo (1963-2006), Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Proceratophrys dibernardoii* Brandão et al., 2013. (2) *Trachycephalus dibernardoii* Kwet & Solé, 2008.

didactyla, didactylus: G. *dyo* (δύο), two + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Psyllophryne didactyla* Izecksohn, 1971. (“... 1^o e 4^o dedos vestigiais; reduzidos a calos. 2^o dedo pequeno e 3^o mais longo e espesso. Extremidades do 2^o e 3^o dedos cônicas ...”). Today *Brachycephalus didactylus* (Izecksohn, 1971).

didymus: G. *didymus* (δίδυμος), (of persons) born as a twin, twin. *Leptodactylus didymus* Heyer et al., 1996. (“... From the Greek *didymos*, double or twin, referring to the morphological similarity between this species and *L. mystaceus* ...”).

diedrus: G. *di-edreíá* (δι-εδρεΐά), sitting apart, separate perching (of birds, seen as an unfavourable omen). *Leptodactylus diedrus* Heyer, 1994. (“... From the Greek *diedros*, sitting apart, separated, in allusion to the distinctiveness of this species within the *L. podicipinus-wagneri* cluster ...”).

diploister: G. *diplo* (διπλο), double + G. *listron* (λίστρον), implement for working soil; spade or hoe. *Cystignathus diploistris* Peters, 1870. (“... mit kurzem Fingern und Zehen, beide Mittelfufshöcker schneidend und grösser ...”). Also *Paludicola diploistris* — Boulenger, 1882. *Pleurodema diploistris* — Nieden, 1923. *Pleurodema diploistre* — Duellman, 1993. Today *Pleurodema diploister* (Peters, 1870).

diptycha, diptyx: G. *dyo* (δύο), two+ G. *ptychos* (πτύχως), fold, or G. *ptychi* (πτυχή), cromptle, crease. (1) *Leptodactylus diptyx* Boettger, 1885. (“... *Tergum plicis glandulosus longitudinalibus instructum ... plica glandulosa lateralis distincta* ...”). Also *Leptodactylus diptix* — Peracca, 1895 (incorrect subsequent spelling). Today *Adenomera diptyx* (Boettger, 1885). (2) *Bufo diptychus* Cope, 1862. (“... Paratoids beginning behind upper margin of tympanum, divergent, trilateral, extending posterior to the axilla, and continuous with a lateral dermal fold ...”). Also *Chaunus diptychus* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella diptycha* (Cope, 1862).

diringshofeni: Diringshofen + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ricardo von Diringshofen (1900-1986), Brazilian entomologist. *Cycloramphus diringshofeni* Bokermann, 1957.

discodactylus: G. *disco* (δίσκο), disk + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Leptodactylus discodactylus* Boulenger, 1884. (“... tips of fingers and toes dilated into small disks ...”). Also *Vanzolinius discodactylus* — Heyer, 1974.

discolor: L. *discolor*, another color, not of the same color; variegated. *Cystignathus discolor* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... Farven er paa Rygsiden lys askegraa med ubestemt mdrkere Tegning ...”). Also *Leptodactylus discolor* — Boulenger, 1882. In the synonymy of *Thoropa miliaris* (Spix, 1824).

dispar: L. *dispar*, unequal, unlike. *Crossodactylus dispar* A. Lutz, 1925. (?). Perhaps due to the presence of three horny spots on the first finger of males and females. Also *Crossodactylus dispar dispar* — B. Lutz, 1951.

distincta, distinctus: L. *distincta*, separate, distinct; definite. (1) *Cyclorhamphus distinctus* A. Lutz, 1932. (“... Lembra o *asper* Werner, mas distingue-se facilmente pela formação do pé, a pigmentação do lado ventral e outros caracteres; do *granulosus* de Lutz difere pela fôrma do pé e da mão ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus ohausi* (Wandolleck, 1907). (2) *Phyllomedusa distincta* A. Lutz in B. Lutz, 1950. (“... Esta *Phyllomedusa* foi estudada inicialmente pelo Professor Lutz em 1924 e 1928. Anotou os caracteres diagnósticos, deu-lhe o nome de *distincta* e mandou aquarelar o espécime de 1928 que chegou de Corupá recém-morto ...”). Also *Phyllomedusa (Pithecopus) burmeisteri distincta* — B. Lutz, 1950. *Pithecopus burmeisteri distincta* — B. Lutz, 1966. *Pithecopus distincta* — Laurent, 1967.

divaricans, divaricatus: L. *divaricans*, *-atus*, stretch apart, spread out. (1) *Cochranella divaricans* Taylor & Cochran, 1953. (?). Also *Centrolenella divaricans* — Duellman, 1977. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana eurygnatha* (A. Lutz, 1925). (2) *Hemiphractus divaricatus* Cope, 1868. (?). In the synonymy of *Hemiphractus scutatus* (Spix, 1824).

divisa: L. *divisus*, divide; separate, break up. *Elosia divisa* Wandolleck, 1907. (“... Die Scheiben sind am Vorderrande durch eine horizontale Kerbe je in eine

obere und eine untere Scheibe zerlegt, die obere Scheibe ist tief ausgekerbt, wodurch sie zweilappig wird ...”). In the synonymy of *Ischnocnema guentheri* (Steindachner, 1864).

Docidophryne: *G. dokidos* (δοκίδος), stick, twig + *G. phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Docidophryne* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

dolloi: Dollo + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Louis Antoine Marie Joseph Dollo (1857-1931), French-Belgian paleontologist. *Hyla dolloi* Werner, 1903. Today *Scinax dolloi* (Werner, 1903).

dorbignyi: D’Orbigny + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alcide Charles Victor Marie Dessalines d’Orbigny (1802-1857), French naturalist. *Bufo d’Orbignyi* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. Also *Chilophryne d’orbignyi* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Bufo orbignyi* — Bibron in d’Orbigny & Bibron, 1847. *Bufo d’orbignyi* — Günther, 1859 “1858”. *Phrynoidis d’orbignyi* — Cope, 1863. *Bufo dorbignyi* — Cope, 1885 “1884”. *Bufo globulosus d’orbignyi* — Parker, 1935. *Bufo granulatus d’orbignyi* — Müller & Hellmich, 1936. *Chaunus dorbignyi* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella dorbignyi* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

dorisae: Doris + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Doris Mable Cochran (1898-1968), US American herpetologist. *Sphoerohyla dorisae* Goin, 1957. Also *Dryomelictes dorisae* — Goin, 1961. *Hyla dorisae* — Gorham, 1963. Today *Sphaenorhynchus dorisae* (Goin, 1957).

dorsalis: L. *dorsalis*, pertaining to a dorsum or back. (1) *Bufo dorsalis* Spix, 1824. (“... *dorsum planiusculum, medio longitudinaliter usque ad anum fulvo-lineatum* ...”). Also *Bufo lentiginosus dorsalis* — Garman, 1884. In the synonymy of *Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Caecilia dorsalis* Peters, 1877. (“... Auf dem Hinterrücken beginnt eine niedrige Längswulst, welche sich in das zusammengedrückte Schwanzrudiment fortsetzt, welches die Afteröffnung um 2 Mm. überragt ...”). Also *Typhlonectes dorsalis* — Peters, 1880 “1879”. In the synonymy of *Potomotyphlus kaupii* (Berthold,

1859). (3) *Dendrophryniscus stelzneri dorsalis* Mertens, 1933. (“... keine hellen Flecken auf dem Rücken, aber häufig ein roter Dorsal-streifen auf der Mittellinie ...”). Also *Melanophryniscus stelzneri dorsalis* — Gallardo, 1961. Today *Melanophryniscus dorsalis* (Mertens, 1933).

dorsata: L. *dorsata*, having, having a, provided with a dorsum or back. *Ceratophrys dorsata* Wied-Neuwied, 1825. (“... mehrere schwarzbraune warzige Hautkämme auf dem Oberkörper, welche den Mittelstreif des Rückens einfassen ...”). Also *Stombus dorsatus* — Gravenhorst, 1829. *Ceratophryne dorsata* — Schlegel, 1858. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys aurita* (Raddi, 1823).

dorsigera: L. *dorsi*, back + L. *gera*, bear, carry, wear; carry on. *Rana dorsigera* Schneider, 1799. (“... ubi ova, cellulis dorsi suis quaeque recepta ...”). Also *Bufo dorsiger* — Latreille in Sonnini de Manoncourt & Latreille, 1801 “An. X”. *Pipa dorsigera* — Oken, 1816. *Pipa dorsigerus* — Gistel in Gistel & Bromme, 1850. *Asterodactylus dorsigera* — Gistel, 1851. *Asterodactylus dorsiger* — Fitzinger, 1864. In the synonymy of *Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

doumercii: Doumerc + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Adolphe-Jacques-Louis Doumerc (1802-1868), French naturalist. *Hyla doumercii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. Also *Hypsiboas doumericii* — Cope, 1867. In the synonymy of *Boana xerophylla* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

dryade: G. *Dryados* (δρυάδος), tree nymphs, inhabitant of trees. Additionally, phyto-geographic region corresponding to the Atlantic Coastal Forest according to Martius et al. (1824) (see *Pithecopus oreades*). *Phrynomedusa dryade* Baêta et al., 2016. (“... The name of this new species refers to the occurrence of this beautiful Monkey Frog in the Atlantic Forest Domain ...”).

Dryaderces: G. *dryas* (δρύας), oak; by extension, tree + G. *aderktos* (ἀ-δερκτος), sightless, blind. *Dryaderces* Jungfer et al., 2013. (“... A noun of feminine gender derived from Ancient Greek *dryad* (tree) and *aderces* (unseen, invisible) in the sense of ‘unseen in a tree’ ...”).

Dryomelictes: G. *dryos* (δρυος), oak, tree + Gr. *meliktes* (μελικτες), flute player. *Dryomelictes* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). Also *Dryomelictes* Cope, 1865 (preoccu-

pied by *Dryomelictes* Fitzinger, 1843). In the synonymy of *Sphaenorhynchus* Tschudi, 1838.

duartei: Duarte + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Wanderbilt Duarte de Barros (1916-1997), Brazilian botanist. *Hyla rubra duartei* B. Lutz, 1951. Also *Hyla duartei* — Bokermann, 1966. *Ololygon duartei* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax duartei* (B. Lutz, 1951).

dubia, dubium, dubius: L. *dubium*, doubtful, dubious, uncertain; variable. (1) *Brasilotyphlus dubium* Correia et al., 2018. (“... The epithet *dubium* means “dubious”, reflecting our doubt whether or not *Brasilotyphlus* should be considered a synonym of *Microcaecilia* ...”). (2) *Cochranella dubia* Taylor & Cochran, 1953. (?). Also *Centrolenella dubia* — Duellman, 1977. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana uranoscopa* (Müller, 1924). (3) *Iliodiscus dubius* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... Pelle rugosa, laxa, às vezes de aspecto escamoso, às vezes recoberta de verrugas maiores, óra simples, óra providas ainda de concreções margaritoides externas, em toda a face superior ou às vezes deixando lisas as extremidades. Na inferior óra é lizo só o meio do peito, braços e côxas, óra também o são as extremidades como todo esse lado inferior, desde o papo ...”). Also *Grypiscus dubius* — Barbour, 1925. Today *Cycloramphus dubius* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

dumerili: Duméril + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring André Marie Constant Duméril (1774-1860), French herpetologist. *Engystoma dumerili* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926 (substitute name for *Engystoma microps*). In the synonymy of *Myersiella microps* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

dundeei: Dundee + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Harold Abraham Dundee (1924-2018), US American herpetologist. *Eleutherodactylus dundeei* Heyer & Muñoz, 1999. Today *Pristimantis dundeei* (Heyer & Muñoz, 1999).

duseni: Dusén + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Per Dusén (1855-1926), Swedish naturalist. *Telmatobius duseni* Andersson, 1914. Today *Cycloramphus duseni* (Andersson, 1914).

dutrai: Dutra + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Alfredo Pinheiro Dutra, Brazilian entomologist. *Hyla dutrai* Gomes & Peixoto, 1996. Today *Dendropsophus dutrai* (Gomes & Peixoto, 1996).

eccentricum: L. *ex-*, out of + L. *centrum*, center (circle/sphere/earth). *Hyalinobatrachium eccentricum* Myers & Donnelly, 2001. (“... The species name is a Latin adjective meaning “not concentric”, in allusion to the unconventional elliptical to domelike shape of the median part of the iris ...”). In the synonymy of *Hyalinobatrachium cappellei* (van Lidth de Jeude, 1904).

ecuadorensis: Ecuador, South American country (from L. *aequare*, to make equal, equalize) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Rhaebo ecuadorensis* Mueses-Cisneros et al., 2012. (“... The specific name of this new species is proposed to honour the Republic of Ecuador, as a tribute to its people and natural diversity ...”).

Edalorhina: G. *oidaleos* (οἰδαλέος), swollen, bursting + G. *rhis* (ῥίς), nose. *Edalorhina* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. (“... *Caput parvum, productum, compressum, rostro simato ...*”).

edelmoi: Edelmo + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Edelmo de Melo Gonçalves, Brazilian herpetologist. *Phyllodytes edelmoi* Peixoto et al., 2003.

edentula: L. *edentula*, toothless. (1) *Paludicola edentula* Boettger, 1885. (“... *dentibus vomerinis nullis ...*”). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus nattereri* (Steindachner, 1863). (2) *Phyllomedusa edentula* Andersson, 1945. (“... No vomerine teeth but a low transverse bony ridge behind each choana ...”). In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa tarsius* (Cope, 1868).

egleri: Egler + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Walter Alberto Egler (1924-1961), Brazilian botanist and geographer. *Hyla egleri* B. Lutz, 1968. Also *Ololygon egleri* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. In the synonymy of *Scinax nebulosus* (Spix, 1824).

- ehrharti***: Ehrhardt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Wilhelm Ehrhardt (1860-1936?), German collector and taxidermist. *Hyla ehrhardti* Müller, 1924. Also *Ololygon ehrhardti* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax ehrhardti* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Aplastodiscus ehrhardti* (Müller, 1924).
- eiselti***: Eiselt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Josef Eiselt (1912-2001), Austrian herpetologist. *Typhlonectes eiselti* Taylor, 1968. Today *Atretochoana eiselti* (Taylor, 1968).
- Elachistocleis***: G. *elachistos* (ελάχιστος), the smallest + G. *kleis* (κλείς), collar-bone. *Elachistocleis* Parker, 1927. (“... differs from the type species of *Gastrophryne* in the possession of a pair of clavicles ... These are very small and the shoulder girdle may be regarded as being intermediate between that of *Chiasmocleis* ... and *Gastrophryne* ...”).
- Eladinea***: Eladio + L. *-inea*, related to. Honouring Eladio da Cruz Lima (1900-1943), Brazilian lawyer, painter, and archaeologist, co-collector of the original clutch. *Eladinea* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. In the synonymy of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854.
- elegans***: L. *elegans*, elegant, fine, handsome. (1) *Hyla elegans* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. (“... Eingefasster Laubkleber ...”). Also *Hyla elegans* — Caramaschi & Jim, 1982. Today *Dendropsophus elegans* (Wied-Neuwied, 1824). (2) *Pleurodema elegans* Steindachner, 1863. (“... Die Totalgestalt ist stark gedrungen, der Kopf kurz, die Schnauze stumpf abgerundet und fast vertical zum oberen Mundrande abfallend ...”). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema brachyops* (Cope, 1869).
- elena***: Elena + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Elena Heyer, W. Ronald Heyer’s daughter. *Leptodactylus elenae* Heyer, 1978.
- eleutherodactylus***: G. *eleutheros* (ελεύθερος), free + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. (1) *Iliodiscus eleutherodactylus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... Os artelhos não deixam perceber sequer vestígios de membranas ...”). Also *Grypiscus eleutherodactylus* — Barbour, 1925. Today *Cycloramphus eleutherodactylus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920). (2) *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril

& Bibron, 1841. (“... Les Hylodes ont les mains & les pieds complètement dépourvus de palmure, caractère qui, joint à celui de l’existence de dents, non sur le vomer, mais sur les os palatins, les fait aisément reconnaître entre les genres qui précèdent & ceux qui suivent immédiatement ...”). Same root in Eleutherodactylidae: Eleutherodactylinae B. Lutz, 1954.

elianeae: Eliane + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Eliane de Freitas Napoli, the senior author’s wife. *Hyla elianeae* Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999. Today *Dendropsophus elianeae* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 2000).

elongata: L. *elongatus*, prolonged. *Hyla elongata* A. Lutz, 1925. (?). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus rubicundulus* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

Elosia: G. *elos* (ἔλος), marsh or marshland + G. *-ias* (-ιας), having the nature of. *Elosia* Tschudi, 1838. (?). Also *Elesia* — Brazil & Vellard, 1926 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Hylodes* Fitzinger, 1826 and *Ischnocnema* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 (*part.*).

emrichi: Emrich + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring M. Emrich (?), from Porto Alegre, collector of the type. *Hyla emrichi* Mertens, 1927. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus minutus* (Peters, 1872).

Emydops: G. *emydos* (ἐμύδος), fresh-water tortoise + G. *-opsis* (-ὄψης), suffix denoting likeness. *Emydops* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920 (preoccupied by *Emydops* Broom, 1912, an extinct genus of dicynodont therapsid from the Permian of South Africa). (“... Corpo de contorno obvoide, deprimido ...”). In the synonymy of *Stereocyclops* Cope, 1870.

engelsi: Engels + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Wolf Engels (1935-2021), German biologist. *Adenomera engelsi* Kwet et al., 2009. Also *Leptodactylus engelsi* — Angulo and Icochea, 2010.

Engystoma: G. *engys* (ἐγγύς), come near or close + G. *stoma* (στόμα), mouth. *Engystoma* Fitzinger, 1826. (“... *Rictus angustus* ...”). In this context, partially in the synonymy of *Chiasmocleis*, *Elachistocleis*, *Myersiella*, and other

microhylid genera. In the synonymy of *Breviceps* Merrem, 1920 *vide* Segalla et al. (2021).

Engystomops: *G. engys* (ἐγγύς), nearby, close at hand + *G. stoma* (στόμα), mouth + *G. ops* (οψ), eye. *Engystomops* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872. (? “...cabeza corta ... boca pequeña; ojos regulares...”).

ensenadensis: S. Ensenada, locality in Buenos Aires province, Argentina; also, a South American mammal age + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ceratophrys ensinadensis* Rusconi, 1932. (“... Olivos provincia de Buenos Aires, piso ensinadense, plioceno superior ...”). In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys ornata* (Bell, 1843).

Entomoglossus: *G. entomi* (ἐντομή), cutting into, hewing + *G. glossa* (γλώσσα), tongue. *Entomoglossus* Peters, 1870. (“... Zunge hinten ausgeschnitten ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826.

Enydrobius: *G. enydrobios* (ἐνῦδροβίος), the one who lives in the water. *Enydrobius* Wagler, 1830 (“...*qui in aqua vivit*...”). Substitute name for *Hylodes* Fitzinger, 1826. In the synonymy of *Hylodes* Fitzinger, 1826.

Eotheca: *G. eos* (ἠώς), dawn or sunrise; east + *G. theke* (θήκη), storage-container, chest. *Eotheca* Duellman, 2015. (“... The name is derived from the Greek *eos*, meaning “early,” and the Greek *theke*, meaning “container”. The name refers to the basal position of this clade of *Gastrotheca* ...”).

epacrorrhina: *G. epakros* (ἔπακρος), pointed at the end + *G. rhinos* (ῥινόσ), nose, snout. *Hyla epacrorrhina* Duellman, 1972. (“... the name *epacrorrhina* alludes to the pointed fleshy tip to the snout ...”). Also *Ololygon epachrorrhina* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax epacrorrhina* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. In the synonymy of *Scinax garbei* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

ephippifer, ephippium: L. *ephippi(i)*, pad saddle, horse blanket (to ride on), from *G. ephippios* (ἐφ-ἵππιος), (of a cloth) for a horse’s back. (1) *Bufo ephippium* Spix, 1824. (“... *fascia dorsi medii nigra, larga, ephippio similis* ...”). Today *Brachycephalus ephippium* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Leiuperus ephippifer* Steindachner, 1864. (the “saddle” probably refers to the space

limited by the elongated dorsolateral glands “... zwei bis sechs erhabene drüsige, mehr oder minder deutlich ausgeprägte Längenfalten auf der Oberseite des Körpers ...”). Also *Physolaemus ephippiger* Jan, 1857 (*nomen nudum*). *Gomphobates ephippifer* — Günther, 1865. Today *Physalaemus ephippifer* (Steindachner, 1864).

Ephippipher: L. *ephippium*, pad saddle, horse blanket (to ride on), from G. *ephippios* (ἐφ-ἵππιος), (of a cloth) for a horse’s back. *Ephippipher* Cocteau, 1835. (?). Also *Ephippifer* — Agassiz, 1845 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Brachycephalus* Fitzinger, 1826.

epipeda, epipedus: G. *epipedos* (ἐπί-πεδος), surface (of the earth, opp. what is below it). *Eleutherodactylus epipedus* Heyer, 1984. (“... in allusion to the species most commonly being collected from the forest floor ...”). Today *Ischnocnema epipeda* (Heyer, 1984).

Epipedobates: G. *epipedos* (ἐπί-πεδος), surface (of the earth, opp. what is below it) + G. *bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (from βαίνω, move by taking step). *Epipedobates* Myers, 1987. (“... in reference to the primarily terrestrial nature of most species ...”).

Epirhexis: G. *ipeiros* (ἡπειρος), land, mainland + G. *hexis* (ἔξις), state of having, possession, habit, practice. *Epirhexis* Cope, 1866. (?). In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

ericae: Erica + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Érica Maria Pellegrini Caramaschi, Brazilian ichthyologist. *Hyla ericae* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2000. Also *Hypsiboas ericae* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana ericae* (Caramaschi & Cruz, 2000).

erikae: Erika + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Érika Costa Elias, authors’ friend and assistant. *Physalaemus erikae* Cruz & Pimenta, 2004.

eringiophila: L. *Eryngium*, genus of Apiaceae (Umbelliferae) + G. *philos* (φίλος), friend. *Hyla strigilata eringiophila* Gallardo, 1961. [“... Este nombre se debe a la costumbre que tienen diversas ranas del género *Hyla*, de vivir en-

tre las hojas de las varias especies de *Eringium* (*sic*), en la zona antes indicada ...”]. Also *Hyla eringiophila* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Hyla x-signata eringiophila* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Oloolygon x-signata eringiophila* — Gudynas, 1983. *Oloolygon eringiophila* — Gudynas & Rudolf, 1987. *Scinax eringhiophila* — Langone & Cardoso, 1997. In the synonymy of *Scinax granulatus* (Peters, 1871).

ernestoi: Ernesto + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ernst Wilhelm Garbe (1853-1925), German naturalist. *Gastrotheca ernestoi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. Also *Gastrotheca* (*Opisthodelphys*) *ernestoi* — Dubois, 1987 “1986”. *Gastrotheca* (*Australotheca*) *ernestoi* — Duellman, 2015. *Gastrotheca* (*Alainia*) *ernestoi* — Duellman & Cannatella, 2018. Today *Alainia ernestoi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

erugatum: L. *erugatum*, take wrinkles/creases from. *Chthonerpeton erugatum* Taylor, 1968. (“... Conspicuous skin glands of two sorts, the larger ones often somewhat elevated and causing the surface to appear slightly granular ...”). In the synonymy of *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

erythrogaster: G. *erythros* (έρυθρός), red + G. *gastir* (γαστήρ), abdomen. *Elachistocleis erythrogaster* Kwet & Di-Bernardo, 1998. (“... in reference to the distinct red-orange coloration of the venter ...”). Also *Engystoma erythrogaster* — Dubois et al., 2021.

erythromera, erythromerus: G. *erythros* (έρυθρός), red + G. *meros* (μηρός), thigh. *Eleutherodactylus erythromerus* Heyer, 1984. (“... signalling the distinctive red thighs characteristic of this species in life ...”). Today *Ischnocnema erythromera* (Heyer, 1984).

erythrophthalmus: G. *erythros* (έρυθρός), red + G. *ophthalmos* (οφθαλμός), eye. *Frostius erythrophthalmus* Pimenta & Caramaschi, 2007. (“... iris red in life ...”).

erythros: G. *erythros* (έρυθρός), red. *Physalaemus erythros* Caramaschi et al., 2003. (“... used in reference to the remarkably bright ventral color pattern of the species ...”).

estheri: Esther + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Esther Cruz Lima (?), co-collector of the original clutch. *Eladinea estheri* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. In the synonymy of *Bolitoglossa paraensis* (Unterstein, 1930).

Eubaphus: G. *eu* (εὐ), complete, true + G. *bapheus* (βαφεύς), dyer. *Eubaphus* Bonaparte, 1831. (?). An allusion to the specific epithet of its type species (by monotypy), *Rana tinctoria* Shaw. In the synonymy of *Dendrobates* Wagler, 1830.

eucharis: G. *eu-charis* (εὐ-χαρίς), (of persons, their way of thinking, social behaviour) charming, gracious; (of a place) pleasing, attractive. *Boana eu-charis* Fouquet et al., 2021. (“... The specific epithet is derived from the Greek word *eukharis*, which means gracious or charismatic, as a reference to the delicate and gracious aspect of the species ...”).

eucnemis: G. *eu* (εὐ), complete, true + G. *cnimi* (κνήμη), lower part of the leg, shin. *Dendrobates eucnemis* Steindachner, 1864. (“... Auf der oberen Seite der Wurzel des Schenkels liegt ein fast viereckiger, und auf der hinteren Seite desselben, bis an das Knie reichend, ein länglicher Fleck von orangerother Farbe ...”). Also *Dendrobates pictus eucnemis* — B. Lutz, 1952. In the synonymy of *Ameerega picta* (Bibron in Tschudi, 1838).

eugenioi: Eugenio + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Eugenio Izecksohn (1932-2013), Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Hyla eugenioi* A. Carvalho-e-Silva & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2005. Today *Aplastodiscus eugenioi* (A. Carvalho-e-Silva & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2005). (2) *Xenohyla eugenioi* Caramaschi, 1998.

Euhyas: *Euhyas*, G. *eu* (εὐ), complete, true + G. *ylas* (υλάς), thick vegetation (esp. assoc. w. mountains). *Euhyas* Fitzinger, 1843. In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841 and *Ischnocnema* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 (*part.*).

Euparkerella: G. *eu-* (εὐ-), complete, true, original + Parker [Hampton Wildman Parker (1897-1968), English herpetologist] + L. *-ella*, suffix diminutive. *Euparkerella* Griffiths, 1959. (?).

- Eupemphix:** G. *eu-* (ευ-), complete, true, original + G. *pompholix* (πομφόλυξ), (ref. to the songs of frogs) bubbly splutterings. *Eupemphix* Steindachner, 1863. (?). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus* Fitzinger, 1826.
- Eupomplyx:** G. *eu-* (ευ-), complete, true, original + G. *pompholix* (πομφόλυξ), (ref. to the songs of frogs) bubbly splutterings. *Eupomplyx* Jan, 1857 (*nomen nudum*). (?). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838.
- Eupsophus:** G. *eu-* (ευ-), complete, true, original + G. *psophos* (ψόφος), noise, sound, resound. *Eupsophus* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). Genus today restricted to the S of Argentina and Chile, although various Brazilian species of the genera *Ischnocnema*, *Thoropa*, *Cycloramphus*, etc. were once included in it.
- Eurhina:** G. *eu-* (ευ-), complete, true, original + G. *rhinos* (ῥινός), nose, snout. *Eurhina* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.
- eurhostus:** G. *eurhostos* (εὐ-ρωστος), strong, robust, vigorous, stout. *Sphaenorhynchus eurhostus* Rivero, 1969. (“... *S. eurhostus* is probably the largest and the most fully webbed species in the genus ...”). In the synonymy of *Sphaenorhynchus lacteus* (Daudin, 1800).
- eurydactylus:** G. *eurys* (ευρύς), broad, wide, far-reaching + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Eleutherodactylus (Eleutherodactylus) eurydactylus* Hedges & Schlüter, 1992. (“... in allusion to the greatly expanded digital tips of this species ...”). Today *Pristimantis eurydactylus* (Hedges & Schlüter, 1992).
- eurydice:** G. *Eurydice* (Εὐρυδίκη), the wife of Orpheus in Greek mythology. *Hyla eurydice* Bokermann, 1968. (?). Also *Ololygon eurydice* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax eurydice* (Bokermann, 1968).
- eurygnatha:** G. *eurys* (ευρύς), broad, wide, far-reaching + G. *gnathos* (γνάθος), jaw. *Hyla (Hylella) eurygnatha* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Tête courte, élargie derrière les yeux, ce qui est dû à la largeur de la mandibule ...”). Also *Centrolenella eurygnatha* — B. Lutz, 1947. *Cochranella eurygnatha* — Taylor & Cochran, 1953. *Hyalinobatrachium eurygnathum* — Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. Today *Vitreorana eurygnatha* (A. Lutz, 1925).

evangelistai: Evangelista + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. In reference to João Evangelista da Silva (?), Brazilian zoologist. *Physalaemus evangelistai* Bokermann, 1967.

evelynae: Evelyn + L. -ae, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Evelyn Marshall Field (a. k. a. Evelyn Isabella Marshall Suarez) (1889-1979), US American philanthropist, patroness of the Brazilian Expedition of 1926. *Hyla evelynae* Schmidt, 1944. Also *Hyla squalirostris evelynae* — Klappenbach in Klappenbach & Orejas-Miranda, 1969. In the synonymy of *Scinax squalirostris* (A. Lutz, 1925).

exanthematicus: G. *exantheo* (ἐξ-ανθέω), an eruption or blister of the skin + G. -ico (-ίζω), suffix indicating condition of. (?). *Phyllobius exanthematicus* Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. Also *Hyla exanthematica* — Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. In the synonymy of *Boana albomarginata* (Spix, 1824).

exastis: G. *exastis* (εξάστης), rough edge, fringe. *Hyla exastis* Caramaschi & Rodrigues, 2003. (“... alludes to the extensively fringed forearms, hands, feet, and anal region of the new species ...”). Also *Hypsiboas exastis* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana exastis* (Caramaschi & Rodrigues, 2003).

exiguus: L. *exiguus*, small, meager. *Ololygon exigua* Duellman, 1986. (“... The specific name is Latin meaning small ...”). Also *Scinax exigua* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax exiguus* (Duellman, 1986).

exile, exilis: L. *exile*, small, thin; poor. (1) *Chthonerpeton exile* Nussbaum & Wilkinson, 1987. (“... The name *exile* (Latin, *exilis*) refers to the relatively slender, delicate shape of the body and head ...”). (2) *Phyllomedusa exilis* Cruz, 1980. (“... *Phyllomedusa exilis* sp. n. distingue-se das demais espécies do grupo “*guttata*” ... principalmente pela magreza de seu corpo e membros ...”). Today *Phasmahyla exilis* (Cruz, 1980).

exostosica: G. *exos* (εξώς), out + G. *osto* (οστό), bone + L. -ica, pertaining/belonging to; connected with. *Rhinella exostosica* Ferrão et al., 2020. (“... reference to the strongly developed bony protrusion at the angle of the jaw of the new species ...”).

- faber:** L. *faber*, workman, artisan; smith. *Hyla faber* Wied-Neuwied, 1821. (“... Da der Abend äusserst angenehm und mondhell war, so sandte ich meine Leute aus, um Frösche von der Art des Ferreiro zu fangen, welche in den benachbarten Sümpfen ausserordentlich häufig waren ...”). Also *Hypsiboas faber* — Wagler, 1830. Today *Boana faber* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).
- facureae:** Facure + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Kátia G. Facure, Brazilian researcher. *Pseudopaludicola facureae* Andrade & Carvalho, 2013.
- faivovichi:** Faivovich + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Julián Faivovich, Argentinian herpetologist. *Scinax faivovichi* Brasileiro et al., 2007. Also *Ololygon faivovichi* — Duellman et al., 2016.
- falcipes:** L. *falcis*, sickle, scythe; pruning knife; curved blade + L. *pes*, foot. *Liuperus falcipes* Hensel, 1867. (“... Der innere Hautsaum der innersten Zehe berührt den Tarsalhöcker derselben Seite und setzt sich noch hinter diesem als starke etwas sichelförmig gekrümmte Hautleiste auf dem Tarsus fort, um ungefähr in der Mitte von dessen Länge mit einer unmerklichen Anschwellung zu endigen ...”). Also *Paludicola falcipes* — Boulenger, 1882. Today *Pseudopaludicola falcipes* (Hensel, 1867).
- fasciata, fasciatus:** L. *fasciata*, having band/strip; ribbon. (1) *Calamita fasciatus* Schneider, 1799. (“... *maculis transversis dilutioribus frontem, caput, truncum et pedes superne distinguuntibus ...*”). In the synonymy of *Boana albopunctata* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Hyla fasciata* Günther, 1858. (“... Seiten des Bauches, vordere und hintere Seite der hinteren Extremität mit abwechselnden schwarzen und weissen Querbinden ...”). Also *Hypsiboas fasciatus* — Cope, 1862. Today *Boana fasciata* (Günther, 1858). (3) *Nectocaecilia fasciata* Taylor, 1968. (?). In the synonymy of *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).
- faustoi:** Fausto + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Fausto Pires de Campos, Brazilian biologist and conservacionist. *Cycloramphus faustoi* Brasileiro et al., 2007.

- feioi:** Feio + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Renato Neves Feio, Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Hyla feioi* Napoli & Caramaschi, 2004. Also *Bokermannohyla feioi* — Faivovich et al., 2005. *Boana feioi* — Wiens et al., 2005. In the synonymy of *Bokermannohyla nanuzae* (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973). (2) *Ischnocnema feioi* Taucce et al., 2018. (3) *Physalaemus feioi* Cassini et al., 2010. (4) *Scinax feioi* Lourenço et al., 2020.
- feltoni:** Felton + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring O. C. Felton (?), collector of the type. *Phyllomedusa feltoni* Shreve, 1935. In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa vaillantii* Boulenger, 1882.
- femoralis:** L. *femoris*, thigh + L. *-alis*, related to. *Prostherapis femoralis* Boulenger, 1884 “1883”. (“... an oblique band on inner half of upper surface of femur, bright yellow ...”). Also *Phyllobates femoralis* — Barbour & Noble, 1920. *Dendrobates femoralis* — Myers et al., 1978. *Epipedobates femoralis* — Myers, 1987. Today *Allobates femoralis* (Boulenger, 1884).
- fenestratus:** L. *fenestratus*, windowed. *Hylodes fenestratus* Steindachner, 1864. (“... innere Nasenöffnungen und Oeffnungen der Eustachischen Tuben rund und von bedeutender Grösse ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus fenestratus* — Stejneger, 1904. Today *Pristimantis fenestratus* (Steindachner, 1864).
- fernandezae:** Fernandez + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Katy Marcinowsky-Fernandez (1877-1955), Argentinian embriologist. *Bufo granulatus fernandezae* Gallardo, 1957. Also *Bufo fernandezae* — Cei, 1964. *Chaunus fernandezae* — Frost et al., 2006. *Rhinella fernandezae* — Chaparro et al., 2007. In the synonymy of *Rhinella dorbignyi* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).
- fernandoi:** Fernando + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Fernando Pernambuco (?), owner of the currently Reserva Particular do Patrimônio Natural (RPPN) Vereda Grande, in the municipality of Presidente Olegário, state of Minas Gerais, Brazil. *Hyla fernandoi* Pombal & Haddad, 1993 (*nomen nudum*). In the synonymy of *Bokermannohyla ravida* (Caramaschi et al., 2001).

- ferruginus:** L. *ferruginus*, rust-colored, dun. *Brachycephalus ferruginus* Alves et al., 2006. (“... The name is used in allusion to the frog’s dorsal reddish-brown irregular markings ...”).
- fiebrigi:** Fiebrig + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Karl August Gustav Fiebrig (1869-1951), German biologist, active in Paraguay and Argentina. *Hyla fiebrigi* Ahl, 1927. In the synonymy of *Scinax acuminatus*.
- fimbriata:** L. *fimbria*, border, edge. *Phrynomedusa fimbriata* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. (“... uma fimbria branca percorre os beijos e antebraço e dedo externo ...”). Also *Phyllomedusa fimbriata* — Funkhouser, 1957.
- fissilis:** L. *fissilis*, easily split; split. It probably alludes to the need to separate this species into a different genus from those then recognized. *Coelonotus fissilis* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... O genero *Nototrema*, não pôde evidentemente conter estas duas especies conjuntamente, como tambem não pôde considerar as *N. sensu strictu*, *N. fissilis* e a especie de Boettger ...”). Also *Nototheca fissilis* — Bokermann, 1950. *Flectonotus fissilis* — Bokermann, 1966. Today *Fritziana fissilis* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).
- fissipes:** L. *fissus*, split, cleave, divide; + L. *pes*, foot. *Nototrema fissipes* Boulenger, 1888. (“... Fingers free, first longest and opposable to the others; toes short, with a very slight rudiment of web ...”). Also *Opisthodelphis fissipes* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. *Gastrotheca fissipes* — Gorham, 1963. *Gastrotheca* (*Opisthodelphys*) *fissipes* — Dubois, 1987 “1986. *Gastrotheca* (*Eothea*) *fissipes* — Duellman, 2015. Today *Eothea fissipes* (Boulenger, 1888).
- flamma:** L. *flamma*, flame, blaze. *Gastrotheca flamma* Juncá & Nunes, 2008. (“... The specific epithet *flamma* ... is a Latin substantive used in allusion to the color pattern, which resemble “fire” ...”). Also *Gastrotheca* (*Eothea*) *flamma* — Duellman, 2015. Today *Eothea flamma* (Juncá & Nunes, 2008).
- flavescens:** L. *flavescens*, become/turn yellow. *Atelopus flavescens* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Parties supérieures jaunâtres, tachetées de brun fauve ...”). Also *Phryniscus flavescens* — Boulenger, 1882.

flaviventris: *L. flavus*, yellow + *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly. *Allobates flaviventris* Melo-Sampaio et al., 2013. (“... The specific name refers to the golden-yellow bellies in both sexes ...”).

flavoguttata, flavoguttatus: *L. flavus*, yellow + *L. guttatum*, provided with drops, spots or specks. *Hyla flavoguttata* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939. (“... characterised by conspicuous yellow-drops on the hidden parts of the legs, thighs and adjacent surfaces of the body at the sides ...”). Also *Hyla strigilata flavoguttata* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. *Ololygon flavoguttata* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax flavoguttata* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax flavoguttatus* (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939).

flavolineatus: *L. flavus*, yellow + *L. lineatus*, lined. *Osteocephalus flavolineatus* Steindachner, 1862. (“... Von der Nasenspitze bis ans Steissende geht ein halbgelber Längsstrich ...”). Also *Trachycephalus (Osteocephalus) flavolineatus* Steindachner, 1867. In the synonymy of *Osteocephalus taurinus* Steindachner, 1862.

flavopicta, flavopictus: *L. flavus*, yellow + *L. picta*, paint, tint, color; adorn/decorate w/colored designs. (1) *Hylaplesia flavopicta* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... une raie canthale & marginale, un autre submédiane formée de points & de taches dispersées sur les extrémités & qui sont toutes couleur jaune doré ...”). Also *Dendrobates pictus flavopictus* — B. Lutz, 1952. *Epipedobates flavopictus* — Myers, 1987. Today *Ameerega flavopicta* (A. Lutz, 1925). (2) *Bokermannohyla flavopicta* Leite et al., 2012. (“... Small yellow dots on upper and lower lips, eyelids, loreal and gular regions, supratympanic fold, fingers, arms, forearms, flanks, feet, tibiae, thighs, and cloacal region ...”). (3) *Leptodactylus flavopictus* A. Lutz, 1926 (“... the red ornamentation is substituted by a yellow one, the ground color of which is deeper than in *L. gigas* and less limited ...”). Also *Leptodactylus pentadactylus flavopictus* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”.

Flectonotus: *L. flecto*, to bend, bow, curve, turn, turn round + *G. notos* (νοτος), back, dorsum. *Flectonotus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. [?].

florencei: Florence + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Antoine Hercule Romuald Florence (1804-1879), French artist, painter, polygrapher, and inventor. *Pseudopaludicola florencei* Andrade et al., 2018.

fluminensis: P. *fluminense*, demonym of the natives of Rio de Janeiro, from L. *flumen*, river + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Bufo marinus* var. *fluminensis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (“... los ejemplares del *B. marinus* que poseemos, pueden dividirse en tres grupos ó variedades de importancia, si se considera que cada una de ellas corresponde á determinada región del continente sur-americano: la marítima central del Brasil, la parte de la cuenca del rio Napo inmediata á los andes ecuatoriales, y las tierras llanas cercanas al rio de la Plata. Voy á distinguirlas con nombres expresivos de su procedencia ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758).

flumineus: L. *fluminis*, river, stream + L. *-eus*, suffix of action and agency. *Hyla fluminea* Cruz & Peixoto, 1985 “1984”. (“... O nome atribuído é de origem latina e faz referência ao fato de a espécie ter sido encontrada nas proximidades de um riacho ...”). Today *Aplastodiscus flumineus* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1985).

foliamorta: L. *foli(i)*, leaf + L. *mortis*, death. *Hyla foliamorta* Fouquette, 1958. (“... Brownish above with darker pattern of irregular marbling ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax rostratus* (Peters, 1863).

fontanarrosai: Fontanarrosa + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Roberto “El Negro” Fontanarrosa (1944-2007), Argentinian writer and cartoonist. *Scinax fontanarrosai* Baldo et al., 2019.

franciscaae: Francisca + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Francisca (“Chica”) Carolina do Val, Brazilian entomologist. *Physalaemus franciscaae* Heyer, 1985. In the synonymy of *Physalaemus moreirae* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

franciscana, franciscanus: P. *franciscana* (f.), *-ana*, *-anus* (m.), demonyms of the inhabitants of the River São Francisco. (1) *Crossodactylus franciscanus* Pimenta et al., 2015. (“... The specific epithet ... aludes to the Rio São

Francisco ... Its headwaters are located in the Parque Nacional da Serra da Canastra, type locality of the new species ...”). (2) *Vitreorana franciscana* Santana et al., 2015. (“... The specific epithet ... is a noun in apposition referring to the São Francisco River, because the species habitat is in the São Francisco and its tributaries ...”).

franciscus: L. *franciscus*, the frank, the Frenchman. *Atelopus franciscus* Lescure, 1974. (?).

fredi: Fred + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carlos Frederico (“Fred”) Duarte da Rocha, Brazilian ecologist and zoologist. (1) *Hylodes fredii* Canedo & Pombal, 2007. (2) *Luetkenotyphlus fredii* Maciel et al., 2019.

freibergi: Freiberg + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Marcos Abraham Freiberg (1911-1990), Argentinian herpetologist. *Eupemphix freibergi* Donoso-Barros, 1969. Also *Physalaemus freibergi* – Cannatella et al., 1998. Today *Engystomops freibergi* (Donoso-Barros, 1969).

freicanecae: Frei Caneca+ L. *-ae*, suffix indicating pertence. Honouring the sugarcane farm and distillation plant Usina Frei Caneca for its effort to conserve one of the few remaining fragments of Atlantic Montane Forest in northeastern Brazil, in which the species was found. *Hyla freicanecae* Carnaval & Peixoto, 2004. Also *Hypsiboas freicanecae* – Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana freicanecae* (Carnaval & Peixoto, 2004).

Fritziana: Fritz + L. *-ana*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to. Honouring Fritz Friedrich Theodor Müller (1822-1897), German-Brazilian zoologist. *Fritziana* Mello-Leitão, 1937. Replacement name for *Fritzia* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920 (preoccupied by *Fritzia* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1879, a salticid spider) (same root).

frontalis: L. *frontalis*, related to the forehead. *Hyla frontalis* Daudin, 1800. (“... Tête petite, un peu obtuse; front ceint d’un large bandeau blanc luisant et prolongé sur les cotés antérieurs du dos ...”). Also *Dendropsophus frontalis* – Fitzinger, 1843. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus leucophyllatus* (Beireis, 1783).

Frostius: Frost + L. *-ius*, suffix commemorative and dedicative. Honouring Darrel Richmond Frost, US American herpetologist. *Frostius* Cannatella, 1986.

fryi: Fry + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alexander Fry (1821-1905), British entomologist. *Ceratophrys fryi* Günther, 1873. Also *Stombus fryi* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. *Proceratophrys fryi* — Lynch, 1971. In the synonymy of *Proceratophrys boiei* (Wied-Neuwied, 1824).

fuentei: Fuente + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Murray de la Fuente (?), Surinamese naturalist. *Hyla fuentei* Goin & Goin, 1968. Also *Boana fuentei* — Dubois, 2017. In the synonymy of *Boana xerophylla* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

fulginosus, fuliginosus: L. *fuliginis*, soot; lamp-black + L. *-osus*, suffix denoting abundance. (1) *Bufo fuliginosus* Wied-Neuwied, 1821 (*nomen oblitum*). (“... Oberleib ungefleckt dunkel schwärzlich-braun ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella icterica* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Cycloramphus fulginosus* Tschudi, 1838 (*Cycloramphus fuliginosus* is an incorrect subsequent spelling but now prevailing usage by Duméril & Bibron, 1841). Also *Pithecoposis fuliginosus* — Duméril & Bibron, 1841. *Cyclorhamphus fuliginosus* — Boulenger, 1882. *Grypiscus fuliginosus* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1935. *Grypiscus lutzi* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1935. (3) *Eupsophus fuliginosus* Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. Also *Cystignathus (Eupsophus) fuliginosus* — Steindachner, 1867. In the synonymy of *Thoropa miliaris* (Spix, 1824).

fulva: L. *fulva*, tawny, reddish yellow; yellow. *Hyla fulva* Quoy & Gaimard, 1824. (“... Cette rainette, qui est d’une grande taille, a une couleur générale fauve, parsemée de quelques légères marbrures de brun clair ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana faber* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).

fulvoguttatus: L. *fulvus*, tawny, reddish yellow; yellow + L. *guttatum*, provided with drops, spots, or specks. *Dendrophryniscus stelzneri fulvoguttatus* Mertens, 1937. (“... mit zahlreichen kleinen ockergelben Fleckchen von annähernd gleicher Größe, die auf dem Rücken ziemlich gleichmäßig zerstreut sind ...”). Also *Melanophryniscus stelzneri fulvoguttatus* — Gallardo, 1961. Today *Melanophryniscus fulvoguttatus* (Mertens, 1937).

fulvorufa: *L. fulvus*, tawny, reddish yellow + *L. rufus*, red (of various shades). *Nototrema fulvorufa* Andersson, 1911. (“... The colour in spirit: Upper parts of head and body ochraceous brown with dark shades. Under parts uniform reddish brown; legs pale yellow with broad distinct brown cross-bands, bordered with black ...”). Also *Gastrotheca fulvorufa* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. *Gastrotheca (Australotheca) fulvorufa* — Duellman, 2015. *Gastrotheca (Alainia) fulvorufa* — Duellman & Cannatella, 2018. Today *Alainia fulvorufa* (Andersson, 1911).

funereus: *L. funereus*, funereal; deadly; fatal. *Scytopsis funereus* Cope, 1874. (“... Dark brown or blackish with a broad black cross-band between the eyes ...”). Also *Hyla funerea* — Boulenger, 1882. *Phyllomedusa (Scytopsis) funereus* — Knauer, 1878. *Ololygon funerea* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax funerea* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax funereus* (Cope, 1874).

furnarius: *L. furnus*, oven + *L. -arius*, pertaining to. *Leptodactylus furnarius* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978. [“... O nome *furnarius* (= oleiro) é dado em alusão ao hábito desta espécie de construir seus ninhos com formato semelhante a um forno ...”].

fusca: *L. fuscus*, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse. (1) *Pseudis fusca* Garman, 1883. (“... Clouded dark brown above ...”). Also *Pseudis paradoxus fuscus* — Gallardo, 1961. *Pseudis paradoxa fusca* — Bokermann, 1966. (2) *Rana fusca* Raddi, 1823. (“... Il colore di tutta la parte superiore del corpo e dell'estremità è interamente bruno o quasi nero ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815). (3) *Trachycara fusca* Tschudi, 1845. (“... *T. supra fusca* ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768).

fuscellus: *L. fuscus*, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse + *L. -ellus*, diminutive suffix. *Colostethus fuscellus* Morales, 2002 “2000”. (“... Deriva del latín *fuscus* que significa obscuro y el subfijo *-ellus* que significa pequeño, diminuto. Se refiere a que el macho de esta especie también tiene el vientre obscuro como *C. masniger*, pero es menor ...”). Today *Allobates fuscellus* (Morales, 2002).

fuscigula: *L. fuscus*, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse + *L. gula*, throat, neck, gullet, maw. (1) *Crossodactylus fuscigula* A. Lutz, 1930. (“... Mandibula com pontinhos brancos ... De lá até a metade da barriga a face ventral mostra uma reticulação parda com malhas largas separadas por linhas finas ...”). In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus dispar* A. Lutz, 1925. (2) *Phyllobates fuscigula* Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. (?). In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus gaudichaudii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

fusciventris: *L. fuscus*, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse + *L. ventris*, stomach, womb, belly. *Ceratophrys fusciventris* A. Lutz, 1926. (“... En dessous, le fond est brun foncé, avec de petites taches blanchâtres irrégulières et éparses ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus parvulus* (Girard, 1853).

fuscolineatus: *L. fuscus*, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse + *L. lineatus*, lined. *Brachycephalus fuscolineatus* Pie et al., 2015. (“... In life, a dark-brown to black stripe on the central region of the dorsum of the head and extending along the anteroposterior region of the dorsum of the body ...”).

fuscomaculata*, *fuscomaculatus: *L. fuscus*, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse + *L. maculata*, -us, spotted. *Hyobates fuscomaculatus* Jan, 1857 (*nomen nudum*). *Eupemphix fuscomaculatus* Steindachner, 1864. (“... Die übrigen Theile der Rückenfläche sind undeutlich bräunlich marmorirt ...”). *Hiobates fuscomaculatus* Steindachner, 1864. *Gomphobates fuscomaculata* — Steindachner, 1867. *Lystris fuscomaculata* — Cope, 1869 “1868”. *Paludicola fuscomaculata* — Boulenger, 1882. *Physalaemus fuscomaculata* — Parker, 1927. *Physalaemus fuscomaculatus* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. *Pleurodema fuscomaculata* — Nascimento et al., 2006. The same root in *Hiobates fuscus* Steindachner, 1867. In the synonymy of *Physalaemus biligonigerus* (Cope, 1861).

fuscomarginata*, *fuscomarginatus: *L. fuscus*, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse + *L. marginata*, -us, provided with borders. *Hyla fuscomarginata* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... double bande marginale brunne de l’oeil à l’aîne ...”). Also *Ololygon fuscomarginata* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax fuscomarginata* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax fuscomarginatus* (A. Lutz, 1925).

fuscovaria, fuscovarius: L. *fuscus*, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse + L. *varia*, -us, colored; party colored, variegated. *Hyla fuscovaria* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Le dos est de couleur café au lait avec un grand nombre de points & un réseau de taches plus sombres & parsemé de points clairs ...”). Also *Ololygon fuscovaria* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Ololygon fuscovarium* — Laurent & Teran, 1981. *Scinax fuscovaria* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax fuscovarius* (A. Lutz, 1925).

fusca, fuscus: L. *fusca*, -us, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse. (1) *Rana fusca* Schneider, 1799. (“... *Corpus fuscum linea a naribus ad femora ducta distinguit ...*”). Also *Cystignathus fuscus* — Günther, 1859 “1858”. Today *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Schneider, 1799). (2) *Limnocharis fuscus* Bell, 1843. (“... Colour of the upper part rich dark brown ...”). In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus gaudichaudii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

Gabohyla: S. Gabo, nickname for Gabriel + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. Honouring Gabriel (“Gabo”) Omar Skuk Sugliano (1962-2011), Uruguayan herpetologist active in Brazil. *Gabohyla* Araujo-Vieira et al., 2020.

gaigeae: Gaige + L. -ae, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Helen Beulah Thompson Gaige (1886-1976), US American herpetologist. *Leptodactylus gaigeae* Cochran, 1938. Today *Paratelmatobius gaigeae* (Cochran, 1938).

gaimardi: Gaimard + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Joseph Paul Gaimard (1793-1858), French naturalist. *Rana gaimardi* Bory de Saint-Vincent, 1828. Also *Hyla gaimardi* Bory de Saint-Vincent, 1828 (alternative original spelling). In the synonymy of *Bonana faber* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).

galactonotus: G. *galactos* (γάλακτος), milk + G. *notos* (νотος), back, dorsum. *Dendrobates galactonotus* Steindachner, 1864. [“... es war im Leben schwarz mit theilweise gummigutgelbem Scheitel, Hals und Rücken. Dieser grosse gelbe Rückenleck wird durch eine schmale schwarze, stellenweise unterbrochene und am Rande ausgezackte Längsline ...”]. Today *Adelphobates galactonotus* (Steindachner, 1864).

galeata: *L. galeata*, helmeted. *Corythomantis galeata* Pombal et al., 2012. (“... The specific name, a substantive Latin word, is an allusion to the head co-ossified; its meaning is covered with a helmet ...”). Today *Nyctimantis galeata* (Pombal et al., 2012).

Garbeana, garbeanus, garbei: Garbe + L. *-ana*, belonging to. Honouring Ernst Wilhelm Garbe (1853-1925), German-Brazilian naturalist. (1) *Brachycephalus garbeanus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. Also *Brachycephalus ephippium* var. *garbeana* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (2) *Garbeana* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Scinax* Wagler, 1830. (3) *Garbeana garbei* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. Also *Hyla (Garbeana) garbei* — B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952. *Osteocephalus garbei* — Goin, 1961. *Hyla garbei* — Duellman, 1970. *Ololygon garbei* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax garbei* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

garciai: Garcia + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paulo Cristiano de Anchieta Garcia, Brazilian herpetologist. *Ichnocnema garciai* Taucce et al., 2018.

gardai: Garda + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Adrian Antonio Garda, Brazilian herpetologist. *Amazophrynella gardai* Mângia et al., 2020.

garibaldiae: Garibaldi + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Ana Maria de Jesus Ribeiro di Garibaldi (a. k. a. Anita Garibaldi) (1821-1849), Brazilian heroine and freedom fighter. *Scinax garibaldiae* Lourenço et al., 2019. By chance or not, “rua Anita Garibaldi nº 45, São Paulo”, was the address noted by Werner Bokermann in many of his works; a couple of blocks ahead, the street is one of the limits of Praça Clóvis, theme and title of one of the memorable songs of Paulo Emílio Vanzolini.

gasconi: Gascon + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Claude Gascon, Canadian ecologist. *Colostethus gasconi* Morales, 2002 “2000”. Today *Allobates gasconi* (Morales, 2002).

Gastrophryinae: L. *Gastrophryne*, genus or anurans due to Fitzinger (1843), in turn, from G. *gastir* (γαστήρ), belly, stomach + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + L. *-inae*, suffix that indicates the category of subfamily in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). *Gastrophryinae* Fitzinger, 1843.

***gaucheri*:** Gaucher + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Philippe Gaucher, French zoologist active in French Guiana. *Hyla gaucheri* Lescure & Marty, 2000. Today *Dendropsophus gaucheri* (Lescure & Marty, 2000).

***gaudichaudii*:** Gaudichaud + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Charles Gaudichaud-Beaupré (1789-1854), French botanist. *Crossodactylus gaudichaudii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. Also *Phyllobates gaudichaudii* — Cope, 1866. *Leptodactylus gaudichaudii* — Boulenger, 1882.

***geayi*:** Geay + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Martin François Geay (1859-1910), French pharmacist, natural history collector, and traveller. *Ctenophryne geayi* Mocquard, 1904. Also *Ctenophryne geagi* — Nieden, 1926 (incorrect subsequent spelling).

***gehrti*:** Gerth + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Augusto Gehrt (1897-?), Brazilian collector. *Basanitia gehrti* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. Also *Eleutherodactylus gehrti* — Pombal & Cruz, 1999. Today *Ischnocnema gehrti* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

***geminus*:** L. *geminus*, twin, double; twin-born. *Leptodactylus geminus* Barrio, 1973. (“... Owing to its great morphological similarity with *L. gracilis* it is considered a sibling species ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus plau-manni* Ahl, 1936.

***gemmata*:** L. *gemmata*, jeweled. *Rana gemmata* Lacépède, 1788. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768).

***geographica*, *geographicus*:** L. *geographica*, geographic; geographical (1) *Hyla geographica* Spix, 1824. (?). Also *Hypsiboas geographica* — Wagler, 1830. *Hyla (Centrotelma) geographica* — Burmeister, 1856. *Centrotel-*

ma geographica — Cope, 1867. *Hyla geographica geographica* — Parker, 1935. *Hypsiboas geographicus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana geographica* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Trachycephalus geographicus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Le dessus et les côtés du tronc offrent un mélange de taches, de raies, de lignes et de bandes, grises, blanches, brunes, rous-sâtres et bleuâtres, qui forment sur ces parties un dessin aussi irrégulier que celui que présente une carte géographique ...”). Also *Hyla geographica* — Duméril & Bibron, 1841. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus nigromaculatus* Tschudi, 1838.

Geotriton: *G. gea* (γῆα), earth, land + *L. Triton*, genus of salamanders due to Laurenti (1768) [in turn from *G. triton* (Τρῖτων), sea god, son of Poseidon and Amphitrite], preoccupied by *Triton* Linnaeus, 1758 (a gastropod); frequent ending in urodele names. *Geotriton* Bonaparte, 1832. (“... Le altre che hanno la coda terete, almeno alla radice, che sogliono esser terrestri, meno agili, e in tutto più simili alle Salamandre, costituiscono per noi un’altro gruppo, che denominiamo *Geotriton* ...”). In the synonymy of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854.

germani: Germán + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Germán Chávez, Peruvian herpetologist. *Osteocephalus germani* Ron et al., 2012. In the synonymy of *Osteocephalus helenae* (Ruthven, 1919).

giarettai: Giaretta + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ariovaldo Antonio Giaretta, Brazilian herpetologist. *Pseudopaludicola giarettai* Carvalho, 2012.

gibbosa: *L. gibba*, bulge, protuberance. *Rana gibbosa* Raddi, 1823. (“... Il torso ha una rilevante curvatura ovvero gobba fra l’addome, e il torace ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815).

giesleri: Giesler + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paul Giesler (?), German physician established in Rio de Janeiro. *Hyla giesleri* Mertens, 1950. Today *Dendropsophus giesleri* (Mertens, 1950).

gigas: L. *gigas*, giant. (1) *Rana gigas* Walbaum, 1784. [“... Sollte dieser Name nicht angemessener seyn? *Rana (Gigas) superciliis verrucosis conchatis* ...”]. In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Rana gigas* Spix, 1824 [preoccupied by *Rana gigas* Wallbaum, 1784 (= *Rhinella marina*)]. (“... *Maxima, fusco olivacea* ...”). Also *Doryphoros gigas* — Mayer, 1835. *Gnathophysa gigas* — Cope, 1866. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768).

gilbertogili: Gilberto Gil + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Gilberto Passos Gil Moreira, Brazilian music, composer, and singer. *Rhinatrema gilbertogili* Maciel et al., 2018.

gildae: Gilda + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Gilda Vasconcelos Andrade, Brazilian herpetologist. *Rhinella gildae* Vaz-Silva et al., 2015. In the synonymy of *Rhinella dapsilis* (Myers & Carvalho, 1945).

giorgii: Giorgi + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Adriano Giorgi, Brazilian entomologist. *Pristimantis giorgii* Oliveira et al., 2020.

glaber: L. *glaber*, hairless, smooth. *Elosia glabra* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (?). Also *Hylodes glabrus* — Lynch, 1971. Today *Hylodes glaber* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

gladius: L. *gladius*, sword. *Proceratophrys gladius* Mângia et al., 2014. (“... is used to represent the primary swords of Ancient Roman foot soldiers named “gladiators”. The symmetrical dorsal crest of the new species resembles these swords shape ...”).

glandulata: L. *glandulata*, glandular. *Adelophryne glandulata* Lourenço-de-Moraes et al., 2014. (“... used in refers to the glandular ridge line that runs from the posterior part of the eye to the insertion of the forelimb ...”).

glandulosus: L. *glandulosus*, full of glands. (1) *Leptodactylus glandulosus* Cope, 1887. (“... two rows of glands or glandular warts, one on the upper part of the side, extending from above the humerus to the groin, and the other

above it, which terminates in a number of low warts on the posterior iliac region. Numerous similar warts on the side below the inferior glandular ridge ...”). In the synonymy of *Adenomera diptyx* (Boettger, 1885). (2) *Phyllobates glandulosus* Steindachner, 1867. (“... einige, grössere, längliche Warzen an den Seiten des Körpers zunächst und in der Lendengegend ...”). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus signifer* (Girard, 1853).

glauciae: Glaucia + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Glaucia M. Funk Pontes, Brazilian herpetologist. *Adenomera glauciae* Carvalho et al., 2020.

globulosus: L. *globulo*, bead, button + L. *-osus*, full of. *Bufo globulosus* Spix, 1824. (“... *supra granuloso-subhispidum* ...”). Also *Chaunus globulosus* — Wagler, 1830. In the synonymy of *Rhinella granulosa* (Spix, 1824).

Glossostoma: G. *glossa* (γλώσσα), tongue + L. *stoma*, ending of *Engystoma* (see). *Glossostoma* Günther, 1901 [junior homonym of *Glossostoma* LeConte, 1851 (Turbellaria)]. (“... Resembling *Engystoma*. Tongue very large, elliptic, free and entire behind ...”). In the synonymy of *Ctenophryne* Mocquard, 1904.

Gnathophysa: G. *gnathos* (γνάθος), jaw + G. *physao* (φυσάω), inflate with air; puff out. *Gnathophysa* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826.

gnoma: F. *gnomus*, from modern Latin *gnomus*, a word used by Paracelsus (in his *Liber de nymphis, sylphis, pygmaeis et salamandris, et de caeteris spiritibus*) as a synonym of *gnarus*, denoting a mythical race of very small people said to inhabit underground. *Chiasmocleis gnoma* Canedo et al., 2004. (“... here used in allusion to the small size of this *Chiasmocleis* ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis (Relictocleis) gnoma* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Relictocleis gnoma* (Canedo et al., 2004).

goeldii: Goeldi + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Émil August Goeldi (1859-1917), Swiss-Brazilian zoologist. (1) *Bufo granulatus goeldii* Gallardo, 1965. In the synonymy of *Rhinella major* (Müller & Helmich, 1936). (2) *Hyla goeldii* Boulenger, 1895 “1894”. Also *Fritzia goeldii* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. *Fritziana goeldii* — Mel-

lo-Leitão, 1937. *Flectonotus goeldii* — B. Lutz, 1954. Today *Fritziana goeldii* (Boulenger, 1895). (3) *Hylodes goeldii* Baumann, 1912. Also *Elosia goeldii* — Müller, 1927. *Megalelosia (sic) goeldii* — A. Lutz, 1930. Today *Megaelosia goeldii* (Baumann, 1912).

goiana, goianus, goyana, goyanus: P. pertaining to or from the state of Goiás, Central Brazil; also Goiás, name of an ancient native-Brazilian tribe, *silvícolas Goiá*, from T. *guay'-ya*, alike people + L. *-ana*, pertaining to. (1) *Colostethus goianus* Bokermann, 1975. (“... Chapada dos Veadeiros, 1700 m, cerca de 30 km de Alto Paraíso, Goiás, Brasil ...”). Today *Allobates goianus* (Bokermann, 1975). (2) *Hyla polytaenia goiana* B. Lutz, 1968. (“... Jatobasinho, São João da Aliança, highland of Goiás ...”). Also *Hyla goiana* — Cruz & Caramaschi, 1998. *Hypsiboas goianus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana goiana* (B. Lutz, 1968). (3) *Stombus goyanus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. (“... Seis exemplares, procedentes de Veadeiros e Rio São Miguel, Goyaz ...”). Also *Ceratophrys goyanus* — Gorham, 1966. *Stombus goianus* — Bokermann, 1966. *Proceratophrys goyanus* — Lynch, 1971. Today *Proceratophrys goyana* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

goinorum: Goin + L. *-orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. Honouring Olive Lynda Bown Goin (1912-2000) and Coleman Jett Goin (1911-1986), US American herpetologists. *Hyla goinorum* Bokermann, 1962. Also *Ololygon goinorum* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scarthyla goinorum* (Bokermann, 1962).

goliath: H. *Goliath* biblical, (גִּלְיָת) giant. *Leptodactylus goliath* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (“... Dábanle el nombre de *Hatun-Hambato*, que equivale á gran rana ó sapo ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768).

gollmeri: Gollmer + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Julius Gollmer (?-1861), German Consul in Caracas, Venezuela. *Ranula gollmeri* Peters, 1859. In the synonymy of *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824).

Gomphobates: G. *gomphos* (γόμφος), wooden bolt, peg, dowel (for fastening timbers together) + G. *bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (from βαίνω,

move by taking step). *Gomphobates* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... Af γομφος og βαίνω: den, der traeder paa Plöke ...”). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus* Fitzinger, 1826.

gonzagai: Gonzaga + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Luiz Gonzaga do Nascimento (1912-1989), Brazilian singer, songwriter, and musician. *Pithecopus gonzagai* Andrade et al., 2020.

goodfellowi: Goodfellow + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring a “Mr. Goodfellow” (?), who collected in Esperanza, E. Bolivia, and presented the specimens to the British Museum. *Hyla goodfellowi* Procter, 1921. In the synonymy of *Boana raniceps* (Cope, 1862).

goughi: Gough + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Lewis H. Gough (?), British naturalist, collector of the types. *Dendropsophus goughi* (Boulenger, 1911) (not a Brazilian species).

gouveai: Gouvêa + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Élio Gouvêa (1924-1999), Brazilian zoologist. *Hyla gouveai* Peixoto & Cruz, 1992. Today *Bokermannohyla gouveai* (Peixoto & Cruz, 1992).

goya: T. *goyá*, from T. *guay-a*, similar people. *Ololygon goya* Andrade et al., 2018. (“... The name evokes the morphological similarity of the new species with the *Ololygon skaios* ...”). Today *Scinax goya* (Andrade et al., 2018).

gracilis: L. *gracilis*, slender, thin, slim, slight; fine. (1) *Bufo gracilis* Girard, 1853. (?). Also *Rhaebo gracilis* — Cope, 1862. In the synonymy of *Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Caecilia gracilis* Shaw, 1802. (“... Slender *Caecilia* ...”). (3) *Cystignathus gracilis* Duméril & Bibron, 1840. (“... se distingue particulièrement de l’ocellé par ses formes plus élancées, par sa tête plus étroite, par son museau tout à fait pointu ...”). Today *Leptodactylus gracilis* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841). (4) *Hyla granosa gracilis* Melin, 1941. (“... Body wedge-shaped, depressed, with large head and long, narrow hind limbs ...”). Today *Boana gracilis* (Melin, 1941). (5) *Paludicola gracilis* Boulenger, 1883. (“... The general proportions are considerably more slender ...”). Today *Physalaemus gracilis* (Boulenger, 1883).

grandis: L. *grandis*, full-grown, large, great, grand, tall. *Crossodactylus grandis* B. Lutz, 1951. [“... A sub-espécie do Itatiaia se diferencia da forma típica pelo tamanho muito maior (36-40 mms. em vez de 26) ...”]. Also *Crossodactylus dispar grandis* B. Lutz, 1951.

grandoculis: L. *grandis*, large, great, grand + L. *oculi*, eye. *Hylodes grandoculis* Van Lidth de Jeude, 1904. (“... Eyes very large and protruding ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus grandoculis* — Stejneger, 1904. In the synonymy of *Pristimantis marmoratus* (Boulenger, 1900).

granosa, granosus: L. *granuli*, granule + L. -osa, -osus, full of. (1) *Ceratophris granosa* Cuvier, 1829. (“... Sont des grenouilles à large tête, à peau grenue en tout ou en partie ...”). Also *Rana (Ceratophris) granosa* — Guérin-Méneville, 1838. *Stombus granosus* — Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. In the synonymy of *Proceratophrys boiei* (Wied-Neuwied, 1824). (2) *Hyla granosa* Boulenger, 1882. (“... Upper surfaces, belly and lower surface of thighs granulate ...”). Also *Hypsiboas granosus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. In the synonymy of *Boana cinerascens* (Spix, 1824).

granulatum, granulatus: L. *granulatum*, -us, provided with granules. (1) *Cinclidium granulatum* Cope, 1867. (“... skin minutely granular on upper surfaces ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana boans* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Hyla granulata* Peters, 1871. (“... Die Oberseite des Kopfes und Körpers ist wie bei *H. verrucosa* stark granuliert, aber die Granulationen sind nicht so dicht gedrängt und gleichmäßig wie die des Bauches, der Unterseite der Oberschenkel und die etwas feinere Granulation der Submentalgegend ...”). Today *Scinax granulatus* (Peters, 1871).

granulosa, granulosum, granulosus: L. *granuli*, granule + L. -osa, -osum, -osus, full of. (1) *Cycloramphus granulosus* A. Lutz, 1929. (“... Aqui porém toda a pelle do dorso é coberta de grânulos miliares tão densamente conchegados como em *C. asper* Werner ...”). Also *Iliodiscus granulosus* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1929. (2) *Phyllomedusa granulosa* Cruz, 1989 “1988”. (“... com acentuada granulação nas superfícies dorsais ...”). Also *Hylomantis granulosa* — Cruz, 1991 “1990”. *Agalychnis granulosa* — Faivovich et al., 2010. *Hylomantis granulosus* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Hylomantis granulosa* (Cruz, 1989). (3) *Pleurodema granulosum* Jiménez de la Es-

pada, 1875. (“... La piel sobre la cabeza, tronco y muslos y en los costados es granugienta, extendiéndose los granitos en la cabeza por los párpados superiores, por el testuz hasta las narices y por las mejillas hasta el hocico ...”). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema bibroni* Tschudi, 1838. (4) *Bufo* (*Oxyrhynchus*) *granulosus* Spix, 1824. (“... *Subexiguus, cinnamomeus, granulis punctisque nigris subhispidus* ...”). Also *Bufo* (*Rhinella*) *granulosus* — Cuvier, 1829. *Phrynoidis granulosus* — Cope, 1862. *Bufo granulosus granulosus* — Müller & Hellmich, 1936. *Chaunus granulosus* — Frost et al., 2006. *Rhinella granulosus* — Pramuk et al., 2008 (incorrect subsequent spelling). Today *Rhinella granulosa* (Spix, 1824).

gravenhorstii: Gravenhorst + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Johann Ludwig Christian Gravenhorst (1777-1857), German zoologist. *Euhyas gravenhorstii* Fitzinger, 1861 “1860” (*nomen nudum*). In the synonymy of *Ischnocnema guentheri* (Steindachner, 1864).

greeningi: Greening + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Linnaeus Greening (1855-1927), English businessman and naturalist. *Corythomantis greeningi* Boulenger, 1896.

gridipappi: Gridi-Papp + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Marcos Gridi-Papp, Brazilian herpetologist. *Adenomera gridipappi* Carvalho et al., 2021.

grillicantus: L. *grillus*, cricket; grasshopper + L. *cantus*, song, chant; singing; cry (bird); blast (trumpet). *Allobates grillicantus* Moraes & Lima, 2021. [“... The specific epithet *grillicantus* means “cricket song” and refers to the cricket-like advertisement call emitted by this species. ... The name is purposely similar to the sister taxon *A. grillisimilis* to refer to common ancestry ...”].

grillisimilis: L. *grillus*, cricket; grasshopper + L. *similis*, like, similar, resembling. *Allobates grillisimilis* Simões et al., 2013. [“... The specific epithet refers to the species distinctive advertisement call, which resembles (to the human ear) to the sound produced by crickets ...”].

Grypiscus: Unclear. *G. grypos* (γρυπός), aquiline; curved snout; also a mythical creature, griffin + *G. -ikos* (-ίκος), looking like, belonging to. *Grypiscus* Cope, 1867. (Probably referred to “... The form of the cranium, with its broad outline ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus* Tschudi, 1838.

gualambensis: S. Gualamba, name given to the Chaco plain between the current Salado and Bermejo rivers (in turn, from Ka. *gual*, great, large, big + Ka. *ampa*, water or river, original denomination of the upper course of Bermejo river) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Leptodactylus gualambensis* Gallardo, 1964. (“... Su nombre proviene de que procede de la region chaqueña, conocida antiguamente como el Gran Chaco Gualamba ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Schneider, 1799).

gualteri: Gualter + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Gualter Adolpho Lutz (1903-1969), Brazilian physician and naturalist. *Eleutherodactylus gualteri* B. Lutz, 1974. Today *Ischnocnema gualteri* (B. Lutz, 1974).

guarani: S. Guaraní, South-American native culture, calling themselves *Ava*. *Brachycephalus guarani* Clemente-Carvalho et al., 2012. (“... The species is named after the Guaraní Indians, the present-day native people inhabiting the region where the new species was found ...”).

guarantanus: P. Guarantã [do Norte (S 9°40'59.44" W 54°57'46.58"), state of Mato Grosso, Brazil], from T. *guara-antã*, a hardwood (probably the guarantã, *Esenbeckia leiocarpa*: Rutaceae). *Brasilotyphlus guarantanus* Maciel et al., 2009. (“... The name of the species refers to the type-locality ...”).

guayanensis: S. Guayana, South American region, from Ar. *guyana*, the land of many waters + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Dendrobates pictus guayanensis* Heatwole et al., 1965. (“... The form from the Guianas which Lutz ... calls *D. pictus* subsp. may also be *guayanensis* ...”). Also *Epipedobates guayanensis* — Barrio-Amorós, 2004. In the synonymy of *Ameerega picta* (Bibron in Tschudi, 1838). (2) *Eleutherodactylus conspicillatus guayanensis* Rivero, 1968 “1967”. (“... Hasta ahora *E. conspicillatus guayanensis* es solamente conocido de la Guayana Venezolana ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis vilarsi* (Melin, 1941).

guentheri: Günther + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Albert Carl Ludwig Gotthilf Günther (1830-1914), German-British zoologist. (1) *Hyla guentheri* Boulenger, 1886. Also *Hypsiboas guentheri* — Faivovich et al., 2005. [Today *Boana guentheri* (Boulenger, 1886)]. 2) *Hylodes güntheri* Steindachner, 1864. Also *Eleutherodactylus guentheri* — Stejneger, 1904. Today *Ischnocnema guentheri* (Steindachner, 1864).

guerreroi: Guerrero + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Peter Lascenio Guerrero (?), Venezuelan physician from Division de Endemias Rurales de Venezuela. *Hyla lanciformis guerreroi* Rivero, 1971. In the synonymy of *Boana lanciformis* (Cope, 1871).

guianensis: E. Guiana, South American country, from Ar. *guyana*, the land of many waters + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Leptodactylus guianensis* Heyer & de Sá, 2011. (“... The species is named for its distribution coinciding in large part with the Guiana Shield ...”). (2) *Rana clamata* var. *guianensis* Peters, 1863. (“... im Eingangsjournal der Schomburgkschen Sammlungen überhaupt nur drei Exemplare von *Cystignathus* und *Rana* zusammen aufgeführt, so dass sich sicher annehmen lässt, dass das vorliegende Exemplar wirklich aus Guiana stammt ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824).

Güntheria: Günther + L. *-eria*, suffix denoting place of. Honouring Albert Carl Ludwig Gotthilf Günther (1830-1914), German-British zoologist. *Güntheria* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus* Fitzinger, 1843.

guttata, guttatus: L. *guttata*, *-us*, having drops, spots, specks. (1) *Phyllomedusa guttata* A. Lutz, 1924. (“... La *guttata* montre sur les flancs une vingtaine de taches rondes d’un bleu violacé sur fond orangé ...”). Also *Phyllomedusa (Hylomantis) guttata* — B. Lutz, 1950. Today *Phasmahyla guttata* (A. Lutz, 1924). (2) *Bufo guttatus* Schneider, 1799. (“... *Corpus supra griseo flavescens, oblongum, infra flavo guttatum* ...”). Today *Rhaebo guttatus* (Schneider, 1799).

gutturalis: L. *guttur*, throat + L. *-alis*, adjectival suffix. *Eleutherodactylus gutturalis* Hoogmoed et al., 1977. (“... pertaining to the throat, because of its conspicuous pattern ...”). Today *Pristimantis gutturalis* (Hoogmoed et al., 1977).

gutturosa: L. *gutturosus*, with enlarged throat. *Adelophryne gutturosa* Hoogmoed & Lescure, 1984. (... in reference to the gigantic subgular vocal sac in adult males ...”).

Gymnophiona: G. *gymnos* (γυμνός), naked + G. *ofis* (ὄφις), serpent + L. *-ona*, diminutive or hypocoristic suffix. *Gymnophiona* Rafinesque, 1814. (“... I Ginnofi. Corpo senza squame ...”).

gyrinaethes: G. *gyrinos* (γυρινός), tadpole + G. *a-ithis* (ἀ-ήθης), unaccustomed, unused. *Phyllodytes gyrinaethes* Peixoto et al., 2003. (“... a morphologically specialized tadpole with dumb bell shaped body in dorsal view ...”).

habra: G. *abros* (ἀβρός), graceful, elegant, refined. *Sphoerohyla habra* Goin, 1957. (?). Also *Dryomelictes habra* — Goin, 1961. *Hyla habra* — Gorham, 1963. *Sphaenorhynchus habrus* — Rivero, 1969. In the synonymy of *Sphaenorhynchus carneus* (Cope, 1868).

haddadi: Haddad + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Célio Fernando Baptista Haddad, Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Chiasmocleis haddadi* Peloso et al., 2014. Also *Chiasmocleis* (*Syncope*) *haddadi* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. (2) *Dendrophryniscus haddadi* Cruz et al., 2019. (3) *Hyla haddadi* Bastos & Pombal, 1996. Today *Dendropsophus haddadi* (Bastos & Pombal, 1996). (4) The same root in *Haddadus* Hedges et al., 2008.

haddadorum: Haddad + L. *-orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. *Scinax haddadorum* Araujo-Vieira et al., 2016. Honouring “Célio Fernando Baptista Haddad ... and his family, including his wife, Patricia L. Morelato, their daughter, Alice Haddad, and son, André Haddad ...”.

hadroceps: G. *hadros* (αδρός), well-grown, sturdy + G. *kephali* (κεφάλι), head. *Hyla hadroceps* Duellman & Hoogmoed, 1992. (“... the name *hadroceps*

alludes to the short, heavy head of the frog ...”). Also *Phrynohyas hadroceps* — Lescure & Marty, 2000. Today *Trachycephalus hadroceps* (Duellman & Hoogmoed, 1992).

hahneli: Hahnel + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paul Hahnel (1843-1887), German collector. *Dendrobates hahneli* Boulenger, 1884 “1883”. Also *Dendrobates pictus hahneli* — B. Lutz, 1952. *Epipedobates hahneli* — Martins & Sazima, 1989. *Epipedobates hahneli hahneli* — Schulte, 1999. Today *Ameerega hahneli* (Boulenger, 1884).

Hamptophryne: Hampton + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Hamptophryne* Carvalho, 1954. (“... This genus is named in honor of Dr. Hampton Wildman Parker [1897-1968] of the British Museum (Natural History), the describer of its only species and monographer of the family Microhylidae ...”).

haraldschultzi: Harald Schultz + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Harald Schultz (1909-1966), Brazilian ethnologist and anthropologist. *Hyla haraldschultzi* Bokermann, 1962. Today *Dendropsophus haraldschultzi* (Bokermann, 1962).

hardyi: Hardy + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring F. Hardy du Dréneuf (?), Belgian collector and traveller. *Siphonops hardyi* Boulenger, 1888.

hayii: Hay + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Clarence Leonard Hay (1884-1969), US American anthropologist. *Hyla hayii* Barbour, 1909. Also *Ololygon hayi* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax hayii* (Barbour, 1909).

hebes: L. *hebes*, blunt, dull; languid. *Scytotis hebes* Cope, 1862. (?). Also *Phrynohyas hebes* — Duellman, 1956. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

helenae: Helen + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Helen Beulah Thompson Gaige (1886-1976), US American herpetologist. *Hyla helenae* Ruthven, 1919. Today *Osteocephalus helenae* (Ruthven, 1919).

helianneae: Helianne + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Helianne de Niemeyer, Brazilian archaeologist. *Elachistocleis helianneae* Caramaschi, 2010. Also *Engystoma helianneae* – Dubois et al., 2021.

helioi: Helio + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Helio Ricardo da Silva, Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Hemiphractus helioi* Sheil & Mendelson, 2001. (2) *Trachycephalus helioi* Nunes et al., 2013.

hellmichi: Hellmich + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Probably honouring Karl George Walter Hellmich (1906-1974), German herpetologist. *Chthonerpeton hellmichi* Taylor, 1968. In the synonymy of *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

hemidactyloides: L. *Hemidactylus*, genus of lizards due to Oken (1817) [in turn from G. *hemisys* (ἡμισυς), half + G. *dactylo* (δάκτυλο), digit] + L. *-oides*, suffix indicating likeness. *Leptodactylus hemidactyloides* Andersson, 1945. (“... All upper surfaces are densely covered with small uniform pointed tubercles, the back resembling that of some *Hemidactylus* lizards ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithodytes lineatus* (Schneider, 1799).

Hemiphractus: G. *hemisis* (ἡμισυς), half + G. *fraktis* (φρακτής), fence, protection, in reference to the “helmet” that covers the front half of the head. *Hemiphractus* Wagler (1828). (?). Same root in Hemiphractidae Peters, 1862.

Hemipipa: G. *hemisis* (ἡμισυς), half + L. *Pipa*, genus of anurans due to Laurenti (1768) (see). *Hemipipa* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. (“... Eis de como podemos ver que o modo de evolução de *Pipa* e *Protopipa* é secundario de *Xenopus* e *Hymenochyrus* e subsequente de *Hemipipa*, que é intermediario ...”). In the synonymy of *Pipa* Laurenti, 1768.

henseli: Hensel + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Reinhold Friedrich Hensel (1826-1881), German zoologist. (1) *Hylodes henselii* Peters, 1870. Also *Eleutherodactylus henselii* – Stejneger, 1904. Today *Ischnocnema henselii* (Peters, 1870). (2) *Paludi-*

cola henseli Boulenger, 1882. Today *Physalaemus henselii* (Peters, 1872). (3) *Bufo crucifer* var. *Henseli* A. Lutz, 1934. Also *Bufo henseli* — Baldissera et al., 2004. *Chaunus henseli* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella henseli* (A. Lutz, 1934).

hermogenesi: Hermógenes + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hermógenes de Freitas Leitão Filho (1944-1996), Brazilian botanist. *Psyllophryne hermogenesi* Giaretta & Sawaya, 1998. Today *Brachycephalus hermogenesi* (Giaretta & Sawaya, 1998).

heterodactylum, heterodactylus: G. [*h*]eteros (ἕτερος), another + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Teletrema heterodactylum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937 (“... Mãos grandes, o 3.º dedo egualando ao antebraço; 3.º e 4.º fortemente, 1.º e o 2.º muito menos dilatados ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus heterodactylus* — Myers, 1962. Today *Oreobates heterodactylus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

heterophonicus: G. [*h*]eteros (ἕτερος), another + G. *phoni* (φωνή) voice + L. *-icus*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to, pertaining to, having the nature of, made of, quality of, state or condition of. *Aplastodiscus heterophonicus* Pinheiro et al., 2021. (“... The resulting specific epithet, *heterophonicus*, means “the one with a different voice”, in allusion to the very distinct call of the new species of *Aplastodiscus* described here ...”).

heyeri: Heyer + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring William Ronald Heyer, US American herpetologist. (1) *Adenomera heyeri* Boistel et al., 2006. Also *Leptodactylus (Lithodytes) heyeri* — Frost et al., 2006. (2) *Cycloramphus heyeri* Segalla et al., 2021. Replacement name for *Cycloramphus carvalhoi* Heyer, 1983, junior subjective homonym of *Cycloramphus carvalhoi* (Izecksohn, 1983). (3) *Hylodes heyeri* Haddad et al., 1996. (4) *Ololygon heyeri* Peixoto & Weygoldt, 1987. Today *Scinax heyeri* (Peixoto & Weygoldt, 1987).

Heyerus: Heyer + L. *-us*, pertaining to. Honouring W. Ronald Heyer, US American herpetologist. *Heyerus* Motta et al., 2021. In the synonymy of *Bahius* Dubois et al., 2021.

hiemalis: L. *hiemalis*, wintry; stormy; of/for winter time/rainy season. *Hyla hiemalis* Haddad & Pombal, 1987. (“... O epíteto específico, em latim, significa invernal, em alusão à estação reprodutiva desta espécie, que ocorre nos meses frios e secos ...”). Also *Ololygon hiemalis* — Caramaschi & Kistenu-macher, 1989. Today *Scinax hiemalis* (Haddad & Pombal, 1987).

hilli: Hill + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring James Peter Hill (1873-1954), British zoologist. *Hyla hilli* Boulenger, 1920. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus microps* (Peters, 1872).

histrío: L. *histrío*, actor; performer in pantomime. *Hyophryne histrío* Carvalho, 1954 (“... The trivial name *histrío* is from the Latin, meaning clown, in reference to the bicolored garb of this frog ...”). Today *Stereocyclops histrío* (Carvalho, 1954).

hobbsi: Hobbs + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Horton Holcombe Hobbs Jr. (1914-1994), US American zoologist. *Hyla hobbsi* Cochran & Goin, 1970. Also *Hypsiboas hobbsi* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana hobbsi* (Cochran & Goin, 1970).

hodli: Hodl + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Walter Hödl, Austrian herpetologist. *Allobates hodli* Simões et al., 2010.

hoehnei: Hoehne + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Frederico Carlos Hoehne (1882-1959), Brazilian botanist. *Eleutherodactylus hoehnei* B. Lutz, 1958. Today *Ischnocnema hoehnei* (B. Lutz, 1958).

Holoaden: G. *holos* (ολος), whole, entire + G. *adenas* (αδέννας), gland. *Holoaden* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... Pelle muito glandulosa em todo o corpo, especialmente na região post-tympanica onde as glandulas affectam à forma de grandes parotoides ...”). The same root in *Holoadeninae* Hedges et al., 2008.

hololius: G. *holos* (ὅλος), the whole of, whole, entire + G. *leios* (λείος), smooth. *Lep-
todactylus hololius* Boulenger, 1918. (“... Skin perfectly smooth; no dorso-lat-
eral fold ...”). In the synonymy of *Adenomera hylaedactyla* (Cope, 1868).

holti: Holt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ernest Golsan Holt (1889-1983), US American ornithologist. *Eleutherodactylus unistrigatus holti* Cochran, 1948. Also *Eleutherodac-
tylus holti* – Heyer, 1985. *Eleutherodactylus (Eleutherodactylus) holti* –
Lynch & Duellman, 1997. *Ischnocnema holti* – Heinicke et al., 2007. To-
day *Ischnocnema holti* (Cochran, 1948).

hoogmoedi: Hoogmoed + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Marinus Steven Hoogmoed, Dutch-Brazilian her-
petologist. (1) *Atelopus hoogmoedi* Lescure, 1974. Also *Atelopus pulcher
hoogmoedi* Lescure, 1974 “1973”. *Atelopus spumarius hoogmoedi* – Les-
cure et al., 1980. *Atelopus hoogmoedi hoogmoedi* – Ouboter & Jairam,
2012. (2) *Rhinella hoogmoedi* Caramaschi & Pombal, 2006.

horridus: L. *horridus*, wild, frightful, rough, bristly, standing on end, unkempt;
grim; horrible. *Bufo horridus* Daudin, 1802 “An. XI”. (“... Crapaud herisée
...”). Also *Bombinator horridus* – Merrem, 1820. In the synonymy of *Rhi-
nella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758).

hübneri: Hübner + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring George Hübner (1862-1935), German photogra-
pher-ethnographer active in Manaus. *Hyla rubra hübneri* Melin, 1941. In
the synonymy of *Scinax ruber* (Laurenti, 1768).

hudsoni: Hudson + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring C. A. Hudson (?), collector for the Natural History Mu-
seum, London. *Chiasmocleis hudsoni* Parker, 1940. Also *Syncope hudsoni*
– de Sá et al., 2012. *Chiasmocleis (Syncope) hudsoni* – de Sá et al., 2018
“2019”.

Huicundomantis: Q. *huicundo*, vernacular name for bromeliads + G. *mantis*
(μάντις), tree-frog (etymology by the authors). *Huicundomantis* Páez &
Ron, 2019. (“... We name this clade *Huicundomantis* because these frogs are

frequently found inside bromeliad plants. *Huicundo* is a word in Quechua, an indigenous South American language, locally used to referring to bromeliads ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

humeralis: L. *humeralis*, cape, protective shoulder cover. *Bufo humeralis* Daudin, 1803 “An. XI”. (“... Le crapaud épaule armée ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758).

humeralis-armata: L. *humeralis*, upper arm, shoulder + L. *armata*, armed, defensively armed. *Rana humeralis-armata* Lacépède, 1788. (“... L'épaule-armée ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758).

humilis: L. *humilis*, small, insignificant. *Hyla humilis* A. Lutz & B. Lutz in B. Lutz, 1954. (“... Caracteres morfológicos do ciclo de *Hyla catharinae*. Tamanho muito menor ...”). Also *Oloolygon humilis* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax humilis* (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1954).

huntingtoni: Huntington + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Herbert Huntington Smith (1851-1919), US American naturalist. *Proceratophrys huntingtoni* Ávila et al., 2012.

Hyalinobatrachium: G. *yalos* (ὑαλος), glass + G. *batrachos* (βάτραχος), frog. *Hyalinobatrachium* Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. (“... El nombre del género se origina del griego *hyalos* (= cristal) y *batrachion* (= ranita) en referencia al aspecto semitranslúcido y delicado de las especies del género ...”). The same root in *Hyalinobatrachinae* Guayasamin et al., 2009.

Hydrolaetare: G. *hydor* (ὕδωρ), water (in or from a spring, stream, river, lake or well) + S. *Leticia*, in L. *Laetitia*, from L. *laetare*, gladden, cheer; be glad. *Hydrolaetare* Gallardo, 1963. (“... *Hydrolaetare* de la familia Leptodactylidae, nombre que proviene de *Hydro* = agua y *Laetare*, derivado de *Leticia*, nombre, de la localidad de Colombia del ejemplar tipo descrito por Cochran y Goin ...”). Same root in *Hydrolaetere* — Pyron and Wiens, 2011 (incorrect subsequent spelling).

Hyla: G. *Hylas* (Ἦλας), the young lover of Heracles kidnapped by water nymphs, a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Hyla* Laurenti, 1768. (“... *Hyla comes Herculis, ab eo in Bithinia perditus; sacris postea institutis, ut continuo clamaretur hyla! hyla! hyla! quasi ad eundem repetendum; ad cujus imitationem dixit VIRGILIUS: Ut littus hyla hyla omne sonaret. Eccl. VI. 44. Quam ob rem haec quasi Hylae sacerdos nomen ejusdem merita est ...*”].

hylaedactyla, hylaedactylus: G. *yla* (υλά), wood (in the sense of log) + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Cystignathus hylaedactylus* Cope, 1868. (“... the digits without dermal margins ...”). Also *Leptodactylus hylaedactylus* — Boulenger, 1882. *Leptodactylus marmoratus hylaedactylus* — Rivero, 1961. *Leptodactylus (Lithodytes) hylaedactylus* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Adenomera hylaedactyla* (Cope, 1868).

hylaeformis: L. *hylaeformis*, shaped like a *Hyla*. *Hylodes hylaeformis* Melin, 1941. (“... Habit *Hyla arborea*-like ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis ockendeni* (Boulenger, 1912).

Hylaemorphus: L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs + G. *morphi* (μορφή), form. *Hylaemorphus* Jan, 1857. *Nomen nudum*. Also *Hylaemorphus* Schmidt, 1857. In the synonymy of *Atelopus Duméril & Bibron*, 1841.

Hylaplesia: L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs + G. *plisios* (πλησίος), close, nearby. *Hylaplesia* — Boie in Schlegel, 1826 (incorrect subsequent spelling of *Hysaplesia* Boie, 1826). (?). Also *Hyloplezia* Agassiz, 1846 (unjustified emendation of *Hylaplesia* Boie, 1827). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825 and *Dendrobates* Wagler, 1830.

hylax: G. *ýláō* (ύλάω), (of dogs) bark (as a hostile reaction to a stranger). *Hyla hylax* Heyer, 1985. (“... Latinized Greek for barker, in allusion to the distinctive dog bark-like advertisement call ...”). Also *Boana hylax* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla hylax* (Heyer, 1985).

hyleaustralis: G. *hyleis* (ἕληεις), (of locations) thickly covered with vegetation + L. *australis*, southern; of/brought by the south wind. *Pseudopaludicola*

hyleaustralis Pansonato et al., 2013. "... The specific epithet ... is derived from the Greek word "*Hylea*" meaning "great forest", and the Latin word *australis*, meaning "south" or "southern", which together is translated as "from the southern part of the Hylea" ...").

Hylella: L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs + L. *-ella*, suffix diminutive. *Hylella* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 "1861. ("... Reinhardt har endelig fra Omegnen af Lagoa Santa hjembragt 2 smaa Lövfröer, hver af dem dog kun i et enkelt Exemplar, som vilde kunne henføres til Slægten Hyla i alle andre Henseender, naar de ikke manglede ethver Spor til Ganetænder ..."). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus* Fitzinger, 1843.

Hylidae: L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs + L. *-idae*, suffix indicating the category of family in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). Hylidae Rafinesque, 1815.

Hylodes: L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs + L. *-odes*, suffix for likeness; additionally, from G. *hylos* (ὑλά), crub, brush, woodland, forest. (1) *Hylodes* Fitzinger, 1826. (?). (2) *Cystignathus hylodes* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 "1861". ("... Ryggen er mørkebrun; 3 Rækker af mørkere, mere eller mindre tydelige Pletter, der dog langt fra have saa skarp en Form eller saa bestemt en Begrænsning som hos *C. ocellatus* og *typhonius*, kunne forfølges langs ned ad Ryggen og Siderne, og en stor mørk Plet findes paa Issen mellem og bagved Öinene ..."). Today *Leptodactylus hylodes* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862). (3) The same root in Hylodidae Günther, 1858.

Hylomantis: G. *hylos* (ὑλά), crub, brush, woodland, forest + G. *mantis* (μαντις), tree-frog. *Hylomantis* Peters, 1873 "1872". (?).

Hylomedusa: G. *hylos* (ὑλά), crub, brush, woodland, forest + G. *medeon* (μεδέων) *medeoussa* (μεδέουσα), ruling, holding. *Hylomedusa* Burmeister, 1856. (?). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

hylonomus: G. *hylos* (ὑλά), crub, brush, woodland, forest + G. *nomos* (νομός), (of persons) dwelling in. *Adelastes hylonomus* Zweifel, 1986. ("... The Greek adjective *hylonomos* means forest dwelling ...").

- Hylopsis:** L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs + G. *-opsis* (-ὄψης), suffix denoting likeness. *Hylopsis* Werner, 1894. (“... Übergang zu den Dendrophrynisciden ...”). In the synonymy of *Sphaenorhynchus* Tschudi, 1838.
- Hyloxalus:** G. *hylos* (ὑλά), crub, brush, woodland, forest + G. *ixalos* (ἰξαλος), bounding, springing. *Hyloxalus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. (“... Ὑλη, *sylva*; ἰξαλος, *saltatorius* ...”). Same root in *Hyloxalinae* Grant & al., 2006. Same root in *Hylixalus* Boulenger, 1882 (injustified emendation of *Hyloxalus*).
- Hyobates:** Unclear. G. *hyos* (ὕος), pertaining to the Greek letter upsilon (Υ), or G. *hyo* (ὕω), rain + G. *bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (from βαίνω, move by taking step). *Hyobates* Jan, 1857 (*nomen nudum*). (?). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838.
- Hyophryne:** G. *hys* (ὕς), swine (male or female, wild or domesticated), boar, sow, pig, hog + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Hyophryne* Carvalho, 1954. (“... The generic name is from the Greek ὕς and φρύνος (pig-frog), with reference to the physiognomy of this form ...”). In the synonymy of *Stereocyclops* Cope, 1870.
- hypereumeces:** G. *hyper* (ὑπερ), beyond + G. *eumêkes* (εὐ-μήκης), very long, extensive, impressive. *Oscaecilia hypereumeces* Taylor, 1968. (“... A slender, much-elongated species, reaching a known length of 640 mm ...”).
- Hyperoodon:** G. *hyper* (ὑπερ), over-much, above measure + G. *odoús* (οδοῦς), tooth (human or animal, usu. pl.). *Hyperoodon* Philippi, 1902 [preoccupied by *Hyperoodon* Lacépède, 1804 (Cetacea)]. (“... Está densamente cubierta de granos orbiculares duros, que la hacen áspera como papel de lija ...”). (Philippi attributes the genus to Duméril & Bibron). In the synonymy of *Odontophrynus* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862.
- hypocellata:** G. *hypo* (ὑπό), beneath, below, under + L. *ocellata*, having ocelli, little eyes or buttonholes [in the sense of round spots]. *Hyla hypocellata* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... dous ocellos circulares amarelos no papo, dous outros maiores, oblongos na base do humerus, sobre o peito e tres outros menores entre os ultimos da base do humerus ...”). In the synonymy of *Bonana lanciformis* (Cope, 1871).

hypochondrialis: G. *hypochondrio* (υποχονδριο), under the cartilage (of the breastbone). *Hyla hypochondrialis* Daudin, 1800. (“... *Hyla supra griseo - caerulea*, *hypochondriis lateribusque artuum transversim fusco vittatis* ...”). Also *Hyla hypochondrialis* —Latreille in Sonnini de Manoncourt & Latreille, 1801 “An. X” (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Calamita hypochondrialis* — Merrem, 1820. *Phyllomedusa hypochondrialis* — Cope, 1862. *Phrynomedusa hypochondrialis* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. *Bradymedusa hypochondrialis* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. *Phyllomedusa (Pithecopus) hypochondrialis* — B. Lutz, 1950. *Pithecopus hypochondrialis hypochondrialis* — B. Lutz, 1966. Today *Pithecopus hypochondrialis* (Daudin, 1800).

Hypodictyon: G. *hypo* (ὑπό), beneath, below, under + G. *diktyon* (δικτυον), net (for fishing). *Hypodictyon* Cope, 1885 “1884”. (“... The *Phyllobates* with areolated bellies, form, I think, a separate genus, for which I propose the name *Hypodictyon* ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

hypomelas: G. *hypo* (ὑπό), beneath, below, under + G. *melas* (μέλας), black. *Emydops hypomelas* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... todo o lado inferior do corpo, desde o mento até a ponta dos artelhos, negra ...”). Also *Ribeirina hypomelas* — Parker, 1934. In the synonymy of *Stereocyclops incrassatus* Cope, 1870.

Hypsiboas: G. *hypsilos* (ὑψηλόσ), (of a harp) high-pitched + G. *boao* (βοάω), scream, howl. *Hypsiboas* Wagler, 1830. (“... Ὑψιβοας. *Nomen ranae, sic dictae ab alta voce* ...”). One of the characters of the *Batrachomyomachia*, the war between the frogs and the mice, a satire on the Iliad mistakenly attributed to Homer, known as “the loud brawler”, who killed the mouse Lychenora. In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

Hypsipsophus: G. *hypsi* (υψη), high up in the air, on high, aloft + G. *psophos* (ψόφος), noise, sound, resound. *Hypsipsophus* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

Hysaplesia: As such, *Hysaplesia* is an etymological nonsense, and probably is a *lapsus calami* for *Hylaplesia* (see), but stand as the correct original spell-

ing under Article 32. 2 of the Code. *Hysaplesia* Boie in Schlegel, 1826 (suppressed for purposes of the Principle of Priority, but not for those of the Principle of Homonymy). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825 and *Dendrobates* Wagler, 1830.

iaspidiense: G. *iaspis* (ἰασπίς), jasper + L. *ense*, suffix denoting place, locality, country. *Centrolenella iaspidiensis* Ayarzagüena, 1992. (“... del L. *iaspes*, piedra de jaspe, que forma el lecho de la Quebrada Jaspe, única localidad donde se ha encontrado hasta la fecha...”). Also *Centrolene iaspidiensis* — Duellman, 1993. *Hyalinobatrachium iaspidiense* — Myers & Donnelly, 1997. Today *Hyalinobatrachium iaspidiense* (Ayarzagüena, 1992).

ibiara: T. *ibiara*, corr. *yby-ra*, what is born from the ground. *Caecilia ibiara* Daudin, 1803 “An. XI” (substitute name for *Caecilia tentaculata*). (“... Le nom qui sert à désigner cette espèce a été employé par Marcgrave, d’après les habitans du Brésil, pour l’amphisbène enfumé ...”). In the synonymy of *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758.

ibirapitanga: P. [Município de] Ibirapitanga, state of Bahia, Brazil; from T. *ibira-pitanga*, brasilwood, *Paubrasilia echinata* (T. *ibirá-* stick, tree, wood; trunk + T. *pitanga*, reddish, brownish, or T. *piranga*, red). *Hyla ibirapitanga* Cruz et al., 2003. [“... Além de homenagear a localidade-tipo, *ibirapitanga* é uma palavra tupi-guarani que significa “madeira-vermelha”, denominação indígena para o Pau-Brasil (*Cesalpinia echinata*) ...]. Today *Aplastodiscus ibirapitanga* (Cruz et al., 2003).

ibisoroca: T. *yby* or *yvy*, earth, ground + T. *sorok*, crevice, crack, with the meaning of ravine or gully. *Pseudopaludicola ibisoroca* Pansonato et al., 2016. (“... By coining the nomina *ibisoroca*, we intend to call attention to not only the fact that the toponymic population of our new species inhabits a highly impacted site, but also the urgent need for catchment conservation programs in the Neotropics ...”).

ibitiguara: T. *ibitiguara*, fom *ybytyriguara*, inhabitant of the sierra, highlander. *Hyla ibitiguara* Cardoso, 1983. [“... O nome aplicado à espécie em questão é de origem Tupi (*ibitiguara*, *ibitiriguara* = *ybytyriguara*) e significa

morador da serra ...”]. Also *Boana ibitiguara* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla ibitiguara* (Cardoso, 1983).

ibitinga: P. Ibitinga, from T. *yby-tinga*, white earth or white clay, in the sense of cloud or fog. *Brachycephalus ibitinga* Condez et al., 2021. (“... The specific epithet *ibitinga* is a Portuguese noun derived from the indigenous Tupi-Guarani words *yby* + *tinga* ... which together compose a name applied to describe the fog ...”).

ibitipoca: P. [Serra do] Ibitipoca, mountain range in the state of Minas Gerais, Brazil; from T. *ybytyra-poca*, broken mountain; volcano. *Hyla ibitipoca* Caramaschi & Feio, 1990. (“... The species is named for the type locality in the Serra do Ibitipoca ...”). Also *Boana ibitipoca* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla ibitipoca* (Caramaschi & Feio, 1990).

icamiaba: (?) Icamiaba, a woman from the matriarchal Amazonian community who lived around Lake Iacinaruá and used the green stones known as *muiraquitãs* as a symbol. *Boana icamiaba* Peloso et al., 2018. [“... These warriors, first described by friar Gaspar de Carvajal (a member of the Francisco Orellana expedition ... were members of isolated tribes composed of women only ...”].

icterica, ictericus: L. *icterica*, or G. *ikterikos* (ικτερίκος), jaundiced. (1) *Bufo ictericus* Spix, 1824. [“... *cacaotico-brunnescens* (...) *albo-flavis supra & subtus variegatus* ...”]. Also *Docidophryne icterica* — Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. *Bufo marinus ictericus* — Müller, 1927. *Bufo ictericus ictericus* — Cochran, 1950. *Chaunus ictericus* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella icterica* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Scinax icterica* Duellman & Wiens, 1993. (“... refers to the pale yellow color characteristic of these frogs when they are active at night ...”). Today *Scinax ictericus* Duellman & Wiens, 1993.

igniocolus: L. *ignis*, fire, brightness + L. *oculus*, eye. *Hyalinobatrachium igniocolus* Noonan & Bonett, 2003. (“... The name refers to the distinctive red color of part of the iris ...”). Also *Hyalinobatrachium igniocolus* — Barrio-Amorós & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2008 (incorrect subsequent spelling of the species name). In the synonymy of *Hyalinobatrachium cappellei* (van Lidth de Jeude, 1904).

iheringii: Ihering + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hermann Friedrich Albrecht von Ihering (1850-1930), German-Brazilian zoologist. *Phyllomedusa iheringii* Boulenger, 1885. Also *Phyllomedusa burmeisteri iheringii* — B. Lutz, 1950. *Phyllomedusa (Pithecopus) burmeisteri iheringii* — B. Lutz, 1950. *Pithecopus burmeisteri iheringii* — B. Lutz, 1966.

ileamazonicus: S. Ilea Amazônica, the largest humid tropics zone in the world. *Eleutherodactylus stegolepis ileamazonicus* Rivero, 1961. (“... All specimens were collected on the forest floor or on the stems of plants at not more than a foot from the ground ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis vilarsi* (Melin, 1941).

Iliobates: G. *ilyos* (ιλύος), mud + G. *bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (from βαίνω, move by taking step). *Iliobates* Steindachner, 1867. (?). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema Tschudi*, 1838.

Iliodiscus: L. *ilum*, area from hips to groin + L. *discus*, disk/disc; disk-shaped object. *Iliodiscus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... O macho provido de um forte disco lateral na região iliaca ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus Tschudi*, 1838.

imbegue: T. *i*, it is + T. *mbegue*, slow. *Scinax imbegue* Nunes et al., 2012. (“... in allusion to the pulse rate, which is much slower than that of *Scinax alter* ...”).

imitator: L. *imitator*, one who imitates or copies. (1) *Atelopus imitator* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... Esta forma muito se aproxima de *A. cruciger* Martens, conforme a estampa dada por Günther, mas com o colorido semelhante ao de um joven de *Bufo crucifer* ...”). Today *Dendrophryniscus imitator* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920). (2) *Paludicola imitator* Barbour & Dunn, 1921. (“... In habit and marking recalling the common European *Hyla* ...”). Today “*Hyla*” *imitator* (Barbour & Dunn, 1921) *Incertae sedis*.

imitatrix: L. *imitatrix*, female imitator. *Hyla imitatrix* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. [“... A coloração imita a de *H. quadrangulum* sendo o fundo verde oliváceo (em vida) ou sepiáceo mais amarelado no lado abdominal ...”]. Also *Phrynohyas imitatrix* — Bokermann, 1966. Today *Trachycephalus imitatrix* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

- inconspicua:** L. *inconspicua*, not readily noticeable; inconspicuous. *Hyla rubra inconspicua* Melin, 1941. (“... As it does not exactly resemble any species of the group in question and some of them are hardly sufficiently distinguished, it may for the present form a subspecies of *rubra* ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax funereus* (Cope, 1874).
- incrassatus:** L. *incrassatus*, fattened; make thick/stout. *Stereocyclops incrassatus* Cope, 1870. (“... The epidermis is everywhere thickened by a chitin-like deposit, which is readily cracked. It is thickest on the soles, the tarsi, and the gular region ...”). Also *Hypopachus incrassatus* Parker, 1934.
- indistinctum:** L. *indistinctum*, not separated; indistinct, obscure. *Siphonops indistinctus* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... *annuli corporis indistincti & incompleti* ...”). Today *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).
- indris:** L. *Indri*, genus of Primates of the suborder Strepsirrhini. *Hypsiboas indris* Cope, 1867. (?). Also *Hyla indris* — Boulenger, 1882. In the synonymy of *Boana xerophylla* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).
- inframaculata, inframaculatus:** L. *infra*, below + L. *maculata*, -us, spotted. *Hyla inframaculata* Boulenger, 1882. (“... lower surface of head and body whitish, brown-spotted ...”). Also *Osteocephalus inframaculatus* — Jungfer, 2010. Today *Dryaderces inframaculata* (Boulenger, 1882).
- infulata:** L. *infulata*, invest/vest with mitre/episcopal insignia. *Hyla infulata* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. (“... von einem Auge zu dem anderen ein breiter graubrauner Querstreif ...”). Also *Auletris infulata* — Wagler, 1830. *Hyla* (*Centrotelma*) *infulata* — Burmeister, 1856. In the synonymy of *Boana albomarginata* (Spix, 1824).
- ingens:** L. *ingens*, huge, vast, enormous. *Phrynohyas ingens* Duellman, 1956. (“... A gigantic member of the genus ...”). Also *Hyla tibiatrix ingens* — Rivero, 1961. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).

- inguinalis:** L. *inguinis*, groin + L. *-alis*, adjectival suffix. *Eleutherodactylus inguinalis* Parker, 1940. (“... a large, chrome yellow, black-bordered, inguinal ocellus ...”). Today *Pristimantis inguinalis* (Parker, 1940).
- inopina, inopinata:** L. *inopina*, *-ta*, unexpected. (1) *Adenomera inopinata* Carvalho et al., 2021. (“... referring to the unexpected discovery of this species in the region of the middle Tapajós River ...”). (2) *Rhinella inopina* Vaz-Silva et al., 2012. (“... The name is appropriate because is the most inland species of the *Rhinella crucifer* species group ...”).
- inornata, inornatus:** L. *inornata*, *-us*, unadorned. (1) *Bufo crucifer inornatus* A. Lutz, 1934. (“... As faces laterais do tronco e o lado interior das coxas não mostram desenho decorativo, mas pode haver algumas manchas escuras ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Hyla inornata* B. Lutz, 1973. (“... I would suggest calling the plain form *Hyla inornata* ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana cinerascens* (Spix, 1824).
- insperatus:** L. *insperatus*, un hoped for, unexpected, unforeseen. (1) *Physalaeus insperatus* Cruz et al., 2008. (“... in allusion to the fortuitous finding of these old, unnamed specimens ...”). (2) *Scinax insperatus* Silva & Alves-Silva, 2011. (“... used as an allusion to the serendipitous finding of the new species where our expectation was to find the southernmost limit of *Scinax v-signatus* ...”). Also *Oloolygon insperata* — Duellman et al., 2016.
- insulanus:** L. *insula*, island + L. *-anus*, belonging to. *Siphonops insulanus* Ihering, 1911. (“... Est. S. Paulo, Ilha Victoria e Ilha de São Sebastião ...”). Today *Luetkenotyphlus insulanus* (Ihering, 1911).
- intermedia, intermedius:** L. *intermedia*, intermediate. (1) *Ceratophrys intermedia* Barbour, 1908. (“... This species stands between *C. boiei* Wied, and *C. fryi* Günther ...”). Also *Stombus intermedius* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Proceratophrys boiei* (Wied-Neuwied, 1824). (2) *Lepidodactylus intermedius* A. Lutz, 1930. (“... They are not unlike *podicipinus* Cope and *curtus* Barbour and Noble, though different from both and nearly intermediate in size ...”).

intermixta: L. *intermixtus*, intermingle, mix, mix among, mingle. *Hyla intermixta* Daudin in Sonnini de Manoncourt & Latreille, 1801 “An. X”. (“... La raine bigarrée ...”). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).

interrupta, interruptus: L. *interrupta*, -us, drive a gap in, break up; cut short, interrupt. *Caecilia interrupta* Cuvier, 1829. (“... *Caec. interrupta*, Nob., où les lignes blanches des anneaux ne se correspondent pas en dessous ...”). Also *Siphonops interruptus* — Gray, 1850. In the synonymy of *Siphonops annulatus* (Mikan, 1820).

iquitorum: S. Iquitos, South American native culture and a Peruvian city in department Loreto; from Iq. *iquitos*, squirrels + L. -*orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. Honouring the native South American tribe called Iquito. *Scinax iquitorum* Moravec et al., 2009. (“... In Peru the Iquitos inhabit small settlements on the banks of the Marañón, Tigre, and Nanay rivers, which originally included the entire area of today’s town of Iquitos ...”).

irroratus: L. *irroratus*, wet with dew, besprinkle, rain on. *Physalaemus irroratus* Cruz et al., 2007. (“... The specific epithet “*irroratus*” is a latin vernacular name meaning “covered with granules¹⁰”. It refers to the granulated texture of the dorsal skin ...”).

Ischnocnema: G. *ischnos* (ισχνός), thin, lean, weak + G. *knemia* (κνημία), leg. *Ischnocnema* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862. (“...tynde og spinkle Lemmer og navnlig forholdsviis lange Baglemmer ...”).

itacolomi: P. [Parque Estadual do] Itacolomi, Município de Ouro Preto, Estado de Minas Gerais, Brasil (in turn, from T. *itá*, stone + T. *curumi*, children; refers to a peak formed by a large boulder with a smaller one beside it, as a son. *Phyllomedusa itacolomi* Caramaschi et al., 2006. (“... The specific name ... is given after the type locality. “*Itacolomi*” is derived from the native Tupi language “*ita*” (rock) and “*curumin*” (children), meaning “rock with children” or alternatively “children of the rock”, in allusion to a peculiar rock structure found in the region ...”). In the synonymy of *Pithecopus ayeaye* B. Lutz, 1966.

¹⁰ *Irroratus* in the sense of “covered with granules” appears, at least as far as we were able to inquire, only in Brown (1954); despite our efforts, we did not find that meaning in other Latin lexicons.

itamari: Itamar + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Itamar Martins, Brazilian herpetologist. *Proceratophrys itamari* Mângia et al., 2014.

itambe: P. [Parque Estadual do Pico do] Itambé, from T. *itá*, stone + T. *aimbé*, rough, sharp, cutting. *Crossodactylodes itambe* Barata et al., 2013. (Refers to the type locality, “... Parque Estadual do Pico do Itambé, 18°23’53.1”S, 43°20’39.6”W, 1921 m a. s. l., municipality of Santo Antônio do Itambé, State of Minas Gerais, Brazil ...”).

itapoty: T. *itapoty*, lichen or moss, from T. *itá*, rock + T. *poty*, to flower, to flourish. *Bokermannohyla itapoty* Lugli & Haddad, 2006. (“... The specific name is an allusion to the resemblance of the dorsal color to lichens that occur on rocks ...”).

Itapotihyla: T. *itapoty*, lichen or moss, from T. *itá*, rock + T. *poty*, to flower, to flourish + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Itapotihyla* Faivovich et al., 2005. (“... The generic name is an allusion to the resemblance of the unique known species of this genus with lichens and mosses ...”).

izecksohni: Izecksohn + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Eugenio Izecksohn (1932-2013), Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Hyla izecksohni* Jim & Caramaschi, 1979. Also *Boana izecksohni* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla izecksohni* (Jim & Caramaschi, 1979). (2) *Brachycephalus izecksohni* Ribeiro et al., 2005. (3) *Crossodactylodes izecksohni* Peixoto, 1983. (4) *Cycloramphus izecksohni* Heyer, 1983. (5) *Dendrophryniscus izecksohni* Cruz et al., 2019. (6) *Fritziana izecksohni* Folly et al., 2018. (7) *Eleutherodactylus izecksohni* Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989 “1988”. Today *Ischnocnema izecksohni* (Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989). (8) *Proceratophrys izecksohni* Dias et al., 2013.

jackia: E?. *jakia*, vernacular name. *Rana jackia* Bonnaterre, 1789. (According to Fermin, 1765, “... en Nègre Anglois *Jakus* ...”). In the synonymy of *Pseudis paradoxa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

jaguariaivensis: P. Jaguariaiva, from T. *yaguar-i-ahibá*, fierce jaguar river. Municipality of the state of Paraná, Brazil. *Hypsiboas jaguariaivensis* Caramaschi et al., 2010. (“... The specific epithet refers to the type locality of the new species ...”; in turn, Parque Estadual do Cerrado (24°10’S, 49°40’W, 659 m altitude), Municipality of Jaguariaiva, State of Paraná, Brazil). Today *Boana jaguariaivensis* (Caramaschi et al., 2010).

jandaia: T. *jandaia*, king parakeet, *Aratinga jandaya* (Gmelin, 1788). *Phyllomedusa jandaia* Bokermann & Sazima, 1978. (“... O colorido geral do exemplar vivo era verde claro no dorso, com o ventre branco amarelado e as partes escondidas salmão laranja intenso ...”). Today *Phasmahyla jandaia* (Bokermann & Sazima, 1978).

japi: T. *japi*, from T. *y-apó*, the water that overflows, that floods. *Hylodes japi* de Sá et al., 2015. (“... The name of the new species, *japi*, is derived from an indigenous Tupi word meaning springs. Here, it refers to the breeding habitat of the new species, transparent rivulets, which are abundant in its type locality ...”).

jaredi: Jared + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carlos Alberto Gonçalves Silva Jared, Brazilian herpetologist. *Pseudopaludicola jaredi* Andrade et al., 2016.

jazmynmcdonaldae: Jazmyn McDonald + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Jazmyn McDonald, US American conservacionist. *Pseudopaludicola jazmynmcdonaldae* Andrade et al., 2019.

jimi: Jim + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jorge Jim (1942-2011), Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Bufo jimi* Stevaux, 2002. Also *Chaunus jimi* — Frost et al., 2006. *Rhinella jimi* — Chaparro et al., 2007. In the synonymy of *Rhinella diptycha* (Cope, 1862). (2) *Chiasmocleis jimi* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2001. Also *Syncope jimi* — de Sá et al., 2012. *Chiasmocleis (Syncope) jimi* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. (3) *Hyla jimi* Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999. Today *Dendropsophus jimi* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999).

joannae: Jo Ann + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Jo Ann Oxley-Foster, US American philanthropist. *Hyla joannae* Köhler & Lötters, 2001. Today *Dendropsophus joannae* (Köhler & Lötters, 2001).

joaquinii: Joaquim + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Joaquim Venâncio Fernandes (1895-1955), Brazilian technician. *Hyla raddiana joaquinii* B. Lutz, 1968. {"... It is honouring the co-finder, my late assistant and collaborator, Joaquim Venancio, whose name is the same as that of the patron saint of the type locality ..." (in turn, "outside São Joaquim, [Serra Geral,] in the state of Santa Catarina (28°17'19"S., 49°55'56"W.) at about 1,350 meters altitude, in open, montane meadow formation", Brazil}. Also *Hyla pulchella joaquinii* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Hyla joaquinii* — Garcia et al., 2003. *Hypsiboas joaquinii* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana joaquinii* (B. Lutz, 1968).

joazeirensis: P. Joazeiro, in the original description (actually Juazeiro, municipality in the state of Bahia, Brazil, 9°24'50"S, 40°30'10"W; in turn, from T. *juazeiro*, spiny fruit, vernacular name of the tree *Zizyphus joazeiro*, Rhamnaceae) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ceratophrys joazeirensis* Mercadal de Barrio, 1986. ("... Locus typicus: Joazeiro, Estado de Bahia, Brasil ...").

johnstonei: Johnstone + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Robert Stewart Johnstone (1855-1936), British solicitor and colonial administrator. *Eleutherodactylus johnstonei* Barbour, 1914. Also *Hylodes johnstonei* — Nieden, 1923. [Species introduced in Brazil].

jolyi: Joly + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Aylthon Brandão Joly (1924-1975), Brazilian botanist. *Leptodactylus jolyi* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978.

jordanensis: P. [Campos do] Jordão, city in Serra da Mantiqueira, state of São Paulo, Brazil + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Cycloramphus jordanensis* Heyer, 1983. ("... named after the type locality ..."). Also *Megaelosia jordanensis* — Verdade & Rodrigues, 2009 "2008". *Hylodes jordanensis* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Phantasmarana jordanensis* (Heyer, 1983). (2) *Physa-*

laemus jordanensis Bokermann, 1967. (Named after the type locality, "... Lagoinha da Serra, 1. 900 m, Campos do Jordão, São Paulo, Brasil ...").

juami: P. Juami, a black water river, a tributary of the white water Japurá River; also, the name of the Estação Ecológica Juami-Japurá, State of Amazonas, Brazil (1. 96455° S, 67. 93579° W; ~ 87 m a. s. l.), on its east bank. From T. *Juamis*, name of a partiality of native-Brazilians established on the banks of the Japurá River. *Allobates juami* Simões et al., 2018. ("... The specific epithet ... refers to the species type locality, the forests alongside the Juami River, which is currently protected by the ESEC Juami-Japurá ...").

juiju: T. *juí*, frog + T. *ju*, spine. *Bokermannohyla juiju* Faivovich et al., 2009. ("... refers to the prepollical and humeral spines of the new species ...").

juikitam: T. *juí*, frog + T. *kitam*, wart. *Adenomera juikitam* Carvalho & Giaretta, 2013. ("... refers to the warty skin texture of the species ...").

juimirim: T. *juí*, frog + T. *mirim*, small. *Cycloramphus juimirim* Haddad & Sazima, 1989. ("... The name "juimirim" means "small frog" in the language of the Tupi Indians ...").

juipoca: T. *juí*, frog + T. *poca*, to click, snap. *Eleutherodactylus juipoca* Sazima & Cardoso, 1978. ("... *Canto* – Uma série curta e ascendente de estalidos, semelhantes ao som produzido por castanholas ..."). Today *Ischnocnema juipoca* (Sazima & Cardoso, 1978).

Julianus: Julián + L. *-anus*, belonging to. Honouring Julián Faivovich, Argentinian herpetologist. *Julianus* Duellman et al., 2016. Also *Juliana* Duellman et al., 2016 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Scinax* Wagler, 1830.

juncae: Juncá + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Flora Acuña Juncá, Brazilian herpetologist. *Scinax juncae* Nunes & Pombal, 2010.

- juninensis:** S. Junin, Andean lake (a. k. a. Chinchaycocha) in the homonymous Peruvian department, from Q. *surin*, pampa, vast place + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Rana juninensis* Tschudi, 1845. (?). (Probable confusion with *Batrachophrynus macrostomus* Peters, 1873, today in *Telmatobius*). In the synonymy of *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824).
- juquinha:** P. *Juquinha*, nickname of José Patrício, a. k. a. Juquinha das Flores (?-1983), in turn from P. *juquinha*, despective, the silly one of the class. *Odonophrynus juquinha* Rocha et al., 2017. (“... The specific epithet is a noun in apposition and honors “Juquinha das Flores”, a hermit whose simplicity and gentleness made him a folkloric figure at Serra do Cipó, type locality of the new species ...”).
- jureia:** P. [Estação Ecológica da] Juréia-Itatins-Núcleo Rio Verde (24°22’S, 47°04’W, Datum WGS 84; 32 m altitude), municipality of Iguape, state of São Paulo, Brazil (in turn, from T. *jureia*, high tide, from T. *jur*, to grow [the tide] + T. *eia*, wash). (1) *Dendrophryniscus jureia* Cruz et al., 2019. (“... The name of the species is an allusion to the type locality, in the Estação Ecológica da Juréia-Itatins ...”). (2) *Hyla jureia* Pombal & Gordo, 1991. (“... O epíteto específico *jureia* é um nome em aposição, do Tupi (*juré* + *eia*), que significa “maré alta que lava as pedras”, sendo ao mesmo tempo parte do nome do local de coleta, Estação Ecológica da Juréia-Itatins ...”). Also *Ololygon jureia* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Scinax jureia* (Pombal & Gordo, 1991).
- kaingang:** Gê. *kaingang*, people of the forest. *Proceratophrys kaingang* Santana et al., 2021. [“... The specific epithet ... (refers) to the Kaingang (or Cainganguê) ethnic group, which inhabits the plateau regions of the states of Paraná, São Paulo, Rio Grande do Sul and Santa Catarina, Brazil ...”].
- kamagarini:** M. *kamagarini*, demon or devil. *Dendropsophus kamagarini* Rivadeneira et al., 2018. (“... The Matsigenka language is spoken by the Matsigenka people who inhabit the highlands and lowlands of southeastern Peru, in the departments of Cusco and Madre de Dios. Judeo-Christian religions depict the demon as a human figure with horns. The species name is in allusion to the prominent horn-like tubercles on the upper eyelid of *D. kamagarini* ...”).

karcharias: *G. karcharias* (καρχαρίασ), shark. *Eleutherodactylus karcharias* Flores & Rodríguez, 1997. (“... the species name is the Ancient Greek for shark, in reference to the middorsal tubercle, reminiscent of the dorsal fin of a shark ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis skydmainos* (Flores & Rodríguez, 1997).

karst: Ge. *karst*, said of a limestone formation, produced by the erosive or solvent action of water. *Ischnocnema karst* Canedo et al., 2012. (“... refers to the geologic characteristics of the type locality, a typical karst formation of the upper Rio São Francisco basin ...”).

kaupii: Kaupp + L. -ii, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Johann Jakob von Kaup (1803-1873), German zoologist. *Caecilia kaupii* Berthold, 1859. Also *Typhlonectus kaupii* — Ginés, 1959. Today *Potomotyplus kaupii* (Berthold, 1859).

kautskyi: Kautsky + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Roberto Anselmo Kautsky (1924-2010), Brazilian botanist. (1) *Phyllodytes kautskyi* Peixoto & Cruz, 1988. (2) *Ololygon kautskyi* S. Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 1991. Today *Scinax kautskyi* (S. Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 1991).

kayapo: T. *kayapo*, those who look like monkeys; native Brazilian self denominated *mebêngôkre*. *Adenomera kayapo* Carvalho et al., 2021. (“... It is thought that the Kayapó, who name themselves *mebêngôkre*, once inhabited a vast region between the Araguaia and Tocantins rivers, but were pushed westward by the early colonizers in the 19th century ...”).

kilombo: P. *quilombo*, secret place where escaped slaves stayed or went, usually hidden in the woods; from Ki. *kilombo*, war camp. *Leptodactylus kilombo* Silva et al., 2020. (“... The type locality of *Leptodactylus kilombo* is located nearby an ancient quilombola settlement named Chapada dos Negros in Arraias, in the south of Tocantins State, north central Brazil ...”).

klappenbachi: Klappenbach + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Miguel Ángel Klappenbach (1920-2000), Uruguayan zoologist. *Melanophryniscus klappenbachi* Prigioni & Langone, 2000.

knudseni: Knudsen + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jens Werner Knudsen (1928-?), US American biologist. *Leptodactylus knudseni* Heyer, 1972.

koechlini: Koechlin + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Enrique Koechlin von Stein, Peruvian businessman. *Hyla koechlini* Duellman & Trueb, 1989. Also *Hyla koecklini* — Duellman, 2005 (incorrect subsequent spelling). Today *Dendropsophus koechlini* (Duellman & Trueb, 1989).

koki: Kok + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Pierre Kok (?), Dutch missionary and ethnographer in the Colombian mission San Bernardo at Rio Papuri. *Ctenocranius koki* Melin, 1941. Also *Eleutherodactylus koki* — Myers, 1962. In the synonymy of *Strabomantis sulcatus* (Cope, 1874).

korekore: Mu. *korekore*, frog (etymology by the authors). *Proceratophrys korekore* Santana et al., 2021. (“... The specific epithet “*korekore*” ... means frog in the language of the Mundurucus, an indigenous group that inhabits the southwestern parts of Pará state and the northern region of Mato Grosso state, Brazil ...”).

krausae: Krause L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Ligia Krause, Brazilian herpetologist. *Dendrophryniscus krausae* Cruz & Fusinato, 2008.

kroyeri: Krøyer + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Henrik Nikolai Krøyer (1799-1870), Danish marine biologist. *Gomphobates krøyeri* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. Also *Paludicola krøyeri* — Boulenger, 1882. *Physalaemus kroyeri* — Bokermann, 1966. Today *Physalaemus kroyeri* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

kweti: Kwet + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Axel Alexander Karl Kwet, German herpetologist. *Adenomera kweti* Carvalho et al., 2019.

labialis: *L. labialis*, pertaining to the lips. *Cystignathus labialis* Cope, 1877. (“... A brilliant white band extends from the anterior part of the upper lip ...”). Also *Leptodactylus labialis* — Brocchi, 1881. *Leptodactylus mystaceus labialis* — Shreve, 1957. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus mystacinus* (Burmeister, 1861).

labyrinthicus: *L. labyrinthus*, labyrinth, maze + *L. -icus*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to, pertaining to, having the nature of, made of, quality of, state or condition of. *Rana labyrinthica* Spix, 1824. (“... *lituris labyrinthicis, nigro-brunueis variegato* ...”). Also *Cystignathus labyrinthicus* — Wagler, 1830. *Leptodactylus labyrinthicus* — Girard, 1853. *Pleurodema labyrinthicum* — Günther, 1859 “1858”. *Gnathophysa labyrinthica* — Cope, 1865. *Leptodactylus pentadactylus labyrinthicus* — Müller, 1927. Today *Leptodactylus labyrinthicus* (Spix, 1824).

lacrimae: *L. lacrimae*, tear; exuded gum/sap. *Chiasmocleis lacrimae* Peloso et al., 2014. (“... The name is used as an allusion to the teardrop body shape of most gastrophryne microhylids, especially noticeable in many species of *Chiasmocleis* ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) lacrimae* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

lacrimosus: *L. lacrimosus*, tearful, weeping; causing tears. *Cyclocephalus lacrimosus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (?). Also *Hylodes lacrimosus* — Nieden, 1923. *Eleutherodactylus lacrimosus* — Gorham, 1966. Today *Pristimantis lacrimosus* (Jiménez de la Espada, 1875).

lactea, lacteus: *L. lactea*, milky; milk-white. (1) *Basanitia lactea* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. (“... Côr geral branca lactea (carnea?) no alcohol ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus lacteus* — Lynch, 1968. *Eleutherodactylus lactea* — Harding, 1983 (incorrect subsequent spelling). Today *Ischnocnema lactea* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923). (2) *Hyla lactea* Daudin, 1800. (“... Raine couleur du lait ...”). Also *Calamita lacteus* — Merrem, 1820. *Sphaenorhynchus lacteus* — Tschudi, 1838. *Dryomelictes lactea* — Fitzinger, 1843. Today *Sphaenorhynchus lacteus* (Daudin, 1800). (3) *Hyla lactea* Lönnberg, 1896. (?). In the synonymy of *Boana boans* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Lacusirana: *L. lacus*, lake + *L. rana*, frog. *Lacusirana* Hillis & Wilcox, 2005. (“... in reference to the habitat of most of the species in this group ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

Ladailadne: Dubois, 1987 “1986”. (?) *Ladailadne*, arbitrary combination of letters. (“... Il s’agit d’une combinaison arbitraire de lettres, à laquelle nous attribuons le genre grammatical féminin ...”). In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

ladigesi: Ladiges + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Werner Ladiges (1910-1984), German ichthyologist. *Nectocaecilia ladigesi* Taylor, 1968. In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

laevis: *L. levis*, free from irregularities of surface, smooth; slippery. (1) *Pipa laevis* Cuvier, 1831. (“... There is a true *Pipa* in the Cabinet du Roi, from Rio Negro, which is entirely smooth and with an unusually narrow head ...”). In the synonymy of *Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Pseudis laevis* Parker, 1935 [“... The true rough-skinned *Pseudis limellum* (Cope) appears to be confined to the Paraguay-La Plata river system, and its place taken in the Amazon basin by a very similar species distinguished by its completely smooth skin, slightly shorter legs, and rather different colour ...”]. Also. *Lysapsus limellus laevis* — Gallardo, 1961. Today *Lysapsus laevis* (Parker, 1935).

lamasi: Lamas + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Gerardo Lamas, Peruvian entomologist. *Dendrobates lamasi* Morales, 1992. Also *Ranitomeya lamasi* — Grant et al., 2006. In the synonymy of *Ranitomeya sirensis* (Aichinger, 1991).

lanciformis: *L. lanciformis*, spear-shaped. *Hypsiboas lanciformis* Cope, 1871 “1870”. (“... It is characterized by its elongate acuminate head, with nearly straight, sharp canthus rostralis and vertical concave loreal region ...”). Also *Hyla lanciformis* — Boulenger, 1882. *Hyla lanciformis lanciformis* — Rivero, 1971. Today *Boana lanciformis* (Cope, 1871).

langei: Lange + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Rudolf Bruno Lange (1922-2016), Brazilian zoologist. *Hyla langei* Bokermann, 1965. Also *Boana langei* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla langei* (Bokermann, 1965).

langsdorffii: Langsdorff + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Georg Heinrich Freiherr von Langsdorff [a. k. a. Grigori Ivanovitch Langsdorff] (1774-1852), German-Russian naturalist and traveler. *Hyla Langsdorffii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. Also *Hypsiboas langsdorffii* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Hyla (Centrotelma) langsdorffii* — Burmeister, 1856. *Hyla langsdorffii* — Günther, 1859 “1858”. *Osteocephalus langsdorffii* — Cope, 1867. Today *Itapotihyla langsdorffii* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

lanthanites: G. *lanthano* (λανθάνω), undetected, hidden one + G *-ites* (-ῖτης), having the nature of, like. *Eleutherodactylus lanthanites* Lynch, 1975. (“... in reference to my belief prior to field work that this frog might be a polymorph of the sympatric *E. conspicillatus* ...”). Today *Pristimantis lanthanites* (Lynch, 1975).

lateristriga: L. *lateris*, side; flank + L. *striga*, row or strip of anything. (1) *Hyla lateristriga* Spix, 1824. (“... *stria inter utrumque oculum transversa, nigra, alia ad latera dorsi fulva* ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax ruber* (Laurenti, 1768). (2) *Nattereria lateristriga* Steindachner, 1864. (“... Eine breite, intensiv schwarzbraune, sammtartige Längsbinde, nach vorne und hinten zugespitzt, zwischen dem hinteren Augenwinkel und der Lendengegend, am vorderen unteren Rande zwischen dem Auge und der Schulter hell gesäumt ...”). Today *Physalaemus lateristriga* (Steindachner, 1864).

lateristrigata, lateristrigatus: L. *lateris*, side; flank + L. *striga*, row or strip of anything + L. *atus*, having the nature of. *Elosia lateristrigata* Baumann, 1912. (“... in den meisten Fällen nur eine dunkelbraun und weiße Marmorierung der Hinterseite auf. Am Unterschenkel und Fuß beobachtet man dunkle Flecken ...”). *Hylodes lateristrigatus* (Baumann, 1912).

laticeps: L. *latus*, wide, broad; spacious, extensive+ L. *-ceps*, -headed. *Procera-tophrys laticeps* Izecksohn & Peixoto, 1981. (“... Tamanho grande, com

apêndices palpebrais longos e um pequeno apêndice anterior no lábio superior, distinguindo-se de *P. appendiculata* e *P. boiei* principalmente pela maior largura da cabeça ...”).

latinus: *L. latus*, wide, broad; spacious, extensive + *L. nasus*, nose. *Leptodactylus latinus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (“... contorno maxilar saliente, avanzado sobre la abertura de la boca, inferior en casi toda su extensión, y particularmente en el hocico, cuya punta es cónica y encorvada hacia abajo ...”). Also *Leptodactylus latinus latinus* — Ceï, 1980.

latistriata: *L. latus*, wide, broad; spacious, extensive + *L. striata*, provided with channels; grooves; wrinkles. *Hyla latistriata* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2004. [“...O nome da espécie é composto por dois adjetivos latinos, *latus*, largo, e *striatus*, listrado ou estriado, em alusão às largas faixas que compõem seu padrão de colorido dorsal...”]. Also *Hypsiboas latistriatus* — Faivovich et al. (2005). In the synonymy of *Boana polytaenia* (Cope, 1870).

latrans: *L. latrare*, bark, bark at. *Rana latrans* Steffen, 1815. [(?) “... Ranae latrantis descriptio ... Rana latrans a cel. Tilesio in Brasilia detecta est ...”]. Also *Leptodactylos latrans* — Lavilla et al., 2010 (*error typographicus*). Today *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815).

latro: *L. latro*, robber, brigand, bandit; plunderer. *Pristimantis latro* Oliveira et al., 2017. (“... refers to the common name generally attributed to the species of *Pristimantis* - “Robber Frogs” - that exhibit a dark band on the snout, creating the illusion of a robber’s mask ...”).

laurae: Laura + *L. -ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Laura Miriam Heyer, W. Ronald Heyer’s daughter. *Leptodactylus laurae* Heyer, 1978. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus furnarius* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978.

lauramiriamae: Laura Miriam + *L. -ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Laura Miriam Heyer, W. Ronald Heyer’s daughter. *Leptodactylus lauramiriamae* Heyer & Crombie, 2005. (“... The species is named for Laura Miriam Heyer, daughter of WRH. Laura previously had a species of *Leptodactylus* named for her, which had to be placed in the synonymy of *L. furnarius* ...”).

lauroi: Lauro + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Lauro Pereira Travassos (1890-1970), Brazilian parasitologist. *Dendrophryniscus brevipollicatus lauroi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. Today *Dendrophryniscus lauroi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926.

lavillai: Lavilla + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Esteban Orlando Lavilla, Argentinian herpetologist. *Odontophrynus lavillai* Cei, 1985.

laynei: Layne+ L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring James Nathaniel Layne (1926-2017), US American mammalogist. *Hyla laynei* Goin, 1957. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus reticulatus* (Jiménez de la Espada, 1870).

lazarus: G. *lazaros*, (λαζαρος) corpse. (1) *Bufo lazarus* Spix, 1824. In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758). (“... *Grandis, olivaceo-virescens* ...”). *Docidophryne Lazarus* — Fitzinger, 1861 “1860”. In the synonymy of *Rhinella poeppigii* (Tschudi, 1845).

leali: Leal + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paulo Nunes Leal (1916-2003), Brazilian military and politician, Governor of the state of Rondonia (1954-1955 and 1958-1961). *Hyla leali* Bokermann, 1964. Today *Dendropsophus leali* (Bokermann, 1964).

Leiuperinae: L. *Leiuperus*, genus of anurans due to Duméril & Bibron, 1841 (see; today in the synonymy of *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838) + L. *-inae*, suffix indicating the category of subfamily in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). *Leiuperinae* Bonaparte, 1850.

Leiuperus: G. *leios* (λείος), smooth + G. *yperoa* (υπερώα), palate. *Leiuperus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Pas de dents au palais ...”). Also *Liyperus* Agassiz, 1846 (unjustified emendation of *Leiuperus*). *Lihyperus* — O’Shaughnessy, 1875 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838.

lentiginosus: L. *lentiginosus*, lentil-shaped spot; freckle. *Bufo lentiginosus dorsalis* — Garman, 1884. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824).

leopardus: *L. leopardus*, believed to be hybrid from lion (*L. Leo*) and panther (*L. Pardus*); leopard. *Brachycephalus leopardus* Ribeiro et al., 2015. (“... dorsum, belly, arms, legs, thighs, hands, and feet covered with minute dark spots; larger dark spots scattered along the sides of the body ...”).

Lepidobatrachus: *G. lepidos* (λεπίδος), scale + *G. batrachos* (βάτραχος), frog. *Lepidobatrachus* Budgett, 1899. (?).

lepida, lepidus: *L. lepidus*, agreeable, charming, delightful, nice. *Phrynohyas lepida* Pombal et al., 2003. (“... The specific name is a Latin adjective ... meaning elegant, fine ...”). Today *Trachycephalus lepidus* (Pombal et al., 2003).

leprieurii: Leprieur + *L. -ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring François Mathias René Leprieur (1799-1870), French botanist. *Hyla Leprieurii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. Also *Hypsiboas leprieurii* — Cope, 1867. *Hyla leprieurii leprieuri* — Melin, 1941. Today *Osteocephalus leprieurii* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

leptodactyloides: *L. Leptodactylus*, genus of anurans due to Fitzinger, 1826 (see) + *G. -oeides* (-οειδής), similar to. (?). *Eleutherodactylus leptodactyloides* Andersson, 1945. Although there is no explicit information about the meaning of the name in the original description, the resemblance is such that it is indeed a *Leptodactylus*. Today *Leptodactylus leptodactyloides* (Andersson, 1945).

Leptodactylus: *G. leptos* (λεπτος), fine, thin + *G. dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826. (“... *Digiti non dilatatis, graciles* ...”). The same root in *Leptodactylidae* Werner, 1896 (1838) and *Leptodactylinae* Werner, 1896 (1838).

leptolineata, leptolineatus: *G. leptos* (λεπτος), fine, thin + *L. lineata*, -us, lined. *Hyla leptolineata* P. Braun & C. Braun, 1977. (“... O nome *leptolineata* está relacionado com as delicadas linhas longitudinais que aparecem, especialmente no dorso ...”). Also *Hypsiboas leptolineatus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana leptolineata* (P. Braun & C. Braun, 1977).

- Leptopus:** G. *leptos* (λεπτός), fine, thin + G. *pous* (πούς), foot. *Leptopus* Mayer, 1835. (“... *plantae largissime palmatae* ...”). In the synonymy of *Pipa* Laurenti, 1768.
- leptoscelis:** G. *leptos* (λεπτός), fine, thin + G. *skelos* (σκέλος), leg. *Hyla leptoscelis* Boulenger, 1918. (“... Hind limb extremely slender ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana calcarata* (Troschel in Schomburgk, 1848).
- leschenaulti:** Leschenaut + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jean Baptiste Louis Claude Théodore Leschenault de la Tour (1773-1826), French botanist and ornithologist. *Bufo Leschenaulti* Tschudi, 1838. Also *Bufo leschenaultii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. *Phrynomorphus leschenaulti* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Rhaebo leschenaultii* — Cope, 1862. In the synonymy of *Rhaebo guttatus* (Schneider, 1799).
- lescurei:** Lescure + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jean Lescure, French herpetologist. *Rhinella lescurei* Fouquet et al., 2007.
- leucocheila:** G. *leuco* (λευκο), white + G. *cheilos* (χείλος), lips. *Hyla leucocheila* Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2003. (“... The specific name is derived from the Greek substantive *cheilos* (lips) and from the Greek adjective *leucos* (white), meaning “treefrog with white lips ...”). Also *Hypsiboas leucocheilus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana leucocheila* (Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2003).
- leucoderus:** G. *leuco* (λευκο), white + G. *deros* (δερός), skin, hide. *Siphonops leucoderus* Taylor, 1968. (“... Dark brown dorsally, lighter beneath; a white area on chin and throat ...”).
- leucomelas:** G. *leuco* (λευκο), white + G. *melas* (μέλας), black. (1) *Dendrobates leucomelas* Steindachner, 1864. (“... Die ganze Oberseite der Vorder- und Hinterfüsse mit Ausnahme der orangerothen Wurzel, ferner die Unterseite der Hände und Füsse ist mit schwarzen, runden Flecken besetzt und zwar die hinteren Extremitäten reichlicher als die Vorderbeine, Die Unterseite des Körpers ist gelblich weiss, und mit grossen schwarzen, theils runden,

theils ovalen, theils noch gestreckteren Flecken geziert ...”). (2) *Hyla leucomelas* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... La rainette demi-deuil. ... Tempes noires, liserées de blanc ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana pulchella* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

leucomystax: G. *leuco* (λευκο), white + G. *mystax* (μύσταξ), moustache. *Dendrophryniscus leucomystax* Izecksohn, 1968. (“... semelhante a *Dendrophryniscus brevipollicatus* Espada, do qual difere superficialmente por mostrar uma faixa branca, como bigode, da extremidade do focinho até quase a base do úmero ...”).

leucophyllatus: G. *leuco* (λευκο), white + G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + L. -atus, having the nature of. *Rana leucophyllata* Beireis, 1783. (“... *Rana cana laevis, maculis oblongis albis inter oculos, ad latera & in medio dorsi atque in tibiis ...*”). Also *Calamita leucophyllata* — Schneider, 1799. *Calamita leucophyllatus* — Merrem, 1820. *Hypsiboas leucophyllatus* — Tschudi, 1838. *Hyla (Hyla) leucophyllata* — Burmeister, 1856. Same root in *Hyla leucophylla* — Gmelin, 1789. Today *Dendropsophus leucophyllatus* (Beireis, 1783).

leucopygius: G. *leuco* (λευκο), white + G. *pygi* (πύγή), buttock, rump, anus. *Hyla leucopygia* Cruz & Peixoto, 1985 “1984”. (“... O nome atribuído é de origem grega e faz alusão à cor da ornamentação cloacal ...”). Today *Aplastodiscus leucopygius* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1985).

leucosticta: G. *leuco* (λευκο), white + G. *stiktos* (στικτός), marked with spots, dappled. *Engystoma leucosticta* Boulenger, 1888. (“... Dark brown above, with scattered, minute, white dots ...”). Also *Gastrophryne leucosticta* — Stejneger, 1910. *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) leucosticta* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. Today *Chiasmocleis leucosticta* (Boulenger, 1888).

leucotaenia: G. *leuco* (λευκο), white + L. *taenia*, ribbon, tape, band. (1) *Hyla leucotaenia* Burmeister, 1861 [senior synonym (*nomen oblitum*) of *Hyla squalirostris* A. Lutz, 1925]. (“... einen vom Nasenloch durch das Auge zur Schenkelfuge gezogenen silberweißen Streifen hat, der an jeder Seite von einem braunen Streifen begleitet wird ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax squalirostris* (A. Lutz, 1925). (2) *Hyla leucotaenia* Günther, 1869 «1868»

(preoccupied by *Hyla leucotaenia* Burmeister, 1861). (“... a white inferiorly greyish line runs along the canthus rostralis and upper part of the side of the body ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana guentheri* (Boulenger, 1886).

levaillantii: Levaillant + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring François Levaillant (a. k. a. Le Vaillant) (1753-1824), French traveller and naturalist. *Hyla levaillantii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. Also *Hypsiboas levaillantii* — Cope, 1867. In the synonymy of *Boana xerophylla* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

levicristatus: L. *levis*, free from irregularities of surface, smooth; slippery. + L. *cristatus*, tufted, crested. *Bufo levicristatus* Boettger, 1885. (“... *Caput cristis parum validis osseis instructum, similibus illis B. D’Orbigny D. B., sed crista anteorbitali nulla ...*”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella scitula* (Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2003).

Levirana L. *levis*, free from irregularities of surface, smooth; slippery. + L. *rana*, frog. *Levirana* Cope, 1894. (“... Identical with *Ranula*, but without vomerine teeth ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

lichenosa: L. *lichen*, from G. *leichen* (λειχήν), lichen + L. *-osus*, suffix indicating fullness and abundance. *Hyla lichenosa* Günther, 1858. (?). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).

limai: Lima + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring João Leonardo Lima (?), Brazilian zoologist. *Hyla limai* Bokermann, 1962. Today *Dendropsophus limai* (Bokermann, 1962).

limellum: L. *lima*, file (carpenter’s) + L. *-ellum*, suffix diminutive. *Lysapsus limellum* Cope, 1862. This is one of the very few etymologies explained by Cope in a herpetological work; the asterisk after the specific epithet indicates **Lima*, a file, shagreen. (“... Upper surfaces as far as interior orbital region, minutely and firmly rugose, resembling shagreen ...”). Also *Lisapsus limellum* — Steindachner, 1867 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Pseudis limellum* — Boulenger, 1882. *Lysapsus limellus* — Savage & Carvalho, 1953. *Lysapsus limellus limellus* — Gallardo, 1961.

Limnocharis: G. *limnos* (λίμνος), swamp, lake + G. *charis* (χάρις), indulge, satisfy, gratify. *Limnocharis* Bell, 1843. (?). *Limnocharis* is one of the characters of the *Batrachomyomachia*, the war between the frogs and the mice, a satire on the Iliad mistakenly attributed to Homer, known as lake-rejoining. In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

Limnomedusa: G. *limnos* (λίμνος), swamp, lake + G. *medeon* (μεδέων) *medeoussa* (μεδέουσα), ruling, holding¹¹. *Limnomedusa* Fitzinger, 1843.

Limnophys: Gr. *limnophys* (λιμνοφυς), born in the swamp or marsh (etymology by the author). *Limnophys* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. (“... Λιμνοφυς, *in palude natos* ...”). In the synonymy of *Strabomantis* Peters, 1863.

lindneri: Lindner + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Erwin Lindner (1888-1988), German entomologist. *Hyla lindneri* Müller & Hellmich, 1936. In the synonymy of *Scinax squalirostris* (A. Lutz, 1925).

lindsayi: Lindsay + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hague L. Lindsay Jr., US American zoologist. *Scinax lindsayi* Pyburn, 1992.

lineata, lineatum, lineatus: L. *lineata*, *-um*, *-us*, lined. (1) *Rana lineata* Schneider, 1799. (“... *linea alba a naribus per palpebras & latera ad pedes posteriores ducta* ...”). Also *Bufo lineatus* — Daudin, 1802 “An. XI”. *Hylodes lineatus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. *Hylodes (Lithodytes) lineatus* — Cope, 1862. *Eleutherodactylus lineatus* — Noble, 1917. *Leptodactylus (Lithodytes) lineatus* — Parker, 1935. Today *Lithodytes lineatus* (Schneider, 1799). (2) *Engystoma ovale lineatum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... Finalmente, outras ha, ainda, em que reaparece a linha rachidiana tão commum em outros representantes da família, uma finissima linha escura que vem das narinas ao orifício anal. Este carácter poderá designar a var. *lineata* ...”). In the synonymy of *Elachistocleis cesarii* (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920).

¹¹ See comments under *Phyllomedusa*.

lineomaculata: L. *linea*, thread, line + L. *maculata*, spotted. *Hyla lineomaculata* Werner, 1899. (“... Oberseite hell rothbraun mit vier aus kleinen dunkelbraunen Flecken gebildeten Längsbinden ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax ruber* (Laurenti, 1768).

Liohyla: G. *leios-* (λείος), smooth + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. (Keferstein noted: “... zeichnet sich überdies durch eine ganz glatte Bauchseite aus ...”, while Cope wrote: “... The belly of the *L. ranoides* is free from rugosities ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis Jiménez de la Espada*, 1870.

lisbella: P. Lis + Bella, honouring Lis Alves Pereira de Oliveira da Rocha and Bella Alves Pereira Custódio da Rocha, nieces of L. C. L. Rocha. *Phasmahyla lisbella* Pereira et al., 2018.

lisei: Lise + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Arno Antonio Lise, Brazilian arachnologist. *Physalaemus lisei* P. Braun & C. Braun, 1977.

Lithobates: G. *lithos* (λίθος), stone, rock + G. *bates* (βάτω), who walks or walks. *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843. (?).

Lithodytes: G. *lithos* (λίθος), stone + G. *dýtis* (δύτης), diver. *Lithodytes* Fitzinger, 1843. (?).

lithomimeticus: G. *lithos* (λίθος), stone + G. *mimetikos* (μιμητικός), imitative, mimetic. *Cycloramphus lithomimeticus* Silva & Ouvernay, 2012. (“... used in allusion to the species color pattern that serves as camouflage and makes individuals similar to the rock surface where they are at rest ...”).

Litopleura: G. *litos* (λίτός), plain, simple + Gr. *pleura* (πλευρά), side. *Litopleura* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. [“... distinción y analogía, que he querido expresar con su nombre genérico, cuya primera raíz alude á la sencillez, i la desnudez de las regiones inguinales, bajo una organización análoga á los que llevan en esa parte una glándula gruesa saliente y aislada á manera de lobanillo ...”]. In the synonymy of *Limnomedusa* Fitzinger, 1843.

littoralis: L. *littoris*, shore, seashore, coast, strand; river bank; beach + L. *-alis*, related to. *Hyla littoralis* Pombal & Gordo, 1991 (“... faz referência ao fato da série-tipo ter sido coletada em região litorânea ...”). Also *Oloolygon littoralis* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Scinax littoralis* (Pombal & Gordo, 1991).

littorea, littoreus: L. *littoris*, shore, seashore, coast, strand; river bank; beach + L. *-ea, -eus*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to, pertaining to, having the nature of, made of, quality of, state or condition of. *Oloolygon littorea* Peixoto, 1988. (“... O epíteto específico faz referência à ocorrência dessa espécie apenas em regiões litorâneas ...”). Also *Scinax littorea* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax littoreus* (Peixoto, 1988).

Liuperus: G. *leios* (λείος), smooth + G. *pira* (πήρᾱ), bag. *Liuperus* Cope, 1861 “1860”. (“... Skin above and below very smooth, some granulations upon the posterior faces of the femora ...”). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus* Fitzinger, 1826.

Lobipes: L. *lobus*, a rounded projection or protuberance + L. *pes*, foot. *Lobipes* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

longilinea, longilineus: L. *longilinea*, *-eus* (from L. *longus*, long + L. *linea*, line), elongated. *Hyla longilinea* B. Lutz, 1968. (“... This solitary specimen is streamlined in appearance. The name, suggested by Prof. G. A. Lutz, was derived from terminology of the Italian typologists, who divide humans into long-lined and short-lined types ...”). Also *Oloolygon longilinea* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax longilineus* (B. Lutz, 1968).

longirostris: L. *longus*, long + L. *rostrum, rostri*, beak, snout. *Leptodactylus longirostris* Boulenger, 1882. (“... Snout acuminate, much longer than the greatest orbital diameter ...”).

Lophopus: G. *lophia* (λοφία), crest, headdress + G. *podos* (ποδος), foot. *Lophopus* Tschudi, 1838 (primary homonym of *Lophopus* Dumortier, 1835, a Polyzoa). (“... Er zeichnet sich gleich auf den ersten Anblick durch die mit einer breiten Schwimnhaut verbundenen Zehen, sowohl der Vorder- als Hinterfüsse, ausv...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus* Fitzinger, 1843.

Lophyohyla: *G. lophia* (λοφία), crest, headdress + *Hyla* (see). *Lophyohyla* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. (? “... Facies de *Hyla* ... pelle lisa pouco adherente na cabeça e livre no dorso ...”). Also *Lophiohyla* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Phyllodytes* Wagler, 1830. Same root in Lophyohylineae Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926.

lucianae: Luciana + L. -ae, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Luciana Barreto Nascimento, Brazilian herpetologist. *Hyla lucianae* Napoli & Pimenta, 2003. Also *Boana lucianae* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla lucianae* (Napoli & Pimenta, 2003).

luctator: *L. luctator*, wrestler, fighter. *Rana luctator* Hudson, 1892. (“... I cannot for a moment believe that an instinct so admirable, correlated as it is with the structure of the fore legs, can be merely an individual variation ... *Rana luctator* would be a good name for this species ...”). Today *Leptodactylus luctator* (Hudson, 1892).

luctuosa: *L. luctuosa*, mournful; grievous. *Hyla luctuosa* Pombal & Haddad, 1993. [“... the specific name, a Latin adjective (*luctuosus* = sad), is an allusion to the mournful calls heard late in the night ...”]. Today *Bokermannohyla luctuosa* (Pombal & Haddad, 1993).

luederwaldti: Lüderwaldt + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hermann Lüderwaldt (1865-1934), Brazilian zoologist. *Holoaden luederwaldti* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920.

Luetkenotyphlus: Lütken + *G. tyflos* (τυφλος), blind. *Luetkenotyphlus* Taylor, 1968. (“... The genus is named in honor of Charles Lütken, who described the type species ...”) [actually, the author of the species was Christian Frederik Lütken (1827-1901), Danish zoologist]. Also *Lutkenotyphlus* — Nussbaum, 1986 (unjustified emendation).

luizotavioi: Luiz Otávio + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Luiz Otávio Possas Gonçalves, owner of the “Vale Verde Alambique e Parque Ecológico”, municipality of Betim, state of Minas Gerais, Brazil. *Ololygon luizotavioi* Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989. Today *Scinax luizotavioi* (Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989).

lumbricoïdaea: *L. lumbricus*, earthworm + *L. -oides*, suffix indicating likeness. *Caecilia lumbricoïdaea* Daudin, 1803 “An. XI”. (“... On ne peut mieux comparer cette cécilie qu’à un lombric ou ver de terre, à cause de sa forme qui est mince, très-longue d’égale grosseur depuis la tête jusqu’au bout de la queue ...”). Also *Caecilia gracilis* var. *lumbricoidea* — Duméril, 1863. *Caecilia lumbricoides* — Merrem, 1820. *Coecilia lumbricoïdaea* — Fitzinger, 1864. In the synonymy of *Caecilia gracilis* Shaw, 1802.

lundii: Lund + *L. -ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Peter Wilhelm Lund (1801-1880), Danish paleontologist and zoologist. *Hyla (Centrotelma) Lundii* Burmeister, 1856. *Hyla lundii* — Caramaschi & Napoli, 2004. Also *Hypsiboas lundii* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana lundii* (Burmeister, 1856).

luscombei: Luscombe + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring B. Anthony Luscombe, US American-Peruvian naturalist. *Eleutherodactylus luscombei* Duellman & Mendelson, 1995. Today *Pristimantis luscombei* (Duellman & Mendelson, 1995).

luteolus: *L. luteus*, yellow; saffron + *L. -olus*, suffix diminutive. *Hyla luteola* Wied-Neuwied, 1821. (“... Ein noch unbeschriebener kleiner Laubfrosch, *Hyla luteola*, von blassgelblicher Farbe mit einem dunkleren Striche durch das Auge ...”). Also *Hylaplesia luteola* — Boie in Schlegel, 1826. *Phyllodytes luteolus* — Wagler, 1830. *Hypsiboas luteolus* — Tschudi, 1838. *Hyla (Phyllodytes) luteolus* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Hyla (Hyla) luteola* — Burmeister, 1856. Today *Phyllodytes luteolus* (Wied-Neuwied, 1820).

lutzae: Lutz + *L. -ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Bertha Maria Julia Lutz (1894-1976), Brazilian herpetologist. *Megaelosia lutzae* Izecksohn & Gouvêa, 1987 “1985”. Also *Hylodes lutzae* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Phantasmarana lutzae* (Izecksohn & Gouvêa, 1987).

lutzi, lutzii: Lutz + *L. -i*, *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Adolpho Lutz (1885-1940), Brazilian sanitarian and zoologist. (1) *Bufo granulosis lutzi* Gallardo, 1965. In the synonymy of *Rhinella mirandaribeiroi* (Gallardo, 1965). (2) *Dendrophryniscus brevipollicatus lutzi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Dendrophryniscus*

brevipollicatus Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. (3) *Hyla lutzi* Melin, 1941. In the synonymy of *Scinax garbei* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926). (4) *Iliodiscus lutzi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1929. In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus fuliginosus* Tschudi, 1838. (5) *Paratelmatobius lutzii* B. Lutz & Carvalho, 1958. (6) *Thoropa lutzi* Cochran, 1938. Also *Eupsophus lutzi* — Myers, 1946.

lutzorum: Lutz + L. -orum, genitive plural of the second declension. Honouring Adolpho and Bertha Lutz, Brazilian herpetologists (see). (1) *Aplastodiscus lutzorum* Berneck et al., 2017. (2) *Cochranella lutzorum* Taylor & Cochran, 1953. Also *Centrolenella lutzorum* — Duellman, 1977. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana uranoscopa* (Müller, 1924). (3) *Crossodactylus lutzorum* Carcerelli & Caramaschi, 1993. (4) *Cycloramphus lutzorum* Heyer, 1983. (5) *Scinax lutzorum* Woitovicz-Cardoso & Pombal, 2010. In the synonymy of *Scinax fuscomarginatus* (A. Lutz, 1925).

Lysapsus: Unclear. Probably G. *lysis* (λύσις), release, freeing + G. *saphes* (σαφές), distinct. *Lysapsus* Cope, 1862. (“... This genus is related to *Litoria*, but differs from it, and from most, if not all, other genera of Opisthoglossa platydactyla, in the freedom of the basal phalanx of the external digit ...”). Same root in *Lisapsus* — Steindachner, 1867 (incorrect subsequent spelling).

Lystris: G. *lytron* (λυτρών), paddles. *Lystris* Cope, 1869 “1868”. (“... same group as *Pleurodema*, differing only from that genus in the presence of two strong shovel-like metatarsals, as in the genus *Systema* ...”). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838.

macero: M. *macero*, frog. *Epipedobates macero* Rodríguez & Myers, 1993. (“... The species name *macero*, a noun in apposition, is the Machiguenga Indian word for “frog.” The Machiguenga are one of the indigenous tribes of the Rio Manu region ...”). Today *Ameerega macero* (Rodríguez & Myers, 1993).

machadoi: Machado + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ângelo Barbosa Monteiro Machado (1934-2020), Brazilian entomologist. (1) *Dendrobates machadoi* Bokermann, 1958. In the synonymy of *Dendrobates tinctorius* (Cuvier, 1797). (2) *Hyla machadoi* Bokermann & Sazima, 1973. Also *Oloolygon machadoi* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Scinax machadoi* (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973).

macroblepharus: G. *makro* (μακρό), long + G. *blepharus* (βλέφαρον), eyelid. *Leptodactylus macroblepharus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... duas cristas cutaneas partem dos olhos, uma atingindo a articulação femural e a outra a axilla humeral, depois de ter se bifurcado atraz do tympano ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768).

macrocephala, macrocephalus: G. *makro* (μακρό), long + G. *kéfali* (κεφάλη), head. (1) *Hylodes macrocephalus* Peracca, 1904. (“... Capo robustissimo, spesso, molto più largo che lungo, eguagliante in lunghezza circa i tre quarti della larghezza ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus macrocephalus* — Stejneger, 1904. In the synonymy of *Strabomantis sulcatus* (Cope, 1874). (2) *Rana macrocephala* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. G. *makro* (μακρό), long + G. *kéfali* (κεφάλη), head. (“... Kopf beynahe halb so lang als das ganze Thier ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815)? or *Ceratophrys aurita* (Raddi, 1823)?

Macrogenioglottus: G. *makro* (μακρό), long + G. *genioglossus*, muscle that forms a major part of the tongue, from *geneion* (γένειον), chin or beard, and *glossa* (γλώσσα), tongue (although Carvalho used the Attic spelling, *glotta*, γλώττα). *Macrogenioglottus* Carvalho, 1946. (“... *Macrogenioglottus* se diferencia de *Ceratophrys*, *Stombus* e *Odontophrynus*, que é o gênero mais próximo, pela constituição especial da língua ...”).

macroglossa: G. *makro* (μακρό), long + G. *glossa* (γλώσσα), tongue. *Cystignathus macroglossus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Langue très-grande, épaisse, fongueuse, circulaire entière, libre à son bord postérieur ...”). Also *Rana (Limnomedusa) macroglossus* — Fitzinger, 1843. Today *Limnomedusa macroglossa* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

macrogranulosus: G. *makro* (μακρό), long + L. *granuli*, granule + L. *-osus*, full of. *Melanophryniscus macrogranulosus* P. Braun, 1973. (“... notando-se em toda a sua extensão a presença de enormes glândulas terminadas em espinhos cônicos e de consistência córnea ...”).

macrosternum: G. *makro* (μακρό), long + G. *sternon* (στέρνον), sternum. *Leptodactylus macrosternum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. Although there is no written allusion to the characteristics of the sternum, figure 79 illustrates the

peculiarities of this structure. Also *Leptodactylus ocellatus macrosternum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. *Leptodactylus ocellatus macrosternus* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1927 (incorrect subsequent spelling).

maculateralis: L. *macula*, spot, stain + L. *lateralis*, lateral, of/on side of body. *Hypsiboas maculateralis* Caminer & Ron, 2014. (“... in reference to the brown dark blotches on the flanks of these frogs ...”). Today *Boana maculateralis* (Caminer & Ron, 2014).

maculatus: L. *maculatus*, spotted. (1) *Bombinator maculatus* Merrem, 1820. (German vernacular name, in the opposite page, indicates “fleckige”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Siphonops paulensis* var. *maculatus* Sawaya, 1937. (“... Do mesmo modo que em *S. annulatus*, aqui nesta especie deparei com dois exemplares ... providos de manchas esbranquiçadas absolutamente idênticas ás já descritas para a variedade daquela especie ...”). In the synonymy of *Siphonops paulensis* Boettger, 1892.

maculiventris: L. *macula*, spot, stain + L. *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly. (1) *Bufo maculiventris* Spix, 1824. (“... *subtus virescenti-flavicans, maculis nigris variegatus* ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Eupemphix maculiventris* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... assez grandes taches noires à centre clair sur le ventre ...”). Today *Physalaemus maculiventris* (A. Lutz, 1925).

maculosus: L. *maculosus*, spotted. *Phyllodytes maculosus* Cruz et al., 2007. (“... refers to distinctive dorsal color pattern. *Maculosus* is a latin vernacular name meaning “covered with stains ...”).

madeira, madeirae: P. Madeira, a river in the Brazilian states of Rondônia and Amazonas; on its margins is the capital of the state of Rondônia, Porto Velho. (1) *Bolitoglossa madeira* Brcko et al., 2013. (“... The specific epithet is taken from Madeira river, which borders the type locality ...”). Also in the combinaton *Bolitoglossa (Eladinea) madeira* — Raffaëlli, 2013. (2) *Hyla madeirae* Bokermann, 1964. (type series “... capturados por el autor en Porto Velho, Territorio Federal de Rondonia, Brasil, en noviembre de 1962 ...”). Today *Scinax madeirae* (Bokermann, 1964).

magalhaesi: Magalhães + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Carlos Reis de Magalhães (1921-2002), Brazilian farmer and naturalist. *Elosia magalhãesi* Bokermann, 1964. Today *Hylodes magalhaesi* (Bokermann, 1964).

magna, magnus: L. *magna*, *-us*, large/great/big/vast/huge. (1) *Elachistocleis magna* Toledo, 2010. (“... size larger than 31 mm in adult males ...”). Also *Elachistocleis magnus* Toledo, 2010. *Engystoma magnum* — Dubois et al., 2021. (2) *Phyllodytes magnus* Dias et al., 2020. (“... refers to the large size of the adult males collected from this species, which are among the largest known in the genus ...”).

Magnadigita: L. *magna*, large/great/big/vast/huge + L. *digiti*, finger; toe. *Magnadigita* Taylor, 1944. (“... Digits wide, more or less truncate ...”). In the synonymy of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril et al., 1854.

magnussoni: Magnusson + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring William Ernest Magnusson, Australian-Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Allobates magnussoni* Lima et al., 2014. (2) *Rhinella magnussoni* Lima et al., 2007.

maisuma: P. *mais uma*, one more. *Odontophrynus maisuma* Rosset, 2008. [“... The specific epithet *maisuma* is a noun in apposition, and means “one more” in Portuguese (*mais uma*). The name is an allusion to the existence of this new species within the *O. americanus* species group, which traditionally was considered as formed by only two diploid-tetraploid cryptic counterparts ...”].

major: L. *major*, large, great, big. *Bufo granulatus major* Müller & Hellmich, 1936. (“... Am auffallendsten erscheint uns die grosse Form von Chiquitos, für die wir den Namen *B. granulatus major* vorschlagen würden ...”). Also *Bufo major* — Cei et al., 1968. Today *Rhinella major* (Müller & Hellmich, 1936).

Malachylodes: Gr. *malakos* (μαλακός), soft, delicate + *Hylodes*, genus or anurans due to Fitzinger (1826) (see). *Malachylodes* Cope, 1879. (“... This new genus is of interest as exhibiting the lowest station in the series which

is typified by *Hylodes*, excepting that the nasal bones are not so reduced as in the type of *Phyllobates* ...”). In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

malkini: Malkin + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Borys Malkin (1917-2009), Polish-US American zoologist. *Eleutherodactylus malkini* Lynch, 1980. Today *Pristimantis malkini* (Lynch, 1980).

mambaiensis: P. Mambaí, municipality of the state of Goiás, Brazil; from T. *amambaí-y*, river of ferns + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Trachycephalus mambaiensis* Cintra et al., 2009. [“... vicinity of Santa Edwiges I hydroelectric powerplant dam, Municipality of Mambaí, State of Goiás, Brazil (14°17’24”S 46°11’37”W) ...”].

manaos: A. (?) *manaós*, mother of gods; name of a native Brazilian nation and, as Manaus, capital of the state of Amazonas, Brazil, on the left Negro river bank. *Amazophrynella manaos* Rojas et al., 2014. (“... We name the species in honor of the Manaos Amerindian tribe that inhabited the region of the present day city of Manaus, Amazonas, Brazil, where the species is distributed ...”).

manauensis: Manaus, capital of the state of Amazonas, Brazil, on the left Negro river bank + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Atelopus manauensis* Jorge et al., 2020. (“... refers to the location of the occurrence of the new species, municipality of Manaus, state of Amazona, Brazil ...”).

manezinho: P. “manezês” or “manezinho”, is a variety of Brazilian Portuguese spoken at Santa Catarina, heavily influenced by the Azorean Portuguese. *Eleutherodactylus manezinho* Garcia, 1996. (“... “Manezinho” é uma expressão regional, usada como um apelido dado aos habitantes nativos das comunidades litorâneas da Ilha de Santa Catarina e arredores, na sua maioria descendentes dos colonizadores açorianos. O nome é uma homenagem aos habitantes da comunidade do Córrego Grande, localidade-tipo da nova espécie ...”). Today *Ischnocnema manezinho* (Garcia, 1996).

manicorensis: P. Manicoré, municipality in the state of Amazonas, Brazil; in turn, from *Anicoré*, a native Brazilian culture that inhabited the region at the time of colonization + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Bufo manicorensis* Gallardo, 1961. (“... Manicoré, Rio Madeira, State of Amazonas, Brasil ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella major* (Müller & Helmich, 1936).

mantidactyla: L. *mantisa*, a worthless addition + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Lysapsus mantidactyla* Cope, 1862. (“... Tips of toes very slightly dilated, brown ...”). Also *Pseudis mantidactyla* — Boulenger, 1882. *Lysapsus mantidactylus* — Gallardo, 1961. In the synonymy of *Pseudis minuta* Günther, 1858.

mantiqueira: P. [Serra da] Mantiqueira, from T. *amand'-y-kyra*, rain drip. (1) *Chiasmocleis mantiqueira* Cruz et al., 2007. [“... O nome específico ... refere-se ao Complexo Serrano da Mantiqueira, conjunto de montanhas que se estende pelos estados do sudeste do Brasil, onde se situa o Parque Estadual da Serra do Brigadeiro no Estado de Minas Gerais, localidade-tipo da espécie ...”]. Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) mantiqueira* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. (2) *Paratelmatobius mantiqueira* Pombal & Haddad, 1999. [“... Serra da Mantiqueira is the name for the Brazilian mountain range where the new species was collected. Its meaning is “home of the rain” (amanty = rain; querd = home or a place for stopping overnight) ...”]. (3) *Proceratophrys mantiqueira* Mângia et al., 2014. [“... Its meaning is “home of the rain”. (“amanty” = rain; “querd” = home or a place for stopping overnight ...”)].

mapinguari: P. *mapinguari*, legendary creature of the Bolivian and Brazilian Amazonian region, similar to a great ape, covered with dense hair, which makes it invulnerable to bullets, and feet with huge toenails turned backwards; from T. *mbaé-pi-guari*, a thing that has a twisted paw. *Dendropsophus mapinguari* Peloso et al., 2016. (“... the mapinguari is an important part of Amazonian folklore, which is here perpetuated as the name of this exquisite frog ...”).

maracaya: T. *maracayá*, corr. *maracaíá*, vernacular name of the ocelot, *Leopardus pardalis*. *Hyla maracaya* Cardoso & Sazima, 1980. (“... Em língua tupi, *maracaya* significa gato do mato e o nome é dado em alusão ao pa-

drão de colorido dorsal desta nova espécie ...”). Also *Ololygon maracaya* — Duellman, 1985. Today *Scinax maracaya* (Cardoso & Sazima, 1980).

marambaiae: *T. marambaia*, from *T. mbará-mbai*, the enclosure of the sea, the restinga, a sandbar surrounding the sea. *Leptodactylus marambaiae* Izecksohn, 1976. [“... Restinga da Marambaia, Estado do Rio de Janeiro, vivendo nas proximidades do mar (aproximadamente 23° 03’ S / 43° 38’ W) ...”].

maranguapensis: P. Maranguape (from *T. maranguá-pe*, valley of the battle or fight) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Adelophryne maranguapensis* Hoogmoed et al., 1994. (“... Named after the type locality, the Serra de Maranguape ...”).

marchesianus: Marchesi + L. *-anus*, belonging to. Honouring Padre João Marchesi (?), Salesian missionary. *Phyllobates marchesianus* Melin, 1941. Also *Colostethus marchesianus* — Edwards, 1971. Today *Allobates marchesianus* (Melin, 1941).

marcusi: Marcus + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Harry Marcus (?), German physician working in Bolivia. *Caecilia marcusi* Wake, 1985.

margaritatus: L. *margaritatus*, provided with pearls. *Brachycephalus margaritatus* Pombal & Izecksohn, 2011. (“... em alusão ao corpo e aos membros recobertos por protuberâncias esbranquiçadas nos exemplares fixados ...”).

margaritifera: L. *margarita*, pearl + L. *fera*, carry, bear. *Rana margaritifera* Laurenti, 1768. (“... *Corpore ex fusco-rubro, granulis margaritifformibus, dilute rubellis, consperso ...*”). Also *Bufo margaritifera* — Latreille in Sonnini de Manoncourt & Latreille, 1801 “An. X”. *Bufo (Otilophis) margaritifera* — Cuvier, 1829. *Otilophus margaritifera* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Otilophus margaritifera* — Günther, 1859 “1858”. *Bufo margaritifera* — Cope, 1870 “1869”. *Bufo margaritifera* — Hoogmoed, 1989. *Rhinella margaritifera* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768).

marginata: L. *marginata*, provided with borders. (1). *Hyla marginata* Boulenger, 1887. (“... a dark brown line from the end of the snout, along the can-

thus rostralis and supraciliary edge, above the tympanum, and along each side of the body as far as the sacral region ...”). Also *Hypsiboas marginatus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana marginata* (Boulenger, 1887) (2) *Phyllomedusa marginata* Izecksohn & Cruz, 1976. [“... Uma espécie pequena de Phyllomedusinae, com apêndices desenvolvidos na articulação tíbio-tarsal, afim de *Phyllomedusa fimbriata* (Miranda-Ribeiro), apresentando faixa clara marginal dorsal e ausência de verde nos lados da cabeça e do tronco, nas mãos e nos pés ...]. Today *Phrynomedusa marginata* (Izecksohn & Cruz, 1976). (3) *Rana marginata* Steindachner, 1867 (*nomen nudum*). (?). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus labyrinthicus* (Spix, 1824)

mariaeterezae: Maria Tereza + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Maria Tereza Jorge Pádua, Brazilian environmentalist. *Brachycephalus mariaeterezae* Bornschein et al., 2015. Same root in *Brachycephalus mariaterezae* — Segalla et al., 2021 (incorrect subsequent spelling).

marina, marinus: L. *marina*, *-us*, marine; of the sea. *Rana marina* Linnaeus, 1758. [Seba’s (1734) *Rana marina maxima* included in the original synonymy]. Also *Bufo marinus* — Schneider, 1799. *Bufo (Palaeobufo) marinus* — Bolkay, 1919. *Bufo marinis* — Barbour & Noble, 1920 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Bufo marinus marinus* — Schmidt, 1932. *Chaunus marinus* — Frost et al., 2006. *Rhinella marinus* — Pramuk, et al., 2008 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Bufo (Rhinella) marinus* — Fouquette & Dubois, 2014. Today *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758).

maritimum: L. *maritimum*, maritime, relative to the sea. *Litopleura maritimum* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. [“... Encontré el único individuo de nuestra colección cerca de Montevideo, en la llamada Playa Ramírez ...”]. In the synonymy of *Limnomedusa macroglossa* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

marmorata, marmoratus: L. *marmorata*, *-us*, marbled; overlaid with marble. (1) *Adenomera marmorata* Steindachner, 1867. (“... Rücken mit undeutlichen, spärlichen, dunkelbraunen Marmorierungen ...”). Also *Leptodactylus (Adenomera) marmorata* — Parker, 1932. *Leptodactylus marmoratus* — Parker, 1935. *Leptodactylus marmoratus marmoratus* — Rivero, 1961. *Leptodactylus (Lithodytes) marmoratus* — Frost et al., 2006. (2)

Bufo marmoratus Laurenti, 1768. (“... Dorso supra ex rubro & cinereo - flavescente, marmoris ad instar variegata ...”). Also *Buffo marmoratus* — Lacépède, 1788. *Hyla marmorata* — Daudin, 1800. *Calamita marmoratus* — Merrem, 1820. *Lophopus marmoratus* — Tschudi, 1838. *Hyla* (*Lophopus*) *marmorata* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Hyla marmorata marmorata* — Rivero, 1961. *Quinzhyla marmorata* — Bauer, 2005. Today *Dendropsophus marmoratus* (Laurenti, 1768). (3) *Gomphobates marmoratus* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... Tegningen er egentlig i Hovedsagen den samme som hos *G. notatus*, men meget kraftigere og tydeligere; Ryggens Vorter indfattes af mørke Kredse ...”). Today *Physalaemus marmoratus* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862). (4) *Hylodes marmoratus* Boulenger, 1900. (“... grey-brown above, with brown, dark-edged marblings on the head and body ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus marmoratus* — Stejneger, 1904. Today *Pristimantis marmoratus* (Boulenger, 1900). (5) *Chaunus marmoratus* Wagler, 1828. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhinella granulosa* (Spix, 1824). (6) *Hyla marmorata* Burmeister, 1856. (“... Farbe blass gelbgrün, mit feinen schwarzen marmorformigen Aderzeichnungen ...”). Preoccupied by *Hyla marmorata* Laurenti, 1768; in the synonymy of *Dendropsophus seniculus* (Cope, 1868). (7) *Eupomplyx marmoratus* Jan, 1857 (*nomen nudum*). Also *Eupemphix marmoratus* Steindachner, 1864 (*nomen nudum*). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus nattereri* (Steindachner, 1863). (8) *Siphonops annulatus* var. *marmoratus* Sawaya, 1937. (“... Dentre os exemplares de *S. annulatus* examinados, 32 apresentam grande número de manchas formadas de um conjunto de semicírculos ou segmentos de arcos de parábolas, ou ainda de espiraes, concêntricos, localizados nos flancos, no dorso e no abdômen, sem uma distribuição uniforme ... Estes traços podem ainda mostrar-se emaranhados, cruzando-se entre si na superfície das pregas anulares em diversas direcções, dando á pelle um aspecto rajado ...”). In the synonymy of *Siphonops annulatus* (Mikan, 1820).

martiae: Marty + L. -ae, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Martha (“Marty”) L. Crump, US American herpetologist. *Eleutherodactylus martiae* Lynch, 1974. Today *Pristimantis martiae* (Lynch, 1974).

martinezi: Martínez + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Antonio Martínez (?), Argentinian entomologist. *Leptodactylus martinezi* Bokermann, 1956. Also in the combinatio *Leptodac-*

tylus (*Lithodytes*) *martinezi* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Adenomera martinezi* (Bokermann, 1956).

martini: Martin + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring John T. Martin (?), collector from Ciudad del Carmen, Campeche. *Hyla microcephala martini* Smith, 1951. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus microcephalus* (Cope, 1886).

martinsi: Martins + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Amílcar Vianna Martins (1907-1990), Brazilian zoologist and parasitologist. *Hyla martinsi* Bokermann, 1964. Also *Boana martinsi* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla martinsi* (Bokermann, 1964).

martyi: Marty + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Christian Marty, herpetologist in French Guiana. *Rhinella martyi* Fouquet et al., 2007. In the synonymy of *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768).

marvaleewakeae: Marvalee Wake + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Marvalee Hendricks Wake, US American herpetologist. *Microcaecilia marvaleewakeae* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2013.

masniger: L. *mas*, male + L. *niger*, black. *Colostethus masniger* Morales, 2002 “2000”. (“... El nombre deriva del latín *mas*, que significa macho, y *niger* que significa negro; en referencia a la coloración ventral oscura de los machos ...”). Today *Allobates masniger* (Morales, 2002).

massarti: Massart + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jean Massart (1865-1925), Belgian physician and botanist. (1) *Atelopus moreirae massarti* Cochran, 1948. In the synonymy of *Melanophryniscus moreirae* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920). (2) *Elosia Massarti* De Witte, 1930. Also *Megaelosia massarti* — Giaretta et al., 1993. *Hylodes massarti* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Phantasmarana massarti* (De Witte, 1930). (3) *Hyla Massarti* De Witte, 1930. In the synonymy of *Boana albomarginata* (Spix, 1824).

matogrosso: P. Mato Grosso, Brazilian state. *Elachistocleis matogrosso* Caraschi, 2010. (“... The specific name ... honors both states of Mato Grosso and Mato Grosso do Sul, Brazil, where the species occurs ...”). Also *Engystoma matogrosso* — Dubois et al., 2021.

mattogrossensis: P. Mat[t]o Grosso, Brazilian state + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Leptodactylus pentadactylus mattogrossensis* Schmidt & Inger, 1951. Refers to the type locality, “Urucum de Corumba, Matto Grosso”. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus labyrinthicus* (Spix, 1824).

matuta: P. *matuta*, rustic, provincial. *Pseudopaludicola matuta* Andrade et al., 2018. (“... related to those who live in the countryside ...”).

maxima, maximus: L. *maxima*, greatest/biggest/largest. (1) *Rana maxima* Laurenti, 1768. (“... XXIV. *Rana maxima*. Seba I. 72. 3 ...”). *Calamita maximus* — Schneider, 1799. *Hyla maxima* — Oken, 1816. In the synonymy of *Boana boans* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Rana maxima* Merrem, 1820. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758). (3) *Physalaemus maximus* Feio et al., 1999. (“... The name of the species, a Latin adjective, refers to its large size ...”).

Mayamandra: S. Maya, Midde-american culture + L. *mandra*, ending of *Salamandra*, genus of urodeles due to Garsault (1764) (in turn, from G. σαλαμάνδρα, vernacular name of the animals). *Mayamandra* Parra-Olea et al., 2004. (?). A subgenus of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854.

mayi: May + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hugo May (?), Brazilian entomologist. *Bufo crucifer mayi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. In the synonymy of *Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824).

Megacephala, megacephalus: G. *megas* (μέγας), great, large, big + G. *képhali* (κεφάλη), head. (1) *Gastrotheca megacephala* Izecksohn et al., 2009. (“... O epíteto *megacephala* significa cabeça grande ...”). Also *Gastrotheca (Eothea) megacephala* — Duellman, 2015. Today *Eothea megacephala* (Izecksohn et al., 2009). (2) *Bradymedusa megacephala* Miranda-Ri-

beiro, 1926. (“... Cabeça grande ...”). Also *Phyllomedusa megacephala* — Brandão, 2002. Today *Pithecopus megacephalus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

Megaelosia: G. *mega* (μεγα), large, great + L. *Elosia*, genus of anurans due to Tschudi, 1838 (in the synonymy of *Hylodes* Fitzinger, 1826), in turn from G. *elos* (ἔλος), swamp + L. *-ia*, pertaining to. *Megaelosia* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. (?). Also *Magaelosia* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923 and *Megalelosia* A. Lutz, 1930 (alternative spellings).

megapodia: G. *mega* (μεγα), large, great + G. *podos* (ποδος), foot. *Hyla megapodia* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (?). Also *Ololygon megapodia* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. In the synonymy of *Scinax fuscovarius* (A. Lutz, 1925).

megastoma: G. *mega* (μεγα), large, great + G. *stoma* (στόμα), mouth. *Rana megastoma* Spix, 1824. (“... os largissimum rotundatum ...”). Also *Stombus megastomus* — Gravenhorst, 1825. *Ceratophrys megastoma* — Wagler, 1830. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys cornuta* (Linnaeus, 1758).

megatympanum: G. *mega* (μεγα), large, great, + L. *tympanum*, from G. *tympano* (τύμπανο), eardrum, tympanum, although originally it referred to a small drum that was played in religious ceremonies. (1) *Phyllodytes megatympanum* Marciano et al., 2017. (“... The specific epithet refers to the prominent tympanum, one of the largest in relation to SVL among the other species of the genus ...”). (2) *Thoropa megatympanum* Caramaschi & Sazima, 1984. (“... O nome específico é dado em alusão ao grande diâmetro do tímpano ...”).

mehelyi: Méhely + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Lajos Ludwig von Méhely (1862-1953), Hungarian herpetologist. *Chiasmocleis mehelyi* Caramaschi & Cruz, 1997. Also *Chiasmocleis* (*Chiasmocleis*) *mehelyi* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

melanargyrea, melanargyreus: G. *melanos* (μέλανος), black + G. *argyros* (ἄργυρος), silver. *Hyla melanargyrea* Cope, 1887 (“... Color above, blackish gray, like a stain of dilute silver nitrate, with slightly darker areas included in darker lines ...”). Also *Hyla marmorata melanargyrea* — Rivero,

1961. *Hyla senicula melanargyrea* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Hyla melanargyrea* — Caramaschi & Jim, 1983. Today *Dendropsophus melanargyreus* (Cope, 1887).

melanochrus: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. chros* (χρῶς), skin, flesh. *Potamotyphlus melanochrus* Taylor, 1968. (“... The color is deep black throughout ...”). In the synonymy of *Potamotyphlus kaupii* (Berthold, 1859).

melanodactylus: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Scinax melanodactylus* Lourenço et al., 2014. (“... The name is an allusion to the black nuptial pad, a so far exclusive feature among all known species of *Scinax* ...”).

melanomystax: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. mystax* (μύσταξ), moustache. *Phyllodytes melanomystax* Caramaschi et al., 1992. (“... The new species is characterized by its small size, absence of dorsal color pattern, and presence of a large dark brown stripe on the snout and canthus rostralis ...”).

Melanophryne: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Melanophryne* Lehr & Trueb, 2007. (“... The name refers to the black or dark brown colour of the skin in combination with phryne, which is a commonly used ending for microhylid generic names ...”). In the synonymy of *Ctenophryne* Mocquard, 1904.

Melanophryniscus: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. + *G. -ikos* (-ίκος), looking like, belonging to. *Melanophryniscus* Gallardo, 1961. (“... Ya que *Phryniscus* Wiegmann y su especie *P. nigricans* con el cual se conoció a *A. stelzneri* durante mucho tiempo no puede usarse, pues fue creado para el juvenil de *Bufo spinulosus* ... es conveniente crear uno nuevo, *Melanophryniscus* ...”).

melanopogon: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. pogon* (πώγων), beard. *Stombus melanopogon* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... negro fuliginoso do peito para a boca ...”). Today *Proceratophrys melanopogon* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

melanops: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. ops* (οψ), eye. *Osteocephalus melanops* Melo-Sampaio et al., 2021 (“... The specific epithet *melanops* is derived from Greek “*melanos-*” meaning black and “*ops-*” meaning eye. The name is a reference to intense dark coloration of the species’ irises ...”).

melanopygia: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. pygos* (πυγος), posterior region or rump. *Ischnocnema melanopygia* Targino et al., 2009. (“... The specific name refers to the dark coloration around the cloacal region, tibia, and tarsus ...”).

melanotis: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. otos* (ώτός), from *G. ous* (οὔς), ear. *Bufo melanotis* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Le Crapaud a Oreilles Noires ...”). *Bufo crucifer* var. *melanotis* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Rhinella crucifer* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).

melini: Melin + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Douglas Edvard Melin (1895-1946), Swedish herpetologist. (1) *Bufo melini* Andersson, 1945. In the synonymy of *Rhaebo guttatus* (Schneider, 1799). (2) *Eleutherodactylus melini* Bokermann, 1958. In the synonymy of *Pristimantis ockendeni* (Boulenger, 1912). (3) *Leptodactylus melini* B. Lutz & Kloss 1952 (replacement name for *Leptodactylus rugosus* Melin, 1941). In the synonymy of *Adenomera hylaedactyla* (Cope, 1868).

melloi: Mello + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Rubens Pinto de Mello, Brazilian entomologist. *Ololygon melloi* Peixoto, 1989 “1988”. Also *Scinax melloi* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax melloi* (Peixoto, 1989).

membranacea: L. *membranacea*, made of/resembling membrane; skin; parchment. *Hyla membranacea* Andersson, 1945. (“... A distinct dermal extension connects the inner half of the upper arm with the side of body and continues as a thin membranaceous fold out on the flanks ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus reticulatus* (Jiménez de la Espada, 1870).

memorans: L. *memorare*, remember; be mindful of. *Eleutherodactylus memorans* Myers & Donnelly, 1997. [“... The name given to this frequent vocalizer is the present participle of the Latin *memoro* (to relate or recount some-

thing) – a remembering of the airplane crash below the high place where it lives ...”]. Today *Pristimantis memorans* (Myers & Donnelly, 1997).

mendocinus: Mendoza (an Argentinian province) + L. *-inus*, having the nature or condition of. *Bufo mendocinus* Philippi, 1869. (“... Das Museum in Santiago hat aus der Provinz Mendoza mehrere Exemplare des *Bufo chilensis* erhalten, welche bei Uspallata gesammelt sind, so wie eine bei Vistaflor in derselben Provinz gesammelte Kröte, welche ich für verschieden halte, und *Bufo mendocinus* nenne ...”). Also *Bufo arenarum mendocinus* – Gallardo, 1964. In the synonymy of *Rhinella arenarum* (Hensel, 1867).

meriana, merianae: Merian + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Maria Sybilla Merian (1647-1717), German illustrator and naturalist. (1) *Rana meriana* Shaw, 1802. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758). (2) *Bufo granulatus merianae* Gallardo, 1965. Today *Rhinella merianae* (Gallardo, 1965). (3) *Pseudis merianae* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. In the synonymy of *Pseudis paradoxa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

meridiana, meridianus: L. *meridiana*, *-anus*, southern. *Hyla misera meridiana* B. Lutz, 1954 [“... Difere de ambas (refers to *Hyla goughi* Boulenger from Trinidad and *Hyla misera* Werner from Venezuela) pelo comprimento dos membros posteriores, dentes vomerinos, detalhes de padrão e distribuição meridional ...”). Also *Hyla meridiana* – Bokermann, 1966. *Hyla microcephala meridiana* – Duellman, 1974. Today *Dendropsophus meridianus* (B. Lutz, 1954).

meridionalis: L. *meridionalis*, southern, from the south. (1) *Adelophryne meridionalis* Santana et al., 2012. (“... It makes reference to the southernmost record known for a species of the genus *Adelophryne* ...”). (2) *Elosia nasus meridionalis* Mertens, 1927 (“... Terra typica: Wasserfall in 900 m Höhe, 3 km nordwestlich von Sao Francisco de Paula, Rio Grande do Sul, Brasilien ...”). Also. *Elosia meridionalis* – Mertens, 1967. Today *Hylodes meridionalis* (Mertens, 1927). (3) *Pseudis meridionalis* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... Devemos esta especie ao Snr. Rud. Gliesch, do Rio Grande do Sul ...”). In the synonymy of *Pseudis minuta* Günther, 1858.

mertensi: Mertens + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Robert Friedrich Wilhelm Mertens (1894-1975), German zoologist. (1) *Bufo ictericus mertensi* Cochran, 1950. In the synonymy of *Rhinella icterica* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Caecilia mertensi* Taylor, 1973. Replaced by *Caecilia marcusii* vide Segalla et al. (2021). (3) *Elosia mertensi* Bokermann, 1956. Today *Hylodes mertensi* (Bokermann, 1956).

mesophaea, mesophaeus: G. *mesos* (μεσός), average, mean + G. *phaios* (φαιός), dusky. *Hyla mesophaea* Hensel, 1867 (“... Der Rücken in seiner ganzen Breite rothbraun, die Farbe vorn und an den Seiten scharf abgesetzt, am After ohne bestimmte Grenze in die Farbe der Hinterbeine übergehend ...”). Also, *Phrynohyas mesophaea* — Bokermann, 1966. Today *Trachycephalus mesophaeus* (Hensel, 1867).

michelin: F. *Michelin*, from Compagnie Générale des Établissements Michelin SCA, a French multinational tyre manufacturing company. *Adelophryne michelin* Lourenço-de-Moraes et al., 2018. (“... honors the Reserva Ecológica Michelin that has been supporting our researches for more than 10 years in the municipality of Igrapiúna, Bahia ...”).

Microcaecilia: G. *mikros* (μικρός), small + L. *Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus (1758) (see). *Microcaecilia* Taylor, 1968. (“... Small species with eye visible or invisible externally ...”).

microcentra: G. *mikros* (μικρός), small + L. *centrum*, center (circle/sphere/earth). *Hyla microcentra* Werner, 1921. (?). In the synonymy of *Boana lanciformis* (Cope, 1871).

microcephalum, microcephalus: G. *mikros* (μικρός), small + G. *kephali* (κεφάλι), head. (1) *Chthonerpeton microcephalum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. (“... Cabeça pequena, igualando a 1/2 do maior diametro do corpo ...”). In the synonymy of *Potamotyphlus kaupii* (Berthold, 1859). (2) *Hyla microcephala* Cope, 1886. (“... The head is small in its dimensions ...”). Today *Dendropsophus microcephalus* (Cope, 1886).

microderma: G. *mikros* (μικρός), small + G. *dermos* (δερμός), skin. *Hyla microderma* Pyburn, 1977. A (“... In reference to the characteristically small

heel appendage of the new species ...”). Also *Hypsiboas microderma* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana microderma* (Pyburn, 1977).

microdiscus: *G. mikros* (μικρός), small + *G. diskos* (δίσκος), circular plate. *Nototrema microdiscus* Andersson, 1910. (“... The disks of the toes are small, somewhat smaller than those of the fingers, which are not larger than half the tympanum ...”). Also *Opisthodelphis microdiscum* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. *Gastrotheca microdisca* — Cochran, 1955 “1954. *Gastrotheca* (*Opisthodelphys*) *microdiscus* — Dubois, 1987 “1986”. *Gastrotheca* (*Australotheca*) *microdiscus* — Duellman, 2015. *Gastrotheca* (*Alainia*) *microdiscus* — Duellman & Cannatella, 2018. Today *Alainia microdiscus* (Andersson in Lönnberg & Andersson, 1910).

Microhylidae: *L. Microhyla*, genus of anurans due to Tschudi (1838), in turn from *G. mikros* (μικρός), small + *L. Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs + *L. -idae*, suffix that indicates the category of family in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). Microhylidae Günther, 1858 (1843).

Microphryne: *G. mikros* (μικρός), small + *G. phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Microphryne* Peters, 1873. (Probably alluding to the small size of the involved species). In the synonymy of *Engystomops* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872.

microps: *G. mikros* (μικρός), small + *G. ops* (οψ), eye. (1) *Engystoma microps* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Yeux extrêmement petits ...”). Also *Gastrophryne microps* — Stejneger, 1910. *Microhyla microps* — B. Lutz, 1954. Today *Myersiella microps* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841). (2) *Hyla microps* Peters, 1872 (?). Today *Dendropsophus microps* (Peters, 1872). (3) *Microps* Wagler, 1828 (preoccupied by *Microps* Megerle, 1823; junior homonym of *Microps* Dahl, 1823 [Insecta]). (“... oculi non prominuli, minutissimi, circulares ...”). In the synonymy of *Elachistocleis* Parker, 1927. (4) *Oocormus microps* Boulenger, 1905. (“... eye very small, as large as the tympanum ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus parvulus* (Girard, 1853).

midas: *G. Midas* (Μίδας), king in Greek mythology, at whose touch everything turned to gold. *Centrolenella midas* Lynch & Duellman, 1973. (“... The

name is associated with this frog known along the Rio Aguarico, meaning rich water, in reference to gold found in the river, and in allusion to the gold flecks on the frogs ...”). Also *Cochranella midas* — Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. Today *Teratohyla midas* (Lynch & Duellman, 1973).

migueli: Miguel + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Miguel Trefaut Urbano Rodrigues, Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Chiasmocleis migueli* Forlani et al., 2017. (2) *Cycloramphus migueli* Heyer, 1988.

milanoi: Milano + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Miguel S. Milano, Brazilian environmentalist. *Melanophryniscus milanoi* Baldo et al., 2015.

miliaris: L. *miliaris*, of millet [in the sense of small grains]. *Rana miliaris* Spix, 1824. (“... *granulis punctisque albis munita* ...”). Also *Ololygon miliaris* — Peters, 1872. *Borborocoetes miliaris* — Boulenger, 1891. *Hylodes miliaris* — Wandolleck, 1907. *Eleutherodactylus miliaris* — Noble, 1917. *Eupsophus miliaris* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. Today *Thoropa miliaris* (Spix, 1824).

Mimosiphonops: L. *mimus*, mime; farce; actor in mimes + L. *Siphonops*, genus of gymnophiones due to Wagler, 1828 (see). *Mimosiphonops* Taylor, 1968. (“... A genus generally resembling *Siphonops annulatus* ...”).

mineira: P. *mineira*, demonym (f.) of the natives of the state of Minas Gerais, Brazil. *Pseudopaludicola mineira* Lobo, 1994. (“... Su nombre hace referencia al estado de Minas Gerais, lugar de origen de esta especie ...”).

mini: T. *mini*, small, little. *Bufo granulosis mini* Gallardo, 1967. (“... Debido a una atenta indicación del Dr. Konrad Klemmer ... quien me comunicó ... que ya había sido descrita una subespecie de *Bufo* con el nombre *Bufo cinereus minor* ... debo cambiar el nombre de esta subespecie de *Bufo granulosis* ... por el de *Bufo granulosis mini* n. n., tomado este último nombre del tupí-guaraní “*mini*”, pequeño ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella major* (Müller & Helmich, 1936).

minima, minimus: L. *minima*, -us, small, little. *Hyla minima* Ahl, 1933. (“... Körperlänge 14 mm ... Die kleine Art ist augenscheinlich am nächsten verwandt mit *Hyla nana* Boulenger und *Hyla bivittata* Boulenger ...”). Today *Dendropsophus minimus* (Ahl, 1933).

minor: L. *minor*, small, little. *Bufo granulosus minor* Gallardo, 1965. (“... The name of this subspecies is given on account of its small size, contrasting with *B. g. major*, geographically close but of large size in general, as indicated by the name ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella major* (Müller & Helmich, 1936).

minuscula, minusculus: L. *minuscula*, -us, somewhat smaller, rather small (size/extent); less important, minor. *Hyla minuscula* Rivero, 1971. (“... Una *Hyla* pequena con *canthus rostralis* bien definido ...”). Today *Dendropsophus minusculus* (Rivero, 1971).

minuta, minutus: L. *minuta*, small, insignificant. (1) *Atelopus minutus* Melin, 1941. (“... Length 15-19 mm ...”). Also *Dendrophryniscus minutus* – *Atelopus minutus* Melin, 1941. McDiarmid, 1971. *Amazonella minutus* – Fouquet et al., 2012. Today *Amazophrynella minuta* (Melin, 1941). (2) *Hyla minuta* Peters, 1872. (?). Today *Dendropsophus minutus* (Peters, 1872). (3) *Leptodactylus minutus* Noble, 1923. (“... Size very small ...”). In the synonymy of *Adenomera hylaedactyla* (Cope, 1868). (4) *Proceratophrys minuta* Napoli et al., 2011. [“... The specific name, a Latin adjective (*minutus* = small, minute), is an allusion to the small size of the new species ...”]. (5) *Pseudis minuta* Günther, 1858. (“... Halb so gross als *Ps. paradoxa* ...”). Also *Pseudis minutus* – Savage & Carvalho, 1953. *Podonectes minutus* – Garda & Cannatella, 2007.

mirandae: Miranda + L. -ae, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Marta E. Miranda, Argentinian herpetologist. *Pseudopaludicola mirandae* Mercadal de Barrio & Barrio, 1994. In the synonymy of *Pseudopaludicola boliviana* Parker, 1927.

miranda-ribeiri: Miranda-Ribeir[o] + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alipio de Miranda-Ribeiro (1874-

1939), Brazilian zoologist. *Hyla miranda-ribeiri* Melin, 1941. The same root in *Hyla miranda-ribeiroi* — Duellman, 2001 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Boana wavrini* (Parker, 1936).

mirandaribeiroi: Miranda-Ribeiro + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alípio de Miranda Ribeiro (1874-1939), Brazilian zoologist. (1) *Cycloramphus mirandaribeiroi* Heyer, 1983. (2) *Bufo granulatus mirandaribeiroi* Gallardo, 1965. Today *Rhinella mirandaribeiroi* (Gallardo, 1965). (3) *Synapturanus mirandaribeiroi* Nelson & Lescure, 1975.

miriamae: Miriam + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Miriam Harriet Muedeking, wife of W. Ronald Heyer. *Phyzelaphryne miriamae* Heyer, 1977. (“... an industrious field collector whose quick reflexes result in captures of many forest floor frogs ...”).

mirim: T. *mirim*, small, little. *Hyla mirim* B. Lutz, 1973. (“... Examination of a series of 69 small tree-frogs from Rio Vermelho ... showed some of the characters found in *Hyla rizibilis* Bokermann but in a population which is very much smaller in size ...”). Also *Oloolygon mirim* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. In the synonymy of *Scinax rizibilis* (Bokermann, 1964). (2) *Sphaenorhynchus mirim* Caramaschi et al., 2009. (“... allusive to the small size of the new species ...”).

mirissimus: L. *mirus*, wonderful, strange, remarkable, amazing, surprising, extraordinary + L. *-issimus*, suffix superlative. *Brachycephalus mirissimus* Pie et al., 2018. (“... The specific epithet *mirissimus* is a superlative of the Latin adjective *mirus*, which means wonderful, marvelous ...”).

misera: L. *misera*, poor, miserable, wretched. *Hyla misera* Werner, 1903. (?). Also *Hyla microcephala misera* — Fouquette, 1968. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus microcephalus* (Cope, 1886).

misionis: Misiones, a province in NE Argentina + L. *-is*, latinizing particle. *Limnomedusa misionis* Schmidt, 1944. [“... Type from Rio Paranay, Misiones Territory, Argentina ...”]. In the synonymy of *Limnomedusa macroglossa* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

- missiessi:** Missiessi + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Édouard Thomas Burgues de Missiessy (1756-1837), French admiral. *Cystignathus missiessii* Eydoux & Souleyet, 1842. (“... Cystignathe de Missiessi ...”). Also *Thoropa missiessii* — Cope, 1865. In the synonymy of *Thoropa miliaris* (Spix, 1824).
- missionum:** Misiones, a province in NE Argentina + L. *-onum*, pertaining to. *Bufo missionum* Berg, 1896. (“... Esta especie, de que recogió un ejemplar en Misiones el Sr. capitán Benjamín García Aparicio ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella icterica* (Spix, 1824).
- mitrata:** L. *mitrata*, wearing the mitre. *Bufo mitrata* Daudin, 1802 “An. XI. (?)”. In the synonymy of *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768).
- mitus:** G. *mitos* (μίτος), warp-thread (on the loom); thread (spun by a spider). *Fritziانا mitus* Walker et al., 2018. (“... The specific epithet ... is a reference to the mitochondrial DNA, which possesses a gene order exclusive to this species ...”).
- miyatai:** Miyata + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Kenneth Ichiro Miyata (1951-1983), US American herpetologist. *Hyla miyatai* Vigle & Goberdhan-Vigle, 1990. Today *Dendropsophus miyatai* (Vigle & Goberdhan-Vigle, 1990).
- moa:** P. Moa, nickname; honouring Romualdo Rosário da Costa (1954-2018), Mestre Moa do Katendê. *Pristimantis moa* Oliveira et al., 2020. (“... The specific epithet is a patronym of the Capoeira Master Romualdo Rosário da Costa[†], known as Mestre Moa do Katendê, for his struggles for the black movement of Bahia ...”).
- mocquardi:** Mocquard + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring François Mocquard (1834-1917), French herpetologist. *Hyla mocquardi* Günther, 1901. In the synonymy of *Boana pulchella* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).
- modesta:** L. *modesta*, restrained, mild; modest. *Hyla modesta* — Mertens, 1952. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758). [Accord-

ing to Taylor & Smith (1945), authors of the specific epithet in the combination *Acrodytes modesta*, this is “... A small member of the genus, the known maximum size (15 specimens) 70 mm ...”].

moehringi: Möhring + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Karl Heinz Möhring (1938-2012), German-Brazilian industrial. *Proceratophrys moehringi* Weygoldt & Peixoto, 1985.

moisesii: Moises + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Moisés Barbosa de Souza, Brazilian herpetologist. *Amazophrynella moisesii* Rojas-Zamora et al., 2018.

molitor: Unclear. L. *molitor*, the one who builds; if derived from *molo*, *molere*, grind (from the supposed resemblance of the male's call to the grinding of mill-stones?). *Bufo molitor* Tschudi, 1845. (?). Also *Phrynoidis molitor* — Cope, 1862. In the synonymy of *Rhinella poeppigii* (Tschudi, 1845).

monachus: L. *monachus*, monk. *Odontophrynus monachus* Caramaschi & Napoli, 2012. (“... in allusion to the followers of Saint Francis of Assis, the Franciscan monks ... The name is given for the type locality, in the headwaters of the São Francisco River ...”).

mondolfi: Mondolfi + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Edgardo Mondolfi Otero (1918-1999), Venezuelan mammalogist. *Hyalinobatrachium mondolfi* Señaris & Ayarzagüena, 2001.

montevidense, montevidensis: Montevideo, capital city of Uruguay + L. *-ense*, *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Phryniscus montevidensis* Philippi, 1902. (“... i en segundo lugar que todos ellos, a principiar por Bibron están equivocados en creer que el *Phryniscus*, común a orillas del mar en Montevideo, es el *Phr. nigricans*; es una especie fácil de distinguir, para la cual propongo el nombre de *Phr. Montevidensis* ...”). Also *Melanophryniscus stelzneri montevidensis* — Klappenbach, 1968. Today *Melanophryniscus montevidensis* (Philippi, 1902). (2) *Pleurodema montevidense* Philippi, 1902. (“... Habitat in Montevideo ...”). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus gracilis* (Boulenger, 1883).

- montivagus:** *L. montivagus*, wandering over the mountains. *Scinax montivagus* Juncá et al., 2015. (“... The specific epithet ... is derived from the sum of the Latin substantive “*monti*” (English, “mountain”) and the Latin adjective “*vagus*” (English, “errant”), alluding to the highland distribution of this new species ...”).
- moratoi:** Morato + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Celso Morato de Carvalho, Brazilian herpetologist. *Odontophrynus moratoi* Jim & Caramaschi, 1980. Today *Proceratophrys moratoi* (Jim & Caramaschi, 1980).
- moreirae:** Moreira + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating belonging to. Honouring Carlos Moreira (1869-1946), Brazilian zoologist, collector of the type. (1) *Atelopus moreirae* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. Also *Atelopus moreirae moreirae* – Cochran, 1948. *Dendrophryniscus moreirae* – Ahl, 1938. *Phryniscus stelzneri moreirae* – Barth, 1957. Today *Melanophryniscus moreirae* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920). (2) *Engystomops moreirae* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. Today *Physalaemus moreirae* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).
- moschata:** *L. moschata*, from G. *moschos* (μόσχος), any young animal + L. *-ata*, suffix indicating quality of. *Bradymedusa moschata* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (?). In the synonymy of *Pithecopus rohdei* (Mertens, 1926).
- motorzinho:** *P. motorzinho*, diminutive of *P. motor*, engine. *Pseudopaludicola motorzinho* Pansonato et al., 2016. (“... in allusion to the typical vocalization of the species, which resembles the continuous functioning of a stationary internal combustion engine ...”).
- mucronata, mucronatus:** *L. mucronis*, sword, sharp point + L. *-ata, -atus*, provided with. *Adelophryne mucronatus* Lourenço-de-Moraes et al., 2012 [“... The name *mucronatus*, from Latin, means “pointed” in allusion to the tips of the fingers with pointed (or mucronate) tips ...”]. Today *Adelophryne mucronata* Lourenço-de-Moraes et al., 2012.
- Mucubatrachus:** (?). Name derived from the prefix “*mucu*”, commonly used by ethnic groups native to the Andes of Venezuela to identify places, and the Greek word for frog, “*batrachos*” (etymology by the author). *Mucubatrachus* La Marca, 2007 “2006”. (“... Nombre derivado del prefijo “*mucu*”

utilizado comúnmente por etnias nativas de los Andes de Venezuela para identificar lugares, y la palabra griega para rana, “*batrachos*” ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

muelleri: Müller + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring August Müller (1853-1913), German ornithologist and natural history dealer, owner or manager of “Institut Linnaea”. *Engystoma Mülleri* Boettger, 1885. (?). Also *Hypopachus mülleri* Peracca, 1895. *Gastrophryne muelleri* — Stejneger, 1910. Today *Dermatonotus muelleri* (Boettger, 1885).

mugicus: L. *mugiens*, low, bellow; make a loud deep noise. + Gr *-icos* (ἦκος), suffix indicating belonging. *Rana mugicus* — Angel, 1947. (“... noms qui font allusion au bruit de sa voix puissante ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802).

mugiens: L. *mugiens*, low, bellow; make a loud deep noise. *Rana mugiens* Merrem, 1820. Characterized with the epithet “*brüllender*” in the German version, facing the Latin “*mugiens*”. In the synonymy of *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802).

muiraquitán: P. *muiraquitã*, zoomorphic stone or wood amulet to which supernatural virtues are attributed. (1) *Elachistocleis muiraquitán* Nunes-de-Almeida & Toledo, 2012. [“... The muiraquitã as a frog-shaped green stone (exceptionally similar to an *Elachistocleis* species) was used in the Brazilian Amazon as an amulet by the women from Tapajós to prevent disease and avoid infertility ...”]. Also *Engystoma muiraquitán* — Dubois et al., 2021. (2) *Hyalinobatrachium muiraquitán* Oliveira & Hernández-Ruz, 2017. [“... The specific epithet “muiraquitán” refers to artifacts carved in stone (jade, greenish color) or wood, representing people or animals (frog, fish, turtle, etc.), to which the supernatural qualities of the amulet are attributed. This epithet is used for the species due to its similarity with the muiraquitán of the legends, usually represented by greenish-colored frogs ...”].

multifasciata: L. *multi*, many things (pl.); much; many + L. *fasciata*, having band/strip; ribbon. *Hyla multifasciata* Günther, 1859 «1858. (“... body

from the snout to the anus, and the extremities with brown, white-edged cross-bands...”). Also *Hyla albopunctata multifasciata* — Rivero, 1961. *Hypsiboas multifasciatus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana multifasciata* (Günther, 1859).

multilineata: L. *multi*, many things (pl.); much; many + L. *lineata*, lined. *Hyla multilineata* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939. (“... multiple, narrow, longitudinal, lines all over the head and back ...”). Also *Hyla bischoffi multilineata* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. In the synonymy of *Boana bischoffi* (Boulenger, 1887).

munduruku: (?) *Munduruku*, ethnic group who call themselves *Wuy jugu*. *Ameerega munduruku* Neves et al., 2017. (“... The specific epithet *munduruku* is a noun in apposition referring to the Munduruku ethnic group, which inhabits the southwestern parts of the state of Pará and the northern region of the state of Mato Grosso, Brazil ...”).

munozorum: Muñoz + *-orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. Honouring Mr. Ildefonso Muñoz B. (?) and Mrs. Blanca Muñoz (?), authors’ hosts in Santa Cecilia. *Centrolenella munozorum* Lynch & Duellman, 1973. Also *Hyalinobatrachium munozorum* — Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. Today *Hyalinobatrachium munozorum* (Lynch & Duellman, 1973).

muriciensis: P. Murici, municipality in the state of Alagoas, Brazil; in turn from T. *murici*, vernacular name of diverse Malpighiaceae of the genus *Byrsonima* + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Scinax muriciensis* Cruz et al., 2011. (“... Specific epithet in allusion to the type-locality, the Municipality of Murici, State of Alagoas, Northeastern Brazil ...”). Also *Ololygon muricensis* — Duellman et al., 2016 (incorrect spelling).

murundu: T. *murundu*, little mound of earth; termite mound (“cupinzeiro”). *Pseudopaludicola murundu* Toledo et al., 2010. (“... The specific name is a Tupi word that means small elevations on the ground, covered by grassy and/or arboreal vegetation. This is the most common calling site of this species ...”).

musica, musicus: L. *musica*, *-us*, of/belonging to poetry or music, musical. *Hyla musica* B. Lutz, 1949 “1948”. (“... A presença de vários machos no mesmo

ponto resulta num côro muito musical que lembra os antigos carrilhões miniatura de percussão. Todos podem cantar no mesmo diapasão por algum tempo, mas de vez em quando há diferenças de semi-tons causando uma dissonância muito curiosa. O nome específico foi escolhido em homenagem à voz ...”). Today *Aplastodiscus musicus* (B. Lutz, 1949).

myersi: Myers + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Charles William Myers (1936-2018), US American herpetologist. (1) *Dendrobates myersi* Pyburn, 1981. Also *Epipedobates myersi* — Myers, 1987. *Ameerega myersi* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Allobates myersi* (Pyburn, 1981). (2) *Leptodactylus myersi* Heyer, 1995.

Myersiella: Myers + L. *-ella*, suffix diminutive. *Myersiella* Carvalho, 1954. (“... The genus is named for Dr. George Sprague Myers [1905-1985], curator of zoological collections in the Natural History Museum of Stanford University, at whose suggestion a revision of the US American microhylids was undertaken ...”).

myrmecoides: G. *myrmex* (μυρμηξ), ant + L. *-oides*, suffix indicating likeness. *Euparkerella myrmecoides* Lynch, 1976. (“... in reference to the small size of the frog ...”). Also *Phyllonastes myrmecoides* — Heyer, 1977. Today *Nothella myrmecoides* (Lynch, 1976).

mystacalis: L. *mystax*, from G. μύσταξ, moustache + L. *-alis*, pertaining to; in a condition of. *Paludicola mystacalis* Cope, 1887. (“... The upper lip is marked as follows: A white vertical bar marks the middle of the premaxilla; two bars are below the nostril, and two larger ones below the eye ...”). Also *Physalaemus mysticalis* — Nieden, 1923. Today *Pseudopaludicola mystacalis* (Cope, 1887).

mystacea, mystaceus: L. *mystax*, from G. μύσταξ, moustache + L. *-ea, -eus*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to, pertaining to, having the nature of, made of, quality of, state or condition of. *Rana mystacea* Spix, 1824. (“... *taenia per tympanum versus nares & ad maxillam superiorem nigra* ...”). Also *Leptodactylus mystaceus* — Fitzinger, 1826. *Cystignathus mystaceus* — Wagler, 1830. *Leptodactylus (Cavicola) mystaceus* — A. Lutz, 1930. Today *Leptodactylus mystaceus* (Spix, 1824).

mystacinus: *L. mystax*, from G. μύσταξ, moustache + L. *-inus*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to, pertaining to, having the nature of, made of, quality of, state or condition of. *Cystignathus mystacinus* Burmeister, 1861. (“... Mundrand, ein Streif vom Nasenloch bis zum Ohr und jederseits 3 z. Th. unterbrochene Fleckenstreifen von schwarzer Farbe neben dem in der Mitte wenig und unregelmäßig gefleckten Rücken ...”). Also *Leptodactylus (Cavicola) mystacinus* — A. Lutz, 1930. Today *Leptodactylus mystacinus* (Burmeister, 1861).

nahdereri: Nahderer + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Karl (or Carlos) Nahderer (?), Brazilian naturalist. *Hyla nahdereri* B. Lutz & Bokermann, 1963. Today *Dendropsophus nahdereri* (B. Lutz & Bokermann, 1963).

nana, nanus: *L. nana*, *-us*, dwarf. (1) *Hyla nana* Boulenger, 1889. (“... This diminutive species is allied to *H. bipunctata*, Spix, and *H. minuta*, Ptrs. ...”). Also *Sphoehyla nana* — Goin, 1957. *Dendropsophus nanus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Dendropsophus nanus* (Boulenger, 1889). (2) *Eupemphix nana* Boulenger, 1888. (“... From snout to vent, 18 mm ...”). Also *Physalaemus nana* — Cochran, 1955 “1954. Today *Physalaemus nanus* (Boulenger, 1888). (3) *Leptodactylus nanus* Müller, 1922. (“... *Leptodactylus nanus* ist, wie erwähnt, wohl die kleinste bisher beschriebene *Leptodactylus*-art ...”). Also *Leptodactylus (Parvulus) nanus* — A. Lutz, 1930. Today *Adenomera nana* (Müller, 1922). (4) *Phrynanodus nanus* Ahl, 1933. (“... Körperlänge 14 mm ...”). In the synonymy of *Ischnocnema parva* (Girard, 1853).

nanahallux: *L. nanus*, dwarf + *L. hallux*, first toe. *Ischnocnema nanahallux* Brusquetti et al., 2013. (“... Toe I reduced ...”).

Nanotriton: *L. nanus*, dwarf + *L. Triton*, genus of salamanders due to Laurenti (1768) [in turn from G. *triton* (Τρῖτων), sea god, son of Poseidon and Amphitrite], preoccupied by *Triton* Linnaeus, 1758 (a gastropod); frequent ending in urodele names]. *Nanotriton* Parra-Olea et al., 2004. (“... Diminutive, short-tailed salamanders with small hands and feet ...”). A subgenus of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854.

- nantaiwuensis:** Nantaiwu + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Rana nantaiwuensis* Hsü, 1930. It refers to the type locality, Nantaiwu Amoy, now Xiamen Shi, Fujian Province, China. In the synonymy of *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802).
- nanuzae:** Nanuza + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Nanuza Luiza de Menezes, Brazilian botanist. *Hyla nanuzae* Bokermann & Sazima, 1973. Also *Boana nanuzae* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla nanuzae* (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973).
- napensis:** Napo, river and province in central Ecuador + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Bufo marinus* var. *napensis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (“... los ejemplares del *B. marinus* que poseemos, pueden dividirse en tres grupos ó variedades de importancia, si se considera que cada una de ellas corresponde á determinada región del continente sur-americano: la marítima central del Brasil, la parte de la cuenca del rio Napo inmediata á los andes ecuatoriales, y las tierras llanas cercanas al rio de la Plata. Voy á distinguirlas con nombres expresivos de su procedencia ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758).
- napolii:** Napoli + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Marcelo Felgueiras Napoli, Brazilian herpetologist. *Bokermannohyla napolii* Carvalho et al., 2012.
- nasica, nasicus:** L. *nasus*, nose + L. *-ica*, *-icus*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to, pertaining to, having the nature of, made of, quality of, state or condition of. *Hyla nasica* Cope, 1862. (“... muzzle depressed, prominent, faint ...). Also *Hyla x-signata nasica* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Ololygon nasica* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Ololygon nasicum* — Laurent & Teran, 1981 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Scinax nasica* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax nasicus* (Cope, 1862).
- nassau:** Nassau, mountain range in Surinam + L. *-i*, suffix indicating pertence. (1) *Atelopus hoogmoedi nassau* Ouboter & Jairam, 2012. (“... A diurnal, terrestrial frog from primary rainforest on and around the Nassau Mt. ...”). In the synonymy of *Atelopus hoogmoedi* Lescure, 1974. (2) *Ameerega trivittata nassau* Ouboter & Jairam, 2012. (“... Distribution in Suriname: pla-

teau of Nassau Mountain, between 450 m and 570 m altitude ...”). In the synonymy of *Ameerega trivittata* (Spix, 1824).

nasus: L. *nasus*, nose. *Hyla nasus* Lichtenstein, 1823. (“... *maxilla superiore nasi forma prominente ...*”). Also *Elosia nasuta* — Tschudi, 1838 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Elosia nasus* — Günther, 1866. *Enydrobius nasus* — Cope, 1866. *Elosia nasus nasus* — Mertens, 1927. Today *Hylodes nasus* (Lichtenstein, 1823).

nasuta, nasutus: L. *nasuta*, -us, having long nose. (1) *Bufo nasutus* Schneider, 1799. (“... *Caput ab oculis inde sinuatum et contractum in rostrum obtusum, ab utroque eius latere posita gerit parva narium foramina ...*”). Also *Bufo (Oxyrhynchus) nasutus* — Spix, 1824. *Bufo (Rhinella) nasutus* — Cuvier, 1829. Same root in *Bufo (Oxyrhynchus) naricus* Spix, 1824. *Bufo (Rhinella) naricus* — Cuvier, 1829. In the synonymy of *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768). (2) *Hylodes nasutus* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... *Le museau est proéminenten avant & au-dessus de la bouche ...*”). Also *Eleutherodactylus nasutus* — Stejneger, 1904. Today *Ischnocnema nasuta* (A. Lutz, 1925).

nasutulus: L. *nasutus*, having long nose + L. -lus, diminutive. *Bufo nasutulus* Wiegmann, 1833. (“... bilden eine von der vorerwähnten ganz bestimmt verschiedene Art, die ich B. nasutulus wegen der abwichenden Bildung der Schnauze im Museum benannt habe ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella granulosa* (Spix, 1824).

natalensis: Natal, capital of the state of Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil + L. -ensis, belonging to a place. *Leptodactylus natalensis* A. Lutz, 1930. [“... Rio Bahú and other places near Natal (Rio Grande do Norte) ...”]

nattereri: Natterer + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Johann Natterer (1787-1843), Austrian naturalist. (1) *Bufo granulatus nattereri* Bokermann, 1967. Today *Rhinella nattereri* (Bokermann, 1967). (2) *Eupemphix Nattereri* Steindachner, 1863. Today *Physalaemus nattereri* (Steindachner, 1863). (3) *Leptodactylus nattereri* A. Lutz, 1926. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus podicipinus* (Cope, 1862).

Nattereria: Natterer + L. *-eria*, suffix denoting place of. Honouring Johann Natterer (1787-1843), Austrian naturalist. *Nattereria* Steindachner, 1864. In the synonymy of *Physalaemus* Fitzinger, 1826.

neblinae: S., P. [Sierra de/da] Neblina, mountain range shared by Venezuela and Brazil; from S./P. *neblina*, fog, mist, haze + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. *Stefania neblinae* Carvalho et al., 2010. [“... The specific name refers to the region, “Pico da Neblina” (foggy peak), where the new species was collected ...”].

nebulosa, nebulosus: L. *nebulosus*, misty, foggy. *Hyla nebulosa* Spix, 1824. (“... *Submediocris, brunneo-fusca* ...”). Also *Scinax nebulosa* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax nebulosus* (Spix, 1824).

Nectocaecilia: G. *nektes* (νεκτες), swimmer + L. *Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus (1758) (see). *Nectocaecilia* Taylor, 1968. (“... two large narial plugs on tongue ...”).

Nectodactylus: G. *nektes* (νεκτες), swimmer + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Nectodactylus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1924. (“... *Palmae crassae, digitis connexi fere ut in Brachycephalo. Pedibus palmatis raninis* ...”). In the synonymy of *Chiasmocleis* Méhely, 1904.

neglecta, neglectus: L. *neglecta*, disregarded, not cared for, neglected, ignored. (1) *Cyclorhamphus neglectus* A. Lutz, 1928. Replacement name for *Telmatobius asper* Boulenger, 1907. In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus asper* Werner, 1899. (2) *Paludicola neglecta* Ahl, 1927. Also *Physalaemus neglecta* — Milstead, 1963. *Physalaemus neglectus* — Cochran & Goin, 1970. *Physalaemus neglectus neglectus* — Cochran & Goin, 1970. In the synonymy of *Physalaemus cuvieri* Fitzinger, 1826.

nekronastes: G. *nekros* (νεκρός), death + G. *nastes* (νάστης), inhabitant; dweller. *Dendropsophus nekronastes* Dias et al., 2017. (“... The name is given in allusion to the collection site of the specimens in a pond near a cemetery ...”).

Nelsonophryne: Nelson + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Nelsonophryne* Frost, 1987 Honouring Craig E. Nelson, US American herpetologist. Replace-

ment name for *Glossostoma* Günther, 1900 [preoccupied by *Glossostoma* LeConte, 1851 (Turbellaria)]. In the synonymy of *Ctenophryne* Mocquard, 1904.

Nenirana: L. *nenia*, a funeral song + L. *rana*, frog. *Nenirana* Hillis & Wilcox, 2005. (“... in reference to the low, mournful advertisement call of the species in this clade ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

nicefori: Nicéforo + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Brother Nicéforo María (1888-1980), né Antoine Rouhaire Siauzade, French priest and naturalist active in Colombia. (1) *Phyllomedusa nicefori* Barbour, 1926. Also *Phyllomedusa niceforoi* — Funkhouser, 1957 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Pithecopus nicefori* — B. Lutz, 1966. In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa tarsius* (Cope, 1868). (2) *Pseudis paradoxus nicefori* Cochran & Goin, 1970. In the synonymy of *Pseudis paradoxa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

nidicola: L. *nidus*, nest + L. *-cola*, dwelling in, inhabiting, living among. *Colostethus nidicola* Caldwell & Lima, 2003. (“... The new species described herein is the fourth know species of *Colostethus* with an endotrophic larva. The larvae are nidicolous, undergoing a modified tadpole stage in a terrestrial nest ...”). Today *Allobates nidicola* (Caldwell & Lima, 2003).

Niedenis: Nieden + L. *-ia*, dedicative suffix. Honouring Fritz Nieden (1883-1942), German herpetologist. *Niedenis* Ahl, 1924. In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus* Tschudi, 1838.

nigerrima: L. *nigerrima*, superlative of L. *niger*, black. *Hyla nigerrima* Spix, 1824. (“... *Corpus maiusculum, nigerrimum, immaculatum* ...”). Also *Hysaplesia nigerrima* — Schlegel, 1826. *Dendrobates nigerrima* — Wagler, 1830. *Dendrobates nigerrimus* — Wagler, 1830. In the synonymy of *Ameerega trivittata* (Spix, 1824).

nigrescens: L. *nigrescere*, become black, grow dark. *Leptodactylus nigrescens* Andersson, 1945. (“... Upper parts of head and body unifrom brownish black ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus discodactylus* Boulenger, 1884.

nigrilatus: L. *nigrum*, black, dark + L. *latus*, side; flank. *Ranula nigrilatus* Cope, 1874. (“... Color, dark brown; sides black ...”). Also *Rana nigrilatus* — Boulenger, 1882. In the synonymy of *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824).

nigriventris: L. *nigrum*, black, dark + L. *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly. *Hylaplesia nigriventris* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Le dessous présente un fond pointillé de noir & des taches noires denses avec quelques points blancs ...”). Also *Basanitia nigriventris* — Bokermann, 1966. *Eleutherodactylus nigriventris* — Lynch, 1968. Today *Ischnocnema nigriventris* (A. Lutz, 1925).

nigromaculatus: L. *niger*, black, dark + L. *maculatus*, spotted. *Trachycephalus nigromaculatus* Tschudi, 1838. (?). Also *Hyla nigromaculata* — Boulenger, 1882.

nimio: L. *nimius*, excessive, too great; by a very great degree, far. Additionally, S. *nimio*, insignificant, very small. *Phyzelaphryne nimio* Simões et al., 2018. [“... The specific epithet *nimio* is a Spanish masculine adjective derived from the Latin word *nimius* (“abundant” or “plentiful”). The Spanish term keeps this meaning, but has also received the additional meaning of “insignificant” and “very small” ... The dual meaning of *nimio* alludes simultaneously to the abundance of the new species in the two localities where it was collected and to its very small body size, and is used in apposition to the genus ...”].

Noblella: Noble + L. *-ella*, ending for the formation of a latinized noun. Honouring Gladwyn Kingsley Noble (1894-1940), US American herpetologist. *Noblella* Barbour, 1930.

noctinectes: L. *noctis*, night + G. *nektes* (νεκτες), swimmer. *Chthonerpeton noctinectes* da Silva et al., 2003. {“... The specific name is an adjective derived from *nocti* (Latin [*nox, noctis*] nocturnal) and *nectes* (Greek [*nekton, nek-tos*] swimmer), as an allusion to the nocturnal swimming activity of the species ...”}.

nodoterga: L. *nodus*, knot; node + L. *tergum*, back, rear; outer covering/surface. *Brachycephalus ephippium* var. *nodoterga* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... tem á mais algumas das verrugas maiores, alongadas como que ossificadas

pela parte superior, aos pares ...”). Today *Brachycephalus nodoterga* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920.

nordestina, nordestinus: P. *nordeste*, North-East + L. *-ina, -inus*, having the nature or condition of. (1) *Adelophryne nordestina* Lourenço-de-Moraes et al., 2021. (“... The name of the new species *nordestina* is a Portuguese feminine adjective meaning “from the northeast,” referring to its distribution in northeastern Brazil ...”). (2) *Phyllomedusa nordestina* Caramaschi, 2006. (“... O nome da espécie, um adjetivo, refere-se à sua distribuição no nordeste do Brasil ...”). Today *Pithecopus nordestinus* (Caramaschi, 2006).

notatus: L. *notatus*, marked, signed. *Gomphobates notatus* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... Grundfarven er lys skifergraa; den er svagt marmoreret af morkere Graat ...”). Also *Paludicola notata* — Peters, 1872. In the synonymy of *Physalaemus cuvieri* Fitzinger, 1826.

notoaktites: G. *notos* (νότος), of or in the south + G. *aktios* (ἄκτιος), of the shore. *Leptodactylus notoaktites* Heyer, 1978. (“... From the Greek *notos*, south, and *aktites*, coast dweller, in reference to the geographic distribution of the species in Brasil ...”).

Nototheca: G. *notos* (νώτος), back, dorsum + G. *theke* (θήκη), storage-container, chest. *Nototheca* Bokermann, 1950. (“... Femeas providas de bolsa incubadora dorsal, abrindo para o exterior por meio de fenda longitudinal mediana anteriormente bifurcada ...”). In the synonymy of *Fritziana* Mello-Leitão, 1937.

nouraguensis: F. [Réserve Naturelle] Nourages, protected area of tropical rainforest in Guyana, in turn from (?) *Nourages*, a Guianese ethnic group that disappeared in the 18th century + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Hyalinobatrachium nouraguensis* Lescure & Marty, 2000. [“... Saut Arataye (environs du camp de base), Réserve des Nouragues (bassin de l’Approuague), Guyane française ...”]. In the synonymy of *Hyalinobatrachium iaspidiense* (Ayarzagüena, 1992).

novaisi: Novais + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alfredo Novais (?), Brazilian farmer, host of Bokermann in Ba-

hia, Brazil. *Hyla novaisi* Bokermann, 1968. Also *Hyla senicula novaisi* — B. Lutz, 1973. Today *Dendropsophus novaisi* (Bokermann, 1968).

nova-teutoniae: Nova Teutônia, locality in the state of Santa Catarina, Brazil + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. *Leptodactylus nova-teutoniae* Ahl, 1936. [“... Drei Exemplare, Männchen, Nova Teutonia, Brasilien, Plaumann leg ...”]. In the synonymy of *Limnomedusa macroglossa* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

Novirana: L. *novus*, new + L. *rana*, frog. *Novirana* Hillis & Wilcox, 2005. (“... in reference to the New World distribution of this clade ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

nunciatus: L. *nunciatus*, announce/report/bring word/give warning. *Allobates nunciatus* Moraes et al., 2019. (“... The specific epithet ... refers to the great conspicuity of the loud advertisement call of the species, allowing it to be readily recognized by the human ear wherever it occurs ...”).

Nyctimantis: G. *nyktos* (νυκτός), period of time from evening to morning, night + G. *mantis* (μαντις), treefrog. *Nyctimantis* Boulenger, 1882. (“... The erect pupil distinguishes this genus from *Hyla* ...”).

nympha: G. *nymphi* (νύμφη), semi-divine female spirit of nature, nymph. *Hypsiboas nympha* Faivovich et al., 2006. (“... in allusion to the beautiful goddesses in Greek mythology that lived in woods and marshes ...”). Today *Boana nympha* (Faivovich et al., 2006).

Oaxakia: S. Oaxaca, Mexican state [from Nahuatl (N) Huaxyacac “guaje” (*Leucaena leucocephala*)]. Refers to the restricted geographic distribution of the subgenus, whose members were previously included in the *Bolitoglossa macrinii* species group. *Oaxakia* Parra-Olea et al., 2004. (“... restricted geographically to southern Oaxaca and southwestern Guerrero, México ...”). A subgenus of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854.

obesus: L. *obesus*, fat, stout, plump. *Typhlonectes obesus* Taylor, 1968. (“... A cylindrical, thick-bodied species ...”). In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

obscurus: L. *obscurus*, dim, dark, obscure. *Dendrobates obscurus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Toutes les parties de ce Batracien seraient d’un brun foncé, sans une légère teinte blanchâtre que présentent les cordons glanduleux qui s’étendent le long des côtés du dos ...”). In the synonymy of *Ameerega trivittata* (Spix, 1824).

obtectus: L. *obtectus*, cover over; conceal; protect. *Physalaemus obtectus* Bokermann, 1966. [“... Esta especie está estrechamente relacionada con *Physalaemus signiferus* (Girard) con el que tiene una extraordinaria semejanza, principalmente cuando se trabaja con material conservado ...”].

obtriangulata, obtriangulatus: L. *ob-*, prefix that usually conveys a sense of opposition or confrontation + L. *triangular*, three-cornered, triangular + L. *-ata, -atus*, having the nature of. *Hyla obtriangulata* B. Lutz, 1973 (replacement name for *Hyla catharinae simplex* B. Lutz, 1968). (Two possibilities, “... Head large, length and width subequal ...”, or “... a large, triangular, interocular spot ...”). Also *Ololygon obtriangulata* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax obtriangulata* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax obtriangulatus* (B. Lutz, 1973).

occidentalis: L. *occidentalis*, of/pertaining to/connected with/coming from the west. *Pseudis paradoxus occidentalis* Gallardo, 1961. (“... El Pailón, Bolivia ...”). In the synonymy of *Pseudis platensis* Gallardo, 1961.

occipitalis: L. *occipitalis*, pertaining to the back of the head, occiput. *Hyla occipitalis* Fitzinger, 1826. (?). *Nomen nudum*. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus nigromaculatus* Tschudi, 1838.

ocellata, ocellatus: L. *ocellata, -us*, having ocelli, little eyes or buttonholes [in the sense of round spots]. *Cystignathus ocellatus* — Wagler, 1830 (not Linnaeus, 1758). *Leptodactylus ocellatus* — Girard, 1853. *Leptodactylus (Pachypus) ocellatus* — A. Lutz, 1930. *Leptodactylos ocellatus ocellatus* — Cei, 1950. Names applied to different populations of *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815). (2) *Bufo ocellatus* Günther, 1858. (“... Rücken braun mit einem gelben Längsstreifen und vier oder fünf paarigen schwarzen, gelb-eingefassten Flecken ...”). Also *Chilophryne ocellata* — Cope, 1862. Today *Rhinella ocellata* (Günther, 1858). (3) *Bombinator ocellatus* Tschudi, 1838. (*nomen nudum*). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema bibroni* Tschudi, 1838.

ochraceus: L. *ochraceus*, ocher-colored. *Leptodactylus ochraceus* A. Lutz, 1930. (“... General coloring very light ochraceus, like old ivory ...”). See Caramaschi, 2008.

ockendeni: Ockenden + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring George Richard Ockenden (1868-1906), British professional collector. *Hylodes ockendeni* Boulenger, 1912. Also *Eleutherodactylus ockendeni* — Dunn, 1931. Today *Pristimantis ockendeni* (Boulenger, 1912).

octavioi: Octavio + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Octávio de Oliveira (?), Brazilian collector. *Eleutherodactylus octavioi* Bokermann, 1965. Today *Ischnocnema octavioi* (Bokermann, 1965).

octoplicata: L. *octo*, eight + L. *plica*, fold. *Rana octoplicata* Werner, 1893. (“... Dieser Frosch, welcher an den acht Längsfalten und den kurzen Schwimnhäuten von allen nordamerikanischen Rana-Arten leicht zu unterscheiden ist ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815).

Odontophrynus: G. *odontia* (ὀδόντια), teeth + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Odontophrynus* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862. (“... *Dentes in maxilla superioris, non in palato ...*”). The same root in *Odontophrynidae* Lynch, 1969.

oea, oeus: G. *oios* (οἶος), alone, unique, peculiar. *Eleutherodactylus oeus* Heyer, 1984. (“... This taxon is further peculiar in that of the many frog specimens collected from the Santa Teresa area, there are only three individuals of *E. oeus* known, all collected in 1942 ...”). Today *Ischnocnema oea* (Heyer, 1984).

Oedipus: G. *oideo* (οἰδέω), (of parts of the body) swell, swell up, be swollen + G. *podos* (πῶδος), foot. *Oedipus* Tschudi, 1838. (?). Preoccupied by *Oedipus* Berthold, 1827 (Insecta, Orthoptera). In the synonymy of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854.

ohausi: Ohaus + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Friedrich Ohaus (1864-1946), German physician and entomologist. (1) *Ceratophrys ohausi* Wandolleck, 1907. Today *Cycloramphus*

ohausi (Wandolleck, 1907). (2) *Hyla ohausi* Wandolleck, 1907. Also *Fritzia hohausi* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. *Fritzia ohausi* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. *Fritziana ohausi* — Bokermann, 1966. *Flectonotus ohausi* — Weygoldt & Carvalho-e-Silva, 1991. Today *Fritziana ohausi* (Wandolleck, 1907).

olfersii: Olfers + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ignaz Franz Werner Maria von Olfers (1793-1871), German naturalist, historian, and diplomat. *Phryniscus olfersii* Lichtenstein & Martens, 1856. Also *Phrynidium olfersi* — Cope, 1867. *Paludicola olfersi* — Peters, 1882. Today *Physalaemus olfersii* (Lichtenstein & Martens, 1856).

olfersioides: L. [*Paludicola*] *olfersii*, anuran species due to Lichtenstein & Martens (1856) (see)¹² + G. -*oeides* (-οειδής), similar to. *Eupemphix olfersioides* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Cette espèce ressemble à *Paludicola olfersii*, qui est bien plus grande ...”). Also *Phyllobates olfersioides* — Bokermann, 1966. *Colostethus olfersioides* — Edwards, 1971. Today *Allobates olfersioides* (A. Lutz, 1925).

olivaceus: L. *olivaceus*, olive-colored. *Brachycephalus olivaceus* Bornschein et al., 2015. (“... In life, dorsum, head, sides of the body, arms, legs, and thighs dark green ...”).

oliveirai: Oliveira + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Francisco M. Oliveira (?), Bokermann assistant. *Hyla oliveirai* Bokermann, 1963. Today *Dendropsophus oliveirai* (Bokermann, 1963).

Ololigon, Ololygon: G. *óloliǵón* (ὄλολιγγών), screecher (by extension, croaking of the frog). (1) *Ololygon* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). (2) *Ololigon abbreviatus petropolitana* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. In the synonymy of *Thoropa petropolitana* (Wandolleck, 1907). Also *Ololigon* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Scinax* Wagler, 1830.

onca: P. *onça*, vernacular name of the jaguar, *Panthera onca*. *Scinax onca* Ferrão et al., 2017. (“... The specific name *onca* refers to the Brazilian common name for the jaguar *Pantera* [sic] *onca* (Linnaeus, 1758) due the blotchy

12 See *Physalaemus olfersii*.

colour pattern of the new species. Furthermore, the specific name is a reference to frequent encounters of *P. onca* during the fieldwork in the PMI. The name is used as a noun in apposition ...”).

Oocormus: Unclear. G. *oon* (ὄον), egg of birds and reptiles + G. *cormos* (κορμός), trunk (of a tree). *Oocormus* Boulenger, 1905. No clues in the original description; probably related to the terrestrial egg-laying characteristic of its type-species, *O. microps*. In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus* Tschudi, 1838.

oophagus: G. *oon* (ὄον), egg + G. *phagos* (φάγος), glutton. *Osteocephalus oophagus* Jungfer & Schiesari, 1995. (“... refers to the larval habit of eating conspecific eggs ...”).

opalina: L. *opalus*, opal ($\text{SiO}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$); opaline color is defined as RGB (193, 209, 196), belonging to the green color family. *Hyla catharinae opalina* B. Lutz, 1968. (“... an opaline flash color on the flank and upper concealed aspects of the thigh ...”). Also *Ololygon opalina* – Heyer, 1980. *Scinax opalina* – Duellman & Wiens, 1992. *Scinax opalinus* – Köhler & Böhme, 1996. In the synonymy of *Scinax albicans* (Bokermann, 1967).

orcesi: Orcés + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Gustavo Orcés Villagómez (1903-1999), Ecuadorian zoologist. *Phyllomedusa orcesi* Funkhouser, 1957. In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa tarsius* (Cope, 1868).

orcus: L. *Orcus*, god of the underworld; also a whale. *Pristimantis orcus* Lehr et al., 2009. [“... The specific name *orcus* is the Latin noun for underworld. The specific name ... refers to the contrasting pattern of black and white in axilla, groin, anterior and posterior surfaces of thighs and concealed surfaces of tibia of preserved specimens, which remind us of the pattern in Orcas (Delphinidae) ...].

oreades: G. *Oreades* (Ὀρειάδς), mountain nimphs. Additionally, phytogeographic region corresponding to central Brazil according to Martius et al. (1824) (see *Phrynomedusa dryade*). *Phyllomedusa oreades* Brandão, 2002. (“... the specific epithet refers to the occurrence of the species in central Brazil,

always in open physiognomies on the top of plateaus and mountains ...”). Today *Pithecopus oreades* (Brandão, 2002).

oreites: *G. oreites* (ορειτης), mountaineer. *Dendrophryniscus oreites* Recoder et al., 2010. (“... It is a reference to the locality of the holotype, a steep forest on the slope of a hill summit ...”).

orejasmirandai: Orejas Miranda + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Braulio Rubí Orejas-Miranda (1933-1985), Uruguayan herpetologist. *Melanophryniscus orejasmirandai* Prigioni & Langone, 1987 “1986”. In the synonymy of *Melanophryniscus pachyrhynus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

Oreobates: *G. oreos* (ὄρεος), mountain + *G. bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (in turn, from βαίνω, move by taking step). *Oreobates* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872. (Probably related to the provenance of the type material, Quijos, on the Cordillera Real, Ecuador).

oreomantis: *G. oreos* (ὄρεος), mountain + *G. mantis* (μαντης), tree-frog. *Lepidodactylus oreomantis* Carvalho et al., 2013. [“... The epithet *oreomantis* stands for ‘mountain frog’, from Greek (*oreos* = mountain; *mantis* = anuran/frog). A literal translation for *Mantis* would be ‘prophet’, but this term was also employed to refer to amphibians, since they represented the ‘weather prophets’ to ancient Greek civilization ...”]¹³.

Oreoprhyne, Oreophrynella: *G. oreos* (ὄρεος), mountain + *G. + phrynos* (φρύνος), toad [+ L. *-ella*, suffix diminutive]. (1) *Oreophryne* Boulenger, 1895 (preoccupied by *Oreophryne* Boettger, 1895, anuran amphibian). (“... Several specimens were found by Messrs. Quelch and McConnell on the summit of Mount Roraima, between British Guiana and Venezuela, at an altitude of 8500 feet ...”). (2) *Oreophrynella* Boulenger, 1895. (“... Since I drew up ... the description of the new Batrachian discovered by Mr. Quelch, I have seen the number of the ‘Zoologischer Anzeiger’ ... in which Prof. O. Boettger describes a new Engystomatoid genus from Halmaheira under the name of *Oreophryne*. I therefore propose to change the name

suggested by me to *Oreophrynella Quelchii* ...”). Replacement name for *Oreophryne* Boulenger, 1895.

organensis: P. [Serra dos] Órgãos, mountain range in the state of Rio de Janeiro, Brasil + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Cycloramphus organensis* Weber et al., 2011. (“... The specific name is a Latinized adjective derived from the geographical name Serra dos Órgãos, referring to the type locality of the new species ...”). (2) *Dendrophryniscus organensis* A. Carvalho-e-Silva et al., 2010. (“... The specific epithet refers to the locality where the species was found, the Parque Nacional da Serra dos Órgãos, in the State of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil ...”).

orientalis: L. *orientalis*, from the East. (“... This is an eastern form of *H. rubra* from the Atlantic area of Brazil ...”). *Hyla rubra orientalis* B. Lutz, 1968 (junior homonym of *Hyla arborea orientalis* Bedriaga, 1890 “1889”). In the synonymy of *Scinax alter* (B. Lutz, 1973).

ornata, ornatum, ornatus: L. *ornata*, *-um*, *-us*, richly adorned, ornate. (1) *Uperodon ornatum* Bell, 1843. (“... The colour of the upper surface is dark olive, becoming lighter at the sides, and having numerous dark brown spots, which are round, oval, elliptical, or irregular, of very various sizes, placed somewhat symmetrically, and each bordered with a whitish or yellow line. Beneath pale, excepting the throat, which is black ...”). Today *Ceratophrys ornata* (Bell, 1843). (2) *Bufo ornatus* Spix, 1824. Refers to the complex color pattern. Also *Phrynomidius ornatus* — Cope, 1862. *Chaunus ornatus* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824). (3) *Elosia ornata* Bokermann, 1967. (?). Today *Hylodes ornatus* (Bokermann, 1967).

ornatissima: L. *ornatissima*, superlative of L. *ornata*, richly adorned, greatly ornate. *Hyla ornatissima* Noble, 1923. (“... Gaudy coloration of pinks and browns; two dark, pink-edged spots on the snout; a dark interorbital bar and a diamond shaped spot just anterior to the pelvis, similarly edged with pink ...”). Also *Hypsiboas ornatissimus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana ornatissima* (Noble, 1923).

orophila, orophilus: G. *oros* (ὄρος), mountain or mountainous region + G. *philos* (φίλος), friend. (1) *Hyla (Sphoerohyla) orophila* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938.

[“... *H. (Sph.) orophila* is a mountain species as its name denotes ...”]. Also *Hyla aurantiaca orophila* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. *Sphoerohyla orophila* — Goin, 1957. *Dryomelictes orophila* — Goin, 1961. *Hyla orophila* — Kenney, 1969. *Sphaenorhynchus orophilus* — Rivero, 1969. In the synonymy of *Sphaenorhynchus platycephalus* (Werner, 1894). (2) *Physalaemus orophilus* Cassini et al., 2010. (“... is given in allusion to the high elevations of the localities where the species is found ...”).

Oscaecilia: L. *os*, bone, + L. *Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus (1758) (see). *Oscaecilia* Taylor, 1968. (“... Eye buried under bone, and may or may not be visible through the bone ...”).

Osteocephalus: G. *osteon* (ὀστέον), bone + G. *kéfali* (κεφάλη), head. *Osteocephalus* Steindachner, 1862. (“... *Caput trigono-ovatum, supra cristis osseis ornatum, cute mobili obtectum ...*”).

ostinodactyla: G. *osteinós* (οστέινος), made of bone + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Scarthyra ostinodactyla* Duellman & de Sá, 1988. (“... The specific epithet is derived from the Greek adjective *ostinos* meaning of bone and the Greek noun *daktylos* meaning toe. The name means literally toes of bone and is used in reference to the ossified intercalary elements in the phalanges...”). In the synonymy of *Scarthyra goinorum* (Bokermann, 1962).

otavioi: Otávio + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Otávio C. de Oliveira, field assistant of I. Sazima and W.C.A. Bokermann. *Hylodes otavioi* Sazima & Bokermann, 1983.

Otilophes: G. *otos* (ὠτός), ear + G. *lophia* (λοφία), crest, headdress. *Otilophes* Cuvier, 1829. [“... la tête a, de chaque côté, une crête qui s’étend sur la parotide ...”]. Same root in the subsequent (incorrect) spellings: *Otilophis* Cuvier, 1831. *Osilophus* — Tschudi, 1838. *Otolophus* Fitzinger, 1843. *Otilophus* — Günther. *Otylophus* — Cei, 1953. In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

Otophryne: G. *otos* (ὠτός), from G. *ous* (οὔς), ear + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Otophryne* Boulenger, 1900. (“... Tympanum very distinct ...”). The same root in *Otophryninae* Wassersug & Pyburn, 1987.

oxente: P. *o*, oh! + P. *gente*, folk, people. *Bokermannohyla oxente* Lugli & Haddad, 2006. (“... The specific name is a name in apposition of the Portuguese words “ó” and “gente”, that is a very popular expression in Northeastern Brazil, meaning astonishment, surprise, or contempt ...”).

oxycephalus: G. *oxys* (οξύς), sharp, acute G. *kephali* (κεφάλι), head. *Cystignathus oxycephalus* Philippi, 1902. (“... Los caracteres esenciales que distinguen a esta especie son la cabeza angosta, el grosor de los muslos ...”). Also *Cystignathus oxicephalus* — Philippi, 1902 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus luctator* (Hudson, 1892).

oxyrhina: G. *oxys* (οξύς), sharp, acute + G. *rhinos* (ῥινός), nose, snout. *Hyla oxyrhina* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... da Hovedet er smalt og spidst, og den spidse Snude springer betydelig frem foran Underkjæben, naar man betragter Dyret franedet, men da Snudens Længde iøvrigt varierer noget, gjør den ikke altid i lige bøi Grad Indtrykket af at være spidssnudet ...”). Also *Hyla (Hypsiboas) oxyrhina* — Cope, 1863. In the synonymy of *Boana albopunctata* (Spix, 1824).

Oxyrhynchus: G. *oxys* (οξύς), sharp, acute + G. *rhynchos* (ρὺγχος), snout, muzzle. *Oxyrhynchus* Spix, 1824. [“... capite breve, acuti rostrato ...”]. Junior homonym of *Oxyrhynchus* Leach, 1818 (an African freshwater fish). In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

oyampiensis: (?) *Oyampi*, native culture of French Guiana from Haut Oyapok + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Centrolenella oyampiensis* Lescure, 1975. (“... Cette espèce est dédiée a mes amis indiennes de la tribu oyampi, ils m’ont souvent guidé dans la forêt et ont trouvé l’holotype de la nouvelle espèce ...”). Also *Cochranella oyampiensis* — Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. *Vitreorana oyampiensis* — Guayasamin et al., 2009. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana ritae* (B. Lutz in B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952).

ozzyi: *Ozzy* + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring John Michael “Ozzy” Osbourne, British rock singer. *Dendropsophus ozzyi* Orrico et al., 2014.

pacaas: (?). *Pacaás-Novos* or Wari', native-Brazilians from the family Chapacura, established in Rondônia. Additionally, the name of a conservation area, Parque Nacional dos Pacaás Novos (10. 84892°S, 63. 63312°W; 911 m above sea level), municipality of Campo Novo de Rondônia, state of Rondônia, Brazil. *Allobates pacaas* Melo-Sampaio et al., 2020. (“... *Allobates pacaas* is named in recognition of an important natural refuge in the Brazilian state of Rondonia ...”).

pachybrachion: G. *pachys* (παχύς), thick + G. *brachion* (βραχίων), arm. *Rana pachybrachion* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. (“... Arme colossal dick ...”). Also *Rana pacybrachion* — Vanzolini & Myers, 2015 (*error typographicus*). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815).

pachykrus: G. *pachy* (παχυ), thick + L. *crus*, leg; shank. *Hyla pachykrus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. (?). (“... Corpo e membros deprimidos ...”). Also *Ololygon pachykrus* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax pachykrus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

pachydactyla: G. *pachy* (παχυ), thick + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Adelephryne pachydactyla* Hoogmoed et al., 1994. (“... in reference to the thick, short, swollen fingers of this species ...”).

pachyderma: G. *pachy* (παχυ), thick + G. *dermos* (δερμος), skin. *Leptodactylus pachyderma* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... Pelle lisa, porém espessa tanto em cima como nos flancos ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus flavo-pictus* A. Lutz, 1926.

Pachymandra: G. *pachys* (παχύς), thick + L. *mandra*, ending of *Salamandra*, genus of urodeles due to Garsault (1764) (in turn, from G. σαλαμάνδρα, vernacular name of the animals). *Pachymandra* Parra-Olea et al., 2004. (“... A group of large to very large salamanders ...”). A subgenus of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854.

Pachypus, pachypus: G. *pachys* (παχύς), thick + G. *-pus*, from *podos* (ποδος), foot. (1) *Pachypus* A. Lutz, 1930 (“... podemos reconhecer uma divisão, formada por espécies grandes ... em que o macho adulto não somente mostra duas pontas duras, freqüentemente córneas e pretas, no lado interno da

mão, mas desenvolve também uma hipertrofia progressiva da musculatura e dos ossos da extremidade anterior ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826. (2) *Rana pachypus* Spix, 1824. (“... *humerus maris in-crassatis* ...”). Also *Cystignathus pachypus* — Wagler, 1830. *Rana pachypus pachypus* — Mayer, 1835. *Leptodactylus pachypus* — Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815). (3) *Rana pachypus* var. 2 Spix, 1824. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Schneider, 1799).

pachyrhynus: G. *pachy* (παχυ), thick + G. *rhinos* (ῥινός), nose, snout. *Atelopus pachyrhynus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... Palpebras salientes; o espaço compreendido entre ellas e as narinas occupado por um intumescimento que assim forma um rebordo supero-anterior que se estende até a linha interocular mediana ...”). Today *Melanophryniscus pachyrhynus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

pailona: S. *pailona*, demonym (f.) of the inhabitants of El Pailón, locality at 17°39’S 62°43’W in provincia Chiquitos, department Santa Cruz, Bolivia. *Phyllomedusa pailona* Shreve, 1959. (“... El Pailon, 5 kilometers from the eastern shore of the Rio Grande, altitude 350 meters, Department of Santa Cruz, Bolivia ...”). In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa boliviana* Boulenger, 1902.

Palaeobufo: G. *palaios* (παλαιός), old + L. *bufo*, toad. *Palaeobufo* Bolkay, 1919. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

paleovarzensis: P. *paleovárzeas*, ancient floodplains that no longer receive sediments from white water rivers, rich in nutrients. *Allobates paleovarzensis* Lima et al., 2010. (“... The specific name refers to the paleovárzea habitat in which the species occurs. Paleovárzeas are ancient floodplains of the Amazon River and its tributaries that are no longer subject to seasonal inundation ...”).

pallens: L. *pallens*, pale; greenish. *Hyla pallens* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Toutes les couleurs sont pâles ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus minutus* (Peters, 1872).

palliata, palliatus: *L. palliata*, -atus, clad in a pallium, cloaked. *Phyllomedusa palliata* Peters, 1873 “1872”. (“... Rückseite violett, wie bei *Ph. hypochondrialis* scharf abgeschnitten gegen die hellen Körperseiten; am Kopfe lässt das Violett die Schläfengegend und das Trommelfell frei, geht durch das obere Augenlid und bis zur Mitte der Frenalgegend herab, und dringt nur vor den Nasenlöchern auf dem Schnauzenende bis nahe zum Lippenrande vor ...”). Today *Pithecopus palliatus* (Peters, 1873).

pallidirostris: *L. pallidus*, pale, yellow-green + *L. rostris*, beak, snout. *Leptodactylus pallidirostris* A. Lutz, 1930. (“... Do espaço interocular, atravessado por uma estria escura irregular e sinuosa, estende-se para diante uma mancha clara com a cor de marfim velho e amarelado ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus validus* Garman, 1888.

palmata, palmatus: *L. palmata*, -atus, webbed. (1) *Podonectes palmatus* Steindachner, 1864 (*nomen nudum*). (?). In the synonymy of *Lysapsus limellum* Cope, 1862. (2) *Rana palmata* Lacépède, 1788. (“... Ce qui la caractérise & ce qui lui a fait donner, par M. d’Aubenton, le nom de Patte-d’oie que nous lui conservons, c’est que les doigts des pieds de devant, ainsi que des pieds de derrière, sont réunis par des membranes ...”; additionally, “... *Pedibus anterioribus posterioribusque palmatis* ...”). Also *Rana palmata* Bonnatte, 1789. *Hyla palmata* Latreille in Sonnini de Manoncourt & Latreille, 1801 “An. X”. *Hyla palmata* — Daudin, 1802 “An. XI”. *Calamita palmatus* — Merrem, 1820. *Hypsiboas palmata* — Wagler, 1830. *Hypsiboas palmatus* — Tschudi, 1838. *Lobipes palmata* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Hyla (Hylo-medusa) palmata* — Burmeister, 1856. In the synonymy of *Boana boans* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Palmatotriton: *L. palmatus*, webbed + *L. Triton*, genus of salamanders due to Laurenti (1768) [in turn from *G. triton* (Τρῖτων), sea god, son of Poseidon and Amphitrite], preoccupied by *Triton* Linnaeus, 1758 (a gastropod); frequent ending in urodele names. *Palmatotriton* Smith, 1945. (?) A subgenus of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854.

palmipes: *L. palmatus*, webbed + *L. pes*, foot. (1) *Rana palmipes* Spix, 1824. (“... *plantae longis, large palmatis* ...”). Also *Pohlia palmipes* — Steindachner,

1867. *Ranula palmipes* — Cope, 1871. *Rana (Rana) palmipes* — Dubois, 1987 “1986”. *Rana (Lithobates) palmipes* — Dubois, 1992. *Rana (Novirana, Sierrana, Ranula, Lithobates) palmipes* — Hillis & Wilcox, 2005. *Lithobates (Lithobates) palmipes* — Dubois, 2006. Today *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Stereocyclops palmipes* Caramaschi et al., 2012. (“... The name, a Latin adjective, refers to the webbed feet of the species ...”).

palpebrogranulata: L. *palpebra*, eyelid + L. *granulatus*, provided with granules. *Hyla palpebrogranulata* Andersson, 1906. (“... the upper eyelid, the whole lower surfaces of the body and of the thighs, and the sides of the body densely granulate ...”). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhoni* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Paludicola: L. *paludis*, swamp, marsh + L. *-cola*, suffix that indicates that it is an inhabitant of. *Paludicola* Wagler, 1830. (?). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus* Fitzinger, 1826.

palustris: L. *palustris*, marshy; of marshes. (1) *Proceratophrys palustris* Giaretta & Sazima, 1993. [“... O epíteto específico deriva do latim “paluster” (= pântano, brejo), em referência ao ambiente onde vocalizam os machos e ocorrem as larvas...”]. (2) *Sphaenorhynchus palustris* Bokermann, 1966. (“... Todos os exemplares foram obtidos cantando à noite entre a vegetação de uma pequena lagoa no local denominado Areia Branca ...”).

Pantherana: L. *panthera*, panther + L. *rana*, frog. *Pantherana* Dubois, 1992. (“... ce nom évoque l’aspect panthérin de ces Grenouilles, dont le dos est habituellement couvert de grosses taches bien distinctes ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

papachibe: P. *papa-chibe*, demonym of the natives of the state of Pará, Brazil; also, who eats “chibé”, a regional food. *Chiasmocleis papachibe* Peloso et al., 2014. [“... Chibé is made by soaking manioc (*Manihot esculenta*) ... The name “Papa-Chibé,” or “Papa-Xibé,” is colloquially used to refer to anyone who is native to the state of Pará ... *Chiasmocleis papachibe* is, up until now, known only from a couple of localities in Pará ...”]. Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) papachibe* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

papillaris: L. *papillaris*, provided with papillae. *Hyla papillaris* Spix, 1824. (“... *punctulis roseo-albicantibus numerosissime conspersum ...*”). In the synonymy of *Boana punctata* (Schneider, 1799).

paracnemis: G. *para* (παρά), by the side of, beside, alongside + G. *cnemis* (κνήμης), lower part of the leg, shin. *Bufo paracnemis* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... En outre des parotides énormes il y a, au long du tibia, une serie de glandes formant une masse et contenant la même sécrétion laiteuse et toxique ...”). Also *Bufo marinus paracnemis* — Müller & Hellmich, 1936. In the synonymy of *Rhinella diptycha* (Cope, 1862).

paradoxa, paradoxus: G. *paradoxos* (παραδοξως), strange, contrary to expectation. *Rana paradoxa* Linnaeus, 1758. [Seba’s 1734 *Rana piscis* included in the original synonymy. Together with Merian (1719), they indicated that the adult frogs of that species were transformed into fish, in a kind of “inverse metamorphosis”]. Also *Pseudes paradoxa* — Wiegmann, 1832. *Pseudis paradoxus* — Savage & Carvalho, 1953. *Pseudis paradoxus paradoxus* — Gallardo, 1961. Today *Pseudis paradoxa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

paraensis: P. Pará, river, city and state in northern Brazil, from T. *pará*, mighty, fast flowing river; sea + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Dendrobates paraensis* Boulenger, 1913. (“... Eight specimens, from Para, are preserved in the British Museum ...”). In the synonymy of *Adelphobates galactonotus* (Steindachner, 1864). (2) *Eupemphix paraensis* Müller, 1923. (“... Peixeboi (an der Bragancabahn), Staat Para, Nord-Brasilien ...”). In the synonymy of *Engystomops petersi* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872. (3) *Leptodactylus paraensis* Heyer, 2005. (“... Brazil; Pará, Serra de Kukoinhokren, 07°46’S,51°57’W ...”). (4) *Oedipus paraensis* Unterstein, 1930. (“... Gefunden wurde das Tier von dem Fänger der Firma Scholze & Poetzschke, Berlin, Herrn Praetorius, in einem Vororte (Sta. Isabel) in der nächsten Nähe der Stadt Para am Amazonenstrom ...”). Also in the combinations *Bolitoglossa (Eladinea) paraensis* — Parra-Olea et al., 2004. Today *Bolitoglossa paraensis* (Unterstein, 1930).

paraguayensis: S. Paraguay, South American country + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Rhinella paraguayensis* Ávila et al., 2010. (“... The specific epithet is an adjective, derived from the type locality of the new species: the Para-

guay River basin ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella scitula* (Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2003).

Paramophrynella: S. *páramo*, high Andean ecosystem, from L. *paramus*, wasteland; uncultivated land + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + L. *-ella*, suffix diminutive (etymology by the author). *Paramophrynella* La Marca, 2007 “2006”. (“... El origen del nombre es una combinación de las palabras “*páramo*”, que denota uno de los ambientes más elevados de los Andes tropicales, “*phrynos*”, del griego para sapo, y el sufijo diminutivo en Latín, “*-ella*” ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

paranaensis: P. *Paraná*, name of a river and a Brazilian state (from T. *pará-nã*, which is similar to the sea) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Eleutherodactylus paranaensis* Langone & Segalla, 1996. (“... El epíteto específico hace referencia al nombre de la localidad y del Estado en el que fue colectado ...”). Today *Ischnocnema paranaensis* (Langone & Segalla, 1996).

paranaíba: T. *paranaíba*, *parnaíba*, muddy-watered or large river. *Hypsiboas paranaíba* Carvalho et al., 2010. T (“... refers to the Paranaíba River, which flows through most of the northern border of the Triângulo Mineiro region, and is close to the sites where the type-series of *H. paranaíba* was collected ...”). Today *Boana paranaíba* (Carvalho et al., 2010).

paranaru: T. *paranã*, sea + T. *aru*, frog (in the tembé-ténêthar dialect). *Leptodactylus paranaru* Magalhães et al., 2020. (“... reference to the new species restricted occurrence along the Brazilian southeastern coastal zone, which can be found at fresh or brackish water bodies a few meters from the shore ...”).

Paratelmatoebius: L. *para-*, near + L. *Telmatoebius*, genus of anurans due to Wiegmann, 1834 [in turn, from G. *telmatos* (τέλματος), stagnant water, pond, marsh, lagoon + G. *bios* (βίος), existence or condition of being alive; life]. *Paratelmatoebius* B. Lutz & Carvalho, 1958. (“... *Paratelmatoebius* parece formar um elo entre as formas do gênero brasileiro *Cyclorhamphus* Tschudi, 1838, endêmico nas nossas serras costeiras, e as formas andinas, pertencentes aos gêneros *Telmatoebius* Wiegmann, 1835 e *Batrachophrynus* Peters, 1873 ...”). The same root in *Paratelmatoebinae* Ohler & Dubois, 2012.

pardalis: L. *pardus*, leopard + L. *-alis*, pertaining to a, in a condition of. *Hyla pardalis* Spix, 1824. (“... *hypochondriis femoribusque nigro-fasciatis* ...”). Also *Hypsiboas pardalis* — Cope, 1867. Today *Boana pardalis* (Spix, 1824).

parecis: Ar. (?) *Parecis*, native Brazilians established in the state of Mato Grosso, Brazil, self-denominated *Haliti* (person or people). *Rhinella parecis* Ávila et al., 2020. (“... The specific name *parecis* ... refers to the Chapada dos Parecis, a plateau occupying large portions of the Brazilian states of Mato Grosso and Rondônia, Brazil ...”).

parkeri: Parker + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hampton Wildman Parker (1897-1968), British herpetologist. (1) *Hyla parkeri* Gaige, 1929. Also *Ololygon parkeri* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax parkeri* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. In the synonymy of *Scinax fuscomarginatus* (A. Lutz, 1925). (2) *Hyla Parkeri* De Witte, 1930. The same root in *Hyla parkeriana* De Witte, 1930 (replacement name for *Hyla parkeri* De Witte, 1930, preoccupied by *Hyla parkeri* Gaige, 1929). In the synonymy of *Alainia fulvorufa* (Andersson, 1911). (3) *Hypopachus parkeri* Wettstein, 1934. Today *Stereocyclops parkeri* (Wettstein, 1934).

parnaiba: P. Parnaíba [a. k. a. Velho Monge], river that forms the border of the states of Maranhão and Piauí, Brazil (in turn, from T. *paranã-ayba*, the big, bad, or impractical flow). *Pseudopaludicola parnaiba* Roberto et al., 2013. (“... The specific epithet *parnaiba* refers to the Parnaíba River, an allusion to the habitat of the species, which occurs along the banks of this river ...”). In the synonymy of *Pseudopaludicola canga* Giaretta & Kokubum, 2003.

parnaso: P. PARNASO, acronym for Parque Nacional da Serra dos Órgãos (Rio de Janeiro, Brazil). *Ischnocnema parnaso* Taucce et al., 2018. [“... The name “PARNASO” is the abbreviation for Parque Nacional da Serra dos Órgãos (Serra dos Órgãos National Park), type locality of the species ...”].

parva: L. *parva*, small, little. *Hylodes parvus* Girard, 1853. [In the redescription of 1858, Girard noted “... The body is comparatively short, not quite the two-thirds of the length, the head included. The limbs are slender; the fingers and toes slender also, and terminated by comparatively small disks ...”]. Also *Eleutherodactylus parvus* — Stejneger, 1904. Today *Ischnocnema parva* (Girard, 1853).

Parvicaecilia: *L. parvus*, small, little; unimportant + *L. Caecilia*, genus of gymnophiones due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see). *Parvicaecilia* Taylor, 1968. (“... Slender, diminutive species ...”). In the synonymy of *Microcaecilia* Taylor, 1968.

parviceps: *L. parvus*, small, little + *L. -ceps*, -headed. *Hyla parviceps* Boulenger, 1882. (“... Head very small, a little broader than long ...”). Today *Dendropsophus parviceps* (Boulenger, 1882).

parvula, parvulus: *L. parvula*, very small, very young. (1) *Hylella parvula* Boulenger, 1895 “1894”. (“... From snout to vent 17 millim. ...”). Also *Cochranella parvula* — Taylor & Cochran, 1953. *Centrolenella parvula* — Duellman, 1977. *Hyalinobatrachium parvulum* — Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. Today *Vitreorana parvula* (Boulenger, 1895 “1894”). (2) *Cystignathus parvulus* Girard, 1853. (?). Also *Zachaenus parvulus* — Cope, 1866. *Leptodactylus parvulus* — A. Lutz, 1932. Today *Cycloramphus parvulus* (Girard, 1853). (3) *Parvulus* A. Lutz, 1930. (“... *Parvulus* para *nanus*, *trivittatus* e algumas outras espécies exíguas ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826.

passarellii: Passarelli + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alcides Passarelli Filho (?), Brazilian commercial collector. *Arcovomer passarellii* Carvalho, 1954.

pauiniensis: P. [Boca do] Pauini, hamlet in the state of Amazonas, Brazil + *L. -ensis*, belonging to a place. *Hyla pauiniensis* Heyer, 1977. (“... The species is named for the location of Boca do Pauini, the type locality, where several very productive days were spent in profitable collecting and feeding mosquitos ...”). Today *Dendropsophus pauiniensis* (Heyer, 1977).

paulensis: P. [São] Paulo, Brazilian city and state + *L. -ensis*, belonging to a place. *Siphonops paulensis* Boettger, 1892. (“... Erw. Saõ Paulo, Brasilien ...”). Also *Siphonops paulensis paulensis* — Sawaya, 1937.

pauloalvini: Paulo Alvim + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paulo de Tarso Alvim Carneiro (1919-2011), Brazilian plant biologist at the Comissão Executiva do Plano da Lavoura Ca-

caueira (CEPLAC), in Ilhéus, Bahia, Brazil. *Sphaenorhynchus pauloalvini* Bokermann, 1973. Today *Gabohyla pauloalvini* (Bokermann, 1973).

paulodutrai: Paulo Dutra + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paulo Coutinho Dutra (?), Brazilian agricultural engineer at the Comissão Executiva do Plano da Lavoura Cacaueira (CEPLAC), in Ilhéus, Bahia, Brazil. *Eleutherodactylus paulodutrai* Bokermann, 1975 “1974”. Today *Pristimantis paulodutrai* (Bokermann, 1975).

paviotii: Pavioti + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Antônio Pavioti (?), Brazilian naturalist. *Proceratophrys paviotii* Cruz et al., 2005.

payaya: (?). *Payaya*, native Brazilian culture, once present at Chapada Diamantina. *Leptodactylus payaya* Magalhães et al., 2020. (“... The region corresponds to the new species type locality ...”).

pearsei: Pearse + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Arthur Sperry Pearse (1877-1956), US American zoologist. (1) *Hylella pearsei* Ruthven, 1922. Also *Hyla pearsei* — Dunn, 1944. In the synonymy of *Boana punctata* (Schneider, 1799). (2) *Hypopachus pearsei* Ruthven, 1914. Also *Elachistocleis pearsei* — Dunn, 1944. *Relictivomer pearsei* — Carvalho, 1954. *Engystoma pearsei* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Elachistocleis pearsei* (Ruthven, 1914).

pearsoni: Pearson + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Nathan Everett Pearson (1895-1982), North American ichthyologist. *Hyla pearsoni* Gaige, 1929. Also *Osteocephalus pearsoni* — Goin, 1961. Today *Dryaderces pearsoni* (Gaige, 1929).

pedromedinae: Pedro Medina + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating belonging. Honouring Pedro Medina Pizango, from Puerto Maldonado, Peru. *Ololygon pedromedinae* Henle, 1991. Today *Scinax pedromedinae* (Henle, 1991).

peixotoi: Peixoto + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Oswaldo Luiz Peixoto, Brazilian herpetologist. *Scinax peixotoi* Brasileiro et al., 2007. Also *Ololygon peixotoi* — Duellman et al., 2016.

Pelorius: G. *pelorios* (πελώριος), (of living beings) of unusual or frightening size or strength (with both positive and negative connotations.). *Pelorius* Hedges, 1989. (“... From the Greek, *Pelorios*, meaning huge, prodigious, awe-inspiring; referring to the large size of the species in this group, and the striking appearance of some ...”). In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

penaxavantinho: P. short for Pena Branca and Xavantinho, Brazilian singers (in turn, from P. “pena branca”, white feather + P. “xavantinho”, diminutive of T. *xavante*, related to the Xavantes, native Brazilian people that inhabit some regions of the states of Mato Grosso and northwestern Goiás). *Ischnocnema penaxavantinho* Giaretta et al., 2007. (“... The specific epithet is an arbitrary fusion of two Portuguese words, pena (meaning feather) and xavantinho (meaning little Xavante, a group of pre-colonization natives). These names were used by two regional singer brothers (Pena Branca and Xavantinho) who in their songs emphasized the beauty of the Brazilian nature and the countryside way of life ...”).

pentadactylus: G. *penta* (πεντα), five + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Rana pentadactyla* Laurenti, 1768. (“... *pedibus fasciatis pentadactylis* ...”). Also *Cystignathus pentadactylus* — Peters, 1872. *Leptodactylus pentadactylus pentadactylus* — Müller, 1927. *Leptodactylus (Pachypus) pentadactylus* — A. Lutz, 1930. Today *Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768).

Peralaimos: G. *pera* (πηρᾶ), bag + G. *laimos* (λαιμός), throat. *Peralaimos* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (“... machos con dos grandes sacos bucales ...”). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838.

perere: P. [Saci] *Pererê*, Brazilian folkloric entity, personified in a one-legged black boy, who wears a red cap, puffs on a pipe, makes mischief, frightens visitors, and scares off cattle; from T. *Yaci-Yaterê*, fragment of the moon. *Hylodes perere* Silva & Benmaman, 2008. [“... O nome *perere* (pererê em Português) refere-se a um personagem do folclore dos índios do Brasil que descreve uma entidade que guarda as florestas e perturba o silêncio com assovios ou apitos. O nome é aqui utilizado em alusão à atividade de canto da nova espécie que vocaliza durante o dia e também à noite ...”].

perereca: T. *perereca*, tree-frog, from T. *pererek'a*, intransitive verb, flap wings, jump. *Scinax perereca* Pombal et al., 1995. [... This is a name frequently used to designate hylid frogs (mainly *Scinax rubra* group), by most people in Brazil ...”].

perezi: Pérez + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Laureano Pérez Arcas (1824-1894), Spanish entomologist and malacologist. *Edalorhina perezi* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. Also *Pleurodema perezi* — Nieden, 1923.

perissodus: G. *perissos* (περισσός), beyond what is normal in number or size + G. *odoús* (οδούς), tooth (human or animal, usu. pl.). *Chthonerpeton perissodus* Nussbaum & Wilkinson 1987. [... This species has more premaxillary-maxillary teeth than any other *Chthonerpeton*, hence the name *perissodus*, from *perissos* (Greek, more than the usual number of) and *odous* (Greek, tooth) ...”].

peritus: L. *peritus*, die, pass away; be ruined, be destroyed. *Melanophryniscus peritus* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2011. (“... in reference to the current [conservation] status of the species ...”).

perlata, perlatus: L. *perlata*, -us, carrying/wearing pearls. (1) *Bufo perlatus* Cuvier, 1816 “1817”. (“... Le crapaud perlé ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768). (2) *Phyllomedusa perlata* Boulenger, 1884 “1883”. (“... a series of pearl-like white tubercles from the eye to half-way down the body. Also *Phyllomedusa (Pithecopus) perlata* — B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952. In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa vaillantii* Boulenger, 1882.

pernambucensis: Pernambuco, Brazilian state; corr. from T. *paranã-buc*, the sea raises, in reference to the reef + L. -ensis, belonging to a place. *Atelopus pernambucensis* Bokermann, 1962. (“... Dois Irmãos, arredores de Recife, Pernambuco, Brasil ...”). Today *Frostius pernambucensis* (Bokermann, 1962).

pernigra: L. *per*, very, completely, thoroughly + L. *nigra*, black, dark. *Pipa pernigra* Barbour, 1923. (“... Coal-black above and below, whereas *P. pipa* is mahogany brown ...”). In the synonymy of *Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

pernix: L. *pernix*, nimble, brisk, active, agile, quick, swift, fleet. *Brachycephalus pernix* Pombal et al., 1998. (“... The specific name ... is an allusion to the characteristic mode of locomotion ...”).

perplicata, perplicatus: L. *perplicata*, -atus, thoroughly folded. *Elosia perplicata* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... com a pelle, embora porosa em toda extensão superior, lisa e tendo um cordão granular longitudinal dos olhos á região inguinal ...”). Today *Hylodes perplicatus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

perpusillus: L. *perpusillus*, very small. *Hyla perpusilla* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939. [“... *Hyla perpusilla* is one of the smallest species of brazilian *Hylae* (19-22 mm) ...”]. Also *Hyla perpusilla perpusilla* — B. Lutz, 1968. *Ololygon perpusilla* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax perpusilla* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax perpusillus* (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939).

personatus: L. *personatus*, masked. *Physalaemus personatus* Steindachner, 1864. (Although the name was attributed to Fitzinger, and coined in synonymy of *Nattereria lateristriga*, the description of that species note: “... Eine breite, intensiv schwarzbraune, sammtartige Längsbinde, nach vorne und hinten zugespitzt, zwischen dem hinteren Augenwinkel und der Lendengegend, an vorderen unteren Rande zwischen dem Auge und der Schulter hell gesäumt ...”). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus lateristriga* (Steindachner, 1864).

peruvianus: S. Perú, South American country + L. -anus, belonging to. *Hylodes peruvianus* Melin, 1941. (“... 1 specimen, Roque, Peru, July 1925 ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus peruvianus* — Stejneger, 1904 (by implication; Gorham, 1966). Today *Pristimantis peruvianus* (Melin, 1941).

peruviridis: L. *peruviana*, from Perú + L. *perviridis*, very green (etymology by the author). *Ameerega peruviridis* Bauer, 1986. [“... As this species is found in Peru and characterised by bright green colour the specific epithet is a contamination of *peruviana* and *perviridis* (= very green). The specific name means Green one from Peru ...”]. In the synonymy of *Ameerega trivittata* (Spix, 1824).

perviridis: L. *per-*, very, completely, thoroughly + L. *viridis*, fresh, green. *Aplastodiscus perviridis* B. Lutz, 1950. (“...Inteiramente verde e muito uniforme...”). Also *Hyla perviridis* — Caramaschi, 1983.

petersi, petersii: Peters + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Wilhelm Karl Hartwig Peters (1815-1883), German zoologist. (1) *Phyllobates petersi* Silverstone, 1976. Also *Dendrobates petersi* — Myers et al., 1978. *Epipedobates petersi* — Myers, 1987. *Phyllobates (Pseudendrobates) petersi* — Bauer, 1988. Today *Ameerega petersi* (Silverstone, 1976). (2) *Engystomops petersi* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872. Also *Engystomops petersii* — Boulenger, 1882. *Physalaemus petersi* — Lynch, 1970. (3) *Platymantis petersii* Steindachner, 1864. Also *Leptodactylus (Platymantis) petersii* — A. Lutz, 1930. *Leptodactylus caliginosus petersi* — Parker, 1935. *Leptodactylus podicipinus petersii* — Gans, 1960. Today *Leptodactylus petersii* (Steindachner, 1864). (4) *Chthonerpeton petersii* Boulenger, 1882 “1861”. Today *Nectocaecilia petersii* (Boulenger, 1882).

petropolitana, petropolitanus: P. Petrópolis, a city in the state of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [from G. *Petros* (Πέτρος), Peter + G. *polis* (πολις), city] + L. *-ana*, *-anus*, pertaining to. (1) *Cochranella petropolitana* Taylor & Cochran, 1953. (“... Type: U. S. National Museum No. 101135, Petropolis, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil ...”). In the synonymy of *Vitreorana eurygnatha* (A. Lutz, 1925). (2) *Hylodes petropolitanus* Wandolleck, 1907. (“... Die Tiere stammen alle aus den Urwäldern von Petropolis ...”). Also *Elosia petropolitanus* — Boulenger, 1909. *Ololygon abbreviatus petropolitana* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. *Eleutherodactylus petropolitanus* — Müller, 1927. *Borborocotes petropolitanus* — Noble, 1927. *Eupsophus petropolitanus* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. Today *Thoropa petropolitana* (Wandolleck, 1907).

pfrimeri: Pfrimer + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Rudolf Pfrimer (1885-1954), Brazilian ornithologist. *Bufo crucifer* var. *pfrimeri* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. Also *Bufo crucifer pfrimeri* — Bokermann, 1966; incorrect subsequent spelling. In the synonymy of *Rhaebo guttatus* (Schneider, 1799).

phaeopleura: G. *phaios* (φαιός), dusky, dun, gray + G. *pleura* (πλευρά), sides or side. *Hyla phaeopleura* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2000. [... O nome da espécie, um adjetivo, deriva de palavras gregas que fazem alusão à faixa lateral (“pleura”) de cor marrom (“phaeo”) ...]. Also *Hypsiboas phaeopleura* — Faivovich et al., 2005. In the synonymy of *Boana goiana* (B. Lutz, 1968).

Phantasmarana: L. *phantasma*, ghost; phantom; spirit + L. *rana*, frog. *Phantasmarana* Vittorazzi et al., 2021. [... in reference to the extraordinary rarity of frogs of this genus in the wild (only few herpetologists have seen these frogs in their natural habitats), the lack of an advertisement call, and the fact that some enigmatic sounds have been reported ...].

Phasmahyla: L. Phasmida or Phasmatodea, order of insects; in turn, from G. *phasma* (φάσμα), spectrum, phantom, vision (in a dream). *Phasmahyla* Cruz 1991 “1990”. (... O nome empregado é em alusão a semelhança do caminhar dos insetos da ordem Phasmatodea ...).

Phirix: Unclear. G. *phiros* (φηρός), wild animal, beast; the Centaurs. (?). *Phirix* Schmidt, 1857. In the synonymy of *Atelopus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

Phobobates: G. *phobos* (φοβέω, φόβος), (of persons, animals) run away in fear or be put to flight + G. *bates* (βατες), walker, who walks. *Phobobates* Zimmermann & Zimmermann, 1988. “... Der Name weist darauf hin, daß die Angehörigen dieser Gattung sehr schreckhaft sind und bei Annäherung schon aus größerem Abstand fliehen ...”. In the synonymy of *Ameerega* Bauer, 1986.

pholeter: G. *pholeter* (φωλητήρ), one who lurks in a hole. *Holoaden pholeter* Pombal et al., 2008. (... in allusion to the cryptic habits of the species ...).

phonotriccus: G. *phonos* (φωνος), voice + G. *triccus* (τριξξος), small bird. *Adenomera phonotriccus* Carvalho et al., 2019. (... is an allusion to the similarity between the vocalization of the new species and those of tody-tyrants ...).

Phrynanodus: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + L. *nodus*, knot, node. *Phrynanodus* Ahl, 1933. (... Oberseite des Kopfes, des Körpers und der Gliedmaßen dicht besetzt mit kleinen Granulen und Tuberkeln, die in der Nackengegend zu zwei konkav gebogenen Leisten und an den Seiten des Rückens zu je einer

Dorsolateralfalte zusammenfließen ...”). In the synonymy of *Ischnocnema* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862.

Phrynidium: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + L. *idium*, diminutive. *Phrynidium* Lichtenstein & Martens, 1856. (“... *Differt ... ab Atelepode, cui proxime affinis, tuberculo metatarsi distincto digitisque elongatis, teretibus, apice subdilatatis, a Phrynisco habitu digitisque ...*”). In the synonymy of *Atelopus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

Phryniscus: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + G. *-ikos* (-ίκος), with the aspect of, belonging to. *Phryniscus* Wiegmann, 1834. [“... Die gesamte Körperform ganz wie bei *Bufo* ...”]. In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

Phrynocerus: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + G. *keras* (κέρας), horn. *Phrynocerus* Rafinesque, 1815 (*nomen nudum*). The same root in *Phrynoceros* Tschudi, 1838. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys* Wied-Neuwied, 1824.

phrynoderma: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + G. *dermos* (δερμος), skin. *Hyla phrynoderma* Boulenger, 1889 (“... Upper surfaces covered with numerous small round warts of unequal sizes ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax acuminatus*.

Phrynohyas: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + G. *ylas* (υλάς), thick vegetation (esp. assoc. w. mountains). *Phrynohyas* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus* Tschudi, 1838.

Phrynomedusa: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + G. *medusa*, apocope of *Phyllomedusa* (see). *Phrynomedusa* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. (“... Forma aliada de *Phyllomedusa*: Pupilla vertical; tympano evidente; parotoides pequenos e de direção obliqua sobre os ombros; vomerinos ausentes; lingua inteira ou distintamente entalhada no bordo posterior. Dedos e artelhos como nas *Hylas*, não opostos, porém os metatarsaes e metacarpas dispostos em curva ...”).

Phrynomorphus: G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad + G. *morphi* (μορφή), form. *Phrynomorphus* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Rhaebo* Cope, 1862.

phryxa: G. *phrix* (φρίξ), ruffling, rippling. *Cochranella phryxa* Aguayo-Vedia & Harvey, 2006. (“... The specific epithet *phryxa* is derived from the Greek word *phryx* meaning ripple or fold. The new name is a noun in apposition alluding to the numerous folds on the body of *Cochranella phryxa* ...”). In the synonymy of *Cochranella resplendens* (Lynch & Duellman, 1973).

Phyllobates: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *bates* (βατες), walker, who walks (from βαίνω, move by taking step). *Phyllobates* Bibron, 1840. (?). In the synonymy of *Allobates*, Zimmermann & Zimmermann, 1988 (*part.*).

Phyllobius: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *bios* (βίος), existence or condition of being alive; life. *Phyllobius* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Boana* Gray, 1825.

phyllodes: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *-oeides* (-οειδής), similar to. *Hylodes phyllodes* Heyer & Cocroft, 1986. (“... in allusion to the difficulty of visually distinguishing the frogs from leaves on or near the ground along streams during the day ...”).

Phyllodromus: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *dromos* (δρόμος), action of running. *Phyllodromus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (?). In the synonymy of *Hylaxalus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

Phyllodytes: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *dýtis* (δύτης), diver. *Phyllodytes* Wagler, 1830. (?).

Phyllomedusa: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *medeon* (μεδέων), *medeousa* (μεδέουσα), ruling, holding. *Phyllomedusa* Wagler, 1830. (“... Φύλλον frons, & μεδω impero ...”) ¹⁴. The same root in *Phyllomedusidae* Günther, 1858.

Phyllonastes: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *nastes* (νάστης), inhabitant. (“... From the Greek *phyllon*, leaf, and *nastes*, dweller, in reference to the leaf

¹⁴ This is the etymology given by Wagler (1830) when describing the genus *Phyllomedusa*; differs from later interpretations, that point to the combination *phyllou* (φυλλου), leaf + *medusa* (μέδουσα), apparently in reference to coelenterated jellyfish, alluding to the masses of gelatinous eggs deposited on the leaves of trees (i. a., Duellman, 1970).

litter habitat characteristic of members of the genus ...”). *Phyllonastes* Heyer, 1977. In the synonymy of *Noblella* Barbour, 1930.

phyllostomus: G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf + G. *stoma* (στόμα), mouth. *Proceratophrys phyllostomus* Izecksohn et al., 1999. (“... O substantivo *phyllostomus* é o nome do gênero-tipo de uma família de morcegos que reúne espécies possuidoras de um conspícuo apêndice foliáceo rostral ...”).

Physalaemus: G. *physao* (φυσάω), inflate with air; puff out + G. *laimos* (λαιμός), throat. *Physalaemus* Fitzinger, 1826. (?).

Physodes: G. *physao* (φυσάω), inflate with air; puff out + G. *-odes* (-οδες), suffix for likeness. *Physodes* Jan, 1857 (*nomen nudum*). (?). In the synonymy of *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838.

Phyzelaphryne: G. *phyzelis* (φύξηλις), shy + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Phyzelaphryne* Heyer, 1977. (“... in reference to members of the genus avoiding capture or recognition by scientists until recently ...”). Same root in *Phyzelaphryninae* Hedges & al., 2008.

piauiensis: P. Piauí, Brazilian state of. Also from T. *py-yáú-y*, small fish river + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Elachistocleis piauiensis* Caramaschi & Jim, 1983. (“... The species is named for the State of Piauí, Brasil, where the specimens were found ...”). Also *Engystoma piauiensis* — Dubois et al., 2021.

pickeli: Pickel + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Bento José Pickel (1906-1963), Benedictine priest, professor at the Superior School of Agriculture of Pernambuco, Brazil. *Hyla pickeli* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938. In the synonymy of *Scinax pachycrus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

picta, pictus: L. *picta*, *-us*, painted; colored; decorated. (1) *Hylaplesia picta* Tschudi, 1838. (?). Also *Dendrobates pictus* — Duméril & Bibron, 1841. *Dendrobates pictus pictus* — B. Lutz, 1952. *Phyllobates pictus* — Silverstone, 1975. *Epipedobates pictus* — Myers, 1987. Today *Ameerega picta* (Bibron in Tschudi, 1838). (2) *Pristimantis pictus* Oliveira et al., 2020. (“... refers to the yellow dots that are characteristic to individuals of this spe-

cies, facilitating its identification in relation to other *Pristimantis* species in its occurrence region ...”).

pictiventris: L. *pictus*, painted; colored; decorated + L. *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly. *Paratelmatobius pictiventris* A. Lutz in B. Lutz & Carvalho, 1958. (“... a côr de um róseo-vermelho tirando a côr de vinho é extensiva a todo o ventre, salvo uma beirada larga escura, na qual se aglomeram as manchinhas brancas ...”). In the synonymy of *Paratelmatobius gaigeae* (Cochran, 1938).

pinderi: Pinder + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hellmuth Pinder (1874-1918), German-Brazilian collector and taxidermist in Museu Paulista. *Iliodiscus pinderi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. Also *Grypiscus pinderi* — Barbour, 1925. *Cyclorhamphus pinderi* — A. Lutz, 1929. In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus brasiliensis* (Steindachner, 1864).

pinima, pinimus: T. *pinima*, -us, painted, spotted. *Hyla pinima* Bokermann & Sazima, 1973. (“... O nome pinima é de origem indígena e significa manchado, dado em alusão ao padrão de desenho do dorso ...”). Also *Scinax pinima* — Faivovich et al., 2005. *Julianus pinimus* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Scinax pinimus* (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973).

pinto: Pinto + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Olivério Mário de Oliveira de Pinto (1896-1981), Brazilian ornithologist. *Crossodactylodes pinto* Cochran, 1938.

pipa: A. *pipa*, name that the inhabitants of Suriname gave to the females of this genus. *Rana Pipa* Linnaeus, 1758. No clues in Laurenti, but about *Bufo s. Pipa Americana*, Seba (1734) notes “... *Surinamenses, aliorumque Americae locorum incolae foemellas horum animalium Pipa, mares vero Pipal appellant ...*”. Also *Buffo pipa* — Lacépède, 1788. *Bufo pipa* — Bonnaterre, 1789. *Bufo (Pipa) pipa* — Cuvier, 1829. *Asterodactylus pipa* — Wagler, 1830. Today *Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758). The same root in *Pipa* Laurenti, 1768 and *Pipidae* Gray, 1825.

Piparius: L. *Pipa*, genus of anurans due to Laurenti (1768) (see) + L. *-ius*, suffix commemorative/dedicative. *Piparius* Rafinesque, 1815. (“... 8. *Piparius* R. *Pipa* Dum ...”). In the synonymy of *Pipa* Laurenti, 1768.

piperata: L. *piperata*, peppered; peppery. *Lophyohyla piperata* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. (“... Coloração carne-amarellada finamente punctulada de chocolate ...”). Also *Lophiohyla piperata* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Amphodus piperatus* — Myers, 1946. In the synonymy of *Phyllodytes luteolus* Wied-Neuwied, 1820.

pipiens: L. *pipiare*, squeak, chirp of birds. *Rana pipiens* Daudin, 1802 “An. XI”. (?). In the synonymy of *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802).

pipilans: L. *pipilare*, twitter, chirp. *Hylodes pipilans* Canedo & Pombal, 2007. (“... The species name, *pipilans*, is a Latin word that means “who sings like a bird”, referring to the advertisement call of this species ...”).

pisanoi: Pisanó + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Juan Pisanó (?), Argentinian paleontologist. *Bufo pisanoi* Casamiquela, 1967. In the synonymy of *Rhinella diptycha* (Cope, 1862).

piscatrix: L. *piscatrix*, one who performs as fish. *Rana piscatrix* Fermin, 1765. (“... C’est effectivement une chose très-singulière, que de voir cette Métamorphose de poisson en Grenouille & de Grenouille en poisson ...”). In the synonymy of *Pseudis paradoxa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

piscis: L. *piscis*, fish. *Rana piscis* Linnaeus, 1766. (“... *Larva piscem referens magnitudine cum ipsa Ranae certat, unde Rana -- piscis perperam essicta a Meriana & Seba ...*”). [Not a substitute name for *Rana paradoxa*, as noted by Frost, 2021; just a comment (under *Rana paradoxa*) on the name used by Merian (1719) and Seba (1734)]. In the synonymy of *Pseudis paradoxa* (Linnaeus, 1758)].

pitanga: T. *pitanga*, reddish. *Brachycephalus pitanga* Alves et al., 2009. (“... It is used here in allusion to the reddish color of the dorsum of *B. pitanga* ...”).

pithecodactylus: G. *pithikos* (πίθηκος), ape + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Bufo pithecodactylus* Werner, 1899. (“... da die Endphalangen dunkelbraun und oben nagelartig durch eine Querfurche von der zweitletzten getrennt sind, was lebhaft den Eindruck von Affenfingern hervorruft ...”). *Bufo pythecodactylus* – Rivero, 1961 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Rhinella marina* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Pithecopis: G. *pithikos* (πίθηκος), ape + G. *-opsis* (-όψης), suffix denoting likeness. *Pithecopis* Günther, 1859 «1858». (?). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus* Tschudi, 1838.

Pithecopus: G. *pithikos* (πίθηκος), ape + G. *pous* (πούς), foot. *Pithecopus* Cope, 1866. (“... second toe shorter than inner ...”).

pixinguinha: P. Pixinguinha, artistic name of the Brazilian singer Alfredo da Rocha Vianna Filho (1897-1973). *Scinax pixinguinha* Lacerda et al., 2021. [“... Alfredo da Rocha Vianna Filho (1897-1973), popularly known as Pixinguinha, was a Brazilian musician and the most famous Choro player ...”].

pizarronis: Pizarro + L. *-nis*, pertaining to. Honouring João Joaquim Pizarro (1842-1906), Brazilian physician and zoologist. *Batrachichthys pizarronis* Garman, 1883 (*nomen nudum*). In the synonymy of *Pseudis fusca* Garman, 1883.

planiceps: L. *planus*, flat + L. *-ceps*, -headed. (“... Head broad and plane on the upper surface ...”). (1) *Hyla planiceps* – Boulenger, 1882. In the synonymy of *Osteocephalus taurinus* Steindachner, 1862. (2) *Osteocephalus planiceps* Cope, 1874. (“... Head broad and plane on the upper surface to the straight and rectangular *canthus rostralis* ...”). Also *Trachycephalus planiceps* – Knauer, 1878.

planicola: L. *planus*, plain, clear, smooth. *Hyla (Sphoerohyla) planicola* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938. (“... verde claro, sem nenhum desenho ...”). Also *Hyla aurantiaca planicola* – Cochran, 1955 “1954”. *Sphoerohyla planicola* – Goin, 1957. *Dryomelictes planicola* – Goin, 1961. *Hyla orophila planicola* – Rivero, 1961. Today *Sphaenorhynchus planicola* (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938).

platensis: [La] Plata [River basin] + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Bufo marinus* var. *platensis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. [“... Poseemos ejemplares procedentes del interior de la República Argentina ... y de Montevideo y de Rio-Grande-do-Sul (Brasil) ...”]. Also *Bufo arenarum platensis* — Gallardo, 1964. In the synonymy of *Rhinella arenarum* (Hensel, 1867). (2) *Pseudis paradoxus platensis* Gallardo, 1961. (“... This subspecies is found from the Upper Paraguay River to Rosario (Santa Fe) on the banks of the Parana ...”, in La Plata River basin). Today *Pseudis platensis* Gallardo, 1961.

platycephalus: G. *platys* (πλατύς), broad flat object or area + G. *kéfali* (κεφάλι), head. *Hylopsis platycephalus* Werner, 1894. (“... Kopf sehr flach, Schnauze vorspringend abgerundet, etwas länger als Augendurchmesser ...”). Today *Sphaenorhynchus platycephalus* (Werner, 1894).

plaumanni: Plaumann + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Fritz Plaumann (1902-1994), German-Brazilian entomologist. *Leptodactylus plaumanni* Ahl, 1936.

Plectromantis: G. *plektros* (πλήκτρον), spur + G. *mantis* (μαντις), tree-frog. *Plectromantis* Peters, 1862. (“... der Metacarpus des Daumens und des ersten Fingers mit je einem conischen, zugespitzten harten Dorn bewaffnet ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826.

Plethodontidae: L. *Plethodon*, genus of urodeles due to Tschudi (1838), in turn from G. *plithos* (πλήθος), great number, multitude + G. *dontis* (δόντια), teeth + L. *-idae*, suffix that indicates the category of family in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). Plethodontidae Gray, 1850.

Pleurodema: G. *pleura* (πλευρά), sides or side (of a person or animal) + G. *dema* (δεμα), bulge. *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838. (“... *In utroque abdominis latere magnam, oblongam glandulam* ...”).

pleuropterus: G. *pleura* (πλευρά), sides or side (of a person or animal) + G. *pteron* (πτερόν), wing. *Bufo pleuropterus* Schmidt, 1857. (“... *marginē supra-orbitali paullulum elata et supra paro tidem et scapulam quasi continuata in plicam cutaneam* ...”). Also *Otilophus ? pleuropterus* — Cope, 1862. In the synonymy of *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768).

plicifera, plicifer: L. *plico*, fold + L. *fera*, carry, bear. *Hylodes plicifera* Boulenger, 1888. (“... Head and back with several symmetrical linear folds, viz. a median straight one from between the nostrils to above the vent, and five undulous others on each side, beginning from the supraciliary edge and crossing obliquely the upper eyelid ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus plicifer* — Stejneger, 1904. Same root in *Eleutherodactylus pliciferus* — Gorham, 1966. Today *Haddadus plicifer* (Boulenger, 1888).

plicifrons: L. *plicis*, folded + L. *frons*, fore part of anything. *Bubonias plicifrons* Cope, 1874. (“... A strong elevated fold ...”). Also *Edalorhina plicifrons* — Boulenger, 1882. *Paludicola plicifrons* — Nieden, 1923. In the synonymy of *Edalorhina perezii* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

pluvian: L. *pluvia*, rain. *Pristimantis pluvian* Oliveira et al., 2020. (“... The frogs of this genus are known as Amazon Rain Frogs ...”).

poaju: T. *poã*, finger + T. *ju*, spine. *Hypsiboas poaju* Garcia et al., 2008. (“... in reference to the prepollex that ends in a curved spine ...”). Today *Boana poaju* (Garcia et al., 2008).

pocoto: P. *pocot’o*, onomatopoeia of a horse trotting. *Pseudopaludicola pocoto* Magalhães et al., 2014. (“... The specific epithet refers to the similarity of the advertisement call to the sound of a horse trotting, which in Portuguese is expressed by the onomatopoeia pocotó ...”).

podicipinus: L. *podicis*, buttocks; anus + L. *-inus*, suffix indicating possession, belonging to, pertaining to, having the nature of, made of, quality of, state or condition of. *Cystignathus podicipinus* Cope, 1862. (“... Skin smooth above, except a few minute warts on the coccygeal region. Lateral and post-anal region verrucose ...”). Also *Leptodactylus podicipinus podicipinus* — Gans, 1960. Today *Leptodactylus podicipinus* (Cope, 1862).

Podonectes: G. *podos* (ποδος), foot + G. *nektes* (νεκτες), swimmer. *Podonectes* Steindachner, 1864. (?). In the synonymy of *Pseudis* Wagler, 1830.

poecilogaster: G. *poikilos* (ποικίλος), having a natural intricacy (of colour, shade, texture); dappled, spotted, mottled + G. *gastir* (γαστήρ), abdomen. *Pa-*

ratelmatobius poecilogaster Giaretta & Castanho, 1990. (“... O epíteto específico tem origem no grego “*poikilos*” + “*gáster*” (= ventre variegado), em alusão à variedade de cores no ventre dos animais aqui descritos ...”).

poepigii: Poeppig + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Eduard Friedrich Poeppig (1798-1868), German naturalist. (1) *Bufo Poeppigii* Tschudi, 1845. Also *Bufo marinus poepigii* — Mertens, 1952. *Chaunus poepigii* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella poepigii* (Tschudi, 1845). (2) *Leptodactylus poepigii* Melin, 1941. In the synonymy of *Adenomera hylaedactyla* (Cope, 1868).

Pohlia: Pohl + L. *-ia*, dedicative suffix. Honouring Johann Emanuel Pohl (1782-1834), Austrian botanist. *Pohlia* Steindachner, 1867. In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

polytaenia: G. *polys* (πολύς), several + L. *taenia*, ribbon, tape, band. *Hyla polytaenia* Cope, 1870 “1869 “. (“... In the lined specimen there are additional lines on the lips, humerus and femur ...”). Also *Hyla polytaenia polytaenia* — B. Lutz, 1968. *Hypsiboas polytaenius* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana polytaenia* (Cope, 1870).

pomba: (?) P. Pomba, river in the states of Minas Gerais and Rio de Janeiro, Brazil; from P. *pomba*, dove. *Aparasphenodon pomba* Assis et al., 2013. (“... The specific name of the new species, a noun in apposition, refers to its discovery in an Atlantic Rain Forest fragment near the Pomba River, Cataguases, Minas Gerais ...”). Today *Nyctimantis pomba* (Assis et al., 2013).

pombali: Pombal + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Perez Pombal Jr., Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Brachycephalus pombali* Alves et al., 2006. (2) *Bufo pombali* Baldissera et al., 2004. Also *Chaunus pombali* — Frost et al., 2006. Noted to be a hybrid of *Rhinella ornata* x *Rhinella crucifer*. (3) *Hyla pombali* Caramaschi et al., 2004. Also *Hypsiboas pombali* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana pombali* (Caramaschi et al., 2004). (4) *Proceratophrys pombali* Mângia et al., 2014. (5) *Scinax pombali* Lourenço et al., 2013. Also *Ololygon pombali* — Duellman et al., 2016.

Potomotyphlus: *G. potamos* (ποταμος), river + *G. tyflos* (τυφλος), blind. *Potomotyphlus* Taylor, 1968. (?). The same root in *Potomotyphlus* Taylor, 1968 (incorrect subsequent spelling; correction in errata distributed with original publication by publisher).

praeceptor: *L. praeceptor*, teacher, instructor. *Phyllodytes praeceptor* Orrico et al., 2018. (“... The name is given as homage to Dr. Miguel Trefaut Rodrigues for his continuous formation of herpetologists ...”).

prasina, prasinus: *L. prasina*, -inus, leek-green. (1) *Hyla (Hyla) prasina* Burmeister, 1856. (“... Rückenseite hellgrün, glatt; Bauchseite weiss ...”). Also *Hyla pulchella prasina* — Barrio, 1965. *Hyla prasina* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Hypsiboas prasinus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana prasina* (Burmeister, 1856). (2) *Gastrotheca prasina* Teixeira, et al., 2012. (“... The specific epithet is a Latin word derived from *prasinus* (= green), which refers to the greenish general body color of this new species ...”). Also *Gastrotheca (Eo-theca) prasina* — Duellman, 2015. Today *Eo-theca prasina* (Teixeira et al., 2012). (3) *Sphaenorhynchus prasinus* Bokermann, 1973. (“... No exemplar vivo, o colorido é verde-claro-esbranquiçado ...”).

precrenulatus: *L. pre*, before, in front of + *L. crenulatus*, minutely crenate/notched. *Stombus precrenulatus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. (“... por terem uma serie de tuberculos na órta anterior da palpebra ...”). *Proceratophrys precrenulata* — Izecksohn & Peixoto, 1980. In the synonymy of *Proceratophrys schirchi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

pressula: *L. pressula*, rather compressed. *Caecilia pressula* Taylor, 1968. (“... A species somewhat resembling *Caecilia tentaculata*, but with the body strongly compressed for most of its length ...”). In the synonymy of *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758.

Pristimantis: *G. pristis* (πριστις), saw + *G. mantis* (μαντης) tree frog. *Pristimantis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. (“... *cantho rostrali acuto, vertice plano ad latera cristis binis osseis compressis, acie serrato, supra nucham elatioribus, armato & crista alia robusta scabrosa super tympanum projecta ...*”). The same root in *Pristimantinae* Pyron & Wiens, 2011.

proboscidea, proboscideus: L. *proboscis*, trunk, proboscis, snout + L. *-idea*, *-ideus*, suffix indicating that are or have the form of. (1) *Phryniscus proboscideus* Boulenger, 1882. (“... snout much produced beyond the lip, truncate ...”). Also *Atelopus proboscideus* — Boulenger, 1894. *Dendrophryniscus proboscideus* — McDiarmid, 1971. *Rhamphophryne proboscidea* — Izecksohn, 1976. *Rhinella proboscidea* — Chaparro et al., 2007. Today *Dendrophryniscus proboscideus* (Boulenger, 1882). (2) *Bufo (Oxyrhynchus) proboscideus* Spix, 1824. (“... rostro proboscideo, longe prominente ...”). Also *Oxyrhynchus proboscideus* — Fitzinger, 1826. *Rhinella proboscidea* — Fitzinger, 1826. *Bufo (Rhinella) proboscideus* — Cuvier, 1829. *Eurhina proboscideus* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Oxyrhynchus proboscideus* — Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. *Bufo proboscideus* — Hoogmoed, 1986. Today *Rhinella proboscidea* (Spix, 1824). (3) *Hyla proboscidea* Brongersma, 1933. (“... In der herpetologischen Sammlung des Zoologischen Museums in Amsterdam fand ich eine Laubfroschart der Gattung *Hyla*, welche sich als neu erwies. Von allen mir aus der Literatur bekannt gewordenen neotropischen *Hyla*-Arten unterscheidet sie sich durch die rüsselartige Verlängerung des Vorderkopfes ... Wegen dieses merkwürdigen Merkmals nenne ich die neue Art: *Hyla proboscidea* nov. spec. ...”). Also *Oloolygon proboscidea* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax proboscidea* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax proboscideus* (Brongersma, 1933).

Proceratophrys: L. *pro-*, like + L. *Ceratophrys*, genus of anurans due to Wied-Neuwied (1824) (see). *Proceratophrys* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... caracterizada pela dilatação ossea post-tympanica e pela palpebra espiculada, sem apêndice ceratoide unico ...”).

prognathus: G. *pro-* (προ-), in front of, ahead of + G. *gnathos* (γνάθος), jaw. *Leptodactylus prognathus* Boulenger, 1888. (“... Snout depressed, acuminate, very prominent ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latinasus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875.

Prostherapis: G. *próthesi* (πρόσθεση), addition; an artificial replacement for a body part, either internal or external + G. *rapis* (ῥαπίς, spelling variation for κρηπίς), a kind of shoe; man's high boot. *Prostherapis* Cope, 1868. (“... dilatations strong, each with two dermal scales on the upper side, separat-

ed by a fissure ... The two leathery scales of the pallettes are peculiar, and resemble those of the under side in *Phyllodactylus* ...”).

Protopipa: G. *protos* (πρώτος), foremost (in position); first + L. *Pipa*, genus of anurans due to Laurenti (1768) (see). *Protopipa* Noble, 1925. (“... *Protopipa* is immediately ancestral to *Pipa* ...”). In the synonymy of *Pipa* Laurenti, 1768.

Pseudendrobates: G. *pseudo* (ψευδο), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Dendrobates*, genus of anurans due to Wagler (1830) (see). *Pseudendrobates* Bauer, 1988. (“... Novum subgenus: *Pseudendrobates* ... Opgesteld voor typesoort *Dendrobates silverstonei* ... In alle opzichten gelijk aan het hoofdgeslacht *Phylllobates*. Verschilt uitsluitend in het geproduceerde huidgif en in de streeptekening, nl. dorsolateraal: zijlijnen doorlopend in de liezen ...”). In the synonymy of *Ameerega* Bauer, 1986.

Pseudis: G. *pseudis* (ψευδής) (referring to persons or living beings) lying, false, deceptive. *Pseudis* Wagler, 1830. (?). Although it was not made explicit in the description, the name refers to the theory that these frogs metamorphosed into fish, as narrated by Merian and Seba. The same root in *Pseudinae* Fitzinger, 1843.

Pseudohyla: G. *pseudo* (ψευδο), false, untrue, mistaken + *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Pseudohyla* Andersson, 1945. (“... The type-specimen of this new genus ... seems to be nearly allied to the genus *Hyla*, but its total want of web both on fingers and toes, is not agreeable to this genus ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

pseudomeridiana, pseudomeridianus: G. *pseudo* (ψευδο), false, untrue, mistaken + L. [*Dendropsophus*] *meridianus*, frog species due to B. Lutz (1954) (see). *Hyla pseudomeridiana* Cruz et al., 2000. (“... O epíteto específico, que significa “falsa *meridiana*”, se refere à semelhança da nova espécie com *Hyla meridiana*, com a qual foi freqüentemente confundida ...”). Today *Dendropsophus pseudomeridianus* (Cruz et al., 2000).

Pseudopaludicola: G. *pseudo* (ψευδο), false, untrue, mistaken + *Paludicola*, genus of anurans due to Wagler (1839) (in turn, from L. *paludis*, swamp, marsh +

L. *-cola*, suffix that indicates that it is an inhabitant of). *Pseudopaludicola* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... A pelle da região sacral às vezes oferece espessamento e pygmentação desenhando as glandulas das Paludicolas ...”).

pseudopseudis: G. *pseudo* (ψευδο), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Pseudis*, frog genus due to Wagler, 1830 (see). *Hyla pseudopseudis* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. (“... Côr da face superior olivacea maculada de denegrado como em *Pseudis mantidactyla* ... O aspecto exterior deste animal lembrou-me o nome sob o qual fiz esta descrição ...”). Also *Hyla pseudopseudis pseudopseudis* — B. Lutz, 1973. Today *Bokermannohyla pseudopseudis* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

Pseudosiphonops: G. *pseudo* (ψευδο), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Siphonops*, genus of gymnophiones due to Wagler, 1828 (see). *Pseudosiphonops* Taylor, 1968. (“... The type of the genus bears a superficial resemblance to *Siphonops annulatus* and *S. paulensis* and to certain forms of African *Geotrypetes* ...”). In the synonymy of *Mimosiphonops* Taylor, 1968.

Pseudotyphlonectes: G. *pseudo* (ψευδο), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Typhlonectes*, genus of gymnophiona due to Peters (1880) (see). *Pseudotyphlonectes* Lescure et al., 1986. (?). In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes* Peters, 1880.

Psyllophryne: G. *psylla* (ψόλλα), flea + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Psyllophryne* Izecksohn, 1971. (“... O nome genérico, que significa “sapo pulga”, faz referência ao diminuto tamanho da especie típica ...”). In the synonymy of *Brachycephalus* Fitzinger, 1826.

ptychodermis: G. *ptychos* (πτύχως), fold + G. *dermos* (δερμος), skin. *Pseudosiphonops ptychodermis* Taylor, 1968. (“... The two nuchal collars are distinct ...”). In the synonymy of *Mimosiphonops vermiculatus* Taylor, 1968.

pulchella: L. *pulchella*, pretty. *Hyla pulchella* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... La rainette gentille ...”). Also *Hyla pulchella pulchella* — Barrio, 1965. *Hypsiboas pulchellus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana pulchella* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

pulchra: L. *pulchra*, pretty; beautiful; handsome. (1) *Elosia pulchra* B. Lutz, 1951. (“... Diverge das outras pelo seu colorido muito belo ...”). Also *Hylodes pulcher* — Myers, 1962. In the synonymy of *Hylodes glaber* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926). (2) *Gastrotheca pulchra* Caramaschi & Rodrigues, 2007. (“... The specific epithet, “*pulchra*”, is a Latin adjective meaning beautiful, referring to the pretty, tiny, and elegant appearance of the species ...”). Also *Gastrotheca (Eothea) pulchra* — Duellman, 2015. Today *Eothea pulchra* (Caramaschi & Rodrigues, 2007).

pulchripecta: L. *pulcher*, pretty; beautiful; handsome + L. *pectum*, breast, chest. *Phyllobates pulchripectus* Silverstone, 1976. (“... dorsum black; complete yellow lateral stripe; light proximo-ventral calf-spot absent; venter blue with black marbling ...”). Also *Dendrobates pulchripectus* — Myers et al., 1978. *Epipedobates pulchripectus* — Myers, 1987. Today *Ameerega pulchripecta* (Silverstone, 1976).

pulex: L. *pulex*, flea. *Brachycephalus pulex* Napoli et al., 2011. (“... refers to the flea, *Pulex irritans*, and is allusive to the small size and to the striking capacity for large leaps presented by the new species ...”).

pulidoi: Pulido + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Juan R. Pulido (1926-?), Venezuelan entomologist. *Centrolenella pulidoi* Rivero, 1968. Also *Hypsiboas pulidoi* — Faivovich et al., 2005. *Boana pulidoi* — Dubois, 2017. In the synonymy of *Boana benitezi* (Rivero, 1961).

pumila, pumilio: L. *pumilus, pumilio*, dwarf, pygmy. (1) *Hyla pumila* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... La rainette naine ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus bipunctatus* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Leptodactylus pumilio* Boulenger, 1920. (“... from snout to vent 20 mm ...”). In the synonymy of *Ischnocnema parva* (Girard, 1853).

punctata, punctatus: L. *punctata, -us*, punctuated; pointed. (1) *Calamita punctatus* Schneider, 1799. (“... Caput & dorsum punctis niveis notatum ...”). Also *Hyla punctata* — Daudin, 1802 “An. XI”. *Hysaplesia punctata* — Boie in Schlegel, 1826. *Hypsiboas (Scinax) punctata* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Hyla (Hyla) punctata* — Burmeister, 1856. *Hypsiboas punctatus* — Cope, 1867.

Hypsiboas punctatus punctatus — Brusquetti & Lavilla, 2006. Today *Boana punctata* (Schneider, 1799). (2) *Hyla punctata* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. (?). In the synonymy of *Boana albomarginata* (Spix, 1824). (3) *Phyllodytes punctatus* Caramaschi & Peixoto, 2004. (“... dorsum of body pale brown with distinctive brown dots and smaller brown dots on dorsal surfaces of hindlimbs, dorsal surfaces of body ...”).

punctatissima: L. *punctatissima*, greatly punctuated. (1) *Hyla geographica punctatissima* — Parker, 1935. (?). In the synonymy of *Boana geographica* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Hyla punctatissima appendiculata* — Parker, 1933. In the synonymy of *Boana appendiculata* (Boulenger, 1882). (3) *Hylella punctatissima* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... Paa Hyggen af Kroppen og Lemmerne er den graa Grundfarve meget tæt besaaet med sorte Punkter, hvorved disse Partier faae et mørkere Anstrøg; paa Lemmerne er der svage Spor til lignende Punkter ...”). Also *Hyla punctatissima* — Peters, 1872. In the synonymy of *Boana lundii* (Burmeister, 1856).

punctillata: L. *punctillata*, having points; dots/spots. *Cophomantis punctillata* Peters, 1870. (“... Blaugrau mit dichtstehenden dunkeln Pünktchen, welche weitläufiger stehen auf einem schmalen Streifen der Oberschenkel, auf der Außenseite des Vorderarms, des Unterschenkels und Fußes ...”). Also *Hyla (Hylella) punctillata* — Peters, 1873 “1872”. *Hyla punctillata* — Boulenger, 1882. In the synonymy of *Boana semilineata* (Spix, 1824).

puri: Pu. *puri*, daring, audacious. *Brachycephalus puri* Almeida-Silva et al., 2021. (“... The specific name honors the indigenous people from the Puri tribe, who lived from the 16th to 19th centuries in the territory encompassing the river basin of Paraíba do Sul and the boundaries between the Rio Grande and Rio Doce river basins ...”).

pusilla, pusillus: L. *pusilla*, -us, tiny, very small. (1) *Eleutherodactylus pusillus* Bokermann, 1967. [“...Una especie de *Eleutherodactylus* de tamaño pequeño (16 mm), presentando cierta semejanza con parvus...”]. Today *Ischnocnema pusilla* (Bokermann, 1967). (2) *Scinax pusillus* Pombal et al., 2011. (“... refers to the small body sizes of frogs in the new species ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax fuscomarginatus* (A. Lutz, 1925).

pustulatus: L. *pustula*, inflamed sore/blister/pustule + L. *-atus*, suffix indicating possession. *Entomoglossus pustulatus* Peters, 1870. (“... Braun, undeutlich längsgestreift, unten mit zahlreichen kleinen runden gelblichweissen Flecken ...”). Today *Leptodactylus pustulatus* (Peters, 1870).

pustulosa: L. *pustulosa*, with pustules, inflamed sores/blisters. *Hyla pustulosa* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... Huden har hist og her en større Vorte, saavel paa Kroppen gom paa Hovedet og Lemmerne; forresten er den fiint rynket, men ikke egentlig kornet, dog er Halsen (Hovedets Underside) svagt granuleret ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana lundii* (Burmeister, 1856).

pyburni: Pyburn + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring William (“Billy”) Frank Pyburn (1927-2007), US American herpetologist. *Otophryne pyburni* Campbell & Clarke, 1998.

pygmaea, pygmaeus: G. *pygmaios* (πυγμαίος), pygmy, dwarf. (1) *Bufo pygmaeus* Myers & Carvalho, 1952. (“... These represent a form close to typical *B. granulatus* but sharply distinct in its minute size, striking coloration and different cranial morphology ...”). Also *Bufo pygmaeus* — Cei & Roig, 1964. *Bufo granulatus pygmaeus* — Gallardo, 1965. *Chaunus pygmaeus* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella pygmaea* (Myers & Carvalho, 1952). (2) *Hyla pygmaea* Werner, 1894 (junior secondary homonym of *Hyperolius pygmaea* Meyer, 1875). Also *Hyla pygmaea* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus weneri* (Cochran, 1952).

quadrilineata: L. *quadri*, square + L. *lineata*, lined. *Hyla quadrilineata* Steindachner, 1864 (*nomen nudum*). (?). In the synonymy of *Lysapsus limellum* Cope, 1862.

queimadensis: [Ilha] Queimada [Grande], state of São Paulo, Brazil + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Hyla perpusilla queimadensis* B. Lutz, 1973. (“... A little tree-frog of this species was collected on the island of Queimada Grande on the coast of the state of São Paulo ...”). (*Nomen nudum*). In the synonymy of *Scinax peixotoi* Brasileiro et al., 2007.

quelchii: Quelch + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring John Joseph Quelch (1854-?), British zoologist. *Oreophryne Quelchii* Boulenger, 1895. Today *Oreophrynella quelchii* (Boulenger, 1895).

quilombola: *P. quilombola*, from *P. quilombo*, secret place where escaped slaves stayed or went, usually hidden in the woods; from Ki. *kilombo*, war camp. *Chiasmocleis quilombola* Tonini et al., 2014 (“... The specific epithet *quilombola* refers to people who inhabit quilombo communities. Historically, quilombos were communities constituted by and used as refuges for escaped slaves between 1530 and 1815 during colonial Portuguese rule in Brazil. Nowadays in the north of Espírito Santo State quilombola communities still remain and maintain alive their traditions, such as quilombola food and craftwork ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) quilombola* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

quinquevittatus: L. *quinque*, five + L. *vittata*, wearing or carrying a ritual vitta. *Dendrobates tinctorius* var. *quinquevittatus* Steindachner, 1864. (“... Der Oberleib ist schwarz und mit fünf schmalen gelblichweissen Längsstreifen, die in gleicher Entfernung von einander stehen, geziert ...”). Also *Dendrobates quinquevittatus* Jan, 1857 (*nomen nudum*). *Ranitomeya quinquevittata* — [Bauer, 1985]. Today *Adelphobates quinquevittatus* (Steindachner, 1864).

Quinzhyla: F. *quinze*, fifteen + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Quinzhyla* Bauer, 2005 [replacement name for *Lophopus* Tschudi, 1838, preoccupied by *Lophopus* Dumortier, 1835 (Polyzoa)]. [“... The name is referring to the haploid chromosome number in latin languages (*quinze*, *quince*, *quindecem*) contaminated with *Hyla* ...”]. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus* Fitzinger, 1843.

quiririensis: *P.* [Serra do] Quiriri [(26°01'17"S, 48°59'47"W, at 1,263 m a. s. l.), municipality of Campo Alegre, state of Santa Catarina, southern Brazil]; in turn, from T. *quiriri*, silence, peace + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Brachycephalus quiririensis* Pie & Ribeiro, 2015. [“... The epithet “*quiririensis*” is derived from the Tupi-Guarani language word “*quiriri*” (= silence, peace) and refers to type locality ...”].

quixensis: (?) Quijos [Quixos], locality in Napo Province, Ecuador + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Oreobates quixensis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872. ["... H(abita) la provincia de Quijos en el Ecuador ..."]. Also *Borborocotes quixensis* — Boulenger, 1882. *Eupsophus quixensis* — Peters, 1955. *Ischnocnema quixensis* — Lynch & Schwartz, 1971.

quoyi: Quoy + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jean René Constant Quoy (1790-1869), French zoologist. *Hyla quoyi* Bory de Saint-Vincent, 1828 (*nomen oblitum* – see Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2010). In the synonymy of *Boana prasina* (Burmeister, 1856).

raddiana: Raddi + L. *-ana*, of or pertaining to. Honouring Giuseppe Raddi (1770-1829), Italian naturalist. *Hyla raddiana* Fitzinger, 1826 (replacement name for *Hyla lateralis* Raddi, 1823). In the synonymy of *Boana albomarginata* (Spix, 1824).

ramagii: Ramage + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring George Albert Ramage (1858-1937), British zoologist. *Hylodes ramagii* Boulenger, 1888. Also *Eleutherodactylus ramagii* — Stejneger, 1904. *Ischnocnema ramagii* — Heinicke et al., 2007. Today *Pristimantis ramagii* (Boulenger, 1888).

randorum: Rand + L. *-orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. Honouring Patricia (?) and Austin Stanley Rand (1932-2005), US American herpetologists. *Eleutherodactylus randorum* Heyer, 1985. Today *Ischnocnema randorum* (Heyer, 1985).

raniceps: L. *rana*, frog + L. *-iceps*, headed. *Hypsiboas raniceps* Cope, 1862. (?). Today *Boana raniceps* (Cope, 1862).

Ranidae: L. *Rana*, genus of anurans due to Linnaeus (1758), in turn, from L. *rana*, frog + L. *-idae*, suffix that indicates the category of family in the zoological classification (Art. 29, ICZN). Ranidae Batsch, 1796.

raniformis: L. *raniformis*, frog-shaped. *Leptodactylus raniformis* Werner, 1899. ("... Aehnlich der gewöhnlichen *Rana virescens* Kalm ..."). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Schneider, 1799).

ranina, raninus: L. *ranina*, -us, frog-like. (1) *Paludicola ranina* Cope, 1885 “1884”. (?). In the synonymy of *Physalaemus gracilis* (Boulenger, 1883). (2) *Proteus raninus* Laurenti, 1768. (?). In the synonymy of *Pseudis paradoxa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Ranitomeya: S. *ranita*, small frog (divided in *ranit-* as a prefix and *-a*, as suffix) + Tomey; honouring Wil Tomey, Dutch hobbyist. (“... His uncertainty whether to say *ranitas rojos*, *ranitos rojos*, *ranitos rojas* induced me a fine name for this new genus to be described. The Spanish word *ranita* combined with his name makes Rani-Tomey-a: *Ranitomeya* ...”). *Ranitomeya* Bauer, 1985.

ranki: Rank + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Abilio Rank (?), Brazilian naturalist. *Hyla ranki* Andrade & Cardoso, 1987. Also *Ololygon ranki* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Scinax ranki* (Andrade & Cardoso, 1987).

ranoides: L. *rana*, frog + L. *-oides*, like, resembling, having the form of. *Hyla ranoides* Spix, 1824. (“... *digitis ranaeformibus, elongatis, non palmatis* ...”). *Hylodes ranoides* — Fitzinger, 1826. *Enydrobius ranoides* — Wagler, 1830. *Hylodes ranoides* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. In the synonymy of *Hylodes nasus* (Lichtenstein, 1823).

Ranula: L. *rana*, frog + L. *-ula*, suffix diminutive. *Ranula* Peters, 1859. (“... In Gestalt, Bau der Gliedmaßen, der Schwimmhäute, des Ohrs, der Zunge, des Brustbeins und der Sacralwirbel ganz mit *Rana* übereinstimmend, aber verschieden durch den Zahnbau ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

ravida: L. *rauidus*, grey, yellowish grey. *Hyla ravida* Caramaschi et al., 2001. (“... O nome da espécie, um adjetivo, deriva do Latim “*rauidus*” (acinzentado, escurecido) e faz alusão à coloração dorsal acinzentada do animal em vida ...”). Also *Boana ravida* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla ravida* (Caramaschi et al., 2001).

recava: L. *re-*, back- + L. *cavus*, concave. *Gastrotheca recava* Teixeira et al., 2012. [“... The specific epithet is derived from the Latin word *recavus* (= arched

inward, concave) in reference to the posterior edge of skull bones, which are arched inward ...”]. Also *Gastrotheca (Eothecca) recava* — Duellman, 2015. Today *Eothecca recava* (Teixeira et al., 2012).

redacta: L. *redactus*, drive back; reduce; render. *Proceratophrys redacta* Teixeira et al., 2012. (“... The name of the new species is derived from the Latin adjective *redactus* that means reduced, in allusion to the small size of the new species ...”).

regius: L. *regius*, royal, of a king, regal. *Hylodes regius* Gouvêa, 1979. (“... Forma de tamanho médio, ... apresentando no dorso linha lateral e pontos amarelo-ouro, e com o dorso dos tarsos e a face ventral das pernas de cor vermelho-púrpura ...”).

reichlei: Reichle + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Steffen Reichle, German herpetologist active in Bolivia. *Pristimantis reichlei* Padial & de La Riva, 2009.

reigi: Reig + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Osvaldo Alfredo Reig (1929-1992), Argentinian biologist. *Odontophrynus reigi* Rosset et al., 2021.

reinhardti: Reinhardt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Johann Theodor Reinhardt (1816-1882), Danish zoologist. *Mimosiphonops reinhardti* Wilkinson & Nussbaum, 1992.

relicta: L. *relicta*, forsaken, abandoned, derelict; left untouched. *Allophryne relicta* Caramaschi et al., 2013. [“... The specific epithet, a Latin adjective. (“*relicta*”), meaning abandoned, forsaken, is an allusion to the occurrence of the new species associated to the “Hileia Bahiana,” a portion of the Atlantic Rain Forest that holds many biological components similar to, or directly related to, ones found in the Amazon; a relic of a past connection between these two biomes ...”].

Relictivomer: L. *relictus*, forsaken, abandoned, derelict; left untouched + L. *vomer*, a palatal bone. *Relictivomer* Carvalho, 1954. [“... *Relictivomet* is Latin (left behind and vomer), describing the condition of the posterior part of the prevomer ...”]. In the synonymy of *Elachistocleis* Parker, 1927.

Relictocleis: L. *relictus*, forsaken, abandoned, derelict; left untouched + L. ending of *Chiasmocleis* Méhely, 1904. *Relictocleis* Dubois et al., 2021. (Etymology by the authors). Either a valid genus (Segalla et al., 2021), or in the synonymy of *Chiasmocleis* Méhely, 1904 (Frost, 2021).

Relictus L. *relictus*, forsaken, abandoned, derelict; left untouched. *Relictus* de Sá et al. 2018 “2019” [preoccupied by *Relictus* (a freshwater fish)]. (“... name derived from the Latin “*relictus*”, meaning “left behind”, acknowledges the long separate history of this lineage from the other two clades of *Chiasmocleis* ...”). In the synonymy of *Chiasmocleis* Méhely, 1904.

remotus: L. *remotus*, remote; distant, far off. *Oreobates remotus* Teixeira et al., 2012. (“... in reference to the geographical gap of more than 1. 000 km between the area of occurrence of the new species and that of all other *Oreobates* ...”).

renalis: L. *renalis*, pertaining to kidneys. *Ceratophrys renalis* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... Não deixa de ser curiosa a forma mimética apresentada por essa intanha que em repouso e com os membros encolhidos, parece reproduzir uma pequena rã encolhida, cujos olhos seriam representados pelos callos renais, sendo assim a cabeça representada pela parte posterior do seu corpo ...”). Also *Stombus renalis* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. Today *Proceratophrys renalis* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

resinifictrix: L. *resina*, a product secreted by various trees, resin (whether in its liquid or solid form) + L. *fictrix*, that which moulds or fashions. *Hyla resinifictrix* Goeldi, 1907. (“... Inhabiting the virgin forest, it chooses certain tall trees for its dwelling, where it takes possession of a hollow branch ... and constructs there as a nursery a good-sized basin of resinous substances, with a central depression ...”). Also *Phrynohyas resinifictrix* — B. Lutz, 1973. Today *Trachycephalus resinifictrix* (Goeldi, 1907).

resplendens: L. *resplendens*, radiate light; shine brightly. (1) *Allophryne resplendens* Castroviejo-Fisher et al., 2012. [“... The specific name *resplendens* is derived from the Latin verb *resplendo* meaning “to glitter,” which we used in allusion to the bright and ornate coloration of the frog ...”]. (2) *Centrolenella resplendens* Lynch & Duellman, 1973. (“... used in allusion to the jewel-like appearance of the living frog ...”). Today *Cochranella resplendens* (Lynch & Duellman, 1973).

restinga: *P. restinga*, lowland on the sea coasts and entering the sea; in Brazil, strip of forest on the bank of a river or stream; in turn, from the Dutch *rotssteen*, crag, boulder. *Pseudopaludicola restinga* Cardozo et al., 2018. (“... The word “restinga” has an unclear origin in Brazilian Portuguese, but it is the proper name of the vegetation near the sea where the new species occurs: the restingas ...”).

reticularis: *L. reticularis*, provided with a net, mesh. *Rana reticularis* Lacépède, 1788. (“... le caractère distinctif est d’avoir le dessus du corps veiné & tacheté de manière à présenter l’apparence d’un réseau ...”). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).

reticulata, reticulatus: *L. reticulata*, -us, net-like. (1) *Hyla reticulata* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870. (“... *ad rostrum, genas, latera & artus pulcherrime reticulata* ...”). Today *Dendropsophus reticulatus* (Jiménez de la Espada, 1870). (2) *Leptodactylus ocellatus* var. *reticulata* Cei, 1948. (? “... De estas dos formas, la que provisoriamente hemos indicado, por su pigmentación ventral, como *reticulata* ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus luctator* (Hudson, 1892).

Rhaebo: *G. rhaebo* (ραιβο), bowlegged, crooked. Without justification in the original proposal of the name, although it clearly refers to the appearance of the forelimbs of the toads in general. *Rhaebo* Cope, 1862.

Rhamphophryne: *G. ramphos* (ράμφος), beak + *G. phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Rhamphophryne* Trueb, 1971. [“... The generic name is derived from the Greek words *rhampho*, meaning beak, and *phryne*, meaning toad, with reference to the protuberant snout characterizing this group of bufonids ...”]. In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

rhea: *L. Rhea*, avian genus due to Brisson (1760), in turn from the Titaness Rhea, daughter of Uranus (Heaven) and Gaia (Earth). *Hyla rhea* Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999. [“... The specific name, a noun in apposition, refers to the type locality, Cachoeira de Emas. “Ema” is the Brazilian vernacular name for *Rhea americana* (greater rheas) ...]. Today *Dendropsophus rhea* (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999).

Rhinatrema: G. *rhin* (ῥίς), nostrils or nose + -a-, particule privative + G. *trima* (τρήμα), that which is created by drilling or piercing, aperture, hole. *Rhinatrema* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... De ριν, nasus, nez; a privatif, & de τρήμα, foramen, trou, narines sans trous, ou nez non percé ...”). The same root in *Rhinatrematidae* Nussbaum, 1977.

Rhinella: G. *rhinos* (ῥινός), nose, snout. + L. -ella, suffix diminutive. *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826. The name contradicts the brief characterization given by Fitzinger, who indicates that members of this genus have long snouts, unlike members of the genus *Bufo* who have short snouts.

rhodomystax: G. *rhodo* (ρόδο), rose, red + G. *mystax* (μύσταξ), moustache. *Leptodactylus rhodomystax* Boulenger, 1884. (“... a band round the upper lip pinkish white ...”).

rhodonotus: G. *rhodo* (ρόδο), rose, red + G. *notos* (νοτός), back, dorsum. *Cystignathus rhodonotus* Günther, 1869 «1868». (“... Brown; a broad rose-coloured band occupies the whole back from the nostril to the sacrum ...”). Today *Leptodactylus rhodonotus* (Günther, 1869).

rhodopepla, rhodopeplus: G. *rhodo* (ρόδο), rose, red + G. *peplos* (πέπλος), woven cloth, cloth, sheet. *Hyla rhodopepla* Günther, 1858. (“... Rücken und die obere Seite des Unterschenkels rosenroth, der erstere mit einigen violetten Fleckchen ...”). Today *Dendropsophus rhodopeplus* (Günther, 1858).

rhodoporus: G. *rhodo* (ρόδο), rose, red + G. *poros* (πόρος), pore; crossing-place. *Hyla rhodoporus* Günther, 1869 «1868». (“... Skin smooth, with numerous minute pores on the upper parts. Light olive-coloured, each pore with a minute rose-coloured dot ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana punctata* (Schneider, 1799).

rhyakonastes: G. *ρύαξ άκος* (ρύαξ άκος), watercourse + G. *nastes* (νάστης), inhabitant. *Cycloramphus rhyakonastes* Heyer, 1983. (“... From the Greek *rhyakos*, rushing stream and *nastes*, inhabitant ...”).

- Ribeirina:** Ribeiro + L. *-ina*, having the nature or condition of. Honouring Alípio de Miranda-Ribeiro (1874-1939), Brazilian herpetologist. *Ribeirina* Parker, 1934. In the synonymy of *Stereocyclops* Cope, 1870.
- rickettsii:** Ricketts + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Harry Falkland Ricketts (1870-1929), collector of the type. *Phyllomedusa Rickettsii* Günther, 1897. Also *Phyllomedusa sauvagii rickettsii* — Cei, 1956. In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa sauvagii* Boulenger, 1882.
- riograndensis:** Rio Grande [do Sul], a Brazilian state + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place *Physalaemus riograndensis* Milstead, 1960. ["... *Type locality*. - 4 kilometers southeast of Osorio, Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil ..."].
- rionapensis:** S. Río Napo, river and province in central Ecuador + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Rana palmipes* forma *rionapensis* Andersson, 1945 ("... Rio Napo, 400 m ..."). In the synonymy of *Lithobates palmipes* (Spix, 1824).
- riopiedadensis:** P. Rio Piedade + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Pseudopaludicola riopiedadensis* Mercadal de Barrio & Barrio, 1994. ("... Nombre derivado de la localidad tipo ..."). In turn, "Rio Piedade, São Preto (*sic*), São Paulo, Brasil"; actually, Piedade, São José do Rio Preto, São Paulo, Brazil. In the synonymy of *Pseudopaludicola ternetzi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937.
- ritae:** Rita + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Gertrud Rita Kloss (1929-?), Brazilian parasitologist. *Centrolene ritae* B. Lutz in B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952. Also *Centrolenella ritae* — Duellman, 1977. *Cochranella ritae* — Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. "*Cochranella*" *ritae* — Guayasamin et al., 2009. Today *Vitreorana ritae* (B. Lutz in B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952).
- riveroi:** Rivero + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Juan Arturo Rivero-Quintero (1923-2014), Puerto Rican herpetologist. (1) *Hyla riveroi* Cochran & Goin, 1970. Today *Dendropsophus riveroi* (Cochran & Goin, 1970). (2) *Leptodactylus riveroi* Heyer & Pyburn, 1983.

rizibilis: L. *risibilis*, capable of laughing, causing laughter. *Hyla rizibilis* Bokermann, 1964. (“... Em outubro de 1963 tivemos a oportunidade de colecionar ... uma interessante espécie de *Hyla* que nos chamou a atenção pelo seu singular canto, semelhante a uma gargalhada ...”). Also *Ololygon rizibilis* – Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax rizibilis* (Bokermann, 1964).

robersimoni: *Hyla robersimoni* Donoso-Barros, 1965. Etymology not elucidated. In the synonymy of *Scinax ruber* (Laurenti, 1768).

robusta: L. *robusta*, strong, robust. *Euparkerella robusta* Izecksohn, 1988. (“... O nome específico assinala o aspecto mais volumoso da espécie ...”).

rochai: Rocha + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Reginaldo Augusto Trindade Rocha, a technician in the herpetological laboratory of the Museu Paraense Emílio Goeldi. *Microcaecilia rochai* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2011.

roeschmanni: Röschmann + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hermann Röschmann (?), German physicist active in Bolivia. *Hyla roeschmanni* De Grys, 1938. In the synonymy of *Boana raniceps* (Cope, 1862).

rogerioi: Rogério + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Rogério Pereira Bastos, Brazilian herpetologist. *Scinax rogerioi* Pugliese et al., 2009.

rohdei: Rohde + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring H. Rohde (?), a ship’s physician. *Phyllomedusa rohdei* Mertens, 1926. Today *Pithecopus rohdei* (Mertens, 1926).

romani: Roman + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Per Abraham Roman (1872-1943), Swedish entomologist. *Leptodactylus romani* Melin, 1941. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus bolivianus* Boulenger, 1898.

ron: E. Ron, nickname of Ronald. Honouring Ronald Archie Nussbaum, US American herpetologist. *Rhinatrema ron* Wilkinson & Gower, 2010.

rondonae, rondoniae: Rondônia, a Brazilian state, in turn, honouring Marshal Cândido Mariano da Silva Rondon (1865-1958), Brazilian militar and explorer + L. -ae, suffix indicating belonging. (1) *Hyla rondoniae* Bokermann, 1963. (“... fazem parte de um lote de anfíbios colecionados nas proximidades da localidade de Rondônia, no território Federal de Rondônia ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus bokermanni* (Goin, 1960). (2) *Proceratophrys rondonae* Prado & Pombal, 2008. (“... O epíteto específico se refere ao estado de Rondônia, cujo nome é uma homenagem ao Marechal Cândido [Mariano da Silva] Rondon ...”).

roseanus: L. *roseanus*, rose-colored, red. *Bufo crucifer* var. *roseanus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. [“... e por fim outro cuja tarja dorsal muito se amplia e deixa os desenhos do dorso rubescentes (var. *roseana*) ...”]. In the synonymy of *Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824).

roseus: L. *roseus*, rose-colored, red. *Hylodes roseus* Melin, 1941. (“... In alcohol, upper surface greyish white with a pink tint and brownish designs ...”). (Preoccupied by *Hylodes roseus* Boulenger, 1918). Also *Eleutherodactylus roseus* — B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952. In the synonymy of *Pristimantis vilarsi* (Melin, 1941).

rosmelinus: ? *rosmelinus*, apocope from *roseus* and Melin + L. -us, pertaining to. *Eleutherodactylus rosmelinus* Gorham, 1966 (replacement name for *Hylodes roseus* Melin, 1944). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis vilarsi* (Melin, 1941).

rossaferesae: Rossa-Feres + L. -ae, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Denise de Cerqueira Rossa-Feres, Brazilian herpetologist. *Scinax rossaferesae* Conte et al., 2016.

rossalleni: Ross Allen + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ensil Ross Allen (1908-1981), North American herpetologist. *Hyla rossalleni* Goin, 1959 (replacement name for *Hyla alleni* Goin, 1957, secondary junior homonym of *Scytotis alleni* Cope, 1870). Today *Dendropsophus rossalleni* (Goin, 1959).

rostrata, rostratus: L. *rostrata*, -atus, having beaked or hooked prow. *Hyla rostrata* Peters, 1863. (“... Der Kopf ist merklich länger als breit, die Schnauze lang, platt, elliptisch vorspringend, mit fast zugeschärfter Spitze, indem sich die untere und obere schwach convexe Fläche vorn in einem stumpfen Rande begegnen ...”). Also *Ololygon rostrata* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax rostrata* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax rostratus* (Peters, 1863).

rotenbergae: Rotenberg + L. -ae, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Elsie Laura K. Rotenberg, Brazilian conservacionist. *Brachycephalus rotenbergae* Nunes et al., 2021.

rotundipalpebra: L. *rotundus*, round, circular; wheel-like + L. *palpebra*, eyelid. *Proceratophrys rotundipalpebra* Martins & Giaretta, 2013. (“... It is a reference to the rounded upper eyelid of the new species, which helps to differentiate it from *P. goyana* ...”).

royi: Roy + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Roy Wallace McDiarmid, US American herpetologist. *Chiasmocleis royi* Peloso et al., 2014. Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) royi* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

rubeola: L. *rubeola*, reddish colored. *Hyla rubeola* Cochran & Goin, 1970. [“... (in life) bright red, narrow, dorsolateral stripes and scattered pepper-like spots of bright red on the back ...”]. In the synonymy of *Boana punctata* (Schneider, 1799).

ruber: L. *ruber*, red, ruddy, painted red. *Hyla rubra* Laurenti, 1768. (“... corpore rubro ...”). Also *Calamita ruber* — Merrem, 1820. *Auletris rubra* — Wagler, 1830. *Dendrohyas rubra* — Tschudi, 1838. *Hyla (Hyla) rubra* — Burmeister, 1856. *Hyla rubra* — Peters, 1872. *Scytopis ruber* — Cope, 1874. *Ololygon rubra* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax rubra* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax ruber* (Laurenti, 1768).

ruberoculatus: L. *ruber*, red, ruddy, painted red + L. *oculatus*, having eyes. *Scinax ruberoculatus* Ferrão et al., 2018. (“... iris bicolored, upper half reddish, lower half grey ...”).

- rubescens:** L. *rubescere*, turn red, redden, become red. *Bufo rubescens* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Ce qui caractérise surtout l’espèce, c’est d’abord la couleur rouge brique des crêtes céphaliques & des membres pouvant envahir le ventre, simulant des taches d’érythème & les parotides formant un bourrelet étroit & long ...”). Also *Bufo rufescens* — Brazil & Vellard, 1926 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Chaunus rubescens* — Frost et al., 2006. Today *Rhinella rubescens* (A. Lutz, 1925).
- rubicundulus:** L. *rubicundulus*, somewhat red. *Hyla rubicundula* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... Rygsiden af Kroppen samt Hovedet har en smuk rosenrod Farve ...”). Today *Dendropsophus rubicundulus* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).
- rubido:** L. *rubido*, tending to be red. *Gnathophysa rubido* Cope, 1874. (“... Color, above reddish to brown, in one specimen bright-red ...”). Also *Pleurodema (Gnathophysa) rubida* — Knauer, 1878. *Leptodactylus rubido* — Boulenger, 1882. *Leptodactylus rubidus* — Boulenger, 1884 “1883”. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus rhodonotus* (Günther, 1869).
- rubidoides:** L. *rubidoides*, similar to [*Leptodactylus*] *rubido* (in turn, from L. *rubido*, becoming red; in the synonymy of *L. rhodonotus*). *Leptodactylus pentadactylus rubidoides* Andersson, 1945. (“... I have called it forma *rubidoides*, as connecting the two species *pentadactylus* and *rubido* ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus pentadactylus* (Laurenti, 1768).
- rubro-lineata:** L. *rubrum*, red, ruddy, painted red + L. *lineata*, lined. *Hyla punctata rubro-lineata* B. Lutz, 1951. (“... linhas dorsolaterais e manchas côr de carmim ...”). Also *Hyla punctata rubrolineata* — Cei, 1980. *Hypsiboas punctatus rubrolineatus* — Brusquetti & Lavilla, 2006. In the synonymy of *Boana punctata* (Schneider, 1799).
- ruedai:** Rueda + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Vicente Rueda Almonacid, Colombian herpetologist. *Hyalinobatrachium ruedai* Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1998. In the synonymy of *Hyalinobatrachium munozorum* (Lynch & Duellman, 1973).

rufopunctata: L. *rufus*, red (of various shades) + L. *punctata*, punctuated; pointed. *Hyla rufopunctata* Andersson, 1906. (“... remaining parts of the back and the head densely covered with small rufous dots ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus rhodopeplus* (Günther, 1858).

rufus: L. *rufus*, red (of various shades). *Bufo rufus* Garman, 1877 “1876” (primary homonym of *Bufo rufus* Schneider, 1799). (“... which has been named *B. rufus* on account of the red color on the hinder half of the body ...”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella rubescens* (A. Lutz, 1925).

rugiceps: L. *rugis* (from *ruga*), wrinkle; crease, small fold + L. *-ceps*, -headed. (?). *Trigonophrys rugiceps* Hallowell, 1857 “1856”. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys ornata* (Bell, 1843).

rugosus: L. *rugosus*, full of wrinkles, folds, or creases. (1) *Leptodactylus rugosus* Noble, 1923. (“... A small species, very similar to *L. caliginosus*, but with a broader head, shorter leg and very rugose dorsum ...”). (2) *Leptodactylus rugosus* Melin, 1941 (preoccupied by *Leptodactylus rugosus* Noble, 1923). (“... a couple of vertebral and dorso-lateral folds on the back ...”). In the synonymy of *Adenomera hylaedactyla* (Cope, 1868).

rugulosus: L. *ruga*, wrinkle; crease + L. *-osus*, suffix denoting abundance. *Hylodes rugulosus* Peters, 1870. (“... Kopf- und Körperoberseite fein granuliert und mit zahlreichen erhabenen Längslinien ...”). In the synonymy of *Haddadus binotatus* (Spix, 1824).

rupestris: L. *rupes*, cliff; rock + L. *-tris*, place for or where. (1) *Physalaemus rupestris* Caramaschi et al., 1991. (“... The species is named for the characteristic vegetation of open montane areas, the “campo rupestre,” where it was collected ...”). (2) *Scinax rupestris* Araujo-Vieira et al., 2015. (“... The specific epithet “*rupestris*” is an allusion to the use of rock outcrops along temporary creeks in rock meadows at Chapada dos Veadeiros region, Central Brazil ...”).

rupicola: L. *rupis*, cliff; rock + L. *-cola*, dwelling in, inhabiting, living among. *Pristimantis rupicola* Taucce et al., 2020. (“... The name is used in reference to the habits of the new species, which is commonly found among rocks of the *Campo Rupestre* environment of the Chapada Diamantina ...”).

- Rupirana:** L. *rupis*, cliff; rock + L. *rana*, frog. *Rupirana* Heyer, 1999. (“... The name is to highlight the association of this genus with the campos rupestres of Brazil ...”).
- ruschii:** Ruschi + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Augusto (“Guti”) Ruschi (1915-1986), Brazilian naturalist. *Hyla ruschii* Weygoldt & Peixoto, 1987. Today *Dendropsophus ruschii* (Weygoldt & Peixoto, 1987).
- rusticus:** L. *rusticus*, country, rural; plain, homely, rustic. *Phyllomedusa rustica* Bruschi et al., 2014. [“... The epithet *rustica* originates from the Latin *rusticus* and is used to indicate the characteristics of the fields where this species is found (open fields) ...”]. Today *Pithecopus rusticus* (Bruschi et al., 2014).
- ruthveni:** Ruthven + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alexander Grant Ruthven (1882-1971), US American herpetologist. *Allophryne ruthveni* Gaige, 1926.
- sabanensis:** E. *sabana*, herbaceous formation characteristic of tropical regions with a long dry season, where grasses and large rhizomatous plants predominate, with some sparse trees. + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Lepidodactylus sabanensis* Heyer, 1994. (“... Named to indicate this species is geographically centered on the Gran Sabana of Venezuela ...”).
- sachsi:** Sachs + L. *-i*, suffix that indicates the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carl Sachs (?), German physicist. *Pleurodema sachsi* Peters, 1877. Also *Paludicola sachsi* — Stejneger, 1933. In the synonymy of *Pleurodema brachyops* (Cope, 1869).
- saci:** P. *saci*, from T. *sa’si*, *sassy perere*, an entity of Brazilian folklore, represented by a one-legged black boy, who wears a red cap, smokes a pipe and lives playing mischief, frightening visitors or scaring off cattle. *Adenomera saci* Carvalho & Giaretta, 2013. (“... is an allusion to the whistle call pattern emitted by the species that we associate to this well-known character in Brazilian folklore ...”).

sagarana: *P. sagarana*, neologism coined by João Guimarães Rosa (1908-1967), Brazilian writer. *Bokermannohyla sagarana* Leite et al., 2011. (“... Sagarana is cited by its author as of the expressive strength of a neologism, as it is totally new, for any reader and not explained yet, virgin of sight and understanding ...”).

salinicola: *L. salinicola*, from a salty place. *Lepidobatrachus salinicola* Reig & Cei, 1963. (“... Charcos y esteros temporarios mixohalinos del área de transición Monte-Chaco de las Salinas grandes de Santiago del Estero ...”). In the synonymy of *Lepidobatrachus asper* Budgett, 1899.

salli: Sall + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring John Sall, US American businessman. *Dendropsophus salli* Jungfer et al., 2010.

salseri: Salser + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jay K. Salser Jr., US American ethnographer. *Synapturanus salseri* Pyburn, 1975.

saltica: *L. saltus*, leap, spring, jump + L. *-ica*, pertaining/belonging to; connected with. *Paludicola saltica* Cope, 1887. (“... Characterized by the great length of its posterior legs. It has the form of the North American *Acris*, and is probably like it, a great jumper ...”). Today *Pseudopaludicola saltica* (Cope, 1887).

salvatori: Salvador + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Salvador Monteiro, Brazilian editor. *Odontophrynus salvatori* Caramaschi, 1996. Today *Proceratophrys salvatori* (Caramaschi, 1996).

sambaqui: P. - T. *sambaqui*, name given to layers constituted by deposits of shells, oyster shells, and other cooking remains of prehistoric Brazilian cultures, and found along the coast or in rivers and lakes close to them. *Eleutherodactylus sambaqui* Castanho & Haddad, 2000. (“... The sambaquis were used as a substrate to construct huts and as burial grounds and can be found near the type locality of the new species ...”). Today *Ischnocnema sambaqui* (Castanho & Haddad, 2000).

sanborni: Sanborn + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Colin Campbell Sanborn (1897-1962), US American ornithologist and mammalogist. *Hyla sanborni* Schmidt, 1944. Also *Hyla nana sanborni* — Barrio, 1967. Today *Dendropsophus sanborni* (Schmidt, 1944).

sanctaritae: P. Santa Rita, in Timbó range, state of Bahia, Brazil. *Proceratophrys sanctaritae* Cruz & Napoli, 2010. [“... Santa Rita forest (13°04’S, 39°38’W, 800 m above sea level), Serra do Timbó mountain, Municipality of Amargosa, State of Bahia, Brazil ...”].

sanmartini: San Martín + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Pablo Rubens San Martín (1934-1969), Uruguayan zoologist. *Melanophryniscus sanmartini* Klappenbach, 1968.

santae-catharinae: P. Santa + L. *-ae* + P. Catharina + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. *Craspedoglossa Santae-Catharinae* Müller, 1922. (“... Sie stammen aus dem Flußgebiet des Rio Novo, Sta Catharina, Brasilien und wurden mir nebst zahlreichen anderen von dem Naturalienhändler Karl Fritsche, Bremerhaven ...”). Also *Craspedoglossa sanctae-catharinae* — Miranda-Ribeiro (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Craspedoglossa* (= *Zachaenus*) *sanctae-catharinae* — Noble, 1927. In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus bolitoglossus* (Werner, 1897).

sapiranga: T. *esapi’ranga*, from T. *e’sa*, eye + T. *pi’ranga*, red. (1) *Bokermannohyla sapiranga* Brandão et al., 2012. (“... In Tupi indigenous language, *sapiranga* means red eye, an allusion to the reddish iris in the most individuals of the species. The specific epithet is also homage to Marco (Sapiranga) Freitas, for his continuous efforts to popularize the Brazilian herpetofauna ...”). (2) *Chiasmocleis sapiranga* Cruz et al., 2007. [“... The name of the species, “*sapiranga*” ... refers to the type locality ... Reserva Sapiranga (12°34’S; 38°02’W, 12 m altitude), Municipality of Mata de São João, State of Bahia, Brazil ...”].

sarayacuensis: S. Sarayacu, locality in Pastaza province, Ecuador (in turn, from Q. *sara*, maize + Q. *yacu*, creek, stream) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Hyla leucophyllata sarayacuensis* Shreve, 1935. (“... Type ... a gravid female, from Sarayacu, Ecuador, collected by O. C. Felton in 1933 ...”). Also

Hyla sarayacuensis — Goin, 1957. Today *Dendropsophus sarayacuensis* (Shreve, 1935).

sateremawe: T. Sataré-Mawé [from T, *sateré*, caterpillar of fire (lagarta de fogo) + T *mawé*, talking parrot (papagaio falante)], native Brazilian group inhabiting the Rio Madeira-Rio Tapajós interfluvial area. *Scinax sateremawe* Sturaro & Peloso, 2014. (“... where both localities from where the species is known are situated ...”).

sauvagii: Sauvage + L. -ii, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Henri-Emile Sauvage (1842-1917), French paleontologist and zoologist. *Phyllomedusa sauvagii* Boulenger, 1882. Also *Phyllomedusa sauvagii sauvagii* — Cei, 1956. *Phyllomedusa sauvagii rickettsii* — Cei, 1956. *Phyllomedusa sauvagei* — Funkhouser, 1957 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Pithecopus sauvagii* — B. Lutz, 1966.

savagei: Savage + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jay Mathers Savage, US American herpetologist. *Barycholos savagei* Lynch, 1980. In the synonymy of *Barycholos ternetzi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

sawayae: Sawaya + L. -ae, suffix indicating belonging. Honouring Paulo Sawaya (1903-1995), Brazilian physician, zoologist, and teacher. *Zachaenus sawayae* Cochran, 1953. Today *Scythrophrys sawayae* (Cochran, 1953).

saxatilis: L. *saxatilis*, found among rocks. *Thoropa saxatilis* Cocroft & Heyer, 1988. (“... along roadcuts where a thin film of water trickled over steeply inclined or vertical rock faces; larvae were collected from the same habitat ...”).

saxicola: L. *saxicola*, rock dweller. *Hyla saxicola* Bokermann, 1964. (“... En los ejemplares vivos el colorido era bien más claro durante la noche que durante el día, mimetizándose con las piedras donde cantan ...”). *Hyla pseudopseudis saxicola* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Hyla saxicola* — Pombal & Caramaschi, 1995. Today *Bokermannohyla saxicola* (Bokermann, 1964).

sazimai: Sazima + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ivan Petr Sazima, Brazilian ichthyologist and herpetol-

ogist. (1) *Hyla sazimai* Cardoso & Andrade, 1982. Also *Boana sazimai* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Bokermannohyla sazimai* (Cardoso & Andrade, 1982). (2) *Hylodes sazimai* Haddad & Pombal, 1995.

scapularis: L. *scapularis*, related to the shoulder-blades (pl.); shoulder; sword-belt; shoulder-strap. *Rana scapularis* Harlan, 1826. (“... a golden coloured line above the scapulae ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802).

Scarthyla: G. *skarthmos* (σκαρθμός), prancing (of a horse) + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Scarthyla* Duellman & de Sá, 1988. (“... The name *Scarthyla* is used in reference to the skipping habit of the adults on the surface of the water and the habit of the tadpoles of leaping out of the water ...”).

skeleton: G. *skeletos* (σκελετός), dried-up corpse, mummy. *Hyla skeleton* Laurenti, 1768. (“... dorso ex rubro variegato, undequaque extenuatissima ...”). In the synonymy of *Sphaenorhynchus lacteus* (Daudin, 1800).

scheneri: Scherer + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paul Scherer (?), collector of the holotype and son of William G. Scherer, of the Evangelical Mission at Peves, Perú. *Eupemphix scheneri* Myers, 1942. In the synonymy of *Engystomops petersi* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872.

schirchi: Schirch + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Paulo F. Schirch (?), Brazilian biologist. (1) *Dasypops schirchi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1924. Also *Microhyla schirchi* — Parker, 1934. *Hypopachus schirchi* — Bokermann, 1952. (2) *Stombus schirchi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. Also *Ceratophrys schirchi* — Gorham, 1966. Today *Proceratophrys schirchi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937).

schmidti: Schmidt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Karl Patterson Schmidt (1890-1957), US American herpetologist. (1) *Crossodactylus schmidti* Gallardo, 1961. (2) *Limnomedusa schmidti* Cochran & Goin, 1959. Today *Hydrolaetare schmidti* (Cochran & Goin, 1959).

schneideri: Schneider + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Johann Gottlob Theaenus Schneider (1750-1822), German classicist and naturalist. (1) *Bufo schneideri* Werner, 1894. Also *Chaunus schneideri* — Frost et al., 2006. *Rhinella schneideri* — Chaparro et al., 2007. In the synonymy of *Rhinella diptycha* (Cope, 1862). (2) *Rana schneideri* Merrem, 1820. In the synonymy of *Lithodytes lineatus* (Schneider, 1799).

schomburgkii: Schomburgk + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Sir Robert Hermann Schomburgk (1804-1865), German-born explorer for Great Britain. *Cystignathus schomburgkii* Troschel, 1848. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Schneider, 1799).

schubarti: Schubart + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Otto Schubart (1900-1962), German-Brazilian biologist. (1) *Chiasmocleis schubarti* Bokermann, 1952. Also *Chiasmocleis* (*Chiasmocleis*) *schubarti* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. (2) *Hyla schubarti* Bokermann, 1963. Today *Dendropsophus schubarti* (Bokermann, 1963).

schubarti: Schubart + L. *-i*, in this case, suffix indicating belonging to. Honouring Martha Schubart (?), collector of the type. *Corythomantis schubarti* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. (“...Colligido pela Exma. Sra. Dr. Martha Schubart em Salgado, Pernambuco...”). Same root in *Corythomantis schubarthae* — B. Lutz, 1968 (misspelling; clearly Lutz tried to amend M-R’s mistake, changing the masculine ending *-i* to the feminine ending *-ae*). In the synonymy of *Corythomantis greeningi* Boulenger, 1896.

Schwartzius: Schwartz + L. *-ius*, suffix commemorative and dedicative. Honouring Albert Schwartz, US American herpetologist. *Schwartzius* Hedges et al., 2008. In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

Scinacodes: G. *skinax* (σχιναξ), quick, nimble + G. *-ode* (-ὠδε), like that. *Scinacodes* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Hylodes* Fitzinger, 1826.

Scinax: G. *skinax* (σχιναξ), quick, nimble. *Scinax* Wagler, 1830. (“... Σχιναξ, *agilis ad subsiliendum* ...”). The same root in *Scinaxinae* Duellman et al., 2016.

scitula, scitulus: L. *scitula*, -us, neat; elegant. *Bufo scitulus* Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2003. [... O nome da espécie, um adjetivo latino, significa “bonito”, “encantador”, “elegante”, e é dado tanto em alusão à beleza da espécie em si, como também em relação à localidade-tipo (Bonito, MS) ...]. Today *Rhinella scitula* (Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2003).

scleroderma: G. *skleros* (σκληρός), (of material substances), hard to the touch, hard, firm, solid + G. *dermos* (δερμος), skin. *Pithecopus scleroderma* Cope, 1868. (“... skin with stellate bony deposits ...”). In the synonymy of *Phyllomedusa bicolor* (Boddaert, 1772).

scleromeris: G. *skleros* (σκληρός), (of material substances), hard to the touch, hard, firm, solid + G. *meros* (μέρος), part, portion, share. *Grypiscus scleromeris* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1935. (?). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus fuliginosus* Tschudi, 1838.

scrobiculata: L. *scrobis*, ditch, trench; dike + L. -ata, diminutive. *Hyla scrobiculata* B. Lutz, 1973 (*nomen nudum*). (?). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus branneri* (Cochran, 1948).

Scurrilirana: L. *scurrilis*, jesting + L. *rana*, frog. *Scurrilirana* Hillis & Wilcox, 2005. (“... in reference to the advertisement calls of most of the species in this clade, which sound like chuckling laughter ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

scutatus: L. *scutatus*, armed with a long wooden shield. *Rana scutata* Spix, 1824. (“... capite subgrandi, scutato, toto osseo ...”). Also *Stombus scutatus* — Gravenhorst, 1825. Today *Hemiphractus scutatus* (Spix, 1824).

Scythrophrys: G. *skythropos* (σκυθρωπός), sullen, angry + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Scythrophrys* Lynch, 1971. (“... Etymology. —Greek, *scythros* + *phryne*, meaning “sullen toad.” ...”).

Scytopsis: Unclear. G. *skytos* (σκύτος), hide, skin, leather + G. *opsis* (οπής), hole. *Scytopsis* Cope, 1862. Probably referred to the presence of visible eardrum. (“... Ear perfectly developed, tympanum not concealed ...”). Also *Scytopsis* — Knauer, 1878 (subsequent misspelling of *Scytopsis*). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus* Tschudi, 1838.

seabrai: Seabra + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carlos Alberto Campos Seabra (1916-2001), Brazilian entomologist. *Sphoerohyla seabrai* Bokermann, 1958. Also *Dryomelictes seabrai* — Goin, 1961. *Sphaenorhynchus scabrai* — Gorham, 1974 (incorrect subsequent spelling of species name). In the synonymy of *Allophryne ruthveni* Gaige, 1926.

sebae: Seba + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating belonging. Honouring Albertus Seba (1665-1736), Dutch pharmacist, zoologist, and collector. *Ceratophrys Sebae* Gray, 1825. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys cornuta* (Linnaeus, 1758).

sebbeni: Sebben + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Antonio Sebben, Brazilian herpetologist. *Rhinella sebbeni* Vaz-Silva et al., 2015.

secedens: L. *secedens*, withdraw; secede. *Hyla secedens* B. Lutz, 1963. (“... Similar to *H. geographica* and *H. bischoffi multilineata*, it differs from the former in body proportions, webbing, and coloration of the lower eyelid and from the latter in disposition of the vomerine teeth and coloration of the limbs ...”). Also *Hypsiboas secedens* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana secedens* (B. Lutz, 1963).

segallai: Segalla + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Magno Vicente Segalla, Brazilian herpetologist. *Paratelmatobius segallai* Santos et al., 2019.

semiguttata, semiguttatus: L. *semi-*, half, partly + L. *guttata*, *-us*, having drops, spots, specks. *Hyla semiguttata* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... Le dos est brun clair, avec une bande submarginale de chaque côté & une médiane, toutes brunes & fragmentées par places, formant alors des taches longitudinales ovales ou rondes ...”). Also *Hypsiboas semiguttatus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana semiguttata* (A. Lutz, 1925).

semilineata, semilineatus: L. *semi-*, half, partly + L. *lineata*, *-us*, lined. (1) *Bufo* (*Oxyrhynchus*) *semilineatus* Spix, 1824. (“... *linea dorsii posterioris medii longitudinali albicante* ...”). Also *Bufo* (*Rhinella*) *semilineatus* — Cuvier, 1829. In the synonymy of *Rhinella crucifer* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).

(2) *Hyla geographica* var. *semilineata* Spix, 1824. (“... *linea a rostro ad medium dorsum longitudinali, nigra ...*”). Also *Hyla semilineata* — Silveira & Caramaschi, 1989. *Hypsiboas semilineatus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana semilineata* (Spix, 1824).

semipalmatus: L. *semi*, half, partly + L. *palmatus*, webbed. *Iliodiscus semipalmatus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... os artelhos são fimbriados e curtamente sub-palmados ...”). Today *Cycloramphus semipalmatus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920).

seniculus: L. *senex*, old man + L. *-culus*, diminutive suffix. *Hyla senicula* Cope, 1868. (“... ground color above gray ...”). Also *Hyla marmorata senicula* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. Today *Dendropsophus seniculus* (Cope, 1868).

septentrionalis: L. *septentrionalis*, northern part of a country/region, the North; northern regions (pl.). *Crossodactylodes septentrionalis* Teixeira et al., 2013. (“... in reference to the geographical position where the new species was found, as it is the northernmost known *Crossodactylodes* species ...”).

serialis: L. *serialis*, in row, series, secession, sequence. *Leptodactylus serialis* Girard, 1853. (“... yellowish brown on the sides, with a series of black maculae ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus latrans* (Steffen, 1815).

sertanejo: P. *sertanejo*, originally from the sertão; who lives in the sertão (*sertão* = wilder place, away from cultivated points. In NE Brazil, inland area drier than the caatinga). *Leptodactylus sertanejo* Giaretta & Costa, 2007. (“... The specific name “sertanejo” is a Portuguese word to those people who live in the wilderness, far from civilization ...”).

setiba: P. *setiba*, from T. *setiba*, seashells in abundance. *Melanophryniscus setiba* Peloso et al., 2012. (“... Setiba is the popular name of the region where the type locality is located, likely due to the high number of mollusk shells found in the beaches of the region ...”).

shudikarensis: (?) Shudikar-wau, locality in Guyana + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Chiasmocleis shudikarensis* Dunn, 1949. [refers to the type locali-

ty, “... Shudikar-wau, upper Essequibo River, British Guiana (not far from Brazilian border) ...”]. Also *Chiasmocleis* (*Chiasmocleis*) *shudikarensis* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

shushupe: Sh. *shushupe*, vernacular name of *Lachesis muta* (Squamata: Viperidae). *Tepuihyla shushupe* Ron et al., 2016. (“... Our field assistants in Ere river, Alpahuayo Mishana (Peru) and Juyuintza (Ecuador) believed that the advertisement calls of *T. shushupe* and *T. tuberculosa* were produced by *L. muta* ...”).

sibilatrix: L. *sibilatrix*, whistler. (1) *Rana sibilatrix* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. (“... Der pfeifende Frosch ...”). Also *Leptodactylus sibilatrix* — Fitzinger, 1826. *Cystignathus sibilatrix* — Wagler, 1830. *Leptodactylus sibilator* — Müller, 1927 (incorrect subsequent spelling). *Leptodactylus sybilatrix* — Cei, 1950. *Leptodactylus sybilator* — Cei, 1956 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Schneider, 1799). (2) *Sibilatrix* Fitzinger, 1843. (?). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826.

sibilata, sibilatus: L. *sibilatus*, hiss; hiss at. *Hyla sibilata* Cruz et al., 2003. (“... O nome específico deriva do Latim *sibilus*, que significa assovio, em alusão ao canto característico da espécie ...”). Today *Aplastodiscus sibilatus* (Cruz et al., 2003).

Sierrana: L. apocope of *Sierra* [*madrensis*] + L. *rana*, frog. *Sierrana* Dubois, 1992. [“... du nom spécifique *sierramadrensis* Taylor, 1939 (du nom espagnol de la région où cette espèce a été découverte, la Sierra Madre del Sur), et du nom de genre *Rana* Linné, 1758 (du latin *rana*, grenouille ...”]. In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

signifer, signifera, signiferus: L. *signifer*, bearer of the mark, stamp or seal. *Rhinoderma signifera* Girard, 1853. (“... A spear-shaped blotch on the head. A broad dorsal, deep brown band, forked anteriorly to receive the point of the cephalic spear-shaped blotch ...”). Also *Paludicola signifera* — Boulenger, 1891. *Paludicola signifer* — Baumann, 1912. *Physalaemus signiferus* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. *Eupemphix signifer* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Physalaemus signifer* (Girard, 1853).

similis: L. *similis*, like, similar, resembling. *Hyla similis* Cochran, 1952. (“... Resembles *H. fuscovaria* A. Lutz in shape and structure of head and body ...”). Also *Hyla x-signata similis* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Oloolygon similis* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. Today *Scinax similis* (Cochran, 1952).

simonstuarti: Simon Stuart + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Simon Nicholas Stuart, British conservation biologist. *Leptodactylus simonstuarti* Angulo & Icochea, 2010. Today *Adenomera simonstuarti* (Angulo & Icochea, 2010).

simplex: L. *simplex*, simple, unaffected; plain. (1) *Hyla catharinae simplex* B. Lutz, 1968. (“... This subspecies differs from the nominative form and other subspecies by the slightly smaller size, narrow, elongate build, simplified dorsal pattern, and the absence of vivid flash colors ...”). In the synonymy of *Scinax obtriangulatus* (B. Lutz, 1973). (2) *Melanophryniscus simplex* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2002. (“... The name, a Latin adjective, refers to the simple color pattern of this species ...”).

Siphonops: L. *siphon*, tube for sucking/blowing liquid; straw + G. *opsis* (ὄψις), sight, appearance. *Siphonops* Wagler, 1828. (“... *truncus modice longus, omnino cylindraceus, nudus, annulis impressis, integerrimis, numerosis auctus; cauda vix nulla, non annulata, obtusissima* ...”). The same root in Siphonopidae Bonaparte, 1850.

sirensis: [Serrania de] Sira [Rio Lullapichis drainage, 750 m, Departamento Huánuco, Peru (9°28' S, 74°47' W)] + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Dendrobates sirensis* Aichinger, 1991. (“... The species is named after the type locality, the Serrania de Sira ...”). Also *Ranitomeya sirensis* — Grant et al., 2006. Today *Ranitomeya sirensis* (Aichinger, 1991).

skaios: G. *skaios* (σκαίος), left, on the left, western, westward. *Scinax skaios* Pomal et al., 2010 (“... *Skaios* is a Greek word meaning western. Most of the species of the *Scinax catharinae* species group occur in the Atlantic Forest in eastern Brazil ...”). Also *Oloolygon skaios* — Duellman et al., 2016.

skuki: Skuk + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Gabriel Omar Skuk Sugliano (1962-2011) (see *Gabohyla*), Uru-

guayan-Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Rhinella skuki* Caramaschi, 2012. Today *Dendrophryniscus skuki* (Caramaschi, 2012). (2) *Scinax skuki* Lima et al., 2011. Also *Ololygon skuki* — Duellman et al., 2016.

skydmainos: G. *skydmainos* (σκυδμαίνω), be angry. *Eleutherodactylus skydmainos* Flores & Rodríguez, 1997. (“... in loose reference to the furrowed brow expression imparted by the transverse interorbital ridge ...”). Today *Pristimantis skydmainos* (Flores & Rodríguez, 1997).

smaragdinus: L. *smaragdinus*, emerald-green. *Phyllobates smaragdinus* Silverstone, 1976. (“... refers to the green stripes and the green anterior venter ...”). Also *Dendrobates smaragdinus* — Myers et al., 1978. *Epipedobates smaragdinus* — Myers, 1987. *Phyllobates (Pseudendrobates) smaragdina* — Bauer, 1988. In the synonymy of *Ameerega petersi* (Silverstone, 1976).

Sminthillus: Unclear. (1) G. *sminthos* (σμίινθος), mouse. (2) G. *Smintheus* (Σμινθεύς), a surname of Apollo in the Greek mythology + L. *-illus*, diminutive. *Sminthillus* Barbour & Noble, 1920. (?). In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

snethlageae: Snethlage + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Henriette Mathilde Maria Elizabeth Emilia Snethlage (1868-1929), German ornithologist. *Pipa snethlageae* Müller, 1914.

soaresi: Soares + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Benedicto Abilio Monteiro Soares (1914-1985), Brazilian arachnologist. (1) *Hyla soaresi* Caramaschi & Jim, 1983. Today *Dendropsophus soaresi* (Caramaschi & Jim, 1983). (2) *Physalaemus soaresi* Izecksohn, 1965.

Somuncuria: S. Somuncuria, Patagonian plateau, from M. *somun*, the one who speaks or sounds + M. *cura*, stone. *Somuncuria* Lynch, 1978. [“... The generic name is taken from the name of the isolated Patagonian plateau (Meseta de Somuncurá) on which the frog lives ...”]. In the synonymy of *Pleurodema* Tschudi, 1838.

spanios: G. *spanios* (σπανίως), scarce, rare. *Eleutherodactylus spanios* Heyer, 1985. (“... in allusion to its rarity of collection ...”). Today *Ischnocnema spanios* (Heyer, 1985).

spectabilis: L. *spectabilis*, noteworthy, outstanding. (1) *Melanophryniscus spectabilis* Caramaschi & Cruz, 2002. (“... The specific name is a Latin adjective meaning notable or showy, in reference to the remarkable color pattern of this species ...”). (2) *Phasmahyla spectabilis* Cruz et al., 2008. (“... The specific Latin name *spectabilis* is an adjective related to the beauty, elegance, and conspicuous coloration of the specimens ...”).

spectrum: L. *spectrum*, *specter*, apparition. *Hyla spectrum* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (?). Also *Hypsiboas spectrum* — Cope, 1867. In the synonymy of *Boana albopunctata* (Spix, 1824).

spegazzinii: Spegazzini + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carlos Luis Spegazzini (1858-1926), Italo-Argentinian botanist. *Hyla spegazzinii* Boulenger, 1889. In the synonymy of *Boana raniceps* (Cope, 1862).

Spelerpes: G. *speos* or *speios* (σπέος or σπείος), cave, cavern, grotto + G. *erpeton* (ἔρπετόν), creature that moves or crawls (on the ground). *Spelerpes* Rafinesque, 1822. (“... In 1821 I discovered a new Salamander, dwelling permanently in the dark caves of limestone near Lexington ...”). In the synonymy of *Bolitoglossa* Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854.

Sphaenorhynchus: G. *sphinos* (σφηνός), wedge + G. *rhynchos* (ρόγχος), snout. *Sphaenorhynchus* Tschudi, 1838. (“... *caput minimum, trigonum* ...”).

Sphoehyla: G. *sphinos* (σφηνός), wedge + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Sphoehyla* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938. (“... *caput minimum, trigonum* ...”). In the synonymy of *Sphaenorhynchus* Tschudi, 1838.

spiniger: L. *spiniger*, thorn-bearing, thorny. *Engystomops spinigera* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. Interestingly, the description of this species, attributed to Boulenger, does not refer to the presence of spines. Also *Physalaemus spiniger*

— Haddad & Pombal, 1998. *Eupemphix spiniger* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Physalaemus spiniger* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

spinulifer: L. *spinulifer*, thorn-bearer. *Niedenis spinulifer* Ahl, 1924. (“... Oberseite dicht mit kleinen, spitzigen, weißlich gefärbten Warzen besetzt ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus asper* Werner, 1899.

spinulosus: L. *spinula*, diminutive of thorn, thorn + L. -osus, which is abundant in. *Nectodactylus spinulosus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1924. (“... Corpore ranino in mare, laeve, sparce spinuloso ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis spinulosa* — Parker, 1934. In the synonymy of *Chiasmocleis leucosticta* (Boulenger, 1888).

spixi: Spix + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Johann Baptist von Spix (1781-1826), Bavarian traveler and zoologist. (1) *Bufo spixii* Fitzinger, 1826. Also *Oxyrhynchus spixii* — Wied-Neuwied, 1827. In the synonymy of *Rhinella ornata* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Ceratophris spixii* Cuvier, 1829. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys cornuta* (Linnaeus, 1758). (3) *Ephippipher spixii* Cocteau, 1835. In the synonymy of *Brachycephalus ephippium* (Spix, 1824). (4) *Hemiphractus spixii* Wagler, 1828 (substitute name for *Rana scutatus* Spix, 1824). In the synonymy of *Hemiphractus scutatus* (Spix, 1824). (5) *Leptodactylus spixi* Heyer, 1983.

spumaponens: L. *spuma*, foam, froth; slime, scum, spume + L. *ponens*, put, place, set. *Allobates spumaponens* Kok & Ernst, 2007. (“... The specific epithet is derived from the Latin word *spuma*, meaning “foam” and the Latin verb *ponere*, meaning “to place” in reference to the atypical tadpole deposition site observed in the new species ...”). In the synonymy of *Allobates sumtuosus* (Morales, 2002).

spumarius: L. *spuma*, foam, froth; slime, scum, spume+ L. -arius, pertaining to. *Atelopus spumarius hoogmoedi* — Lescure et al., 1980. (“... Above, dark brown, with a broad band from orbit to groin, composed of numerous aggregated annuli of greenish-yellow, which has the appearance of dried foam” ...). In the synonymy of *Atelopus hoogmoedi* Lescure, 1974.

squalirostris: L. *squalus*, *squali*, kind of fish; shark + L. *rostri*, beak, snout. *Hyla squalirostris* A. Lutz, 1925. (“... le museau est projeté en dessus & en avant

de la bouche ...”). Also *Ololygon squalirostris* — Fouquette & Delahous-saye, 1977. Today *Scinax squalirostris* (A. Lutz, 1925).

stawiarskyi: Stawiarsky + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Victor Stawiarsky (1903-1979), Brazilian educator at Museu Nacional, Rio de Janeiro. *Dendrophryniscus stawiarskyi* Izecksohn, 1994.

Stefania: Stefani + *-ia*, dedicative suffix. Honouring Luis Stefani Raffucci (1901-1971), Puerto Rican engineer and a long time Chancellor of the University of Puerto Rico at Mayagüez. *Stefania Rivero*, 1968.

stegolepis: L. *Stegolepis*, genus of Rapateaceae due to Klotzsch, 1872; in turn, from G. *stegos* (στῆγος), roof, cover + G. *lepis* (λεπίς), scales. *Eleutherodactylus stegolepis* Schlüter & Rödder, 2007 “2006”. [“... The new species is named after *Stegolepis squarrosa* (Rapateaceae), dominant floral species on the summit of Guaiquinima Tepui ...”]. Also *Pristimantis stegolepis* — Myers & Donnelly, 2008. In the synonymy of *Pristimantis vilarsi* (Melin, 1941).

stejnegeri: Stejneger + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Leonhard Hess Stejneger (1851-1943), Norwegian herpetologist. *Borborocoetes stejnegeri* Noble, 1924. Also *Craspedoglossa stejnegeri* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. *Zachaenus stejnegeri* — Harding, 1983. Today *Cycloramphus stejnegeri* (Noble, 1924).

stellae: Stellae + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring the company “Stellae Limited” of Leicester, UK. *Hypsiboas stellae* Kwet, 2008. (“... in recognition of its contribution to conserving biodiversity by aiding the reduction of greenhouse gases ...”). Today *Boana stellae* (Kwet, 2008).

stellatus: L. *stellatus*, set/furnish/cover with stars/points of light. *Bufo stellatus* Spix, 1824. (“... *hypochondriis femoribusque aurantio-maculatis vel ocellatis* ...”). Also *Bufo crucifer* var. *stellata* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. In the synonymy of *Rhinella crucifer* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).

stelzneri: Stelzner + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Alfred Wilhelm Stelzner (1840-1895), German geologist, active in Argentina from 1871 to 1874. *Phrynisus stelzneri* Weyenbergh, 1875. Several Brazilian species of *Melanophrynisus* were once considered subspecies of the today *Melanophrynisus stelzneri* (Weyenbergh, 1875).

stenocephala, Stenocephalus: G. *stenos* (στενός), narrow, tight + G. *kéfali* (κεφάλη), head. (1) *Hyla stenocephala* Caramaschi & Cruz, 1999. (“... comprimento da cabeça maior que a largura ...”). Also *Hypsiboas stenocephalus* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana stenocephala* (Caramaschi & Cruz, 1999). (2) *Stenocephalus* Tschudi, 1838. (?). In the synonymy of *Elachistocleis* Parker, 1927.

Stenodactylus: G. *stenos* (στενός), narrow, tight + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Stenodactylus* Philippi, 1902. (“... *digiti pedum anticorum et posteriorum elongati tenues terites basi membrana brevi unitis ...*”). In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

stenodema: G. *stenos* (στενός), narrow, tight + G. *dema* (δεμα), bulge. *Leptodactylus stenodema* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. (“... un tercer cordón ó arruga lisa y un poco más estrecha que la anterior, nace en el punto en que ésta llega al nivel posterior del oído, y va, encorvándose exteriormente, á lo largo de los costados, y en la mitad de estos se ensancha de pronto transformándose en un parche glanduloso de escasa amplitud prolongado hasta el ángulo superior de la ingle ...”).

stepheni: Stephen + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Stephen R. Edwards, US American zoologist. *Colostethus stepheni* Martins, 1989. Today *Anomaloglossus stepheni* (Martins, 1989).

Stereocyclops: G. *stereos* (στερεός), firm, hard, solid + G. *kyklos* (κύκλος), circle, ring. *Stereocyclops* Cope, 1870. (“... Anterior portion of the sclerotica ossified, so as to form a hard annulus round the cornea ...”).

Stertirana: L. *sterto*, snore + L. *rana*, frog. *Stertirana* Hillis & Wilcox, 2005. (“... in reference to the snore-like element of the advertisement call of the frogs in this group ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

stictigularis: G. *stiktos* (στικτός), marked with spots, dappled + L. *gularis*, pertaining to the throat, neck, gullet. *Leptodactylus stictigularis* Noble, 1923. (“... a dark throat studded with white spots ...”). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus rhodomystax* Boulenger, 1884.

Stombus: Unclear. According to the author, from G. *στόμβος* (*sic*; note the *sigma* transposition), of unknown meaning; probably from G. *στόμβος* (στόμβος), who opens a big mouth to speak; bawling or bellow; also a reviler, insult-er, brawler, scold. *Stombus* Gravenhorst, 1825. [“... Von allen diesen Gat-tungen aber unterscheidet sie sich am auffallendsten durch den ungemein großen Kopf, weiten Rachen, und durch die emporstehenden Augenlieder. Deßhalb habe ich diele Art, nebst *Rana megastoma* und *Rana scutata*, welche von Spix auf der 4ten Tafel abgebildet hat, in eine besondere Gat-tung vereinigt, die ich (nach dem griechischen Worte (στόμβος) (*sic*) *Stom-bus* genannt ...”]. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys* Wied-Neuwied, 1824.

Strabomantis: G. *στραβος* (στραβος), squinting + G. *mantis* (μαντης), tree-frog. *Strabomantis* Peters, 1863. (“... die einander genäherten Augen ...”). The same root in *Strabomantidae* Hedges et al., 2008 and *Strabomantinae* Hedges et al., 2008.

striata: L. *striatus*, provided with channels; grooves; wrinkles. *Hyla striata* Pe-ters, 1872. (?). In the synonymy of *Boana polytaenia* (Cope, 1870).

strigilata, strigilatus: L. *striga*, a row or strip of anything + L. *-ata, -atus*, pro-vided with. (1) *Cyclorhamphus eleutherodactylus* var. *strigilata* A. Lutz, 1929. (“... leva apenas umas manchinhas alongadas ou riscos curtos e gros-sos de côr clara, disseminadas sobre a face dorsal, sendo longitudinaes no tronco, nos olhos e nas pernas ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus eleu-therodactylus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920). (2) *Hyla strigilata* Spix, 1824. (“... *striis dorsii lateralis obliquis* ...”). Also *Ololygon strigilata* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax strigilata* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax strigilatus* (Spix, 1824).

strussmannae: Strüssmann + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Christine Strüssmann, Brazilian herpetolo-

gist. (1) *Proceratophrys strussmannae* Ávila et al., 2011. (2) *Scinax strussmannae* Ferrão et al., 2018.

studerae: Studer + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Anita Studer, Swiss conservacionist. *Hyla studerae* S. Carvalho-e-Silva et al., 2003. Today *Dendropsophus studerae* (S. Carvalho-e-Silva et al., 2003).

suarezi: Suarez + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring José Roberto Alves Suarez, Brazilian forest ranger. *Holoaden suarezi* Martins & Zaher, 2013.

subfolionidificans: L. *sub*, under + L. *folium*, leaf + L. *nidificare*, build a nest. *Colostethus subfolionidificans* Lima et al., 2007. (“... The name is in allusion to the reproductive site of the species, which lays its eggs on the lower surfaces of live leaves ...”). Today *Allobates subfolionidificans* (Lima et al., 2007).

subguttata: L. *sub*, under + L. *guttata*, having drops, spots, specks. *Proceratophrys subguttata* Izecksohn et al., 1999. (“... O nome específico enfatiza as gotas escuras que ornamentam a face ventral do tronco ...”).

sub-nigrum: L. *sub*, close to, about + L. *nigrum*, black, dark. *Engystoma sub-nigrum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920. (“... Superiormente plúmbeo denegrido, inferiormente marmorado de isabel ...”). Also *Microhyla subnigra* — Parker, 1934. *Myersiella subnigra* — Carvalho, 1954. In the synonymy of *Myersiella microps* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

subtilis: L. *subtilis*, fine; slender, delicate. *Osteocephalus subtilis* Martins & Cardoso, 1987. (“... o nome é dado em alusão ao porte desta nova espécie ...”).

sulcatus: L. *sulcus*, furrow, groove. *Hylodes sulcatus* Cope, 1874. (“... A peculiarity of the species is seen in the strong ridge that extends along the superciliary border to the posterior border of the cranium, inclosing a groove with its fellow ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus sulcatus* — Gorham, 1966. *Limnophys sulcatus* — Heinicke et al., 2007. Today *Strabomantis sulcatus* (Cope, 1874).

sulfuratus: L. *sulfuratus*, containing sulphur. *Brachycephalus sulfuratus* Condez et al., 2016. (“... The adjective is used in reference to the yellow-lemon blotches on the pectoral skin of the new species ...”).

sumtuosus: L. *sumptuosus*, big and expensive, from L. *sumptus*, cost, charge, expense. *Colostethus sumtuosus* Morales, 2002 (“... El nombre de la especie significa costoso, carísimo. En referencia a lo costoso que me resultó asignarle un nombre ...”). Today *Allobates sumtuosus* (Morales, 2002).

supercilialba: L. *supercilium*, an eyebrow (often includes the ridge on which this grows; applied to analogous parts in creatures other than man) + L. *albus*, white, pale. *Chiasmocleis supercilialba* Morales & McDiarmid, 2009. [“... The name *supercilialbus* of this species (*supercilium* = eyebrow and *albus* = white) is referent to the conspicuous white band over eyes like a eyebrow ...”] (*sic*). Also *Chiasmocleis supercilialbus* Morales & McDiarmid, 2009. *Syncope supercilialbus* — de Sá et al., 2012. *Chiasmocleis (Syncope) supercilialba* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

supernumeraria: L. *supernumerarius*, exceeding the usual, stated, or prescribed number. *Microcaecilia supernumeraria* Taylor, 1969. (“... This form differs from the three other species recognized in this genus in having 40 more secondaries and 20 more primaries ...”).

surda, surdus: L. *surda*, -us, deaf, unresponsive to what is said. (1) *Cochranella surda* Taylor & Cochran, 1953. (“... tympanum hidden under skin ...”). Also *Centrolenella surda* — Duellman, 1977. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana eurygnatha* (A. Lutz, 1925). (2) *Ischnocnema surda* Canedo et al., 2010. (“... is an allusion to the indistinct external tympanum and tympanic annulus in the new species ...”). (3) *Hyla aurantiaca surda* Cochran, 1953. (“... No external tympanum ...”). Also *Sphaenorhyla surda* — Goin, 1957. Today *Sphaenorhynchus surdus* (Cochran, 1953).

surinamensis: D. Surinam, South American country; from A. *Surinen*, taino speaking people who inhabited the area at the time of European contact in 1667 + L. -ensis, belonging to a place. (1) *Bufo surinamensis* Daudin, 1802 “An. XI”. (“... Ce petit Crapaud paroît très-voisin du Crapaud ovale: il

m'a été donné par M. de Bèze, qui l'a trouvé à Surinam ..."). Also *Engystoma surinamense* — Dubois et al., 2021. Today *Elachistocleis surinamensis* (Daudin, 1802). (2) *Pipa surinamensis* Duvernoy in Cuvier, 1849. ("... Le Pipa de Surinam ..."). In the synonymy of *Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758).

surumu: (?). [Vila] Surumu (04°12'N, 60°48'W; 121 m altitude), Municipality of Pacaraima, state of Roraima, Brazil. *Elachistocleis surumu* Caramaschi, 2010. ("... an allusion to the type locality, a small village currently included in the Reserva Indígena Raposa Serra do Sol, in the State of Roraima, northern Brazil ..."). Also *Engystoma surumu* — Dubois et al., 2021.

suturata: L. *suturata*, seamed, stitched. *Hyla suturata* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. ("... pernas lineadas em zig-zag. Essas linhas brancas são salientes como se fossem costuras feitas na pelle, á linha branca ..."). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus minutus* (Peters, 1872).

Synapturanus: G. *synaptos* (συναπτός), fastened together, tied, knotted + G. *ouranos* (οὐρανός), celestial vault; by ext., mouth palate. *Synapturanus* Carvalho, 1954. ["... *Synapturanus* is from the Greek συναπτός and οὐρανός (joined together and roof of mouth), and has reference to the fusion of the palatal elements ...].

Syncope: G. *syncope* (συγκοπή), cutting short, elision, abbreviation, faint, swoon. *Syncope* Walker, 1973. ("... In the present context it alludes to the loss of one presacral element from the vertebral column ..."). In the synonymy of *Chiasmocleis* Méhely, 1904.

syphax: Uncertain. L. *Syphax*, from G. *Syphax* (Σύφαξ), proper name of a Numidian king during the Punic wars. Additionally, "Greek *syphax* (sweet new wine), in allusion to the bright red color in life of the groin, belly, and ventral surfaces of the thighs and shanks occurring in some, but not all, specimens" (De Sá et al., 2014). *Leptodactylus syphax* Bokermann, 1969. No clues in the original description, although Bokermann named several species based on classical or mythological characters (e.g., Ariadna, As-tarte, Atlas, Eurydice).

Syrrhophus: *G. syrroi* (συρροή), flowing together, confluent + *G. lophia* (λοφιά), crest, headdress. *Syrrhophus* Cope, 1878. (?). Also *Syrrhophus* — Boulenger, 1888 (incorrect subsequent spelling of *Syrrhophus*). *Syrrhaphus* — Günther, 1900 (incorrect subsequent spelling of *Syrrhophus*). In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

tamacuarensis, tamacuarina: S. Tamacuari, mountain in Sierra Tapirapecó, Amazonas, on the border of Venezuela and Brazil [from T. *tamakwa're* (tamaquari), trees of the genus *Caraipa* (Calophyllaceae)] + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place, or L. *-ina*, suffix diminutive. (1) *Colostethus tamacuarensis* Myers & Donnelly, 1997. ["... Derived from Tamacuari + the adjectival-forming suffix *-ensis* (belonging to a place) ..."]. Today *Anomaloglossus tamacuarensis* (Myers & Donnelly, 1997). (2) *Stefania tamacuarina* Myers & Donnelly, 1997. ("... ridge N Pico Tamacuari, 1270 m elevation, Sierra Tapirapecó, Amazonas, Venezuela ...").

taophora: *G. tau* (Τ, τ), nineteenth letter of the Greek alphabet + *G. phoreus* (φορέως), bearer, carrier. *Oligon abbreviatus taophora* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923. ("... A coloração do dorso se condensa de modo á constituir um T, cuja travessa repousa sobre os olhos e cuja haste, geralmente se interrompe em manchas quadradas, regulares que se projectam da nuca ao coccyx ..."). Also *Thoropa taophora* — Feio et al., 2006. Today *Thoropa taophora* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923).

tapacurensis: P. [Estação Ecológica do] Tapacurá [Municipality of São Lourenço da Mata, state of Pernambuco, Brazil (8°2'26.13"S, 35°12'0.43"W; 122 m a. s. l.)], from T. *itapacurá*, *i* = river; *ita* = rock; *pa* = spaciousness; *cura* = cover; meaning rock that covers the river or capped rock river + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. Etymology by the authors. *Dendropsophus tapacurensis* Oliveira et al., 2021. ("... The specific epithet "tapacurensis" is ... a direct reference to new species type locality, the Tapacurá Ecological Station ...").

tapajonica, tapajos: P. *Tapajós*, one of the largest clearwater rivers and the main tributary of the right bank of the Amazon River; from T. *tapayos*, which comes from the villages + L. *-ica, -icus*, pertaining to. (1) *Adenomera tapajonica* Carvalho et al., 2021. ("... The epithet is derived from the Tapajós River. The distribution range of *A. tapajonica* comprises a swathe of land entailing the west bank of the middle-lower Tapajós River, limited to the

south of the Amazon River ...”). (2) *Allobates tapajós* Lima et al., 2015. (“... The specific epithet makes reference to the Tapajós River, a major clearwater tributary of the Amazon River ...”). (3) *Bolitoglossa tapajonica* Brecko et al., 2013. (“... The specific epithet is taken from the lower Tapajós river region, the type locality ...”).

tapiti: *T. tapiti*, *tapeti*, Brazilian rabbit, forest rabbit (*Sylvilagus brasiliensis*). *Lepidodactylus tapiti* Sazima & Bokermann, 1978. (“... parecida com *camaquara*, dela diferindo pelo focinho mais comprido, pernas mais longas ...”).

tarsius: *L. Tarsius*, genus of primates due to Storr (1870) [in turn, from *G. tarsos* (ταρσός), flat of the foot between toes and heel], characterized by having huge eyes. *Pithecopus tarsius* Cope, 1868. (“... Diameter of eye three times tympanum ...”). Today *Phyllomedusa tarsius* (Cope, 1868).

Tarsopterus: *G. tarsos* (ταρσός), flat of the foot between toes and heel + *G. pteron* (πτερόν), wing. *Tarsopterus* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... *Tarsopterus differt a Leiupero, cui affinis, tarso et digitis posterioribus membrana cinctis ...*”). In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

taurina, taurinus: *L. taurina*, *-inus*, of or derived from a bull. (1) *Osteocephalus taurinus* Steindachner, 1862. There is no explicit reference to the origin of the name in the text, although it may refer to the shape of the interocular ridges. (“... Knochenkamm an der Oberseite des Kopfes paarig, schwach verkehrt Sförmig |: \/: | gekrümmt ...”). Also *Trachycephalus* (*Osteocephalus*) *taurinus* — Steindachner, 1867. *Hyla taurina* — Boulenger, 1882. *Hyla* (*Trachycephalus*) *taurina* — Melin, 1941. (2) *Rana taurina* Cuvier, 1816 “1817”. [“... La Grenouille taureau. Bull-Frog des Anglo-Américains. (*Rana taurina*. Cuv. *R. pipiens*. Daud.) Catesb. II, lxxi. Daud. Xviii ...”]. In the synonymy of *Lithobates catesbeianus* (Shaw, 1802).

taylori: Taylor + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Edward Harrison Taylor (1889-1978), US American herpetologist. *Centrolenella taylori* Goin, 1968 “1967”. Also *Hyalinobatrachium taylori* — Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. Today *Hyalinobatrachium taylori* (Goin, 1968). (2) *Microcaecilia taylori* Nussbaum & Hoogmoed, 1979.

- tedo:** (?) *tedo*, vernacular name for the species. *Pipa tedo* Merrem, 1820. [No references in Merrem, but earlier authors, like Schneider (1799), noted: “... Sub nomine *Pipa vel Tedo incolis notus, habitat aquas paludosas Guianae et Surinami ...*”). Also *Pipa sedo* — Schlegel, 1858 (incorrect subsequent spelling of *Pipa tedo* Merrem, 1820). In the synonymy of *Pipa pipa* (Linnaeus, 1758).
- teko:** (?) If T., *teko* means being, state of life, condition; if Y. *t^hëka*, crop field. Refers to *Teko*, native South Americans who occupy the southern half of French Guiana. *Amazophrynella teko* Rojas-Zamora et al., 2018. (“... the area occupied by the Teko tribe also encompasses the type locality ...”).
- Teletrema:** G. *tele* (τήλε), far off, far away, at a distance + G. *trema* (τρήμα), aperture, hole. *Teletrema* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. (“... Choanas grandes, bem separadas entre si a junctas à margem da maxilla ...”). In the synonymy of *Oreobates* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872.
- tenera:** L. *tenera*, soft/delicate/gentle; young/immature; weak/fragile/frail. *Hylella tenera* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... har en smækker Krop, et lille, kort og bredt Hoved, spinkle Forlemmer ...”). Also *Hyla tenera* — Nieden, 1923. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus bipunctatus* (Spix, 1824).
- tentaculata:** L. *tentaculata*, provided with a tentaculum. *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758. (?). Also in the combinations *Caecilia (Caecilia) tentaculata* — Van der Hoeven, 1833. *Caecilia lenticulata* Tschudi, 1838 (error for *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758).
- tepequem:** P. Tepequém (3. 750866 N, 61. 705084 W), locality in the state of Roraima, Brazil, from T. *tupá*, the stanza or place of bangs, tumbles, or thunders + T. *quem*, fire. *Anomaloglossus tepequem* Fouquet et al., 2015. [“... The specific epithet is a noun in apposition and refers to the type locality (Tepequém, Roraima State, Brazil) ...”].
- tepuiana, tepuianus:** Pe. *tepui*, mountain + L. *-ana, -anus*, pertaining to. *Hypsiboas tepuianus* Barrio-Amorós & Brewer-Carias, 2008. [“... southern slope of Sarisariñama-tepui, Locality VI, Estado Bolívar, Venezuela (4°25' N, 64°07' W), elev. 420 m ...”]. Today *Boana tepuiana* (Barrio-Amorós & Brewer-Carias, 2008).

Tepuihyla: *P. tepui*, mountain + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Tepuihyla* Ayarzagüena et al., 1993. (“... El nombre genérico es derivado de Tepuy, nombre pemón usado para designar las tierras altas de Guayana, en combinación con el griego *Hyla*, género más común de las ranas de la familia Hylidae ...”).

Teratohyla: *G. teratos* (τερατος), monster + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Teratohyla* Taylor, 1951. (?).

ternetzi: Ternetz + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Carl Ternetz (1870-1928), Swiss naturalist. (1) *Paludicola ternetzi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. *Physalaemus ternetzi* — Bokermann, 1966. Also *Barycholos ternetzi* — Caramaschi & Pombal, 2001. Today *Barycholos ternetzi* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. (2) *Pseudopaludicola ternetzi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937.

tetraploidea: *G. tetraploides*, with four sets of chromosomes, from *G. tetra* (τετρά), four + *G. ploos* (πλόος), folds + *G. -eidēs* (-ειδής), form, likeness. *Phyllomedusa tetraploidea* Pombal & Haddad, 1992. (“... O nome específico é dado em alusão ao número cromossômico tetraplóide ...”).

Tetraprion: *G. tetra* (τετρα), four + *G. prion* (πρίω), saw. *Tetraprion* Stejneger & Test, 1891. (“... One long series of teeth on parasphenoid bone; vomerine teeth; a series of teeth on the palatines ...”). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus* Tschudi, 1838.

tetravittata, tetravittatus: *G. tetra* (τετρα), four + L. *vittata*, *-us*, wearing or carrying a ritual vitta. *Dendrobates tetravittatus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... Cor negra retinta; uma estria dourada do focinho a uma nódoa da mesma côr sobre a articulação da coxa, outra, de sob os olhos ao ileon; coxas, pernas e pés maculados de amarelo, as manchas longitudinaes e interrompidas; parte supero-externa das coxas amarellada diffusa para o joelho ...”). In the synonymy of *Ameerega trivittata* (Spix, 1824).

thomei: Thomé + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring João Carlos Alciati Thomé, Brazilian conservacionist. *Leptodactylus thomei* Almeida & Angulo, 2006. Today *Adenomera thomei* (Almeida & Angulo, 2006).

Thoropa: Indeterminate. As is often the case, Cope gave no indication of the origin of the name, which is contained in a key to the genera of the family Hylidae. Etymologically it can be derived (improbably) from *G. thoros* (θωρός), semen, or, with a little more sense, from *G. thóryvos* (θόρυβος), in the sense of “uproar, clamour, rowdiness, din”, and also “commotion, turmoil”. This last meaning could be linked to the fact that the first individual of its type species (*Cystignathus missiessii* Eydoux & Souleyet, 1842) was collected in a noisy waterfall in Tijuca. (“... Ce Cystignathe provient de la cascade de Tijouka, aux environs de Rio Janeiro ...”). *Thoropa* Cope, 1865.

tibiatrix: *L. tibia*, flute, reed-pipe, double oboe (equivalent to the Greek *aulos*; see *Auletris*). *Hyla tibiatrix* Laurenti, 1768. (“... *Mas coaxans utroque in latere colli vesicam, tibiae instar, inflat ...*”). Also *Auletris tibiatrix* — Wagler, 1830. *Dendrohyas tibiatrix* — Tschudi, 1838. *Hyla tibiatrix tibiatrix* — Rivero, 1961. Same root in *Calamita tibicen* Merrem, 1820. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).

tigrinus: *L. tigrinus*, tigerlike. *Scinax tigrinus* Nunes et al., 2010. (“... in allusion to the color pattern of the thighs ...”).

timbeba: *T. timbeba*, flattened nose. (“... o nome é dado em alusão ao focinho curto e truncado desta nova espécie ...”). *Hyla timbeba* Martins & Cardoso, 1987. Today *Dendropsophus timbeba* (Martins & Cardoso, 1987).

timbo: P. [Serra do] Timbó, in turn from *T. timbo*, leguminous or sapindaceous plants whose roots and/or bark can be used to make the *tingui*, which is widely used in fishing. *Phasmahyla timbo* Cruz et al., 2008. [“... The specific name, a noun in apposition, refers to the type locality, Serra do Timbó (13°04’S, 39°38’W, 800 m altitude), Municipality of Amargosa, State of Bahia, Brazil ...”].

timbuhy: P. [Núcleo] Timbuy, place in the state of Espírito Santo, Brazil; from *T. timbuhy*, originated in *T. timbó-y*, river of timbós (alluding to diverse species of trees with this vernacular name, including *Magonia pubescens*, *Ateleia glazioviana*, *Enterolobium contortisiliquum*, etc.). *Crossodactylus timbuhy* Pimenta et al., 2014. (“... refers to the locality which later became the town of Santa Teresa: the nucleus of Timbuhy, Colony of Santa Leopoldina, established by Italian immigrants in 1874 ...”).

tinae: Tina + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Albertina (“Tina”) Pimentel Lima, Brazilian herpetologist. *Allobates tinae* Melo-Sampaio et al., 2018.

tinctorius: L. *tinctus*, wet/moisten/dip/soak; color/dye/tinge/tint, stain (w/ blood) + L. *-orium*, place where, place for. *Rana tinctoria* Cuvier, 1797 “An. VI”. (“... Elle se trouve en Amérique, & est remarquable par l’usage que les sauvages font de son sang pour tapirer les perroquets; c’est-à-dire pour leur panacher le plumage. Pour cela ils leur arrachent quelques plumes, & imprègnent la plaie du sang de cette raine. Il revient à la place des plumes rouges ou jaunes ...”). Also *Calamita tinctorius* Schneider, 1799. *Hyla tinctoria* — Daudin, 1800. *Hylaplesia tinctoria* — Boie in Schlegel, 1826. *Dendrobates tinctorum* — Silverstone, 1975 (typographic error). Today *Dendrobates tinctorius* (Cuvier, 1797).

tintinnabulum: L. *tintinnabulum*, bell; cow bell; small bell. *Hyla tintinnabulum* Melin, 1941. (“... This species, which occurred in great numbers at a little igarapé (river-branch) on the western side of the river ... had a brittle, bell-like sound ...”). Today *Dendropsophus tintinnabulum* (Melin, 1941).

toby: T. *toby*, greenish. *Brachycephalus toby* Haddad et al., 2010. (“... Toby ... is a Tupi Guarani indigenous word that means “greenish,” and is used here in allusion to the greenish color of the dorsum of *B. toby* ...”).

tocantins: P. Tocantins, state, river, and basin in Brazil, from T. *tocantins*, toucan beak (in turn, T. *tukana*, toucan + T. *tim*, beack). *Pseudis tocantins* Caramaschi & Cruz, 1998. (“... O epíteto específico, um nome em aposição, refere-se ao Estado e bacia do Tocantins, onde a espécie foi coletada ...”).

toftae: Toft + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Catherine A. Toft, North American herpetologist. *Eleutherodactylus toftae* Duellman, 1978. Today *Pristimantis toftae* (Duellman, 1978).

Tomodactylus: G. *tomos* (τομός), with the capacity to cut, cutting, sharp + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. *Tomodactylus* Günther, 1900. (“... These

frogs differ by the presence of digital disks from the species described under *Paludicola*, *Leiuperus*, and other generic names: a character which, in my opinion, should carry generic distinction ...”). In the synonymy of *Eleutherodactylus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

tomopterna: G. *tomos* (τομός), with the capacity to cut, cutting, sharp + G. *pternis* (πτέρνης), back part of the human foot, heel. *Pithecopus tomopternus* Cope, 1868. (“... two angular dermal heel processes, together having a truncate posterior outline ...”). Also *Phyllomedusa tomopterna* — Boulenger, 1882. *Phyllomedusa (Pithecopus) tomopterna* — B. Lutz, 1950. *Pithecopus tomopterna* — B. Lutz, 1950. Today *Callimedusa tomopterna* (Cope, 1868).

tonimi: Tonim + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Antônio de Pádua Almeida (“Tonim”), Brazilian conservationist. *Fritziana tonimi* Walker et al., 2016.

toraro: Ap. *to'raro*, frog. *Ranitomeya toraro* Brown et al., 2011. (“... The species name is in reference to the noun “to ‘raro,” which in the Apurinã language means “frog.” This indigenous Amazonian tribe occupies the center of the range of the new species ...”).

Torrentirana: L. *torrentis*, swift or violent stream + L. *rana*, frog. *Torrentirana* Hillis & Wilcox, 2005. (“... in reference to the typical habitat of many of the species in this clade ...”). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

Trachycara: G. *trachys* (τραχύς), rough, rugged + G. *cara* (κάρα), head. *Trachycara* Tschudi, 1845. [“... *Caput magnum, triangulare, rugosum* ...”]. In the synonymy of *Rhinella* Fitzinger, 1826.

Trachycephalus: G. *trachys* (τραχύς), rough, rugged + G. *kefali* (κεφαλή) head. *Trachycephalus* Tschudi, 1838. (“... *Caput magnum, rugosum* ...”).

Trachyphrynus: G. *trachys* (τραχύς), rough, rugged + G. *phrynos* (φρύνος), toad. *Trachyphrynus* Goin & Cochran, 1963. (No references in the generic description; characterizing the type-species, *T. myersi*, the authors noted: “... Skin of upper parts with many spiny glandules and a network of glandular

lines, the most prominent of which are the dorsolateral ones, an x-shaped pair behind head and several transverse ones on sacrum and across tibia ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

trachystoma, trachystomus: G. *trachys* (τραχύς), rough, rugged + G. *stoma* (στόμα), mouth. *Tarsopterus trachystomus* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... Der findes ingen Tænder paa Ganen, men derimod vel langs med Overkjæbens Rand ...”). Also *Crossodactylus trachystoma* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. Today *Crossodactylus trachystomus* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

trachythorax: G. *trachys* (τραχύς), rough, rugged + L. *thorax*, from G. θώραξ, breastplate, chest. *Hyla trachythorax* Müller & Hellmich, 1936. (“... Wir nammen das Tier *Hyla trachythorax* nach dem grossen plattenförmigen Rauigkeiten auf der Brust des Männchens ...”). Also *Ololygon trachythorax* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax trachythorax* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. In the synonymy of *Scinax fuscovarius* (A. Lutz, 1925).

trapicheiroi: P. Trapicheiros, a river in the city of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil; in turn, “trapicheiro” is the one who owns or manages sugar mills + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Hyla trapicheiroi* A. Lutz & B. Lutz in B. Lutz, 1954. (“... Os primeiros espécimens foram encontrados na represa do rio Trapicheiro, Tijuca, D. F. ...”). Also *Hyla catharinae trapicheiroi* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Ololygon catharinae trapicheiroi* — Heyer, 1980. *Ololygon trapicheiroi* — Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989. *Scinax trapicheroy* — Langone, 1992 (incorrect subsequent spelling). Today *Scinax trapicheiroi* (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1954).

travassoi: Travassos + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Lauro Pereira Travassos (1890-1970), Brazilian parasitologist. *Dendrophryniscus brevipollicatus travassoi* A. Miranda-Ribeiro in P. Miranda-Ribeiro, 1955. (“... Etiquetado pelo autor como: *Dendrophryniscus b. travassoi* ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendrophryniscus brevipollicatus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870.

tremembe: (?). Tremembé, native Brazilian group who have lost their native language and speak Portuguese, established in the state of Ceará, Brazil. *Ch-*

thonerpeton tremembe Maciel et al., 2015. (“... a reference to the Tremembé ethnic group ...”).

triangulum: L. *triangulum*, three-cornered, triangular; triangle. *Hyla triangulum* Günther, 1869 "1868". (“... a triangular isosceles deep-black spot, edged with white, on the head and nape, one angle being on each eyelid, and the third behind the nape ...”). Today *Dendropsophus triangulum* (Günther, 1869).

tricolor: L. *tri*, three + L. *color*, color; pigment; shade/tinge. *Hyalinobatrachium tricolor* Castroviejo-Fisher et al., 2011. (“... refers to its dorsal coloration, which is a combination of three colors: light green, dark green and brown in life, and cream, white and black in preservative ...”).

tridactyla, tridactylus: G. *tria* (τρία), three + G. *dactylos* (δάκτυλος), finger, toe. (1) *Adelophryne tridactyla* Duellman & Mendelson, 1995. (“... the name refers to the presence of only three functional digits on the hand and foot ...”). Also *Syncope tridactyla* — Silva & Meinhardt, 1999. *Chiasmocleis tridactyla* — Peloso et al., 2014; de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. Today *Chiasmocleis tridactyla* (Duellman & Mendelson, 1995). (2) *Brachycephalus tridactylus* Garey et al., 2012. (“... The specific epithet refers to the major diagnostic feature of this species, which is the presence of only three fingers in the hands, with no trace of external Finger IV ...”). (3) *Euparkerella tridactyla* Izecksohn, 1988. (“... O nome específico destaca a conformação das mãos e pés, onde apenas três dedos, ou artelhos, são desenvolvidos ...”).

Trigonophrys: L. *trigonus*, triangular; having three angles/corners + G. *ofrys* (ὄφρυς), eyebrow, supercilium. *Trigonophrys* Hallowell, 1857 “1856”. (“... upper eyelid triangular ...”). Also *Triogonophrys* — Hoffmann, 1878 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys* Wied-Neuwied, 1824.

trilineata, trilineatus: L. *tri-*, prefix [tres-], consisting of, having, etc., three of the things named + L. *lineata*, lined. (1) *Ololygon trilineata* Hoogmoed & Gorzula, 1979. (“... From Latin *tres*, meaning three, and *linea*, meaning line. In reference to the three distinct lines on the dorsum ...”). Also *Sci-*

nax trilineata — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. *Scinax trilineatus* — Köhler & Böhme, 1996. In the synonymy of *Scinax fuscomarginatus* (A. Lutz, 1925). (2) *Phyllobates trilineatus* Boulenger, 1884 “1883”. (“... a greyish streak from eye to groin on each side and a narrow vertebral line of the same colour ...”). Also *Colostethus trilineatus* — Edwards, 1971. Today *Allobates trilineatus* (Boulenger, 1884).

tripui: P. Tripuí, a river in the state of Minas Gerais, Brazil; from T. *tripui*, slender hill (T. *ityra*, hill + T. *poi*, slender); additionally, others translate the name as “dark behind the waters”¹⁵. *Scinax tripui* Lourenço et al., 2010. (“... is the name of the main stream of the Estação Ecológica do Tripuí, the type locality of the described species ...”). Also *Ololygon tripui* — Duellman et al., 2016.

tritaeniata, tritaeniatus: L. tri-, prefix [*tres-*], consisting of, having, etc., three of the things named + L. *taenia*, ribbon, tape, band + L. *-atus*, having the nature of. *Hyla tritaeniata* Bokermann, 1965. (“... Uma faixa castanha vai desde a ponta do focinho até quase o ânus ... Na parte anterior do dorso há duas linhas castanhas cada qual partindo da pálpebra superior e atingindo o sacrum ...”). Today *Dendropsophus tritaeniatus* (Bokermann, 1965).

trivittata, trivittatus: L. tri-, prefix [*tres-*], consisting of, having, etc., three of the things named + L. *vittata*, wearing or carrying a ritual vitta. (1) *Hyla trivittata* Spix, 1824. (“... *taeniis dorsi tribus, longitudinalibus aureo-flavis & post mortem coeruleo ...*”). Also *Hysaplesia trivittata* — Schlegel, 1826. *Hylaplesia trivittatus* — Knauer, 1878. *Phyllobates trivittatus* — Silverstone, 1976. *Epipedobates trivittatus* — Myers, 1987. *Phobobates trivittatus* — Zimmermann & Zimmermann, 1988. Today *Ameerega trivittata* (Spix, 1824). (2) *Leptodactylus trivittatus* A. Lutz, 1926. (“... Dorso com estrias longitudinaes de côr terracotta, uma marginal de cada lado e uma submediana incompleta ...”). Also *Leptodactylus (Parvulus) trivittatus* — A. Lutz, 1930. In the synonymy of *Adenomera marmorata* (Steindachner, 1867).

15 Diogo de Vasconcelos, História antiga das Minas Gerais, 4th edn. Belo Horizonte: Itatiaia, 1999, p. 123.

trogloodytes: *G. troglodytes* (τρογλοδύτας), troglodyte, hole-dweller. *Leptodactylus troglodytes* A. Lutz, 1926. [... The name refers to an adult female *Leptodactylus*, collected by Conrad Guenther in the nest of an ant (*Atta* sp.) in Pernambuco ...]. Also *Leptodactylus (Cavicola) troglodytes* – A. Lutz, 1930.

trombetas: (?). Trombetas¹⁶ [Floresta Estadual (FLOTA) Trombetas (0°57'45.97" S, 55°31'20.28" W), municipality of Óbidos, state of Pará, Brazil]. *Microcaecilia trombetas* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2011. (... The name of the species refers to the type-locality ...).

tropicalia: *G. tropis* (τροπής), time of the solstice (*i.e.*, midsummer or midwinter day), tropic. *Scinax tropicalia* Novaes-e-Fagundes et al., 2021. (... The specific epithet, a noun in apposition, is in allusion to the tropical habitat where the new species occurs, and also in homage to the Brazilian revolutionary artistic movement known as Tropicália, or Tropicalismo ...).

truncata, truncatus: *L. truncatus*, maim, mutilate; cut off. (1) *Hyla truncata* Izecksohn, 1959. Today *Xenohyla truncata* (Izecksohn, 1959). (2) *Hylodes truncatus* Steindachner, 1864. (... Diese Art ist ausgezeichnet durch die Kürze der vorne breit quer abgestutzten Schnauze ...). In the synonymy of *Hylodes nasus* (Lichtenstein, 1823).

Trypheropsis: *G. trypheros* (τρυφερός), delicate + *G. ópsis* (ὄψις), appearance, aspect. *Trypheropsis* Cope, 1868. (?). In the synonymy of *Lithobates* Fitzinger, 1843.

tuberculosus: *L. tuberculum*, small swelling, bump, protuberance, excrescence, tumor + *L. -osus*, suffix denoting abundance. (1) *Leptodactylus tuberculosus* Andersson, 1945. (... All upper surfaces densely covered with small, pointed tubercles and scattered larger ones ...). In the synonymy of *Oreobates quixensis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1872. (2) *Phyllodytes tuberculosus* Bokermann, 1966. (... Espécie pequena, de focinho arredondado, carac-

16 "... Na distância de duas léguas fica a boca do rio das Trombetas, a que podia dar o nome o ser muito largo e logo se estreitar, se não soubéssemos que êste foi o nome de um índio que dirigia a grande nação dos índios que vivem no seu sertão, chamado o principal Trombeta... ". Frei João de São José, *Visita ao sertão*, 212 (cited by Levy-Cardoso (1961)).

terizada pelo grande desenvolvimento dos tubérculos, ao longo do antebraço e do tarso, e pele dorsal finamente granulosa ...”).

tumifrons: *L. tumor*, swollen or distended condition + *L. frons*, fore part of anything. *Atelopus tumifrons* Boulenger, 1905. (“... snout very short, not projecting beyond the mouth, above with a strong rounded swelling extending to between the eyes ...”). Also *Dendrophryniscus tumifrons* – Müller, 1934. Today *Melanophryniscus tumifrons* (Boulenger, 1905).

tupinamba: *T. Tupinambá*, descendent of the first parents (from *T. tuba*, father + *T. ypy*, first + *abá*, man), a native-Brazilian nation. (1) *Proceratophrys tupinamba* Prado & Pombal, 2008. (“... Tupinambá é designação comum a diversas tribos tupi-guaranis que habitavam o litoral do Brasil ...”). (2) *Scinax tupinamba* Silva & Alves-Silva, 2008. (“... Tupinambá is the name of an Indian Nation that once inhabited the coast along the State of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil...”).

tymbamirim: *T. tymba*, animal + *T. mirim*, small. *Scinax tymbamirim* Nunes et al., 2012. (“... in allusion to the SVL amplitude smaller than in *Scinax alter* ...”).

Typhlonectes: *G. tyflos* (τυφλος), blind + *G. nektes* (νεκτες), swimmer. *Typhlonectes* Peters, 1880. (“... im Wasser lebend ...”). Also *Thyphlonectes* – Fuhrmann, 1914 (incorrect subsequent spelling). The same root in *Typhlonectidae* Taylor, 1968.

typhonia, typhoni: *L. typhonis*, violent whirlwind/tornado. (1) *Bufo typhoni* – Schneider, 1799 (not Linnaeus, 1758). (“... *notitiae auctorem Rolandum nominans. Habitare in America, et noctu sono cornicis tetro clamitare dicitur* ...”). *Osilophus typhoni* – Tschudi, 1838. *Otilophus typhoni* – Peters, 1871. *Oxyrhynchus typhoni* – Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. *Bufo typhoni typhoni* – Leavitt, 1933. *Bufo* (= *Otylophus*) *typhoni* – Ceí, 1953. Names applied to different populations of *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti, 1768, *sensu lato*). (2) *Rana typhonia* Linnaeus, 1758. (Possibly in reference to the mating call, “... *clamitans nocte sono cornicis* ...”; although, surely, Linnaeus never heard the call of this species). Today *Trachycephalus typhoni* (Linnaeus, 1758). (3) *Rana typhonia* Daudin, 1802 “An. XI”. (?). Also *Cystignathus typhoni* – Wagler, 1830. *Leptodactylus*

typhonia — Fitzinger, 1826. *Leptodactylus typhoni* — Boulenger, 1882. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Schneider, 1799).

typica: *L. typica*, typical. *Leptodactylus ocellatus* var. *typica* Cei, 1948 (name suppressed for purposes of synonymy). [“... Una de estas (formas de *Leptodactylus*), que denominaremos de ahora en adelante como *typica*, no se diferencia de la forma tucumana ...”]. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus macrosternum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926.

uai: P. *uai!*, expression that indicates surprise or doubt. *Hylodes uai* Nascimento et al., 2001. (“... The specific name is an aleatory arrangement of letters, being also a common interjection used by the people from Minas Gerais, meaning surprise and astonishment ...”).

uaiuai: C. *Uaiuai* or *Wai-Wai*, Carib-speaking native Americans. *Rhinatrema uaiuai* Maciel et al., 2018. (“... honoring the Uaiuai Indians ... which include indigenous communities in southern Guyana and the southeastern part of the state of Roraima, the northeastern part of the state of Amazonas, and the northwestern part of the state of Pará in Brazil ...”).

uakarii: (?) *Uakari*, vernacular name for *Cacajao calvus*, an Amazonian primate + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Dendrobates uakarii* Brown et al., 2006. (“... The epithet was chosen because both the red uakari and *D. uakarii*, sp. nov. shared similar historical distributions and have bright red dermal pigmentation ...”). Today *Ranitomeya uakarii* (Brown et al., 2006).

ulei: Ule + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Ernst Heinrich Georg Ule (1854-1915), German-Brazilian botanist. *Flectonotus ulei* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. Today *Fritziana ulei* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926).

umbrinus: L. *umbra*, shade; ghost; shadow + L. *-inus*, pertaining/belonging to; connected with. *Grypiscus umbrinus* Cope, 1867. (“... Below, and hind and front face of femur dark brown, with yellow punctae ...”). Also *Cycloramphus umbrinus* — Cochran, 1955 “1954”. In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus fuliginosus* Tschudi, 1838.

underwoodi: Underwood + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Cecil Frank Underwood (1867-1943), British-Costarican naturalist. *Hyla underwoodi* Boulenger, 1899. Also *Hyla microcephala underwoodi* — Duellman & Fouquette, 1968. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus microcephalus* (Cope, 1886).

unicolor: L. *unicolor*, of one color. *Stombus appendiculatus* var. *unicolor* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926. (“... a côr geral é o chocolate quasi negro uniforme, tanto superior como inferiormente ...”). Also *Stombus appendiculatus incolor* — Bokermann, 1966 (incorrect subsequent spelling). In the synonymy of *Proceratophrys appendiculata* (Günther, 1873).

Unicus: L. *unicus*, only, sole, single, singular, unique; uncommon, unparalleled; one of a kind. *Unicus* de Sá et al. 2019. (“... we replace the subgenus *Relictus* with the name *Unicus* ...”). In the synonymy of *Chiasmocleis* Méhelÿ, 1904.

unistrigatus: L. *uni-*, one + L. *striga*, lengthwise furrow + L. *-atus*, suffix indicating quality of. *Eleutherodactylus unistrigatus holti* Cochran, 1948. Today *Ischnocnema holti* (Cochran, 1948) (see *holti*).

Uperodon: G. *uperōa* (ὑπερώα), buccal palate + G. *odons* (ὀδονς), teeth. *Uperodon* Duméril & Bibron, 1841 (part). (“... G. *υπερωα*, *oris palatum*, le palais, et de *οδονς*, *οδοντος*, *dens*, dent ...”). In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys* Wied-Neuwied, 1824.

uranoscopa: G. *ouranos* (ουρανός), heaven, sky + G. *scopos* (σκοπός), watcher. *Hyla (Hylella) uranoscopa* Müller, 1924. (“... Die Augen stehen nicht lateral, sondern sind schräg nach oben gerichtet ...”). Also *Centrolenella uranoscopa* — Noble, 1926. *Cochranella uranoscopa* — Taylor & Cochran, 1953. *Centrolenella uranoscopa* — Duellman, 1977. *Hyalinobatrachium uranoscopum* — Ruiz-Carranza & Lynch, 1991. Today *Vitreorana uranoscopa* (Müller, 1924).

urbanae: Urban + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Helga Urban (?), Brazilian naturalist. *Chiasmocleis urbanae* Bokermann, 1952. In the synonymy of *Chiasmocleis leucosticta* (Boulenger, 1888).

- uruguayus:** Uruguay, South American country + L. *-us*, pertaining to. *Hyla uruguayana* Schmidt, 1944. (“... Quebrada de los Cuervos, Departament of Treinta y Tres, Uruguay ...”). Also *Julianus uruguayus* — Duellman et al., 2016. Today *Scinax uruguayus* (Schmidt, 1944).
- vallanti, vallantii:** Vaillant + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Léon Louis Vaillant (1834-1914), French zoologist. (1) *Phyllomedusa vallantii* Boulenger, 1882. Also *Pithecopus vallanti* — B. Lutz, 1966. (2) *Phrynoceros vallanti* Tschudi, 1838. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys cornuta* (Linnaeus, 1758).
- valae:** Val + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Francisca (“Chica”) Carolina do Val, Brazilian entomologist. *Cycloramphus valae* Heyer, 1983.
- validus:** L. *validus*, strong, powerful. *Leptodactylus validus* Garman, 1888. (“... Male with an internal subgular vocal sac, and two strong conical tubercles on the inside of the first digit ...”).
- vanzolinii, vanzolinus:** Vanzolini + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns or + L. *-ius*, suffix commemorative/dedicative. Honouring Paulo Emílio Vanzolini (1924-2013), Brazilian herpetologist. (1) *Cochranella vanzolinii* Taylor & Cochran, 1953. Also *Centrolenella vanzolinii* — Duellman, 1977. In the synonymy of *Vitreorana uranoscopa* (Müller, 1924). (2) *Colostethus vanzolinus* Morales, 2002. Today *Allobates vanzolinus* (Morales, 2002). (3) *Dendrobates vanzolinii* Myers, 1982. Today *Ranitomeya vanzolinii* (Myers, 1982). (4) *Hylodes vanzolinii* Heyer, 1982. (5) *Phrynomedusa vanzolinii* Cruz, 1991. (6) *Vanzolinus* Heyer, 1974. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus* Fitzinger, 1826.
- variabilis:** L. *variabilis*, variable, changeable. (1) *Eleutherodactylus variabilis* Lynch, 1968. (“... in reference to the variety of color patterns and colors in life ...”). Today *Pristimantis variabilis* (Lynch, 1968). (2) *Dendrobates variabilis* Zimmermann & Zimmermann, 1988. (“... deutet auf die große Variabilität in Form, Größe und Anzahl der Flecken hin ...”). Today *Ranitomeya variabilis* (Zimmermann & Zimmermann, 1988).

variegata: L. *variegata*, colored; party colored, variegated. (1) *Cyclorhamphus eleutherodactylus* var. *variegata* A. Lutz, 1929. (“... A primeira que chamarei *variegata* tem desenhos muito variáveis e bastante complicados ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus eleutherodactylus* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920). (2) *Hyla variegata* Daudin, 1802 “An. XI”. (“... Comme je l’ai dans de l’esprit-de-vin, sa couleur est d’un brun grisâtre marbré et pointillé de brun rougeâtre ...”). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758). (3) *Rana variegata* Bonnaterre, 1789. (“... La G. Bigarrée ... *R. Variegata*. *R. corpore angustato, laevi, ex fusco nigricante, maculeis lacteis consperso* ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus leucophyllatus* (Beireis, 1783).

variolosa: L. *variolus*, spot, pustule + L. *-osa*, full of. *Hyla variolosa* Spix, 1824. (“... *subtus ochraceum, granulorum* ...”). Also *Auletris variolosa* — Wagler, 1830. *Scinax variolosa* — Wagler, 1830. In the synonymy of *Boana punctata* (Schneider, 1799).

varius: L. *varius*, colored; party colored, variegated. *Ceratophrys varius* Wied-Neuwied, 1824. (“... mehrere schwarzbraune warzige Hautkamme auf dem Rücken, welche den Mittelstreif des Rückens einfassen; Weibchen mit einem grünen, Männchen mit einem gelblichen Mittelstreifen von der Schnauze nach dem After hin ...”). Also *Ceratophrys varia* — Cocteau, 1835. In the synonymy of *Ceratophrys aurita* (Raddi, 1823).

vastus: L. *vastus*, huge, vast; monstrous. *Leptodactylus vastus* A. Lutz, 1930. (“... This name is given to the species cited in my first paper as ? *gigas* Spix ...”).

vautierii: Vautier + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Abel Félix Vautier (1794-1863), French malacologist. *Hyla vautierii* Bibron, 1843. (?). Also *Scinax vautierii* — Duellman, 1993. In the synonymy of *Boana pulchella* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

velata: L. *velatus*, veil, cover, cover up; enfold, wrap, envelop; hide, conceal. *Hyla velata* Cope, 1887. (“... Tympanic membrane not very distinct ...”). In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus minutus* (Peters, 1872).

velocicantus: L. *velocis*, swift, quick, fleet, rapid, speedy + L. *cantus*, song, call. *Allobates velocicantus* Souza et al., 2020. (“... in reference to the high note-repetition rate of the advertisement call of the new species ...”).

venancioi: Venancio + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Joaquim Venâncio Fernandes (1895-1955), Brazilian technician and collector. *Eleutherodactylus venancioi* B. Lutz, 1958. Today *Ischnocnema venancioi* (B. Lutz, 1958).

venezolana, venezolanus: Venezuela, South American country [from It. *Venezziola*, little *Venezia*] + L. *-ana, -anus*, belonging to. *Corythomantis venezolana* Mertens, 1950. (“... Terra typica: San Fernando, oberer Orinoko, Süd-Venezuela ...”). Also *Aparasphenodon venezolanus* — Trueb, 1970. Today *Trachycephalus venezolanus* (Mertens, 1950).

ventrigranulosus: L. *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly + L. *granuli*, granule + L. *-osus*, full of. *Pristimantis ventrigranulosus* Maciel et al., 2012. (“... *ventrigranulosus* means granular belly, and refers to the feature that most conspicuously distinguishes the new species ...”).

ventrimaculata: L. *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly + L. *maculata*, spotted. (1) *Boana ventrimaculata* Caminer & Ron, 2020. (“... in reference to the brown blotches on the chest and belly of these frogs ...”). (2) *Engystoma ventrimaculata* Andersson, 1945. (“... All lower surfaces except the feet pale yellowish white with large irregular chocolate brown spots ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis* (*Chiasmocleis*) *ventrimaculata* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”. Today *Chiasmocleis ventrimaculata* (Andersson, 1945).

ventrimarmoratus: L. *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly + L. *marmoratus*, marbled; overlaid with marble. *Hylodes ventrimarmoratus* Boulenger, 1912. (“... belly and flanks white with large black spots and marblings ...”). Also *Eleutherodactylus ventrimarmoratus* — Andersson, 1945. Today *Pristimantis ventrimarmoratus* (Boulenger, 1912).

ventrivittatus: L. *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly + L. *vittatus*, wearing or carrying a ritual vitta. *Eleutherodactylus ventrivittatus* Andersson, 1945. (“... Belly whit-

ish with sharply marked irregular sinous and angle-shaped bands and spots ...”). In the synonymy of *Pristimantis ventrimarmoratus* (Boulenger, 1912).

venulosa, venulosus: L. *venulosa*, -osus, veiny; with small channels or fissures. *Rana venulosa* Laurenti, 1768. (“... Corpore venuloso, maculoso ...”). Also *Hyla venulosa* — Daudin, 1800. *Rana zebra* ? var. *venulosa* — Shaw, 1802. *Hypsiboas venulosa* — Wagler, 1830. *Hypsiboas venulosus* — Tschudi, 1838. *Scytopus venulosus* — Cope, 1866. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).

veracruz: P. Vera Cruz¹⁷, first name given to present-day Brazil by Pedro Álvares Cabral. *Chiasmocleis veracruz* Forlani et al., 2017. (“... The name refers to the first name “Terra da Vera Cruz” given to the “new land” of current Brazil by the Portuguese in 1500 ...”). Also *Chiasmocleis (Chiasmocleis) veracruz* — de Sá et al., 2018 “2019”.

veredas: P. *vereda*, swampy or marshy land, usually located near the slope of a river and covered by undergrowth. *Chaunus veredas* Brandão et al., 2007. [“... Vereda is a typical kind of cerrado vegetation, characterized by the occurrence of buriti palms (*Mauritia flexuosa*) ...”]. Today *Rhinella veredas* (Brandão et al., 2007).

vermiculata, vermiculatus: L. *vermiculata*, -us, arranged to give an effect of wavy lines. (1) *Atelopus vermiculatus* McDiarmid, 1973. (“... With reference to the dorsal color pattern I propose that this frog be called *Atelopus vermiculatus*, new species ...”). In the synonymy of *Atelopus flavescens* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (2) *Hyla vermiculata* Peters, 1872. (?). Also *Hyla vermicularis* — Peters, 1872. In the synonymy of *Dendropsophus seniculus* (Cope, 1868). (3) *Mimosiphonops vermiculatus* Taylor, 1968. (?).

vermiformis: L. *vermiformis*, worm-shaped. *Caecilia vermiformis* Shaw in Gray, 1850. (?). In the synonymy of *Caecilia gracilis* Shaw, 1802.

17 “... Neste dia, a horas de véspera, houvemos vista de terra! Primeiramente dum grande monte, mui alto e redondo; e doutras serras mais baixas ao sul dele; e de terra chã, com grandes arvoredos: ao monte alto o capitão pôs nome - o Monte Pascoal e à terra - a Terra da Vera Cruz...” Letter of Pêro Vaz de Caminha to Dom Manuel, King of Portugal.

verrucosa, verrucosus: L. *verrucosa*, warty; rugged. (1) *Brachycephalus verrucosus* Ribeiro et al., 2015. (“... numerous small glandular warts on head and arms ...”). (2) *Leiuperus verrucosus* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. (“... Overallt paa Rygsiden af Hoved, Krop og Lemmer er Huden ru af toppede Vorter, og hele Undersiden er kornetr ...”). Also *Paludicola verrucosa* — Boulenger, 1882. *Pleurodema verrucosa* — Parker, 1927. *Eupsophus verrucosus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. *Eleutherodactylus verrucosus* — Bokermann, 1966. Today *Ischnocnema verrucosa* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

versus: L. *versus*, turn around; change, alter. *Eupsophus versus* Gorham, 1966. Replacement name for *Eupsophus verrucosus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937, thought to be preoccupied. (?). In the synonymy of *Ischnocnema verrucosa* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

vertebralis: L. *vertebralis*, pertaining to vertebrae. *Brachycephalus vertebralis* Pombal, 2001. (“... The specific name is an allusion to the characteristic dermal ossification dorsal to the vertebrae ...”).

vesicaria: L. *vesicaria*, like a bladder or balloon. *Rana vesicaria* Fermin, 1765. (“... Cette Grenouille a à chaque côté de la mâchoire inférieure, une Vessie, qui dans les grandes chaleurs sont remplies d’air ...”). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).

vielliardi: Vielliard + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Jacques Marie Edme Vielliard (1944-2010), French-Brazilian ornithologist. *Proceratophrys vielliardi* Martins & Giaretta, 2011.

vilarsi: Vilars + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Arthur Vilars (?), Brazilian engineer. (1) *Hyla* (*Trachycephalus*) *vilarsi* Melin, 1941. Today *Osteocephalus vilarsi* (Melin, 1941). (2) *Hylodes vilarsi* Melin, 1941. Today *Pristimantis vilarsi* (Melin, 1941). (3) *Leptodactylus vilarsi* Melin, 1941. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus stenodema* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875.

vilavelhensis: P. Vila Velha, protected area in the state of Paraná, Brazil + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Melanophryniscus vilavelhensis* Steinback-Padilha, 2009. (“... The new species is named in reference to the type locality, the Parque Estadual de Vila Velha, Paraná State, Southern Brazil ...”).

- villasboasi:** Villas Bôas + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Orlando Villas Bôas (1914-2002), Brazilian explorer and indigenist. *Scinax villasboasi* Brusquetti et al., 2014.
- vilmae:** Vilma + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Vilma Duran, Peruvian herpetologist. *Osteocephalus vilmae* Ron et al., 2012. In the synonymy of *Osteocephalus buckleyi* (Boulenger, 1882).
- vinhai:** Vinha + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Sergio Guimarães da Vinha, Brazilian botanist at Centro de Pesquisas do Cacau (currently Comissão Executiva do Plano da Lavoura Cacaueira – CEPLAC), Ilhéus, Bahia, Brazil. *Eleutherodactylus vinhai* Bokermann, 1975 “1974”. Today *Pristimantis vinhai* (Bokermann, 1975).
- virginica:** E. Virginia, the first English colony in North America + L. *-ica*, pertaining/belonging to; connected with. *Rana virginica* Laurenti, 1768. (“... Seba I. 75. 4 ...”, i. e., *Rana, Virginiana, maculis lineis notata*). In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus fuscus* (Schneider, 1799).
- viridi-fusca:** L. *viridis*, fresh, green + L. *fuscus*, dark, swarthy, dusky; husky; hoarse. *Hyla viridi-fusca* Laurenti, 1768. (“... Corpore fusco, maculis viridibus emarginatis; pedibus viridi-fasciatis ...”). In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).
- viridis:** L. *viridis*, fresh, green. (1) *Gastrotheca viridis* A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939. [“... light colour (apple-green) allied to striking markings ...”]. Also *Gastrotheca (Opisthodelphys) viridis* — Dubois, 1987 “1986”. In the synonymy of *Alainia ernestoi* (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920). (2) *Leptodactylus viridis* Jim & Spirandeli-Cruz, 1973. (“... chama a atenção a sua coloração verde, caso único no gênero, que lembra *Pseudis paradoxos*” ...).
- Vitreorana:** L. *vitreum*, of glass; resembling glass in its color (greenish), translucency, or glitter + L. *rana*, frog. *Vitreorana* Guayasamin et al., 2009. (“... The name refers to the total or partial transparency of the venter of these frogs ...”).

vittigera: L. *vitta*, band, ribbon; fillet + L. *gero*, bear, carry, wear. *Hyla vittigera* Werner, 1894. (“... Oben hellbraun, ein Längsstreifen von der Schnauzenspitze über Nasenloch, Auge und Tympanum bis zum Ansatz der vorderen Extremität dunkelbraun ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana bischoffi* (Boulenger, 1887).

viviparum: L. *viviparus*, from L. *vivus* + L. *parios*, viviparous. *Chthonerpeton viviparum* Parker & Wettstein, 1929. (“... In *Chthonerpeton viviparum*, however, the eggs are retained within the oviducts ...”).

vizottoi: Vizotto + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Luiz Dino Vizotto, Brazilian herpetologist. *Ischnocnema vizottoi* Martins & Haddad, 2010.

vomerina: L. *vomerina*, related to the vomer. *Elosia vomerina* Girard, 1853. (“... Vomerine teeth disposed on a transverse line, interrupted in its middle, and placed on a level with the anterior margin of the inner nostrils ...”). Also *Grossodactylus vomerinus* — Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926 (*error typographicus*). In the synonymy of *Crossodactylus gaudichaudii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841.

vote: P. *vote*, expression of disdain, aversion, disregard. *Amazophrynella vote* Ávila et al., 2012. (“... The meaning depends on the intonation of voice, and was used several times by the local people when we said that the specimens were adults, rather than juveniles ...”).

v-signatus: L. *v-signatus*, stamped with a V. *Hyla perpusilla v-signata* B. Lutz, 1968. (“... An accumulation of pigment on the gula forms thick, V-shaped figure ...”). Also *Ololygon v-signata* — Peixoto, 1988 “1987”. *Scinax v-signata* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax v-signatus* (B. Lutz, 1968).

vulcaniae: L. *Vulcan*, a classical god of fire + L. *-iae*, suffix used to form a feminine abstract noun. *Hyla vulcaniae* Vasconcelos & Giaretta, 2005 “2003”. (“... in allusion to the occurrence of the species in a geomorphologic formation derived from volcanic activity, the Poços de Caldas Plateau ...”). Today *Borkermannahyla vulcaniae* (Vasconcelos & Giaretta, 2005).

wachei: Wache + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring [J.] Ernst Wache (?), German traveller and collector for Hagenbeck. *Hyla wachei* Nieden, 1911. In the synonymy of *Boana faber* (Wied-Neuwied, 1821).

wagneri: Wagner + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Johann Andreas Wagner (1797-1861), German paleontologist and zoologist. *Plectromantis wagneri* Peters, 1862. Today *Leptodactylus wagneri* (Peters, 1862).

walfordi: Walford + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Roy Lee Walford (1924-2004), US American physician. *Hyla walfordi* Bokermann, 1962. Today *Dendropsophus walfordi* (Bokermann, 1962).

watu: B. *Watu*, river known in Portuguese as Rio Doce. *Leptodactylus watu* Alves da Silva et al., 2020. ["... The epithet is a tribute to the resistance of the Borún people and to the Watu (Doce River) in southeastern Brazil ..."].

wavrini: Wavrin + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Marquis Robert de Wavrin (1888-1971), Belgian traveller. *Hyla wavrini* Parker, 1936. *Hypsiboas wavrini* — Faivovich et al., 2005. Today *Boana wavrini* (Parker, 1936).

weiassipuensis: (?) Wei-Assipu [tepui, Sima de los Guácharos, 2280 m a. s. l., Brazil-Guyana border] + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Oreophrynella weiassipuensis* Señaris et al., 2005. ("... The specific epithet *weiassipuensis* refers to the name of the locality where the species was collected ...").

weneri: Werner + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Franz Joseph Maria Werner (1867-1939), Austrian herpetologist and entomologist. *Hyla weneri* Cochran, 1952 (replacement name for *Hyla pygmaea* Werner, 1894). Also *Hyla misera weneri* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Hyla microcephala weneri* — Duellman, 1974. Today *Dendropsophus weneri* (Cochran, 1952).

- weneri:** Werner + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Werner Carlos Augusto Bokermann (1929-1995), Brazilian herpetologist. *Crossodactylus weneri* Pimenta et al., 2014.
- wettsteini:** Wettstein + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Otto von Wettstein Ritter von Westersheim (1892-1967), Austrian zoologist. *Hyla wettsteini* Ahl, 1933. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhonius* (Linnaeus, 1758).
- weygoldti:** Weygoldt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Peter Johann Henning Weygoldt, German zoologist. *Hyla weygoldti* Cruz & Peixoto, 1987 “1985”. Also *Boana weygoldti* — Wiens et al., 2005. Today *Aplastodiscus weygoldti* (Cruz & Peixoto, 1987).
- wuchereri:** Wucherer + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Otto Edward Henry Wucherer (1820-1873), Portuguese-born German physician and herpetologist. (1) *Amphodus wuchereri* Peters, 1873 “1872”. Today *Phyllodytes wuchereri* (Peters, 1873). (2) *Leptodactylus wuchereri* Jiménez de la Espada, 1875. In the synonymy of *Leptodactylus labyrinthicus* (Spix, 1824).
- xanthostomus:** G. *xantos* (ξανθός), blond, yellow + G. *stoma* (στόμα), mouth. *Melanophryniscus xanthostomus* Baldo et al., 2015. (“... indicating one of the most obvious diagnostic characters of the new species ...”).
- xapuriensis:** (?) Xapuri, a city in the state of Acre, Brazil + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Hyla xapuriensis* Martins & Cardoso, 1987. (“... O nome desta espécie é dado em alusão à sua descoberta em Xapuri ...”). Today *Dendropsophus xapuriensis* (Martins & Cardoso, 1987).
- Xenohyla:** G. *xenos* (ξένος), stranger, foreign + L. *Hyla* (see), a name that is traditionally associated with tree frogs. *Xenohyla* Izecksohn, 1998. (“... O nome genérico proposto significa *Hyla* estranha ...”).
- xerophylla:** G. *xeros* (ξηρός), dry + G. *phyllon* (φύλλον), leaf. *Hyla xerophylla* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. (“... Dessus & dessous du corps d’une couleur feuille-morte ...”). [Not *xerophylla*, as frequently spelled (from G. *xeros*

(ξηρός) dry + G. *philos* (φίλος), friend, in the sense of “thriving in or tolerant or characteristic of a xeric environment”]. Also *Hypsiboas* (*Hypsiposopus*) *xerophyllum* — Fitzinger, 1843. *Hypsiboas xerophyllum* — Cope, 1867. *Hypsiboas xerophylla* — Orrico et al., 2017. Today *Boana xerophylla* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

xinguensis: (?) Xingu, river in the Amazon Basin. *Amazophrynella xinguensis* Rojas-Zamora et al., 2018. (“... The specific epithet refers to geographic distribution of the species within the lower Xingu River basin, Brazil ...”).

x-signatus: L. *x-signatus*, stamped with an X. *Hyla x-signata* Spix, 1824. (“... *maculis dorsi duabus fuscis, X-formibus* ...”). Also *Hyla rubra x-signata* — Müller, 1927. *Hyla x-signata x-signata* — B. Lutz, 1973. *Ololygon x-signata* — Fouquette & Delahoussaye, 1977. *Scinax x-signata* — Duellman & Wiens, 1992. Today *Scinax x-signatus* (Spix, 1824).

yepiranga: T. *yé*, *ygé*, belly + T. *piránga*, red. *Paratelmatobius yepiranga* Garcia et al., 2009. (“... in allusion to orange-reddish colored belly of the new species ...”).

yungicola: S. Yungas, South American eco-region of mountain forests + L. *-icola*, dwelling in, inhabiting, living among. *Epipedobates yungicola* Lötters et al., 2005. (“... The specific name means “inhabitant of the Yungas” and refers to the eco-geographic region in which the new species occur ...”). Also *Ameerega yungicola* — Frost, 2006. In the synonymy of *Ameerega picta* (Bibron in Tschudi, 1838).

Zachaenus: G. *za-* (ζα-), augmentative prefix, very + G. *chalinus* (χαλινός), rein, strap, band. *Zachaenus* Cope, 1866. (“... A black band extends from the end of the muzzle along the canthus rostralis and follows the glandular fold to its end above the axilla. A branch descends, and, crossing the tympanic drum, stops a short distance in front of the shoulder ...”). In the synonymy of *Cycloramphus* Tschudi, 1838.

zebra: A. *zebra* (*Equus quagga*). *Rana zebra* Shaw, 1802. (“... Its colour is an elegant pale rufous brown, beautifully marked on the back and limbs, and even to the ends of the toes, with transverse chestnut-coloured bands,

which on the limbs are double and much more numerous than on the back ...”). In the synonymy of *Boana boans* (Linnaeus, 1758).

zernyi: Zerny + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honouring Hans Zerny (1887-1945), Austrian entomologist. *Hyla zernyi* Ahl, 1933. In the synonymy of *Dryaderces inframaculata* (Boulenger, 1882).

zeuctotylus: G. *zeuktos* (ζευκτος), yolked together, couple + G. *tylos* (τυλος), knot, knob, callus, lump, bolt. *Eleutherodactylus zeuctotylus* Lynch & Hoogmoed, 1977. [“... in reference to the fused (undivided) palmar tubercle ...”]. Today *Pristimantis zeuctotylus* (Lynch & Hoogmoed, 1977).

zimmermanae: Zimmerman + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. Honouring Barbara Lewis Zimmerman, Canadian herpetologist. *Eleutherodactylus zimmermanae* Heyer & Hardy, 1991. Today *Pristimantis zimmermanae* (Heyer & Hardy, 1991).

zombie: HC, from Qi. *zombi*, Soul or ghost that wanders through the night. *Synapturanus zombie* Fouquet et al., 2021. (“... The call of this species is only heard during and after heavy rain showers, when herpetologists are often not properly equipped, thus ending up soaked and digging with their bare hands in the mud in the midst of thunderstorms, reminiscent of zombies extracting themselves from the ground ...”).

zonata: L. *zonata*, encircling band/marking. *Hyla zonata* Spix, 1824. (“... *pedibus coerulescenti-fasciatis* ...”). Also *Hypsiboas zonata* — Wagler, 1830. *Phrynohyas zonata* — Duellman, 1956. Same root in *Hyla zonalis* — Duméril & Bibron, 1841. In the synonymy of *Trachycephalus typhoni* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Zweifelia: Zweifel + L. *-ia*, dedicative suffix. Honouring Richard G. Zweifel (1926-2019), US American herpetologist. *Zweifelia* Dubois, 1992. In the synonymy of *Lithobates Fitzinger*, 1843.

Brachycephalus bufonoides
Cachoeira de Macacu, RJ
@ José P. Pombal Jr.

Pleurodema diplolister
Russas, CE
@ Maria Letícia Silva-Santos

Pithecopus oreades
Paracatu, MG
@ Matheus A. R Fernandes

Boana faber
Santa Bárbara, MG
@ Luiz Paulino